

**PROBLEMATISING PITCH PERSUASION THROUGH THE NEURAL
INFLUENCE OF TONAL CENTRES IN ADVERTISING MUSIC**

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To Lauren Bacall,

*for doing all the High Point coffee commercials back in the 80s.
They have comforted me through several divorces.*

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¹ I'm aware I've been too liberal with the word '*guidance*' so far, but its usage in this context is quite literal. See, on my first day in Scotland, Maria printed me a map (in full colour) so I wouldn't get lost. She also told me to shop at Lidl because it's cheaper than other stores, which is true if you're reading this and you're an international student. Oh, and Maria! Please tell Giselle that I would like to thank her as well (as promised during that pleasantly surprising late train ride).

² I also mean this literally as they let me scan their brains with an electroencephalogram.

AUTHOR DECLARATION

I declare that, except where explicit reference is made to the contribution of others, that this thesis is the result of my own work and has not been submitted for any other degree at the University of the West of Scotland or any other institution.

OMAR HRAIB
May, 2024

ABSTRACT

Music is used in 95% of all advertisements. However, advertising music is seldom planned out within the initial phases of ad creation and is often an afterthought. One constantly neglected variable of advertising music is its tonal centre (TC), which is the single point of gravitation around which other notes orbit. Different TCs have historically been associated with distinctive characteristics due to the vast dissonances between their intervals that were created by expiring tuning systems. The modern tuning system in Western music theory, 12-Tone Equal Temperament (12-TET), equalised those dissonances between different TCs. As a result, an assumption of transpositional invariance prevailed, which led to treating all TCs as perceptually equal. This assumption is either accepted or not addressed by the literature on advertising music. Thus, this research set out to challenge it by problematising it. In addition to challenging this assumption, this research also extends its scope to examine the implications for marketing strategies, as it draws upon the relevant literature in marketing and consumer behaviour to inform marketers of applicable actions to their advertising efforts.

This empirical research adopts a quantitative positivist methodology with a hypothetico-deductive approach. To facilitate this choice, a theoretical framework was synthesised using several theoretical models: problematisation, classical conditioning, elaboration likelihood model (ELM), music congruence, attention economy, and the theory of planned behaviour.

An electroencephalogram (EEG) was used to examine the influence of all major TCs and all minor TCs on consumers' attentional response, brand information retention, and purchase intention. The results revealed a spectrum of TCs that influence those variables differently, whereby the most used TCs with the least number of accidentals evoked the highest attentional response, brand information retention, and purchase intention.

The originality and contribution of this research lie within the challenging of the prevailing assumption of transpositional invariance, revealing a newfound understanding of the influence of tonal centres on consumers' cognitive and behavioural response to advertising music, offering actionable practices for advertisers to optimise their campaigns, proposing future research in multiple disciplines, and validating the use of non-medical EEGs for research within the social sciences.

The research limitations consisted of design limitations (i.e. small sample sizes, self-reporting on some variables, anticipatory biases, and cross-cultural variability), technical stimuli limitations (i.e. the controlling of too many variables), and application limitations (i.e. technical and legal issues hindering transposing music to different TCs).

Keywords: advertising music, tonality, tonal centres, attention, retention, purchase intention, problematisation, electroencephalography (EEG), neuromarketing, music theory.

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TABLE OF INITIALISMS, ACRONYMS, & ABBREVIATIONS

$\frac{1}{4}$ CMT	Quarter Comma Meantone Temperament
12-TET	12-Tone Equal Temperament
<i>A</i>	Attention to the Advertisement
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ANOVA	Analysis of Variance
AP	Absolute Pitch
BPM	Beats Per Minute
<i>C_{maj}, C_{min}</i>	C major, C minor
<i>df</i>	Degrees of Freedom
EEG	Electroencephalography, Electroencephalogram
ERP	Event-Related Potential
H	Research Hypothesis
Hz	Hertz (event per second)
ICA	Independent Component Analysis
IFPI	International Federation of the Phonographic Industry
LTM	Long-Term Memory
<i>M</i>	Advertising Music / Presence of Advertising Music
<i>M₀</i>	Absence of Advertising Music / Silence
<i>n</i>	Sample Size
PFC	Prefrontal Cortex
<i>PI</i>	Purchase Intention
Q	Research Question
<i>R</i>	Brand Information Retention
Sig.	Significance Value
SM	Sensory Memory
STM	Short-Term Memory
<i>TC</i>	Tonal Centre
TIA	Transpositional Invariance Assumption
WM	Working Memory

Italicised items are research variables.

TABLE OF ACCIDENTALS & SYMBOLS

α	Alpha (brain wave) / Cronbach's Alpha (reliability coefficient)
β	Beta
δ	Delta
θ	Theta
γ	Gamma
μ	Mean of Population
σ	Standard Deviation
\bar{x}	Mean of Sample
\tilde{x}	Median
#	Sharp
b	Flat
*	Double sharp
bb	Double flat
♮	Natural
¢	Cent

1. CHAPTER ONE – RESEARCH INTRODUCTION

1.1. Chapter Introduction

1.2. Knowledge Gap

1.3. Research Problem

1.4. Research Questions & Hypotheses

1.5. Research Aim & Objectives

1.6. Originality & Contribution to Knowledge

1.7. Chapter Conclusion

1.1. Chapter Introduction:

Music across different cultures is created by different instruments (including the human voice) with sounds that have a variety of properties. This phenomenon is observed globally as an integral aspect amongst different cultures, and it's considered to be understood, one way or another, by nearly everyone (Rentfrow & Gosling, 2003; Kerr & Das, 2014).

It's no revelation that music is a powerful stimulus that influences many cognitive, affective, and behavioural variables, as this is documented throughout history by musicians, poets, film & television directors, playwrights, and most importantly, researchers (Bruner, 1990). Its influence is ubiquitous and begins at an early age (North, Hargreaves, & O'Neill, 2000), and is seen as one of the most influential sociological phenomena of human history, and as one that is, in one form or another, taught globally (Skelton, 2004).

Furthermore, industries all over the world outlay large sums of their budget for music purchase or composition to be used in their advertisements (Gardner, 1985; Bruner, 1990; North *et al.*, 2004; Arora & Tyagi, 2022). A campaign that exemplifies this is Microsoft's launching of Windows 95 in August 1995 when the company purchased the creative rights to use The Rolling Stones' 'Start Me Up' during the launch for \$3 million (Oakes, 2007). Oakes (2007) and Klein (2008; 2009) further suggested that the global annual spending on advertising music could be worth billions, stressing an urgency to clarify many concerns about advertising music in all that it entails: structure, influence, perception, congruence with core message, cultural factors, and many other variables.

One aspect that has always aided in clarifying the above-mentioned concerns is that even though different cultures use different auditory mechanics to fashion their music, the physiology and neurology of hearing do not differ culturally between different human listeners (Lundin, 1985; Howard & Angus, 2017). This control status over the sense of hearing can facilitate researchers' investigation of the influence different music properties have on the human brain when cross-cultural variables are controlled. Indeed, many researchers have examined the degree to which music can influence a variety of different variables, and the possible benefits of listening to music in general have proven a strong degree of scholarly traction for many years, with numerous studies citing that music has a direct influence on human behaviour (Wilson, 2003; Ziv, 2016; Siponkoski *et al.*, 2022), emotion (Morris & Boone, 1998; Alpert, Alpert, & Maltz, 2005; Swaminathan & Schellenberg, 2015), thought (Kellaris, Cox, & Cox, 1993; He, Wong, & Hui, 2017; Ritter & Ferguson, 2017), communication (Götell, Brown, & Ekman, 2009; Sharda *et al.*, 2018), physiological functions (Horne-Thompson & Grocke, 2008; Korhan, Khorshid, & Uyar, 2011), and a multitude of other variables.

However, with that said, little empirical research has been done to benefit from music within a marketing framework. Indeed, by 1990, less than 20 published empirical studies in marketing had music at the centre of their focus (Bruner, 1990), and that margin grows even thinner when the subject of interest becomes the brain's response to advertising music. Little has changed in the following 30 years as many researchers have repeatedly stated the lack of studies on the use of music in advertisement (Rentfrow & Gosling, 2003; Zander, 2006; Abolhasani, Oakes, & Oakes, 2017; Uhm *et al.*, 2022). This lack of research is likely because of the contradictory results from the previous research, which is what initially alienates researchers from approaching the topic (Alpert & Alpert, 1990; Oakes, 2007).

Despite this contradiction in results, one notable variable seems to continuously hold a stronger impact than other variables, namely, tonality, which is described as the single tonal centre or the "point of gravitation" around which different notes can orbit (Laitz, 2012, p. 2). A more scientific definition of tonality would be the frequency or pitch designation (i.e. sound wave vibration rate per second, which is typically measured in Hertz) between different intervals in a music scale (Apel, 1944). The tonal centre TC (sometimes referred to as tonic, key centre, or simply, key) is the starting point and the resolution point of a musical phrase. It's the target to which all other notes aim, and where music feels most stable (Anta, 2015).

The most well-known tonal system in Western music, as well as across the globe, follows the diatonic major and minor scales, which pitch is typically tuned to the 12-Tone Equal Temperament¹ tuning system (12-TET). 12-TET widely became the main tuning system in Western society as of the early 19th century, replacing other unequal temperament tuning systems, such as the Quarter Comma Meantone Temperament ($\frac{1}{4}$ CMT), which was used in the sixteenth, seventeenth, and some of the eighteenth centuries (Piston, 1987). In addition to major and minor tonalities, there's atonal music, which lacks any TC from which it starts and to which it typically resolves. Atonal music tends to sound more dissonant than music pitched to traditional diatonic tonality (Parncutt & Hair, 2011). Generally, the 12 major TCs reflect positive and happy feelings, whereas the 12 minor TCs reflect negative and sad feelings (Kellaris & Kent, 1991; Juslin & Sloboda, 2010; Zetl, 2017). These simple characterisations are somewhat common within Western culture and shared similarly across Western society (Gundlach, 1932; Dowling & Harwood, 1986; Turner & Huron, 2008; Brattico *et al.*, 2011; Parncutt, 2011; Bogert *et al.*, 2016; Ritter & Ferguson, 2017).

¹ Equal Temperament is a tuning system where an octave, an interval with a frequency ratio of 2:1, is divided into a set of notes which frequencies are equally distanced on a logarithmic scale. The 12-TET tuning system logarithmically divides this octave into 12 equally distanced notes (referred to as semitones) with a ratio equal to the 12th root of 2 ($\sqrt[12]{2} \approx 1.05946$). This results in 12 semitones in an octave, each being 100 cents apart, and a cent is a logarithmic unit of measurement used to help divide and compare musical intervals (Apel, 1944).

Much of the previous literature done on advertising music shows that tonality is likely the most significant variable influencing the affective and cognitive responses to the ad; Stout, Leckenby, & Hecker (1990) found in a study of 40 television ads that tonality¹ is the most effective variable of all other music variables they examined (tempo, melody, and volume) as it conveyed warmth, relevance, and brand reinforcement. The latter consists of brand dependability, willingness to recommend, and purchase intention. Further, Kellaris & Kent (1993), Zander (2006), and Allan (2007) found that tonality has the most significant impact on perceived pleasure as major and minor tonalities induced more pleasure than atonality. This increase in pleasure is found to result in greater purchase intention (Kellaris & Kent, 1993; Kellaris & Rice, 1993; Brooker & Wheatley, 1994; Allan, 2007; Lantos & Craton, 2012).

Even though there has been some focus on the tonality of advertising music in the previous literature, little empirical research has been dedicated to attention, retention, and purchase intention as dependent variables to it, and none, to the knowledge of the researcher, have investigated the influence of all 24 TCs on said variables, especially not through Event-Related Potential measurements (ERP)². Allan (2006; 2007; 2008) states that if the ad does not attain attention, then ad information retention diminishes, which would lead to lesser intent to purchase. Indeed, many studies have further stated that since music has the ability to assist the advertising message to become cognitively processed more efficiently, then each individual component that makes up the advertising music needs to be the centre of academic focus as it must have optimal conditions that can facilitate establishing deeper attention to the ad, which can then ensure that the ad's message is better communicated, hence, more information is recalled (Craton & Lantos, 2011; Marchegiani & Phau, 2012; Craton, Lantos, & Leventhal, 2017). Therefore, it's important to know if music tonality, which is arguably one of the most influential components of advertising music, influences attention towards the ad, and whether or not each TC influences it differently.

Despite the evident impact tonality has on the most paramount variables that govern advertising, it remains mainly viewed by literature as either major or minor without further investigating each of its 24 TCs. Having this area of research uncharted is needless given that different TCs have been deemed by many, as far back as the ancient Greeks, to equip music with certain characteristics that influence its perception (Mattheson, 1713; Mattheson, 1739; Schubart, 1806; Steblin 1983; Young, 1991; Parncutt, 2011). More on how previous tuning systems have resulted in those characteristics can be found in appendix A (section 1).

¹ Stout, Leckenby, & Hecker (1990) used the term 'mode' to describe tonality, and only identified it as either major, minor, or mixed, without considering each specific TC.

² ERPs are electrical signals that occur in the brain in response to certain stimuli. ERPs are typically measured using electroencephalography (EEG), which helps researchers investigate the neural mechanisms involved in brain activity (Picton, 1992; Luck, 2014).

Circling back to advertising, advertising music is almost always an afterthought and is given little consideration in the ad creation process (Bruner, 1990; Dunbar, 1990; Allan, 2006; Eckhardt & Bradshaw, 2014; Shakil & Siddiqui, 2019). More specifically, scrutiny of tonality is completely neglected even though it may be an important factor in prompting a specific cognitive, affective, or behavioural response (Kellaris & Kent, 1993; Zoghaib, 2019).

This research proposes examining the influence of the tonality in advertising music on brain activity using electroencephalography (EEG) to measure any attentiveness variability when participants are subjected to an advertisement with congruent (i.e. fitting) background music where every one of the 12 major TCs and the 12 minor TCs, as well as an additional control no-music condition, are tested in a between-subjects design, then measure if the attentiveness variability could influence brand information retention and purchase intention.

This research spans six chapters; introduction, literature review, research design, data analysis & results, discussion, and conclusion. The introduction chapter will begin by identifying the knowledge gap, establishing the research problem, questions, and hypotheses, as well as stating the main research aim and objectives. Additionally, the originality and contribution of the research will be addressed. Finally, the chapter will conclude by summarising its main points.

1.2. Knowledge Gap:

The gap of knowledge can be outlined by four main issues: lack of research, contradictory results, flawed tools of measurement and analysis, and finally, the musical illiteracy of advertisers.

1.2.1. Lack of research:

Firstly, it's clear there's a lack of research on the topic of advertising music and its impact on cognitive, affective, and behavioural responses (Zander, 2006; Abolhasani, Oakes, & Oakes, 2017; Uhm *et al.*, 2022). However, alternatively, it can be argued that the topic has only recently been gaining more academic attention (Graakjær, 2015; Abolhasani, Oakes, & Oakes, 2017; Bhattacharya, Zioga, & Lewis, 2017; Zoghaib, 2019).

This lack of research is particularly curious since music is an indispensable part of advertising and a prominent promotional tool; in 1986, only 42% of U.S. television ads had music (Stewart & Furse, 1986), yet 6 years later, in 1992, that same number almost doubled to become 80% (Breves, Herget, & Schramm, 2020). Oakes (2007) further stated that music is used in over 90% of television advertisements, Allan (2008) examined 3,456 television advertisements and found that 94% of them contained music, and Breves, Herget, & Schramm (2020) also found that 94% of 1,460 advertisements were accompanied by music. Therefore, it is clear that the use of music in advertising has grown over the past few decades. Hence, it's critical that researchers find out how to scrutinise music selection or composition to optimise its influence within a commercial context. Previous researchers have stressed that this lack of research is mostly due to the contradictory results they yield, which will be discussed in the second point of the knowledge gap.

Particularly, the tonality of advertising music is a notable variable of interest to a lot of the research regarding advertising music. However, in the existing body of literature, tonality has often been reduced to two tonal categories¹, major or minor (Kellaris & Kent, 1992; Kellaris & Kent, 1993; Alpert, Alpert & Maltz, 2005; Lantos & Craton, 2012; Ji, 2016; Herget, Schramm & Breves, 2018; Zoghaib, 2019; Liu, Abolhasani & Hang, 2022), without considering each of the 12 TCs within each category due to the acceptance of the Transpositional Invariance Assumption (Snyder, 1990; Quinn & White, 2017; Lattner, Grachten & Widmer, 2018). The neglect to address and challenge this assumption resulted in a lack of research on the tonal centre front of advertising music. What is provided on tonal centres is not empirical research in advertising. Rather, only descriptions of them by musicologists, historians, and philosophers (Schubart, 1806; Arnn, 1983; Steblin, 1983; Young, 1991; Parncutt, 2011).

¹ Some researchers include atonal music too (Kellaris & Kent, 1992; Kellaris & Kent, 1993; Mencke *et al.*, 2019).

1.2.2. Contradictory results widening to the knowledge gap:

Secondly, when examining the potential impact of advertising music on consumer behaviour and ad performance, previous research provides conflicting and contradictory results. Alpert & Alpert (1990), Oakes (2007), then Abolhasani, Oakes, & Oakes (2017) all argued that the lack of attention given by researchers to the influence advertising music has on consumers' cognitive and affective responses may have to do with the previous empirical research producing these contradictory results due to the complexity of the topic, making it difficult to extrapolate clear conclusions that are applicable within a marketing framework, which in turn alienates researchers from exploring the topic in the first place. Unless further academic effort is made to answer more questions to demystify the topic, this paradoxical occurrence can only protract the contradiction surrounding it.

Some have argued that this contradiction could be a result of the previous research neglecting music congruence (i.e. music fit) (Kellaris & Kent, 1993; Ausina *et al.*, 2021). Consumer preference in terms of how much the music in the advertisement is congruent is rarely examined or discussed in depth in the literature, as the focus tends to be directed more towards the music itself independent from the context in which or to whom it's presented (Lavack, Thakor, & Bottausci 2008; Park, Park, & Jeon, 2014; Ballouli & Heere, 2015; Ausina *et al.*, 2021). This could be a reason why results are contradictory, because if music is not initially controlled from the standpoint of how it is valued by consumers, then there could be inconsistencies in their response to the stimuli. This lack of consumer-focus approach in the literature indicates that research is needed from a more consumer-centric standpoint, hence, musical congruence will be tested first within this research.

Furthermore, to address the issue of contradiction, as well as the lack of predictability of the effects advertising music has on advertising performance, new systematic, and theoretically sound methods are needed (Matthias, 2006; Craton & Lantos, 2011; Abolhasani, Oakes, & Oakes, 2017), which is the next point of discussion.

1.2.3. Flawed tools of measurement & analysis:

Kellaris & Kent (1993) suggested that the contradiction and ambiguity of the previous research results can only be alleviated by a thorough understanding of the complex mechanisms and inner-workings of both the sound stimuli and the listeners' response. They further stated that the latter's processes seem to function internally and are not outwardly apparent, which is why they urged future researchers to rely on indirect, implicit, and passive methods in gauging participants' responses.

Indeed, the overwhelming majority of previous research adopts an active approach of measuring phenomena rather than a passive one; it directly seeks out data through

participants' self-reporting, which may be unreliable when trying to expel their social desirability biases (Fisher & Katz, 2000). It's paramount to recognise that studies where participants are actively and consciously aware that they are in an artificial experimental environment that deliberately probes their response to a musical stimulus do not simulate a genuine scenario where advertising music functions in a passive listening environment (Matthias, 2006; Oakes, 2007).

Thus, by largely employing passive tools of measurement, this research can investigate advertising music with less personal biases from participants. These tools do not require active input from participants and instead rely on data collected passively, which has the potential to include variables of importance that would not otherwise be included (Nunan & Di Domenico, 2013).

There's a pressing need to carry out research using novel methods that can provide a better insight into consumers' responses to stimuli (Allan, 2007). Bruner (1990, p. 100) encouraged raising the "level of experimental sophistication". And Scott (1990) stated that:

One of the signal symptoms of weakness in the [previous literature] is that the theory of music being used is not consistent with the way we experience the phenomenon in everyday life... We must not let our methods drive our theories but must instead design our methods in a way that can encompass whatever theory seems articulate enough to fully describe the phenomenon.

— (p. 234)

As aforementioned, the response to the sound stimuli in advertising music functions internally, and active tools of measurement typically only gauge its external responses, which, as stated previously, can provide inaccurate, incomplete, and conflicting results. Treating the response to advertising music as an Event-Related Potential (ERP) can offer a more comprehensive understanding of the internal processing of the stimuli, as ERP allows for the measurement of the brain's electrical activity in response to specific events, providing insight into the cognitive processes underlying the participant response (Luck, 2014; Williams, McArthur, & Badcock, 2021). This is especially important for measuring attention as there are no reliable indirect tools for measuring it, which is why marketing researchers recommend electroencephalography (EEG) as a direct means of measuring attention for more precise and reliable results (Alvino *et al.*, 2020; Alsharif *et al.*, 2021).

Therefore, utilising tools from the neurosciences, such as electroencephalography (EEG), can provide a better understanding of this phenomenon, especially that there's a lack of research on how different tonalities influence brain activity within a commercial setting, and even a complete blind spot when tonality is considered to encompass all the 24 diatonic major and minor TCs rather than merely two categories: major and minor.

1.2.4. Musical illiteracy of advertisers:

Lastly, the lack of music awareness within the commercial environment is another factor that demonstrates the need for this research. The use of music in auditory and audio-visual advertising has increased in the past 30 years to such an extent that nearly every advertisement now comprises of musical components (Abolhasani, Oakes, & Oakes, 2017; Çupi & Morina, 2020). However, the use of music in advertising has largely been based on advertisers' personal instinct rather than empirical support. And the use of advertising music is seldom planned out within the initial phases of ad creation and is often an afterthought (Dunbar, 1990; Allan, 2006; Eckhardt & Bradshaw, 2014; Shakil & Siddiqui, 2019).

The reliance on personal intuition or subjective preferences when choosing music for advertisements may not align with the desired objectives or target audience preferences. As a consequence, advertisers may overlook the potential of leveraging music as a persuasive tool or fail to effectively connect with consumers on a cognitive and emotional level (Eckhardt & Bradshaw, 2014).

Advertising agencies are verbally and visually literate. Their clients, on the other hand, are verbally literate and have developed some visual literacy to spatial and colour aesthetics. However, neither the agency nor the client have any musical experience or interest beyond the scope of popular mainstream hit songs, and this lack of knowledge stands in the way of ad optimisation (Dunbar, 1990; Oakes, 2007).

As stated before, music is used as a crucial communicative element in nearly 95% of advertisements (Oakes, 2007; Allan, 2008; Breves, Herget, Schramm 2020), and it has been reported that it is the most stimulating component of an ad (Morris & Boone, 1998; Abolhasani, Oakes, & Oakes, 2017), therefore it's vital to make an effort that bridges the gap of musical illiteracy within the industry by encouraging advertisers to employ the recommendations of empirical research during ad creation, and become more discriminatory when selecting or writing advertising music.

1.3. Research Problem:

The research problem is the starting point of any research and is considered by many researchers as the most fundamental keystone around which the research is built; a flawed, inadequate, or incoherent problem statement renders all that follows it unsound (Ellis & Levy, 2008; Creswell, 2015; Marchisotti & Farias, 2022). Kerlinger & Lee (2000) have also stated that identifying the research problem is “the most difficult and important part of the [research] process” (p. 15) and that this difficulty should not cause researchers to overlook the necessity of doing so. They further reported that a research-worthy problem can generally be formulated if one or both of the following conditions are met:

- 1) the previous literature directly and **explicitly reported the problem**, and/or
- 2) the previous literature yielded **contradictory results**

Both of these conditions will be examined in the following discussion, which will help identify a main source problem of tonality definition. This can assist in adequately addressing the problem statement which will inform the structure of the research as a whole.

1.3.1. Explicitly-reported problems:

Regarding the first condition, some of the recent literature has indeed acknowledged a few assumption-based problems. The acknowledgment of these assumptions does not derive from marketing research per se, rather, from music research. However, marketing research on advertising music is by default informed by the music theory that is a product of music research (Alpert, Alpert, & Maltz, 2005; Matthias, 2006; Zoghaib, 2019). Bode (2006) has even stated that research on advertising music is “stuck” conforming to classical music theory (p. 580), and that these fallacies in the traditional music conceptualisations need to be addressed in future research. Because of this dependence on music theory, marketing researchers operate under the same assumptions that musicologists embrace from music research, theory, and overall literature. One assumption that stands out and has been repeatedly criticised is the Transpositional¹ Invariance Assumption.

There are further non-assumption-based research problems as well, pertaining more directly to theories from marketing research such as attention economy, which is an interdisciplinary research area consisting of literature from behavioural and social studies, psychology, cognitive research, neuroscience, and economics. Indeed, marketing researchers have explicitly reported the lack of adequate tools for measuring attention within a commercial setting. These problems will be addressed in the following points of discussion.

¹ Transposition in music is the process of “shifting a melody, a harmonic progression, or an entire musical piece to another key, while maintaining the same tone structure” (Koch & Dommer 1865, quoted in Hewahi, AlSaigal, & AlJanahi, 2019, p. 398).

1.3.1.1. Transpositional Invariance Assumption (TIA):

This assumption is grounded in the idea that the characteristics of a musical piece are preserved even when the music is transposed to a different TC (Krumhansl, 1991; Lerdahl & Jackendoff, 1996). Thus, the perception of different musical TCs is commonly assumed to be invariant under transposition (e.g. music in C_{maj} is perceived similarly when it's transposed to G_{maj}) (Quinn & White, 2017; Harasim *et al.*, 2021). Hence, studies of musical corpora transpose all music in major TCs to one major TC (typically C_{maj}), and all music in minor TCs to one minor TC (typically A_{min} , which is C_{maj} 's relative minor) to facilitate categorisation, pattern detection, and overall analysis (Krumhansl & Kessler, 1982; Snyder, 1990; Smith & Schmuckler, 2004; Temperley & Marvin, 2008; Prince & Schmuckler, 2014; Quinn & White, 2017; Harasim *et al.*, 2021).

This assumption arises from the observation that many musical compositions use similar harmonic patterns despite having different TCs (Snyder, 1990). However, many music theorists and categorists have challenged the appropriateness of assuming transpositional invariance after the adoption of 12-TET as a main tuning system in Western music culture, principally because this presupposition does not account for the compositional technicalities, interpretational and perceptual processing, cultural influences, and instrumental permissions and limitations of the different TCs, which all can contribute to engendering different characteristics for those TCs by musicians, ergo, listeners (Purwins *et al.*, 2003; Lattner, Grachten, & Widmer, 2018). Indeed, Quinn & White (2017) have found in a corpus of over 1,500 musical pieces that the Transpositional Invariance Assumption does not hold as they reported variances in the profiles of different TCs, mainly pertaining to the frequency and distance of modulation based on the number of accidentals in the initial TC; music in TCs that have more accidentals modulate more frequently to more distant TCs, and vice versa.

Similarly to Quinn & White (2017), this research will not accept the TIA. Rather, it will treat this assumption — that the perception of different TCs is invariant under transposition — as the null hypothesis and find evidence towards rejecting it.

1.3.1.2. Inadequate tools for measuring attention within a commercial context:

Attention is a complex neurological construct that is difficult to define and measure. It's influenced by a multitude of factors, including environmental stimuli, sensory input, emotional status, and cognitive load, among many others (Hommel *et al.*, 2019). Attention within humans is especially a difficult research area due to its multi-connectivity to several levels of analysis: neural, cognitive, perceptual, behavioural, and more (Posner & Petersen, 1990). Therefore, in order to properly measure attention, tools that can record all of these levels of analysis and incorporate them into an extensive evaluation are necessary.

Attention is largely seen by advertisers as a commodity which can be bought from consumers as a valuable and finite resource that can be managed and optimised (Alvino *et al.*, 2020). However, most of the previous literature on attention within commercial contexts fails to measure attention adequately as it largely relies on participants' self-reporting, which, as discussed prior in the knowledge gap, is not a reliable method of gauging attention. This led marketing researchers to explore other tools of measurement that can calibrate attention more directly and holistically across all the levels in which it operates (Alsharif *et al.*, 2021).

Electroencephalography (EEG) is a common tool used in medical settings to monitor and measure attention. EEGs which are built for medical use are costly, need advanced training, and are impractical for usage in commercial settings (Sawangjai *et al.*, 2020; Williams, McArthur, & Badcock, 2021). However, there has been a recent rise in availing low-cost alternatives which are oriented less towards research within the medical sciences and more towards research within the social sciences. Such tools, like Emotiv's EPOC+ which is being used in this research, have been reported to be helpful for researching "reliable auditory ERPs" (Badcock *et al.*, 2013, p. 14), "quite accurate" (Strmiska & Koudelkova, 2018, p. 3), "demonstrated the feasibility of low-cost neuroimaging outside of research laboratories" (Williams, McArthur, & Badcock, 2020, pp. 4-5), "similar to those of a research-grade system" (Williams *et al.*, 2020, p. 26), and can be of "convenience, usability, and precision" (Williams, McArthur, & Badcock, 2021, p. 15). Little to no previous advertising literature has seized the benefits of these commercially available tools when measuring attention. This research acknowledges this as a significant gap and aims to utilise these tools.

1.3.2. Contradictory results due to vague definitions:

As aforementioned, the second condition to forming a research-worthy problem is if the previous literature has clearly denoted contradictory results around the subject matter (Kerlinger & Lee, 2000). Creswell (2015) further addressed the issue of the alienating nature of contradictory results that typically deters researchers away from investigating the topic by reassuring that "research accumulates slowly, and what may seem contradictory comes together to make sense in time" (p. 7).

The reasons for these contradictions have been addressed in the knowledge gap, but it's important to remember within the context of the research problem that these contradictions also stem from addressing the problem poorly (Ellis & Levy, 2008; Creswell, 2015). This is especially true when the contradictory results persist even when the research is replicated, which often signifies a research problem of negligence to account for cross-cultural variables and/or a lack of clarity in the definition of those variables. The previous literature has not reported concerns of the former as it fairly accounted for cross-cultural differences when

examining advertising music (Castellano, Bharucha & Krumhansl 1984; Murray & Murray, 1996; Shen & Chen, 2006; Taylor, 2007; Craton, Lantos & Leventhal 2017), however, it has suggested that certain dependant and independent variables within the study of advertising music need to be more clearly defined because different studies have operationalised those poorly defined variables differently which produced contradictions. For instance, many researchers have expressed the need for more clarity and consistency when identifying variables such as the attitude towards the advertising music (Craton & Lantos, 2011; Lantos & Craton, 2012; Craton, Lantos & Leventhal, 2017), attention to the ad (Bolls, Lang & Potter, 2001; Allan, 2006; Allan, 2007; Cambra, Martínez-Martínez & Niño, 2018), brand information retention and recall (Sewall & Sarel, 1986; Bolls, Lang & Potter, 2001; Allan, 2006; Yeoh & North, 2010b; Taher & El Badawy, 2022), advertising music tempo (Milliman, 1986; Kellaris & Kent, 1993; Brooker & Wheatley, 1994; Edworthy & Waring, 2006; Allan, 2007; Knoferle *et al.*, 2011), and advertising music tonality (Stout, Leckenby & Hecker, 1990; Kellaris & Kent, 1993; van Leeuwen, 1998; Vos, 2000; Knoferle *et al.*, 2011; Chandler, 2023).

Particularly, in the case of tonality, Vos (2000) stated that the “fuzziness” around the definition of tonality is due to “the fact that Western tonal music has no clear-cut historical or otherwise categorical boundaries” (p. 405). While Chandler (2023) expressed that “for something to be tonal is defined only implicitly, and often in straw-man fashion” (p. 148). Since the tonality of advertising music is particularly of foremost importance for this research, scrutinising its definition is a principal task.

1.3.3. A problem of definition:

Against the previous points of discussion, it becomes clearer that one of the main problems of the previous literature is a matter of definition as it has reduced the definition of tonality in advertising music to a dichotomous status of either major or minor rather than two sets of the 12 major TCs and the 12 minor TCs of the classical Western music theory. The former definition operates under the Transpositional Invariance Assumption, which leads to asserting that the 12 TCs within the category of major TCs function similarly within a commercial context, therefore, assuming they have no discernible differences in how they influence many brand-related variables (and the same applies to the category of the 12 minor TCs). Thus, this definition overlooks the potential influences of those different TCs within the context of advertising music on brand-related variables such as attention, retention, and purchase intention. This approach to the tonality of advertising music is short-sighted given the historical characteristics of the different tonal centres expressed by many musicians which are thought to have persisted even after the supposed unification of them when 12-TET was slowly adopted by Western music theory in the late 18th century and fully adopted in the early 19th century (Steblyn, 1983; Young, 1991; Parncutt, 2011).

In light of this problem, the definition of tonality must be specified within this research to avoid making similar assumptions to the ones made by the previous literature and to assist future research in expanding their view on what constitutes tonality within the context of advertising music. Therefore, the following view on tonality within this research is proposed:

Tonality is the Tonal Centre (TC) to which all notes gravitate and where the music is perceived as the most stable and resolved (Brodbeck, 1982; Krumhansl, 2000; Anta, 2015). There are two tonal categories in classical Western music theory, major and minor, and each category consists of 12 TCs (Toiviainen & Krumhansl, 2003; Turner & Huron, 2008). The study of tonality within this research does not merely examine the two major and minor tonal categories. Rather, it examines all 24 TCs individually, where each TC will be compared against the other 11 TCs within its category. A table of the names of all tonal centres within each tonal category can be found in appendix A (section 2).

1.3.4. Main research problem statement:

Strong research begins “with an unmistakably clear statement of the problem... [which is] carefully phrased and represents the single goal of the total research effort” (Leedy & Ormrod, 2015, p. 49). According to Ellis & Levy (2008), an adequate problem statement is one that addresses six main questions regarding the research, what, where, when, why, who, and how. The following is an account for each of those questions based on everything which has been discussed so far about the research problem:

- **What is the problem?** The problem can be characterised as an oversight of the influence of TCs in advertising music on brand-related variables, specifically attention to the ad. Previous research has primarily considered tonality as either major or minor, without considering the specific TCs within these categories (Kellaris & Kent, 1993; Knoferle *et al.*, 2011). This assumes a transpositional invariance across the different TCs (i.e. cognitive processing and perception of all major TCs is similar, as is in all minor TCs) (Krumhansl, 1991; Lerdahl & Jackendoff, 1996; Quinn & White, 2017; Harasim *et al.*, 2021), which limits the understanding of how different TCs impact the human cognitive process within the context of advertising.
- **Where is the problem happening?** The problem occurs interdisciplinarily in marketing research, neuroscience, and music theory. The influence of tonality in ad music is becoming a topic of interest in these areas of research, as it pertains to consumer behaviour, neurocognitive responses, and the aesthetics of music (Cambra, Martínez-Martínez & Niño, 2018; Alvino *et al.*, 2020; Ausín *et al.*, 2021). As marketing researchers gain easier access to novel and convenient tools that enable them to bridge marketing with other disciplines such as neuroscience, the scope of

the research problem widens, which requires funnelling to contain the width of the problem (Aboelela *et al.*, 2007; Szostak, 2013; Tobi & Kampen, 2018).

- **When is the problem happening?** Since the problem occurs within advertising music, and since tonal music is a main component of the overwhelming majority of visual and audial advertising (Oakes, 2007; Allan, 2008; Breves, Herget, & Schramm, 2020), then the problem occurs throughout most of the advertising efforts.
- **Why is the problem happening?** The problem arises due to the overarching assumption of transpositional invariance which is accepted throughout the previous literature, and resulted in a failure to account for the influence of each TC of the major and minor tonalities (Quinn & White, 2017; Harasim *et al.*, 2021). Research has not thoroughly examined whether attentional responses to advertisement differ depending on specific TCs of the ad music. Hence, an attempt to rectify this will be made in this research.
- **Who is involved in this problem, and who have addressed it?** Three involved parties can be identified in relation to this problem: consumers, advertisers, and researchers. Consumers are affected by advertising music as it plays a role in capturing attention and influencing emotional responses (Allan, 2006; Ji, 2016; Gkaintatzis *et al.*, 2019). Advertisers almost always employ music within their ad campaigns (Breves, Herget, & Schramm, 2020), and are generally interested in understanding how to optimise consumer attention (Bolls, Lang & Potter, 2001; Haan & Moraga-González, 2011; Bordalo, Gennaioli & Shleifer, 2020), and since different music TCs might impact consumer attention differently, understanding the influence of those TCs should become a frontier for marketing researchers, especially since a few musicologists have highlighted the errors of the Transpositional Invariance Assumption (Purwins *et al.*, 2003; Parncutt, 2011; Quinn & White, 2017).
- **How does the problem negatively impact the understanding of the topic?** What's already known about the topic of advertising music is mostly a result of traditional tools of measurement such as self-report, which, despite their limitations, have assisted in making some conclusions (Gorn, 1982; Kellaris & Kent, 1993; Kellaris & Mantel, 1996; Fisher & Katz, 2000). However, those conclusions did not account for individual TCs, rather, they only examined major and minor music as two categories of tonality, which resulted in a myriad of contradictions as stated earlier. This means that the problem creates a blind spot in the understanding of the relation between the individual TCs of ad music and consumers' response.

The following problem statement can be derived from the answers to the six questions:

Classical Western music theory under the 12-TET tuning system assumes that the perception of music is invariant when music transposition occurs within each tonality category (major and minor). This led marketing researchers to overlook the influence of each music TC on consumers' response and advertising performance, especially pertaining to attention, which has been largely measured indirectly via self-report techniques. Due to the nature of this assumption, the problem can only be examined interdisciplinarily by employing consumer behaviour, neurocognition, and music theory. Addressing this problem involves addressing consumers; how their attention is influenced by the different TCs of advertising music. Advertisers; what changes they can make to advertising music to optimise ad performance. And researchers; what the previous literature informs the current one, and what the future literature could look like. This problem creates a blind spot in understanding the influence, if any, of the TCs of advertising music on consumers' response.

1.3.5. How the research problem informs the research structure:

The research problem plays a primal role in shaping the research structure and is regarded by many as the foundation for the research endeavour as it determines the entire research design, which reflects on all other research aspects (Kerlinger & Lee, 2000; Creswell, 2015; Leedy & Ormrod, 2015; Marchisotti & Farias, 2022). Ellis & Levy (2008) have illustrated a framework of the relationship between the research problem and the other research steps:

Figure 1.1: Conceptual map of the research problem informing the research structure. Adapted from (Ellis & Levy, 2008, p. 19)

According to the figure above, the research problem will initially delimit the research questions, which will “narrow the purpose [or aim] into specific questions that the researcher would like answered or addressed in the study” (Creswell, 2015, p. 60). These questions will then help formulate practicable hypotheses that can be tested. This initial specificity is vital for this research due to its interdisciplinary nature as it already integrates three broad areas of research: marketing, music theory, and neuroscience. Therefore, a specific problem detailing exactly the scope of the questions and hypotheses will help determine the following step of the research, which is methodology.

The methodology for this research, determined by the research questions and hypotheses, will dictate the most appropriate methods and tools that will produce results (i.e. prove or disprove hypotheses). The results will then be supported and validated by the literature review. Moreover, they will permit informed conclusions, which will ultimately answer the research questions and achieve its main aim and objectives, as well as suggest future research, upon which further questions are raised that will address new research problems.

1.4. Research Questions & Hypotheses:

One of the main reasons for the previous emphasis on the research problem is not only to confine the research questions, but to also challenge the assumptions underlying the current literature. Utilising gap-spotting to generate research question, while effective at highlighting what the literature may have missed, does not “deliberately try to identify and challenge the assumptions underlying existing literature in the process of constructing research questions” (Alvesson & Sandberg, 2011, p. 252).

Problematization, however, is a method through which assumptions are directly challenged as it views the current knowledge of a phenomenon as a problem and then questions its status quo (Foucault, 1972; Stengers, 2021). Foucault (1972), who wrote the most on problematization, does not view it simply as pre-existing knowledge being problematic. Rather, he regards it as an active process which helps constitute the problem itself. He further argues that problems are not inherently present or objective, but are socially and discursively constructed through power relations, knowledge systems, and historical contingencies, which is the case for the problem at hand as it’s a result of historical notions, musical technicalities, practices of convenience, and assumptions about music perception (more on problematization in the theoretical framework in the literature review)

It should be noted that gap-spotting and problematization are not mutually exclusive as gap-spotting often requires some effort of critical scrutiny of the problems that often stem from assumptions (Locke & Golden-Biddle, 1997; Alvesson & Sandberg, 2011). However, problematization actively encourages scepticism of those assumptions (Alvesson & Sandberg, 2011; Bacchi, 2015), which will be important given the assumptions addressed previously such as the transpositional invariance in Western music theory. Problematization can also help in the involvement of several discursive fields where certain systems of understanding, classification, and subjects may emerge (Alvesson & Sandberg, 2011), which is helpful for this research given its interdisciplinary nature.

Alvesson & Sandberg (2011) have further developed a means through which problematization can generate the research questions. Its aim is “Generating novel research questions through a dialectical interrogation of one's own familiar position, other stances, and the literature domain targeted for assumption challenging” (p. 260), and it begins by stipulating the typology of the literature’s assumptions, of which they have identified 5 types of assumptions: in-house assumptions, root metaphor assumptions, paradigm assumptions, ideology assumptions, and field assumptions. The following table provides a brief description of each type.

In-house assumptions	Root metaphor assumptions	Paradigm assumptions	Ideology assumptions	Field assumptions
Assumptions that exist within a specific school of thought.	Broader images of a particular subject matter underlying existing literature	Ontological, epistemological, and methodological assumptions underlying existing literature	Political, moral, and gender related assumptions underlying existing literature	Assumptions about a specific subject matter that are shared across different theoretical schools

Table 1.1: Typology of assumptions open for problematisation (Alvesson & Sandberg, 2011, p. 260)

These 5 types of assumptions are viewed, respectively, as a specific-to-broad overlapping continuum. Challenging assumptions in the three latter types might be superficial as it doesn't allow for a more thorough treatment of the nuances of the subject matter, while a challenge of an in-house or root metaphor assumptions can be a "key part in the process of developing new theory" (Alvesson & Sandberg, 2011, p. 255). Nonetheless, challenging an in-house or root metaphor assumption will, of course, reflect on paradigm, ideology, and field assumptions; when these lower-level assumptions are challenged, a re-evaluation of the prevailing paradigm, ideology, and field assumptions occurs, which can potentially prompt a paradigm shift that leads to the emergence of new theoretical and methodological approaches to the subject matter (Knights, 1992; Alvesson & Sandberg, 2011).

The Transpositional Invariance Assumption is an in-house assumption as it exists within the school of Western music theory. While it may transfer to other theoretical schools such as consumer behaviour or neural processing, it still wouldn't be viewed as a field assumption. This is because it's not a vague assumption. Indeed, it's a very specific and technical assumption about music perception regarding one physical characteristic, which is tonality. An example that clarifies the distinction between an in-house assumption and a field assumption is within management theory as many scholars across different fields assume that "there is something called 'management' that should be critically addressed" (Alvesson & Sandberg, 2011, p. 255). This is a broad assumption shared across different schools of thought, therefore, it's a field assumption. On the other hand, an in-house assumption about management would be, for example, that the years of experience positively correlated with leadership skills, which is specific and technical (Yukl, 2013). Similar to this example, it can be argued that when scholars of different schools assume that there is something called 'music' that should be critically addressed is a field assumption due to its broadness.

The following two tables will denote the assumptions within the existing literature of advertising music that are relevant to this research, the typology of these assumptions, and the research questions and accompanying hypotheses generated from them:

1.4.1. Research questions and hypotheses generated via problematisation:

Assumptions	Typology	Questions	Hypotheses
Transpositional Invariance Assumption (major tonal category): music perception is invariant under transposition within the TCs of the major tonal category.	In-house: the assumption exists within classical Western music theory and is shared and accepted as unproblematic. Furthermore, it's a specific and technical assumption.	Q _{a;1} : Does the Transpositional Invariance Assumption hold true for the perception of an advertisement as characterised by attention towards it when the music is transposed across all 12 major tonal centres (TCs) of the major tonal category. Q _{r;1} : Does the Transpositional Invariance Assumption hold true for the perception of an advertisement as characterised by information retention when the music is transposed across all 12 major tonal centres (TCs) of the major tonal category.	H _{a;1} (null): The attention (<i>A</i>) to an advertisement is invariant when the advertising music (<i>M</i>) is transposed across the 12 major tonal centres (TCs) of the major tonal category. H _{r;1} (null): The information retention (<i>R</i>) of an advertisement is invariant when the advertising music (<i>M</i>) is transposed across the 12 major tonal centres (TCs) of the major tonal category.
		Q _{p;1} : Does the Transpositional Invariance Assumption hold true for the perception of an advertisement as characterised by purchase intention when the music is transposed across all 12 major tonal centres (TCs) of the major tonal category.	H _{p;1} (null): The purchase intention (<i>P</i>) of an advertisement is invariant when the advertising music (<i>M</i>) is transposed across the 12 major tonal centres (TCs) of the major tonal category.

Table 1.2: research questions and hypotheses generated via problematisation (major music scenarios)

Assumptions	Typology	Questions	Hypotheses
Transpositional Invariance Assumption (minor tonal category): music perception is invariant under transposition within the TCs of the minor tonal category.	In-house: the assumption exists within classical Western music theory and is shared and accepted as unproblematic. Furthermore, it's a specific and technical assumption.	<p>Q_{a2}: Does the Transpositional Invariance Assumption hold true for the perception of an advertisement as characterised by attention towards it when the music is transposed across all 12 minor tonal centres (TCs) of the minor tonal category.</p> <p>Q_{r2}: Does the Transpositional Invariance Assumption hold true for the perception of an advertisement as characterised by information retention when the music is transposed across all 12 minor tonal centres (TCs) of the minor tonal category.</p> <p>Q_{p2}: Does the Transpositional Invariance Assumption hold true for the perception of an advertisement as characterised by purchase intention when the music is transposed across all 12 minor tonal centres (TCs) of the minor tonal category.</p>	<p>H_{a2} (null): The attention (A) to an advertisement is invariant when the advertising music (M) is transposed across the 12 minor tonal centres (TCs) of the minor tonal category.</p> <p>H_{r2} (null): The information retention (R) of an advertisement is invariant when the advertising music (M) is transposed across the 12 minor tonal centres (TCs) of the minor tonal category.</p> <p>H_{p2} (null): The purchase intention (P) of an advertisement is invariant when the advertising music (M) is transposed across the 12 minor tonal centres (TCs) of the minor tonal category.</p>

Table 1.3: research questions and hypotheses generated via problematisation (minor music scenarios)

1.4.2. Research hypotheses structure:

The figure below illustrates the research hypotheses and its main variables:

- Independent variables: Ad Music (M).
- Dependent variables: Attention (A), Retention (R) and Purchase Intention (PI).
- Moderating variables: Major Tonal Centres (TCs) and Minor Tonal Centres (TCs).

Figure 1.2: Research hypotheses

Hypotheses H_{a1} , H_{r1} and H_{pi1} will test the influence of the Ad Music (M) on Attention (A), Retention (R), and Purchase Intention (PI), respectively, with the 12 major Tonal Centres (TCs) moderating this relationship¹.

The testing of these three hypotheses will help classify the different major TCs in how they may influence attention, retention, and purchase intention. This classification of the major TCs will enable advertisers to make an informed decision when selecting advertising music in a major tonality by choosing the appropriate major TC that aligns with their campaign objectives.

Hypotheses H_{a2} , H_{r2} and H_{pi2} , on the other hand, will test the influence of the Ad Music (M) on Attention (A), Retention (R), and Purchase Intention (PI), respectively, with the 12 minor Tonal Centres (TCs) moderating this relationship².

The testing of these three hypotheses will help classify the different minor TCs in how they may influence attention, retention, and purchase intention. This classification of the minor TCs will enable advertisers to make an informed decision when selecting advertising music in a minor tonality by choosing the appropriate minor TC that aligns with their campaign objectives.

¹ A control scenario with no music (M_0) will be included.

² A control scenario with no music (M_0) will be included.

1.5. Research Aim & Objectives:

The following research aim statement captures the central focus of the research to which all efforts are directed. With reference to all the preceding, the research main aim can be stated as the following:

1.5.1. Main aim statement:

Provide pioneering insight into the influence of the different tonal centres (TCs) of advertising music (*M*), as characterised by the 12 major TCs and the 12 minor TCs in classical Western music theory by problematising the Transpositional Invariance Assumption (TIA), through an interdisciplinary approach utilising neuroimaging techniques to measure and analyse consumers' attention (*A*), and to further examine their information retention (*R*) and purchase intention (*PI*).

1.5.2. Objectives:

For the above aim to be achieved, several research objectives should be accomplished:

1.5.2.1. Review the existing literature:

The research will initially set out to critically examine the existing body of literature on advertising music, narrowing the focus on consumer attention, information retention, and purchase intention, with an emphasis of the role of tonality and why its TCs have not been subject to individual scrutiny. It's also an objective that the literature review highlights the music theory and neural backgrounds relevant to this research.

1.5.2.2. Develop an interdisciplinary theoretical framework:

The research topic requires an interdisciplinary understanding of consumer behaviour, neuroscience, and the music theory behind advertising music. A monodisciplinary framework will fall short of providing a comprehensive understanding of the role of TCs in advertising music on consumers' brain activity and subsequent behaviour. A multidimensional interdisciplinary framework involving all these areas of research will be developed to address the phenomenon.

1.5.2.3. Collect relevant data:

The research aim can only be achieved by collecting relevant high-quality data. Thus, one of the main objectives of this research is to establish a research design strategy that allows for the gathering of the relevant demographical, behavioural, and EEG data from several willing participants for analysis and hypotheses testing. A sampling and participant selection strategy will be developed and applied to ensure all necessary data is acquired and processed properly to prepare it for analysis.

1.5.2.4. Quantify how TCs influence attentional and behavioural responses:

The main objective of this research is ultimately to quantitatively examine the influence of tonal centres (TCs) on attentional and behavioural responses, specifically overall brain activity, brand information retention, and purchase intention. By analysing the data collected via several statistical analyses, this research can provide a measurement of the impact of TCs on individuals' attention and subsequent behavioural outcomes. The findings will contribute to a deeper understanding of the role of TCs in advertising and inform effective strategies for capturing and maintaining consumers' attention.

1.5.2.5. Provide applicable recommendations for advertisers:

It is critical that advertisers and advertising agencies become more firmly discriminative with the ad-creation stage and investigate the potential effects of the music used when purchasing the rights to use already written music or commissioning the composition of original music for the ad (Oakes, 2007). Therefore, research outcomes must be clearly communicated to businesses, and businesses need to adapt their advertising music to the best research recommendations provided. And that's what this research intends to achieve regarding the use of TCs in advertising music.

1.5.2.6. Provide valuable future research suggestions:

Providing empirical evidence that can guide future research is one of the main objectives of this research. By identifying potential gaps and limitations in the current literature about the role of TCs in advertising music, this research can offer directions on the next moves needed to close those gaps and broaden the knowledge on the topic. These suggestions may include exploring different variables (dependent and independent), adopting alternative methodologies and methods, or examining the phenomenon in different contexts and disciplines to enhance the knowledge base of all areas of scientific enquiry.

1.6. Originality & Contribution to Knowledge:

By challenging assumptions, and introducing new perspectives, this research offers several advancements in theory, methodology, and practical implications. The following will elucidate the points of originality of this research, as well as its contribution to the existing body of literature.

1.6.1. Challenging of prevailing assumptions:

The present research's main originality and contribution lie in its attempt to address a complex phenomenon and offer a novel insight that goes beyond the prevailing assumptions and the paradigms designed around them. To the best of the researcher's knowledge, the Transpositional Invariance Assumption has not been challenged in the study of advertising music. The previous literature either uncritically accepts the Transpositional Invariance Assumption or, in most cases, simply does not address it at all.

This research will use problematisation to challenge the underlying assumptions put forth by the existing body of literature. Problematisation will serve as a theoretical framework through which assumptions are critically scrutinised and bringing to light the limitations and oversights they produced. By interrogating the implicit acceptance of transpositional invariance in advertising music, this research opens up new lines of inquiry surrounding advertising music and its potential.

1.6.2. Originality of methods:

One of the main points of originality of this research lies in its ability to challenge the traditional approaches of researching advertising music by viewing the phenomenon through an interdisciplinary lens. This integration of several disciplines; marketing, music theory, and neuroscience, enables the combination of theoretical perspectives from all these disciplines to investigate the role of tonal centres of advertising music on consumers' brain activity through a rigorous empirical process which leads to bringing forth a comprehensive and nuanced understanding of how those tonal centres can be implemented within a commercial context to optimise performance.

Since research participants are incapable of reporting on matters of which they are not aware (i.e. how advertising music may influence their attention, as it can only be realistically measure by directly monitoring, recording, and analysing brain activity), then using non-invasive brain scanning techniques such as EEG could reveal results that traditional marketing techniques that mostly rely on participants' self-report would not be able to reveal, which could be a gateway that provides some hidden data of consumers' experiences which is what originally necessitated the emergence of neuromarketing (Ariely & Berns, 2010).

1.6.3. Practical implications within advertising:

There is always a significant incentive for businesses to optimise the use of music in their advertisements for more advantageous results. Nonetheless, the level of scientific consideration of advertising music remains virtually non-existent (Eckhardt & Bradshaw, 2014; Shakil & Siddiqui, 2019). A clearer understanding of the impact certain musical properties have on how consumers perceive and process an ad will help differentiate between the musical selection or composition that is used in it (Oakes, 2007), and since this research aims to investigate if tonal centres within advertising music have any significant role in influencing consumers' attention, retention, and purchase intention, then answering the questions raised previously should be of interest to advertisers as it may offer applicable recommendations that are easily implemented into the musical elements of their campaigns.

1.6.4. Future research implications:

This research may encourage novel avenues for future investigations of the tonal centres of advertising music. While this research aims to explore the impact of the different TCs on attention, retention, and purchase intention, there are several directions for future research to consider, whether it's within marketing research or beyond:

- Including more independent or moderating variables alongside TCs such as chord progression, tempo, volume, timbre, instrumentation, mode, duration, modulation, atonality, melodic and harmonic complexity... etc.
- Examining other dependent variables such as long-term information retention, purchase behaviour, brand loyalty, attitude towards the ad, perceived brand image, physiological response, emotional response... etc.
- Cross-cultural research: this research predominantly operates within the context of classical Western music theory and its tuning system, 12-TET. While this tuning system is the most popular and most used across the globe, other tuning systems are used in different cultures. If this research delivers some evidence that different TCs result in different neural responses, then other researchers, not only in advertising, but in other areas of research as well, may be encouraged to explore the influence of the TCs within other tuning systems like other equal temperaments (such as 9-TET, 19-TET, 24-TET... etc), meantone temperaments (such as $\frac{1}{4}$ CMT or $\frac{1}{3}$ CMT), well temperament, just intonation, Pythagorean intonation, and many more. Exploring the influence of other musical traditions and the TCs of different tuning systems may provide insights into the cultural specificity of music's persuasiveness.
- Comparative analysis between major and minor TCs: this research explores the two tonal categories independent from one another. Cross-examining them might yield interesting results.

1.6.5. Providing an understanding of the underlying psychological mechanisms:

While this research doesn't directly examine the psychological responses of its participants, it does indeed provide insights into the mechanisms underlying their psychological traits; Examining participants' attention, retention, and purchase intention also means examining information processing, memory formation, and decision-making, respectively. These are a part of fundamental psychological processes involved in human behaviour.

Attention is a fundamental cognitive process that determines which stimuli are prioritised for processing (Posner & Petersen, 1990). By investigating how different TCs in advertising music influence attention, this research contributes to our understanding of how individuals may allocate their cognitive resources and selectively engage with music stimuli. These findings may then have broader implications for psychologists studying attentional processes to music stimuli and how they shape the perception and analysis of information.

Furthermore, the exploration of participants' retention provides insights into memory formation processes. Memory plays a crucial role in human cognition, as it enables individuals to encode, store, and retrieve information (Bordalo, Gennaioli & Shleifer, 2020). By investigating how different TCs in advertising music impact participants' ability to retain information, this research offers implications for the study of memory formation and consolidation. Understanding how specific tonal characteristics influence memory may contribute to theories and models of memory processes and retention.

Lastly, the examination of participants' purchase intention taps into decision-making processes. Decision-making is a complex cognitive process that involves evaluating options, weighing advantages and disadvantages, and ultimately making choices (Sunaga, 2018). By exploring how different TCs in advertising music influence participants' purchase intention, this research provides insights into the role of music tonality in shaping decisions. These findings may contribute to the field of decision-making research, informing psychologists about the role of music in influencing psychological factors such as consumer behaviour.

1.6.6. Validation of non-medical EEGs as tools for marketing research:

By using EEGs such as Emotiv's EPOC+, which are designed specifically as a convenient tool for non-medical research, this thesis contributes to the validation of EEG as a reliable way to measure attention within the context of advertising, and overall social sciences. Furthermore, utilising this EEG technology to measure and analyse neural activity within the context of this research will enhance the methodological rigor of using non-medical EEGs, and adds further support to the research that already validates the use of these tools (Badcock *et al.*, 2013; Strmiska & Koudelkova, 2018; Gkaintatzis *et al.*, 2019; Sawangjai *et al.*, 2020; Williams *et al.*, 2020; Williams, McArthur & Badcock, 2020; 2021).

1.7. Chapter Conclusion:

Tonality is one of the most important characteristics of music, and music is an integral part of advertising. However, in the study of advertising music, tonality has been reduced to two tonal categories (major or minor) without examining each of the 12 Tonal Centres (TC) within each category due to the prevailing assumption of transpositional invariance. As a result, little to nothing is known about the influence of the TCs of advertising music on variables such as attention to the ad, information retention, and purchase intention. This research raises scepticism of the Transpositional Invariance Assumption and challenges it through problematisation.

The use of neuroimaging tools, such as electroencephalography (EEG), for measuring attention is proposed as way of gauging consumers' direct response to the music stimuli rather than relying on self-report data.

Six hypotheses are proposed: H_{a1} , H_{r1} and H_{pi1} which will test the influence of the Ad Music (M) on Attention (A), Retention (R), and Purchase Intention (PI), respectively, with the 12 major Tonal Centres (TCs) moderating this relationship. And H_{a2} , H_{r2} and H_{pi2} , on the other hand, will test the influence of the Ad Music (M) on Attention (A), Retention (R), and Purchase Intention (PI), respectively, with the 12 minor Tonal Centres (TCs) moderating this relationship.

Testing these hypotheses will help realise the main aim of the research, which is to provide pioneering insight into the influence of the different TCs of advertising music on consumers' attention utilising neuroimaging techniques, and further examining their information retention and purchase intention.

This research originality and contribution have also been highlighted as it derives from several angles: the challenging of the transposition invariance assumption within a commercial context, utilising neuroimaging methods for measuring attention, providing practical implications for advertisers, offer several future research opportunities in a variety of disciplines, provide an understanding of the underlying psychological mechanisms when listening to music, and validate the use of non-medical EEGs in the social sciences.

The following chapters will underline the literature review, research design, data analysis & results, discussion, and research conclusion, respectively.

2. CHAPTER TWO - LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Chapter Introduction

2.2. Overview of the Main Research Variables

2.3. Theoretical Framework

2.4. Ethical Considerations

2.5. Methodology of the Literature Review

2.6. Themes of the Literature

2.7. Analysis of the Literature

2.8. Chapter Conclusion

2.1. Chapter Introduction:

According to Snyder (2019), a review of the literature is vital to “map and assess the research area to motivate the aim of the study and justify the research question and hypotheses” (p. 334). By systematically reviewing and critically evaluating the existing body of knowledge, a comprehensive understanding of the research topic will be formed, which will assist in the research design and the analysis and interpretation of the research data.

This review will seek to uncover insights into the research on advertising music and contribute to the ongoing discourse of this topic. It will also provide the music theory and neuroscience backgrounds needed to establish a full understanding of how advertising music functions as a neural stimulus.

The chapter will begin by providing a necessary overview of the main research variables: advertising, music, tonal centres, attention, retention, and purchase intention. This overview will facilitate the comprehension of the theoretical framework, which will be a synthesis of several theories pertaining to problematisation of the Transpositional Invariance Assumption, classical conditioning, elaboration likelihood model (ELM), music congruence, attention economy, and the theory of planned behaviour. This will be anchored in the context of several ethical considerations.

The methodology for the systematic literature review will detail the inclusion and exclusion of selection criteria of the literature, which will assist in highlighting the main themes of the previous research. An analysis of this literature will then reveal its shortcomings, further justifying the need for this research.

2.2. Overview of the Main Research Variables:

Providing a brief overview of the main variables of interest in this research is important to establish a clear understanding of the key factors being investigated and their relevance to the research aim and objectives. The following overview will help contextualise the subsequent sections of the literature review and the following chapters, which will allow for a more comprehensive and coherent discussion of the relevant literature and its findings.

2.2.1. Advertising:

The history of advertising, as persuasion to take commercial action, can be traced back to ancient civilisations, but modern advertising as known today began to emerge in the late 19th and early 20th centuries with the rise of mass media. This rise alongside the increasing availability of consumer goods led to a new era of consumer culture in which advertising played a central role in shaping people's desires and aspirations (Kerr & Richards, 2021).

Since then, advertising has continued to evolve and adapt to changes in technology, media consumption habits, and cultural trends. The field of advertising has also become an interdisciplinary area of research, drawing on insights from psychology, sociology, economics, communication studies, and neuroscience (Ford, 2019; Munsch, 2021).

Advertising has been traditionally defined as a form of marketing communication that utilises paid promotion to communicate with a target audience and persuade them to take a specific action, such as purchasing a product, service, or idea (Arens, 1996). This definition was mostly unchanged 20 years later (Arens, 2016). Kerr & Richards (2021) have stressed a necessity for revising this definition as 'taking action' should not only mean behavioural action such as purchasing, but also affective, cognitive, and attitudinal. They even reported that cognitive actions can even be subconscious processing such as attention. They further noted that for the first time ever in 2020, digital advertising has accounted for more than half of the global advertising expenditure. This increase in digital advertising provides an opportunity to monitor the long-term impact of campaigns through detailed and accurate analytics that enable advertisers to predict consumers' future actions. Hence, they developed a new definition for advertising using the Delphi¹ method where the definition explicitly includes new types of 'action' and when consumers may take them:

Advertising is paid, owned, and earned mediated communication, activated by an identifiable brand and intent on persuading the consumer to make some cognitive, affective, or behavioural change, now or in the future.

— (Kerr & Richards, 2021, p. 190)

¹ The Delphi method was first developed in the 1950s to apply expert input in a systematic manner using a series of questionnaires with controlled opinion feedback. Its purpose is to structure a communication process that allows a group of expert individuals, as a whole, to deal with a complex problem (Linstone & Turoff, 2011).

This revised definition is important for the discourse on three of the main variables in this research: attention and information retention (feeds into cognition), and purchase intention (feeds into future action). The non-revised traditional definition of advertising would only have been able to focus on purchase intention as an immediate behavioural action. However, under this definition, 'taking action' includes the case of cognitive subconscious action in the future, such as attention to the ad, and brand information retention.

2.2.2. Music:

Much of the literature that specifically investigates the use of music in advertisements does not have a clear definition of advertising music (Morris & Boone, 1998; Lavack, Thakor, & Bottausci, 2008; Lantos & Craton, 2012; Guido *et al.*, 2016). This lack of clarity may have contributed to more ambiguity and contradiction. Saren (2015) argues that it's crucial to clarify what is being consumed when listening to music within any context, and further denotes that music has a variety of associative and indivisible components that must be recognised and addressed when considering it as the focal point of any study. Therefore, it's vital to define it specifically for this research to verify what exactly is being examined. The following are several clarifications of what is meant by music from different angles:

2.2.2.1. Music as a physical entity:

Music as a physical entity refers to the organisation and arrangement of the physical sound elements that create a tangible auditory phenomenon. It incorporates the interplay of various musical components such as melody, harmony, rhythm, tempo, mode, timbre, volume, texture, instrumentation, rests, pitch, time, chords, modulation, expression, and other sonic parameters (Jackendoff & Lerdahl, 2006).

From a physical perspective, music can be understood as a sequence of sound vibrations that cause sonic waves to travel through a non-vacuum medium and then perceived, processed, and interpreted by the human auditory system through a complex network of neuros (Zatorre, Chen & Penhune, 2007).

By acknowledging the physical and tangible dimensions of music, it becomes paramount to recognise that its production, perception, processing, and interpretation are rooted in the physical properties of sound and the technologies that enable its production and dissemination (Novembre & Keller, 2014; Sachs *et al.*, 2016). This understanding establishes a foundation for examining the multifaceted nature of music as it intersects with socio-cultural aspects, economical impact as a product, and integration and functionality within other disciplines.

2.2.2.2. Music as a socio-cultural phenomenon:

Music is not solely a physical entity that's processed by the human brain. Nor is it merely the product of individual artistic expression or technical musicianship. Rather, it's a convoluted and dynamic cultural practice which is thoroughly interwoven into human societies and cultures since records began. It has long served as a means for expressing cultural values, beliefs, identities, and experiences, reflecting the social, historical, and cultural dynamics of a given community or society (Kelly & Chen, 1999; Skelton, 2004).

Historically, music has encouraged the involvement of individuals in larger groups of similar interests and backgrounds to participate in a broad spectrum of activities, including the creation, performance, and sharing of music. It has shaped and reinforced human bonds, fostered a sense of collective belonging and identity, conveyed cultural heritage, expressed emotions and narratives, and served as a form of communication throughout celebrations, ceremonies, rituals, social gatherings, and everyday life (Arora & Tyagi, 2022).

2.2.2.3. Music as a consumable product:

Humans interact with music as a form of entertainment, personal enrichment, and sensory experience. It's viewed as a consumable product that individuals actively seek out through various means such as paying money, spending time, and making a form of effort to derive personal values such as well-being, social cohesion, and identity expression (Prior, 2013). This consumption encompasses activities such as attending concerts or performances, streaming music, purchasing recorded music, and participating in music creation. Furthermore, acquiring, accessing, and consuming music also involves an exchange of emotional, intellectual, and cognitive values (Jain & Bagdare, 2011).

The International Federation of the Phonographic Industry (IFPI) reported that the value of global recorded music revenue in the year 2022 was \$26.2 billion, the highest it has ever been (IFPI, 2023). This increasing figure has been a result of the several ways different technologies have been incorporated into the process of researching music, which furthered its integration with other disciplines such as psychology, physiology, philosophy, literature, and the social sciences such as marketing, amongst many others (Hargreaves & North, 1999; Taylor, 2007; Swaminathan & Schellenberg, 2015).

2.2.2.4. Music as an advertising tool:

Advertising music serves as a tool that often complements visual and verbal aspects to create a persuasive and compelling brand image. The tactical use of music in advertising campaigns to enhance their effectiveness has been an integral part of the marketing strategy for several decades now. In fact, almost 95% of all advertisements integrate music into their advertising efforts one way or another (Allan, 2008; Breves, Herget, & Schramm, 2020).

It is estimated that the global annual expenditure on advertising music is worth several billions (Oakes, 2007; Klein, 2008; 2009). The choice of music, purchased or originally composed, depends on the target audience, the nature of what is being advertised, the desired message, and any other specific objectives of the advertising campaign. Generally, music in advertising can take several different forms such as licensed music, original compositions, or jingles (Scott, 1990; Taher & El Badawy, 2022).

By studying music as an advertising tool, researchers can explore the cognitive and emotional mechanisms through which music influences consumer behaviour. Indeed, advertising music has been the subject of several research efforts. Many of which will be disclosed in the following sections of this chapter. Some of the issues researched involve music's influence on behavioural, emotional, and cognitive variables. Several research gaps and confounding issues remain present in the literature of advertising music due to the reasons mentioned in the first chapter. It is, therefore, a valid assumption that advertisers would be interested in bridging those gaps and clarifying those issues.

However, not all musical elements have been the focus of empirical research. One of these elements is, to the knowledge of the researcher, the tonal centres (TCs) of music. A systematic and narrowed investigation of this variable might shed some light on their role in influencing music's efficacy as a tool for advertising.

2.2.3. Tonal Centres (TCs), their scales, and their historical characteristics:

Tonal centres refer to the key of a musical composition, which is determined by the pitch relationships between musical intervals (i.e. notes) within a piece as well as the tuning system adopted. In the 12-TET tuning system, the octave is divided into 12 logarithmically equal intervals. This division results in the 12 notes that can be seen on a tradition keyboard:

Figure 2.1: The 12 notes in an octave

Ascending chromatically, these notes are C, C#/D \flat , D, D#/E \flat , E, F, F#/G \flat , G, G#/A \flat , A, A#/B \flat , B, and then the notes repeat. The sharp symbol (#) raises the pitch of the note by half a step, whereas the flat symbol (\flat) lowers the pitch of the note by half a step. The distance between two notes such as C and D is called a whole step, whereas the distance between two notes such as C and C#/D \flat is called half a step (Laitz, 2012).

2.2.3.1. The diatonic major and minor scales:

A diatonic scale is a musical construct made up of 7 notes. In Classic Western music theory, a major or minor scale can be created from any of the 12 different notes. This results in 12 major scales and 12 minor scales (Apel, 1944).

A major scale can start from any of the 12 notes and has the following interval sequence in ascending steps: whole - whole - half - whole - whole - whole - half (or W-W-H-W-W-W-H). For example, the C major scale starts from C then goes to D (whole step), then to E (whole step), then to F (half step), then to G (whole step), then to A (whole step), then to B (whole step), then back to the C one octave above (half step). In this case, the note C is the tonic (or tonic centre), and is the most harmonically stable note, and is the centre to which all other notes gravitate and where music is perceived resolved and complete (Brodbeck, 1982; Krumhansl, 2000; Anta, 2015). The following figure illustrates the 12 different major scales and their notes as displayed on a traditional keyboard:

Figure 2.2: The 12 diatonic major scales (tonic marked in red)

A minor scale¹ can start from any of the 12 notes and has the following interval sequence in ascending steps: whole - half - whole - whole - half - whole - whole (or W-H-W-W-H-W-W). For example, the C minor scale starts from C then goes to D (whole step), then to C[♯]/D[♭] (half step), then to F (whole step), then to G (whole step), then to G[♯]/A[♭] (half step), then to A[♯]/B[♭] (whole step), then back to the C one octave above (whole step). In this case, the note C is the tonic (or tonic centre), and is the most harmonically stable note, and is the centre to which all other notes gravitate and where music is perceived resolved and complete. The following figure illustrates the 12 different minor scales and their notes as displayed on a traditional keyboard:

Figure 2.3: The 12 diatonic natural minor scales (tonic marked in red)

¹ Referring here to the natural minor scale. There are other interval sequences for the minor scale, such as the harmonic minor which raises the 7th degree of the scale by a half step making the sequence (W-H-W-W-H-W-H). There's also the melodic minor which is similar to the major scale except that it lowers the 3rd degree of the scale by half a step making the sequence (W-H-W-W-W-W-H) (Laitz, 2012). The current research will only focus on the natural minor scale.

2.2.3.2. The historical characteristics of TCs:

Different TCs sounded different from one another when unequal temperaments such as $\frac{1}{4}$ CMT were used due to slight tuning discrepancies between different TCs (can be found in Appendix A, section 4), which resulted in them being associated with different characteristics by musicians, philosophers, poets, and historians (Charpentier, c. 1682; Schubart, 1806; Hitchcock, 1955; Arnn, 1983; Young, 1991; Steblin, 2002; Parncutt, 2011). Many of these characteristics can be found in appendix A (section 3). These tuning discrepancies have been eliminated in the technical sense since the adoption of 12-TET in the early 19th century (Daum, 2011). 12-TET equalised the distances between intervals making the dissonances between them equally distributed across all TCs, thus making all TCs equally slightly out of tune. This feature was necessary to enable musicians to use all 24 major and minor TCs without worrying about some of them sounding more dissonant than others, which also allowed for more harmonic possibilities and complex modulation to other TCs (True, 2018).

However, a few authors and researchers have suggested that the characteristics of TCs have persisted despite the adoption of 12-TET (Young, 1991; Steblin, 2002; Parncutt, 2011). The proposed reasons for this phenomenon are directly related to the layout and design of certain instruments (Arnn, 1983; Young, 1991):

- **Keyboard layouts:** the layout of keyboard instruments, such as the piano or the harpsichord, make it more convenient to play TCs that have less accented notes (sharps and flats) (e.g, C_{maj} and A_{min} with no accented notes can be played using only the white keys). Black keys are set higher than white keys and have less space on the keyboard making them, generally speaking, more difficult to access than white keys when playing. This led to the development of certain fingerings, patterns, and exercises that favoured certain TCs over others in terms of ease, which made composers favour writing music using a selection of TCs (Duffin, 2007). Indeed, Quinn & White (2017) have noted that there is less music written in TCs that have many black keys than music in TCs that have little to no black keys in a corpus analysis of 995 pieces in major TCs. The following two figures show their findings of how often the different TCs were used (C_{maj} nearly 4 times as much as F \sharp _{maj}), and how often individual notes were used (white/natural notes used more than black/accented notes). These findings are also consistent with the findings of several other researchers (e.g. Marvin & Brinkman, 2000; Temperley & Marvin, 2008; Prince & Schmuckler, 2014). Furthermore, TCs with little to no black keys are recognised faster and more accurately than TCs with more black keys by both absolute pitch (AP) listeners and non-AP listeners, which reveals a white-note bias in both pitch identification and preference (Takeuchi & Hulse, 1991; 1993; Marvin & Brinkman,

2000). Since the piano has been a staple in music composition and performance for several centuries, then it is possible that its keyboard layout have contributed to the development of the characteristics associated with the different TCs. For example, the convenience of access to C_{maj} by playing only the white keys and not having any accented keys could be the reason why many people have associated it with purity and simplicity¹ as can be seen in appendix A (section 3).

Figure 2.4: Major TCs distribution by duration over a corpus (Quinn & White, 2017, p. 538)

Figure 2.5: Note distribution by duration over a corpus (Quinn & White, 2017, p. 538)

- **Open strings:** string instruments, such as the violin, viola, cello, and double bass, have their four strings pre-tuned to specific notes called open string notes (violin: G – D – A – E, viola and cello: C – G – D – A, double bass: E – A – D – G), which can be played by running the bow down on the string without any fingers touching the fingerboard (Drabkin, 1985). Open string notes have the unique feature of convenient

¹ It's important to note that the association of C_{maj} with purity cannot be a result of its keys being white. Modern pianos have uniformed the key colours of the keyboard as white for natural notes and black for accented notes. However, period keyboard instruments from the 17th, 18th, and some of the 19th centuries such as the fortepiano or the harpsichord have had either reversed colours (black for natural and white for accented, such as Mozart's personal fortepiano), or sometimes brown or yellow/golden and black (Dolge, 1972).

accessibility as they do not require a finger on the fingerboard to perform them. However, this means that vibrato¹ cannot be performed on the open string notes. Vibrato is typically performed to “increase the emotional quality of the tone” (Apel, 1944, p. 900), and became common practice as of mid-Classical era, however, it was generally unfavoured during the Baroque era (Neumann, 1991; Fischbach, 1998). Furthermore, the open strings offer a clear and resonant sound quality, which is ideal for the final resolving note or chord, and since Baroque music disapproved of vibrato, then it did not mind compromising the open strings inability to perform it in order to benefit from the open strings easy access, clear sound, and resonant nature (Gable, 1992). This availability of open strings as fixed pitches may have influenced the choice of TCs in music compositions during the Baroque era, which then influenced much of the music in the succeeding eras as well, as TCs of the open string notes were generally favoured (Fischbach, 1998).

- **Brass instruments:** brass instruments, such as the trumpet or horn, are designed with tubing lengths that are naturally more suited to those specific notes (Fromme, 1972). For example, a typical concert trumpet (known as trumpet in B \flat), provides easy access to C, E, and G, without having to press any of its three valves. Access to other natural notes such as D, F, A, and B is also relatively easy by pressing on only one valve. The design of a typical concert horn (known as horn in F) also generally prioritises natural notes over accented ones (Baines, 1993). This instrumental configuration has significant implications for composers, as they usually consider the physical characteristics of brass instruments when writing for them, taking into account their advantages and disadvantages in terms of access to certain notes (Baines, 1993; Campbell, Gilbert & Myers, 2021). Compositions written in TCs that align with the natural notes of the instruments tend to exploit their unique sonorities, optimised tuning, and ensure convenience of playability. As a result, specific TCs have become closely associated with the brass instruments’ repertoire (Baines, 1993). One of these TCs is D $_{\text{maj}}$, which, as can be seen in appendix A (section 3), has been repeatedly associated with militant, victorious, and heavenly traits, which may be due to the boldness and fullness of the brass instruments’ sound quality.

All these design configurations of music instruments coupled with the discrepancies of early tuning systems of western music theory have skewed the distribution of TCs to only a handful of them while marginalising others (Prince & Schmuckler, 2014). Musicians across different periods now favour particular TCs for their supposed expressive qualities, technical

¹ On stringed instruments, a vibrato is a slight fluctuation of pitch produced by quick oscillation of the string on the fingerboard (Apel, 1944).

demands, or idiomatic writing and notation for specific instruments and orchestral arrangements. As a result, a repertoire bias developed, with certain TCs becoming more popular than others (Quinn & White, 2017). This concentration of specific TCs is likely to have influenced our perception of music and may have contributed to the endurance of key characteristics and associations, even under 12-TET.

2.2.4. Attention:

Attention is a convoluted system of cognitive processes and neural mechanisms. It plays an essential role in the ability to perceive, process, interpret, and respond to sensory stimuli (Hommel *et al.*, 2019). The brain's attentional network involves a complex interplay of various brain regions and neural circuits; there's no one region responsible for all attentional processing. Rather, all different regions of the brain can contribute to these processes at different stages and degrees depending largely on the type of stimuli being processed (Posner & Petersen, 1990). Furthermore, attention is influenced by a multitude of factors other than external stimuli such as internal goals, individual differences, personal characteristics, and the context in which attention is deployed. Factors such as relevance, familiarity vs novelty, emotional involvement, and personal interests can also influence the allocation and direction of attention (Hubble, Duncan & Miller, 1999; Krauzlis *et al.*, 2021). Attention is an essential part of various cognitive, emotional, and behavioural functions, such as perception, memory, decision-making, and problem-solving. It allows for the prioritisation of relevant stimuli, elimination of redundant stimuli, and efficient allocation of cognitive resources (Posner & Rothbart, 2007; Posner, 2012).

Attention is generally classified into four main subtypes: sustained, selective, divided, and alternating. Sustained attention involves maintaining focus usually over a prolonged period. Selective attention allows the concentration on specific stimuli while ignoring others. Divided attention occurs by allocating attentional resources to multiple stimuli or tasks simultaneously. And alternating attention is the shifting of the attentional resources between stimuli or tasks (Mangun, 2012).

Attention cannot be reliably measured except directly as an Event-Related Potential (ERP) via neuroimaging tools such as electroencephalography (EEG). Such tools allow the capturing of the temporal information of the neural responses to stimuli, which enables researchers to analyse the neural correlates of attention and investigate how different factors, may modify attentional responses in individuals (Posner, 2012).

2.2.4.1. Neuroimaging:

Neuroimaging involves the use of various imaging technologies to visualise the structure and function of the brain. It offers a means to research the intricate inner-workings of the brain,

and investigating its underlying neural processes and various other neurological responses (Bandettini, 2009). There are several commonly used neuroimaging technologies, including structural imaging techniques such as Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) and Computed Tomography (CT), which provide detailed information about the brain's structure and morphology. While neural imaging techniques, such as Magnetoencephalography (MEG), functional Magnetic Resonance Imaging (fMRI), and Electroencephalography (EEG), measure brain activity and electrical patterns (Camprodon & Stern, 2013).

fMRI and MEG machines are advanced neuroimaging techniques that are often reserved for highly medical purposes. They are not very suitable for neuromarketing research due to several reasons. Firstly, they are expensive to acquire and run, rendering them less accessible for many researchers in the field. Secondly, fMRI machines generate loud noise during scanning, which can be uncomfortable and distracting for participants, potentially influencing their natural responses to the stimulus (Mangun, 2012; Posner, 2012). This is even especially true when the stimulus presented is auditory, such as in this research.

Contrarily, EEG is a more suitable and convenient method for neuromarketing research. EEG is relatively inexpensive compared to MEG and fMRI, especially considering the emergence of commercial EEG machines such as Emotive (Badcock *et al.*, 2013). EEG is also non-invasive, portable, makes no sound, and allows for some natural movement, making it ideal for studying participants' responses in real-world stimuli, such as viewing an advertisement. The increasing demand for neuroimaging has made EEGs accessible to disciplines outside of the medical and clinical environments for a fraction of the cost of medical EEGs (Alvino *et al.*, 2020; Sawangjai *et al.*, 2020; Williams *et al.*, 2020; Williams, McArthur & Badcock, 2020; Alsharif *et al.*, 2021; Williams, McArthur & Badcock, 2021).

2.2.4.2. Electroencephalography (EEG):

The brain consists of billions of interconnected neurons. These neurons communicate with one another by passing electrical signals along the brain fibres. While these signals are very small, usually in the millionth of a volt, they can be picked up on the surface of the scalp by using sensitive equipment (Camprodon & Stern, 2013). An EEG machine is an apparatus designed to measure these electrical signals. Typically, researchers record the brain's electrical activity using a headset or a cap, where there are several soft felt sensors on the inside of it. These sensors, called electrodes, are slightly wetted before the headset is worn, and they touch the surface of the head to pick up those very small electrical signals. Each one of those sensors picks up activity in a different area of the brain. The signals are conducting along cables to an amplifier, which converts the brain signals into digital signals that can be displayed, stored, and accessed via a computer (Casson *et al.*, 2018).

When the electrodes pick up signals, the computer screen will show, in real-time, a line for each electrode (e.g. in a case of an EEG machine with 64 electrodes, 64 electrical signal channels or lines of data can be seen). Typically, the top data lines represent brain activity from the front of the head, and the bottom data lines represent brain activity from the back of the head. The signals change all the time with many peaks and troughs occurring every second. The following graph illustrates an example of EEG raw data with 18 channels, where the X axis represents time, and the Y axis represents the channel:

Figure 2.6: EEG data example (Casson *et al.*, 2018, p. 48)

Several signal processing techniques are applied to this raw data to obtain meaningful information. However, it's often possible to observe a few patterns as the data is being collected in real-time. For example, occasionally, there might be visible troughs in the sensors towards the front of the head (upper channels), which could be eye blinks; an electrical signal coming from the muscles around the eyes. This signal is much larger than the brain activity signals, so it's common to remove it during the analysis stage (Hoffmann & Falkenstein, 2008; Motdhare & Mathur, 2022).

If the test participant closes their eyes during an EEG scan, the signals change drastically as the electrical signals slow down. Particularly, towards the back of the head where most of the visual processing occurs. There would also be less peaks and troughs per second. This is referred to as Alpha Activity, which is a good indication that the brain is not working hard; with the eyes closed, there's less stimuli entering the brain. And when the eyes reopen, the signal shows that active processing starts again (Croft & Barry, 2000).

Once data has been collected, there are two distinct ways of representing EEG signals. One approach is to view all the signals across the brain simultaneously (i.e. observing the average response of all electrodes together). And the other approach is to view the data from selected electrodes to observe the activity from the region of the brain where the electrode is set. Although, a precise location of activity is generally difficult to detect because EEG machines monitor activity in large groups of neurons, typically in the billions per electrode placement (Makeig *et al.*, 2004; Sawangjai *et al.*, 2020).

2.2.4.3. Attention as a Hebbian phenomenon:

Attention is an all-encompassing neural process that isn't exclusive to one region of the brain. Indeed, the level of attentional processing depends on a myriad of variables, external and internal: the stimulus and its type, the environment in which the stimulus is presented, the personal motivations, goals, and characteristics... etc. This means that attention engages a distributed network of interconnected areas all at once (Schumacher, 2021). One influential concept that supports this understanding is Hebb's Rule, which states that when a neuron cell persistently activates another nearby neuron cell, the connection between the two neuron cells becomes stronger (Hebb, 1949; Keysers & Gazzola, 2014). Hebb's Rule is often summarised by Shatz's (1992) statement "cells that fire together wire together" (p. 64), expressing that when certain neural pathways are repeatedly activated in response to certain stimuli, they become strengthened over time. And since attentional processing occurs across all regions of the brain, the repeated engagement of attention in response to stimuli can lead to the strengthening of neural connections throughout the distributed network involved in attention. This phenomenon, known as synaptic plasticity, allows for more efficient and synchronised processing of information related to the attended stimulus (Draganski *et al.*, 2006; Sumner *et al.*, 2020).

Since attentional processing occurs across various regions of the brain, it is important to consider the collective activity of neurons rather than focusing on a single region (Corbetta & Shulman, 2002). This means that analysing the EEG data collectively across all its electrodes as an average response will serve better than focusing on one region of the brain such as the frontal lobe, especially since monitoring regional activity via EEG is typically challenging (Sawangjai *et al.*, 2020). By monitoring the average activity, EEG can provide a holistic view of the brain's response during attentional processing. This approach aligns well with Hebb's Rule, as it captures the collective firing patterns and synchronisation of neural networks involved in the neural attention process (Schumacher, 2021). Nonetheless, regional data will still be accessible throughout the research and any interesting patterns of regional activity will be detected and reported.

2.2.5. Retention (*R*):

Retention refers to the ability to remember or recall information or experiences over time. It is the process by which information is stored in memory and later retrieved when needed. Retention can involve both short-term memory and long-term memory (Bordalo, Gennaioli & Shleifer, 2020). Retention is a crucial aspect of human cognition as it enables us to maintain knowledge, skills, past experiences, and use them to guide behaviours and make decisions (Ranganath and Ritchey, 2012; Klein, 2015).

Memory retention is a psychological and neurological process of everyday life. This section will look into retention from both a psychological perspective and a neurological perspective, discuss types of memory, and then consider what retention is in the context of advertising.

2.2.5.1. Retention from a psychological perspective:

Psychologically, retention is influenced by various factors. The encoding process¹ determines how information is initially processed and encoded into memory (Hintzman, 2004). Factors such as attention, elaboration (making connections and associations), organisation (structuring information), and meaningfulness of the information (relating new information to existing knowledge or personal experiences) can affect the encoding process and its subsequent retention (Ratcliff, 1978; Klein, 2015).

Once information is encoded, it enters the storage phase. Storage refers to the maintenance of encoded information over time. There are different types and stages of memory storage, including sensory memory, short-term memory, working memory, and long-term memory (Sligte *et al.*, 2010; Norris, 2017). Sensory memory briefly holds incoming sensory information, while short-term memory temporarily holds information for immediate processing via the working memory ability to manipulate information, which can then be transferred to long-term memory depending on many factors which will be detailed in the following sections. The effectiveness of storage can be influenced by factors such as the strength of memory traces, interference, and decay (Hardt, Nader & Nadel, 2013). The retrieval process involves accessing and bringing forth the stored information when needed or requested, and factors such as environment, cues, context, and retrieval strategies can impact the success of retrieval (Hintzman, 2004). Retrieval is often more effective when those factors at the time of encoding match the factors at the time of retrieval (e.g. if encoding occurs in a quiet, dimly lit, environment that has a specific scent, then retrieval would be easier under these conditions than the opposite conditions) (Schwabe & Wolf, 2009; Frankland, Josselyn & Köhler, 2019).

¹ Encoding is the initial process of transforming sensory data into a meaningful information that can be stored in memory. The way data is encoded can affect its subsequent retention (Klein, 2015).

2.2.5.2. Retention from a neurological perspective:

From a neurological perspective, retention involves complex processes across all regions of the brain. Encoding and storing information rely on the activity and connectivity of neurons in various brain regions, such as the hippocampus, prefrontal cortex (PFC), and medial temporal lobe (Buchsbaum *et al.*, 2015; Gabrieli, 1998). These regions play critical roles in memory formation and consolidation. Neural plasticity, particularly synaptic plasticity, underlies the long-term storage of memories (Bruel-Jungerman, Davis & Laroche, 2007). When information is initially encoded, it triggers synaptic changes and the strengthening of connections between neurons. This process, known as synaptic potentiation, is influenced by mechanisms such as long-term potentiation and Hebbian plasticity (Hardt, Nader and Nadel, 2013; Sumner *et al.*, 2020). This means that, similar to attention, retention is also subject to Hebb's Rule that when a neuron activates another nearby neuron, the connection between the two strengthens. This implies that retention is a distributed process that involves multiple regions of the brain, rather than being confined to a few specific regions (Guzman-Karlsson *et al.*, 2014).

Once the information is encoded, it undergoes a process called consolidation, which involves the stabilisation and strengthening of the information in the brain. Consolidation is thought to involve the transfer of information from short-term memory to long-term memory and the reorganisation of neural connections (Norris, 2017). This process is influenced by various factors such as emotional significance (Groch *et al.*, 2011; McGaugh, 2015), level of attention (Ricker *et al.*, 2018; Collins & Wamsley, 2020), sleep quality, frequency, and consistency (Groch *et al.*, 2011; Cousins, Wong & Chee, 2019).

During retention, the neural representations of memories are distributed across different brain regions, pathways, and networks. Retrieval involves the reactivation of these distributed patterns and pathways to access the stored information (Gabrieli, 1998). Neurotransmitters¹, such as dopamine (involved in the reinforcement of neural connections), and acetylcholine and norepinephrine (associated with attention and arousal, which can influence the encoding and consolidation of information) also play important roles in modulating memory processes and enhancing retention (Castellano, Cabib & Puglisi-Allegra, 1996; Buchsbaum *et al.*, 2015; Handra *et al.*, 2020).

Throughout the retention process, Different brain regions are triggered differently depending on the type of memory and information being retrieved. For instance, the hippocampus is

¹ Neurotransmitters are chemical substances that transmit signals between neurons in the brain and the nervous system. They play a crucial role in the communication and functioning of the brain by transmitting electrical impulses across synapses, which are the junctions between neurons. Examples of neurotransmitters include dopamine and serotonin (Handra *et al.*, 2020).

crucial for the retrieval of episodic memories. The hypothalamus is engaged in the retrieval of memories associated with surrounding environment conditions. The amygdala facilitates the retrieval of emotions-related memories. And the prefrontal cortex is involved in retrieving memories related to executive functions (Castellano, Cabib & Puglisi-Allegra, 1996; Mamiya *et al.*, 2009; Roozendaal & McGaugh, 2011). The activity of one region may be more than others, however, as per Hebb's Rule, many regions and neural pathways will be triggered simultaneously due to their established interconnectivity over time (Shatz, 1992; Schumacher, 2021).

Overall, retention involves the intricate interplay of various brain regions, neurotransmitters, and neural pathways. The encoding, consolidation, and retrieval of memories rely on several different stages of memory.

2.2.5.3. Memory stages and their processes:

There are several different stages of memory and they each underlie different processes. Memory is a fundamental cognitive function that allows for the encoding, storing, and retrieval of information. Understanding the various memory stages and how they interconnect will be important for this research. This section explores the major stages of memory, including sensory memory, short-term memory, working memory, and long-term memory, highlighting their distinct characteristics and the processes involved in each stage. The figure below illustrates the relationship between the different stages of memory, and their properties:

Figure 2.7: Memory stages and their processes.
Developed from Baddeley (2000), Alshahrani (2017) and Camina & Güell (2017)

- **Sensory memory (SM):** sometimes also referred to as sensory register is the initial stage of memory processing where sensory information from the surrounding environment is briefly stored in its original form (Sligte *et al.*, 2010). It is the first step in the information processing system and serves as a buffer between the external stimuli and the subsequent cognitive processes involved in perception and memory (Baddeley, 2000). Sensory memory holds sensory information for a very brief period, typically ranging from a few hundred milliseconds to a few seconds (Sams *et al.*, 1993; Gomes *et al.*, 1999). Its primary function is to retain a high-fidelity representation of sensory stimuli to allow the brain for further processing and interpretation (Kuhbandner, Rosas-Corona & Spachholz, 2017). There are different types of sensory memory corresponding to the different stimuli presented including iconic memory for visual stimuli, echoic memory for auditory stimuli, and haptic memory for touch stimuli (Coltheart, 1980; Mack *et al.*, 2016; Camina and Güell, 2017). Iconic memory holds visual information in the form of optic representations, which are highly detailed but quickly decay. Echoic memory, on the other hand, retains auditory information in a similar manner, allowing for the perception of brief auditory stimuli. Whereas haptic memory retains information from the sense of touch (Inui *et al.*, 2010; Nishihara *et al.*, 2014). Sensory memory acts as a rapid and automatic buffer, providing a continuous stream of sensory input to the cognitive system (Baddeley, 2000). It allows for the integration and interpretation of the incoming surrounding environment information, enabling the perception of a coherent and continuous experience of the world (Sligte *et al.*, 2010; Li & Cowan, 2021). While sensory memory has a large capacity to store information, it has a limited duration and is susceptible to decay and interference. Only a small portion of the sensory information is selected for further processing and interpretation, with most of the information fading away rapidly unless it is transferred via attentional strategies to other memory levels such as short-term memory, working memory, or long-term memory (Alshahrani, 2017).
- **Short-term memory (STM):** short-term memory is the temporary storage and manipulation of information in the brain for immediate use. It involves the ability to hold a limited amount of information for a short period of time, typically only a few seconds. Short-term memory plays a crucial role in various cognitive processes, such as comprehension, problem-solving, decision-making, and learning (Norris, 2017). Short-term memory is characterised by its limited capacity, which is the number of items that can be retained simultaneously, which was thought to be 7 ± 2 as per Miller's Law (Miller, 1956), however, it's now generally agreed that this number is 4 ± 1 (Cowan, 2001). This capacity may be increased through strategies like chunking

or grouping related items together (Hoddinott, Schuit & Grahn, 2021). The relationship between short-term memory and long-term memory is dynamic and interconnected. Short-term memory acts as a gateway for information to be encoded into long-term memory (Burgess & Hitch, 2006; Norris, 2017). When information is rehearsed, manipulated, and systemically categorised in short-term memory, it has a greater likelihood of being consolidated into working memory, which can lead to its transfer to long-term memory (Cowan, 1993; 2001; Jonides *et al.*, 2008). Effective encoding strategies and rehearsal techniques in short-term memory can enhance the transfer of information to long-term memory (Hintzman, 2004).

- **Working memory (WM):** short-term memory and working memory are related but distinctly different within the fields of cognitive psychology and functional neurology. While they both involve the short temporary storage of information, only working memory involves the active and systematic manipulation of the different items of information (Sligte *et al.*, 2010; Ricker *et al.*, 2018). It encompasses the cognitive processes of updating and rehearsing information in real time with the objective to maintain it for a longer period of time as the information is deemed relevant and important (Li & Cowan, 2021). Working memory consists of various subsystems responsible for manipulating different types of information: central executive (coordinates resource allocation and manages capacity), phonological loop (retains verbal information), the visuo-spatial sketchpad (retains visual and spatial information), and episodic buffer (retains semantic information) (Baddeley, 2000; Alshahrani, 2017). These subsystems often function together to allow information to transfer to long-term memory.
- **Long-term memory (LTM):** long-term memory refers to the storage and retention of information over an extended period of time, ranging from a few minutes to years (Norris, 2017). It is the repository of accumulated knowledge, experiences, and skills that persist beyond the immediate present, and it allows for the remembering of past events, facts, processes, and personal experiences (Burgess and Hitch, 2006; Sumner *et al.*, 2020). It also plays an important role in shaping and facilitating various cognitive processes such as problem-solving (Cowan, 2008). Long-term memory is characterised by its vast capacity and relatively enduring nature compared to sensory, short-term, or working memories. It can store a seemingly unlimited amount of information, ranging from specific details to abstract concepts (Park *et al.*, 1996; Cowan, 2001; Wood, Baxter & Belpaeme, 2011). Long-term memory can be accessed both explicitly (sometimes referred to as active, conscious, or declarative) or implicitly (sometimes referred to as passive, subconsciously, or non-declarative) (Tulving, 1993; Squire & Dede, 2015). Explicit and implicit long-term memories can

be further sub-categorised into different types: explicit memory includes episodic memory (the retrieval of specific events and personal experiences), and semantic memory (the retrieval of general knowledge and facts), whereas implicit memory includes procedural memory (the retrieval of executive and motor skills such as walking or driving), associative memory (the retrieval of information resulting from an association with other information such as Pavlovian responses like certain smells reminding of their associated taste), non-associative memory (the retrieval of newly learned behaviour due to repeated exposure to a single stimulus. It can either lead to a decrease in response, known as habituation, such as tolerating strong odours over repeated exposure, or increase in response, known as sensitisation, such as becoming sensitive to loud noises over repeated exposure), and priming memory (the retrieval of information whereby exposure to certain stimuli influences the response to subsequently presented stimuli such as recalling the word 'fruit' faster when primed with the word 'apple' earlier) (Camina & Güell, 2017).

2.2.5.4. Retention in the context of advertising:

Retention is considered an important aspect in the advertising process as the prime goal is not only to capture viewers' attention, but also to transfer brand information that consumers can then recall and use to take a form of action (Yeoh & North, 2010b). The effectiveness of the retention levels of an ad can be measured by the extent to which individuals are able to recall some of the key elements of it, such as the core message and brand information conveyed (Bolls, Lang & Potter, 2001; Taher & El Badawy, 2022).

The retention of ad information is influenced by various factors such as attention to the ad, core message, content elements, emotional appeal, and personal goals and traits (Morris & Boone, 1998; Mehta & Purvis, 2006). A well-designed and memorable ad is typically one that optimises these factors.

Retention of ad information begins at the encoding process discussed earlier. Once ad information is encoded, it enters the storage phase. Memory storage can be in any of the memory stages (sensory, short-term, working, or long-term) (Alexomanolaki, Loveday & Kennett, 2006). Effective advertising aims to facilitate the transfer of information all the way through these stages to embed a long-term impression on consumers so they can retain as much information as possible for as long as possible, until they ultimately utilise this information to take action (usually characterised in purchase) (Allan, 2006; 2007)

The success of an ad lies in its ability to trigger retrieval cues that prompt individuals to recall the brand or specific components of the ad. This can be achieved through distinctive branding, memorable slogans, catchy jingles, or visually striking imagery (Yalch, 1991;

Wallace, 1994; Shakil & Siddiqui, 2019). The use of repetition and reinforcement also aids in retrieval by strengthening memory associations (Schmidt and Eisend, 2015).

Advertising research often measures retention through recall and recognition tests. Recall tests assess the ability of individuals to retrieve specific information about the ad or brand from memory (Alexomanolaki, Loveday & Kennett, 2006). Recognition tests, on the other hand, examine whether individuals can identify the ad or brand from a set of options (Li and Lo, 2014). High levels of recall and recognition indicate strong retention and suggest that the ad has effectively made an impact on consumers' memory (Jin, Suh & Donavan, 2008).

To enhance retention, advertisers employ various strategies. These may include repetition of key messages, the use of mnemonic devices to aid memory, creating emotional connections through storytelling, and employing visual or auditory stimuli that leave a lasting impression (Yalch, 1991; Mehta & Purvis, 2006; Herget, Schramm & Breves, 2018). The goal is to create a memorable experience that lingers in consumers' minds, increasing the likelihood of future brand recall and recognition, positive attitudes, and purchase intentions.

In the context of this research, retention (*R*) is to the ability of individuals to retain brand information presented to them in an ad. It involves the process of encoding the information during exposure to the ad (while viewing a documentary in order to proximate a realistic environment of ad exposure), then storing that information in memory, and later retrieving it when requested. Assessing retention in this research will involve post-stimulus long-term retention tests to evaluate participants' ability to retain and retrieve information related to the ads presented (this will be detailed much further in the Research Design chapter).

2.2.6. Purchase Intention (*PI*):

Purchase intention is an individual's inclination or willingness to buy a product or service in the future (Peña-García *et al.*, 2020). It's measured by the likelihood or probability that a consumer will engage in a purchase behaviour based on their current attitudes, beliefs, and evaluations of the brand (Spears & Singh, 2004). Purchase intention is a key concept in consumer behaviour and marketing research as it provides insights into consumers' predisposition to make a purchase decision, which is a late-stage action in the consumer journey (Munthiu, 2009).

Purchase intention is influenced by many variables including the consumer's perceptions of the product's values, quality, price, reputation, availability of alternatives, and personal needs and preferences (Lim *et al.*, 2016; Dachyar & Banjarnahor, 2017). Other factors such as marketing communication, promotional activities, word-of-mouth, and social influences can also aid or hinder purchase intention (Zhao *et al.*, 2020).

It's worth noting that while purchase intention indicates consumers' willingness to buy, it does not necessarily guarantee their readiness to buy (Munthiu, 2009; Indiani & Fahik, 2020). Other external barriers may come into play between intention and action, such as availability of funds, accessibility, competitive alternatives, or situational factors (Wilson, 2003; Lu & Su, 2009).

Understanding purchase intention is important for advertisers as it helps predict consumers' future behaviours. By assessing consumers' intentions to purchase, advertisers can tailor their marketing strategies, product offerings, and promotional efforts to effectively influence and convert potential customers into actual buyers (Lim *et al.*, 2016). Measuring and tracking purchase intention via market research allows businesses to gauge the effectiveness of their campaigns and make informed decisions that help them reach their desired goals (Alpert, Alpert & Maltz, 2005).

2.2.6.1. Measuring purchase intention:

Various methods and approaches have been developed to gauge purchase intention, each offering unique insights into consumers' decision-making process. The following will explore these different measurement tools, including self-report measures, behavioural measures, and neuromarketing approaches:

- **Self-Report Measures:** self-report measures are commonly used to assess the levels of purchase intention and involve explicitly asking individuals to provide their subjective intentions related to taking an action characterised by purchasing a brand (Li *et al.*, 2018). This can be done through questionnaires, interviews, or focus groups. Self-report measures often include Likert-scale items or semantic differential scales to capture participants' attitudes, beliefs, or intentions regarding their likelihood of purchasing (Friborg, Martinussen & Rosenvinge, 2006). These measures provide valuable insights into individuals' self-perceived intentions, motivations, and preferences, allowing researchers to understand the factors influencing purchase decisions from the perspective of consumers themselves (Lim *et al.*, 2016). However, self-reporting measures can be influenced by many factors, both internal and external, which may introduce certain limitations to their accuracy and reliability for research. Internal factors can be psychological and cognitive biases that can affect participants' self-reporting (Bergkvist & Langner, 2019). For example, individuals may have inherent biases in their responses due to social desirability, where they may provide answers that align with societal norms or what they perceive as socially acceptable. This desire for social validation and acceptance may lead to over-reporting positive purchase intentions or under-reporting negative ones (Fisher

& Katz, 2000; Vavreck, 2007). The degree to which self-reporting may skew towards these biases largely depends on the topic being investigated, whereby sensitive topics are more likely to generate biased answers than topics that are unproblematic or non-controversial (Walsh, 1967). Additionally, individuals may have personal biases that influence their self-reports. These biases can include cognitive biases such as confirmation bias, where individuals selectively recall or interpret information that confirms their pre-existing beliefs or expectations (Fisher, 2000). This can result in distorted self-reporting of purchase intention as individuals may unknowingly emphasise information that supports their preferred outcomes (Vavreck, 2007). External factors, on the other hand, can also impact self-report measures. For example, the context in which the measurement takes place, the wording of the questions, or the order in which questions are presented can introduce biases (Li *et al.*, 2018). Individuals may also be influenced by priming effects, where previous questions or stimuli can subtly influence their subsequent responses, which "may provide a simple, straightforward method for motivating participants to provide honest responses to self-report measures" (Rasinski *et al.*, 2005, p. 326). The presence of social cues or the perception of being observed during data collection can also influence self-reports, as individuals may modify their answers to align with perceived expectations or norms (Fisher, 2000; Fisher & Katz, 2000). Furthermore, external factors also include the environment in which participants' responses are measured; online surveys with complete anonymity, for instance, may reduce personal biases more than interviews, which may be intimidating for some participants, or focus groups where participants' answers may be influenced by their peers (Bergkvist & Langner, 2019). Moreover, participants' level of comfort within the measuring environment may also influence their responses. Overall, these limitations highlight the importance of considering potential biases and taking steps to mitigate them. Researchers can employ strategies such as anonymity, confidentiality, simulation of real decision-making environment, randomisation of question order, and careful wording of questions to minimise biases and enhance the reliability of self-reported data (Vavreck, 2007; Bergkvist & Langner, 2019).

- **Behavioural Measures:** behavioural measures assess purchase intention by examining participants' behaviours or behavioural indicators related to purchase decisions (Morrison, 1979). This approach focuses on observing and analysing their actions, such as their purchasing history, actual purchases made, or intention-related behaviours, such as adding items to a shopping cart, visiting specific product webpages, or engaging with or seeking out pre-purchase information (Ling, Chai & Piew, 2010; Lim *et al.*, 2016). Behavioural measures provide more objective and

tangible data than self-report measure as they offer insights into real-world consumer behaviour and purchase choices (Barber *et al.*, 2012). These measures can be collected through transactional records, online tracking systems and analytics, or through controlled experiments in laboratory or field settings such in-store shopping observations (Yalch & Spangenberg, 1990; Peña-García *et al.*, 2020).

- **Neuromarketing Approaches:** neuromarketing techniques offer a more nuanced understanding of purchase intention by investigating the underlying neural processes associated with consumer decision-making (Bell *et al.*, 2018). These approaches utilise neuroscientific tools such as fMRI, EEG, or eye-tracking technology to measure brain activity, physiological responses, or eye movements (McDuff *et al.*, 2015; Garczarek-Bąk *et al.*, 2021). By monitoring brain activity or physiological markers, researchers can gain insights into consumers' subconscious reactions, physiological reactions, emotional responses, or attentional patterns during the evaluation of purchase options (Bell *et al.*, 2018; Pozharliev, Rossi & De Angelis, 2022). Neuromarketing approaches can complement self-report and behavioural measures by capturing implicit or subconscious aspects of consumer decision-making, however, they tend to be relatively expensive and time consuming. Furthermore, neuroimaging data analysis is significantly different from self-report and behavioural measures data, and it's more difficult to analyse.

2.2.6.2. Purchase intention measurement within this research:

This research will utilise self-report measures to gauge participants' purchase intention (*PI*) via a three-item tool of Likert scale statements by Grewal, Monroe, & Krishnan's (1998). Self-report is perhaps the weakest measurement tool to gauge purchase intention. It is important to acknowledge the limitations of self-report measures, such as the potential for response biases, social desirability influences, and reliance on participants' self-perception and introspection. To mitigate these limitations and enhance the validity of the results, several cautionary considerations will be implemented. These include providing clear instructions, ensuring anonymity and confidentiality, using validated measurement scales, and conducting low-profile presence of the researcher while participants answer the purchase intention questionnaire. By taking these precautions, this research enhances the reliability and meaningfulness of the purchase intention data, which contributes to a more comprehensive understanding of consumer behaviour.

2.3. Theoretical Framework:

The aforementioned overview of the research variables was necessary for the comprehension of the theoretical framework, which will be detailed in this section, and further called upon throughout the literature review, and the entire research. The theoretical framework of this research will help conceptualise its themes and guide the investigation into the advertising music factors, especially tonal centres, that influence attention, retention, and purchase intention. Due to the interdisciplinary nature of this research, it's difficult to pinpoint one suitable theory to adopt as the main framework for the entire research. Aboelela *et al.* (2007) stressed the need for interdisciplinary studies to expand their theoretical framework to encompass different relevant theories from the disciplines it joins. They have stated that:

Interdisciplinary research is any study or group of studies undertaken by scholars from two or more distinct scientific disciplines. The research is based upon a conceptual model that links or integrates theoretical frameworks from those disciplines, uses study design and methodology that is not limited to any one field, and requires the use of perspectives and skills of the involved disciplines throughout multiple phases of the research process.

— (p. 341)

Hence, it's not only desirable to engage in several theoretical concepts to foster the arguments within this research, but it's also necessary. Reducing the conceptual scope of the research will only undermine the comprehensive understanding of the relationships between its variables. Whereas, by integrating multiple theoretical perspectives, this research can provide a more nuanced explanation of phenomena (Tobi & Kampen, 2018).

As seen in the figure below (and later discussed in depth), the current research will draw upon several relevant theories to address the themes from the different disciplines involved. These theories will discuss problematisation, classical conditioning, elaboration likelihood model (ELM), music congruence, attention economy, and the theory of planned behaviour.

Figure 2.8: Research framework synthesis

2.3.1. Problematisation:

Problematisation serves as the initial theoretical framework in this research, particularly within the discipline of music theory. It has been employed in the first chapter to generate the research questions and hypotheses by directly challenging the Transpositional Invariance Assumption (TIA), which posits that music perception is invariant under transposition (i.e. perception of the different tonal centres (TCs) is similar). This assumes that the perceived cognitive impact of the music remains consistent across different TCs. However, through problematisation, this assumption is critically examined, recognising that the TCs may indeed play a significant role in shaping the listener's cognitive responses.

Problematisation, drawing inspiration from the work of Foucault (1972), serves as a profound theoretical framework for this research, transcending the boundaries of music theory and delving deeper into the broader realm of knowledge production and power dynamics.

Foucault's insights on problematisation illuminate the intricate relationship between the construction of knowledge, social practices, and the exercise of power (Stengers, 2021).

Foucault's notion of problematisation emphasises the transformative potential of critical inquiry. It highlights the importance of questioning taken-for-granted assumptions, availing the opportunity for alternative perspectives and new ways of thinking. This means that within the context of this research, problematisation challenges the dominant discourse that overlooks the nuanced role of TCs. Thus, challenging music theory itself. It invites the rethinking of the theoretical notions used to establish some of the main components of music understanding and research.

As a theoretical framework, problematisation will assist in critiquing the Transpositional Invariance Assumption (TIA), providing Foucauldian perspectives on problematisation, unveiling the historical power dynamics of music theory, and reconceptualising music theory for this research.

2.3.1.1. Critiquing the Transpositional Invariance Assumption (TIA):

The first step in critiquing the TIA is to provide a comprehensive understanding of the assumption itself. The TIA has long been upheld as a foundational premise in music theory and research, suggesting that the TCs of music under the 12-TET tuning system are similar in all aspects except for pitch, and that this variance has no influences on music cognitive or emotional perception (Quinn & White, 2017; Lattner, Grachten, & Widmer, 2018).

Problematising the TIA invites a critical examination of the assumptions that have shaped the study of music perception. Indeed, the TIA has provided a simplified framework for research, focusing primarily on other musical elements such as melody, rhythm, tempo... etc., while overlooking the nuanced role of TCs. This assumption has skewed the literature

towards these other variables and away from the potential influence of the TCs. At best, some research investigated the differences between major tonalities and minor tonalities as two tonal categories, without thoroughly investigating each TC within these categories (Stout, Leckenby, & Hecker, 1990; Kellaris & Kent, 1992; 1993; Zander, 2006). This narrow focus limited the understanding of how different TCs may evoke distinct cognitive and emotional responses in listeners (Quinn & White, 2017). As discussed before, this skewness in research away from tonality has created a research gap which may explain some of the contradiction in the current body of literature surrounding the topic of this research.

Furthermore, the TIA fails to account for personal associations with specific TCs which can shape an individual's cognitive and emotional responses to music. Evidently, it assumes no personal associations after the adoption of 12-TET in Western classic music theory. By disregarding these subjective factors, the TIA neglects the diversity of listeners' experiences and their unique interpretations of music.

2.3.1.2. Foucauldian perspectives on problematisation:

According to Foucault (1972), problematisation is an active process that helps constitute the assumptions of phenomena prior to challenging them. This means that by attempting to disrupt and challenge the status quo, problematisation paradoxically defines it first, and labels it as a 'problem' when it's not deemed as such. A central goal of problematisation is then to "disrupt the reproduction and continuation of an institutionalised line of reasoning" (Sandberg & Alvesson, 2011, p. 32). Furthermore, problematisation is not seen as an end stage. Contrarily, it allows the initiation of highlighting flaws in phenomena and addressing ways to remedy them (Foucault, 1975).

Foucault's (1984) perspective on problematisation clearly does not always call for unconditional radicalisation of all phenomena at all times. It requires the careful understanding of historical nuances as well as the necessity, possibility, and desirability for change. He states that:

... this work done at the limits of ourselves must, on the one hand, open up a realm of historical inquiry and, on the other, put itself to the test of reality, of contemporary reality, both to grasp the points where change is possible and desirable, and to determine the precise form this change should take.

— (p. 43)

However, Foucault is notoriously difficult to read and interpret (Danaher, Schirato, & Webb, 2000). Stengers (2021), for example, finds his views on problematisation confounding, as she reads his work as one that leaves no option but to experiment with possibility in some cases, such as climate change. She states that "possibility may seem foolish, but today there is no way of avoiding the option" (p. 89).

There have been further claims about his work being structuralist (Hoy, 1986), post-structuralist (Agger, 1991), and post-modernist (Danaher, Schirato, & Webb, 2000). Grenz (1996) argues that Foucault is far too complex of a thinker to have his work labelled under one ideology, and that his work can be interpreted differently depending on both the era and area of focus. Indeed, Foucault (1972, 1975) stresses that knowledge should be used in different discourses and practices that frame the knowledge formulated from within them, which Agger (1991) supports, mentioning that “Foucault makes more use of everyday experience and ordinary language to define the parameters of these paradigmatic knowledges” (p. 117).

This goes against Hoy (1986) who believes that even though Foucault provides conceptual tools to problematise phenomena, he’s unable to detail how these tools may operate within empirical contexts, and that while Foucauldian problematisation offers profound insights into power dynamics, knowledge production, and their subjectivity, its abstract nature can present challenges when it comes to translating these ideas into concrete empirical studies. Hoy’s critique raises questions about the feasibility of employing Foucauldian problematisation as a methodological approach. Without clear guidelines on how to operationalise problematisation within empirical contexts, researchers, especially those in the social sciences, may find themselves grappling with the practicalities of applying Foucault’s ideas into their research (Danaher, Schirato, & Webb, 2000). The gap between theory and practice becomes apparent, leaving room for interpretation and potential inconsistencies in the implementation of Foucauldian problematisation.

However, one can also argue that this tension between theory and practice is not necessarily a limitation of Foucault’s writings. Rather, it’s an invitation to engage in a continuous discourse of interpretation, adaptation, and recontextualisation of phenomena (Deacon, 2000). Foucault’s conceptual framework offers a rich and complex understanding of power, knowledge, and subjectivity, which requires thoughtful and creative engagement to bridge the gap between theory and empirical research.

By acknowledging the inherent challenges of operationalising Foucauldian problematisation, this research can explore innovative ways to bring these ideas into empirical investigations. This involves a philosophical commitment to reflexivity, critical thinking, and methodological flexibility (Link, 2004; Terwiel, 2020; Stengers, 2021)

Moreover, Foucault himself acknowledged the need for adaptability and context-specific approaches in his work (Foucault, 1972; 1982; 1984). He recognised that problematisation is not a fixed methodology but a conceptual framework that can be adapted and tailored to specific contexts and research questions. This acknowledgement creates possibilities for

researchers to creatively incorporate Foucauldian insights, such as the freeing of assumptions, into their empirical studies while remaining attentive to the unique demands and constraints of their research contexts (Deacon, 2000).

Based on the adaptability of Foucauldian problematisation, it's possible to expect the following when properly implemented in this research:

- **Analytical depth and critical insights:** Foucauldian problematisation offers a unique analytical depth that goes beyond surface-level explanations and norms. By examining the historical, social, and discursive dimensions of power, problematisation can uncover hidden mechanisms of control and exposes underlying structures that shape the understanding of phenomena (Danaher, Schirato, & Webb, 2000). This critical lens provides valuable insights for researchers seeking to unravel complex social, cultural, and institutional dynamics that are deeply engrained into the literature, as in the case of this research.
- **Contextual sensitivity and flexibility:** Foucauldian problematisation emphasises the contextual nature of power relations and knowledge production. It encourages researchers to consider the specific historical, cultural, and social contexts in which phenomena occur (Grenz, 1996; Stengers 2021). This contextual sensitivity allows for a more nuanced and situated analysis, enabling researchers to capture the complexity and diversity of lived experiences and power dynamics within different contexts.
- **Interdisciplinary potential:** Foucauldian problematisation transcends disciplinary boundaries, making it a versatile approach applicable to various disciplines of investigation. Its focus on power, discourse, and subjectivity creates opportunities for interdisciplinary collaborations and enriches research inquiries by incorporating diverse perspectives (Takács, 2004). This interdisciplinary engagement fosters a holistic understanding of complex phenomena, drawing on insights from sociology, anthropology, psychology, the natural sciences, and other relevant disciplines.
- **Empowering marginalised discourses:** Foucauldian problematisation brings attention to the voices and experiences of marginalised individuals and groups who are often excluded from dominant narratives for challenging the status quo. By problematising power structures and challenging theoretical systems, further theoretical and practical discussions can be had (Agger, 1991; Terwiel, 2020).
- **Reflexive research practice:** Foucauldian problematisation encourages researchers to reflect critically on their own positionality, biases, and assumptions. It promotes self-awareness and constant reflexivity across the different research processes, acknowledging that researchers are not neutral, objective observers but actively and

subjectively involved in knowledge production (Beckett & Nayak, 2008). This is what Link (2004, p. 17) describes as “flexible normalism”, which can enhance the overall rigor of research.

- **Practical applications:** Researchers have employed Foucauldian problematisation concepts and methodologies to investigate topics such as healthcare systems (Frederiksen, Lomborg, & Beedholm, 2015), educational institutions (Alvesson & Sandberg, 2011), criminal justice systems (Terwiel, 2020), sports (Crocket, 2016), and many more. These practical applications demonstrate the adaptability and relevance of Foucauldian problematisation in understanding and transforming real-world phenomena.

2.3.1.3. Historical power dynamics of music theory:

One key aspect of Foucauldian problematisation is the recognition that knowledge and power are intimately intertwined (Hoy, 1986). Foucault argued that knowledge is not a neutral or objective entity, but rather is shaped by subjective existing power relations and dynamics (Foucault, 1975). Problematisation involves questioning the mechanisms through which knowledge is produced, regulated, and disseminated. It exposes how certain forms of knowledge and expertise become authoritative and dominant, while alternative perspectives and voices are marginalised or excluded, which is why he encouraged for the challenging of established norms and practices (Stengers, 2021). This implies that Foucault’s notions on problematisation do not only involve the identification and interrogation of the underlying assumptions, but also the identification and interrogation of history that helped shape them (Sandberg & Alvesson, 2011).

Foucault (1982) further argues that in order to fathom the power dynamics of phenomena, people should investigate different forms of challenging them. He states:

Rather than analyzing power from the point of view of its internal rationality, it consists of analyzing power relations through the antagonism of strategies. For example, to find out what our society means by sanity, perhaps we should investigate what is happening in the field of insanity. And what we mean by legality in the field of illegality. And, in order to understand what power relations are about, perhaps we should investigate the forms of resistance and attempts made to dissociate these relations.

— (p. 780)

The powers embedded within the TIA and the dominant discourse that perpetuates it is several centuries old. Problematisation allows for the questioning of the underlying motives and interests that may have shaped the adoption and perpetuation of this assumption in music theory. This may uncover potential historical biases that explain the attractiveness of this assumption.

There are several historical, institutional, and technical practices that influenced the construction of music theory and music knowledge upon which the TIA is built:

- **Historical factors:** the historical development of music theory and its emphasis on certain theoretical frameworks and paradigms may have contributed to the perpetuation of the TIA. The evolution of tonal music during the Baroque, Classical, and Romantic periods, and the focus on harmonic structures in Western classical music tradition have shaped the assumptions and perspectives regarding tonal centres (Snyder, 1990). Prior to the adoption of 12-TET as the main tuning system in Western classical music, $\frac{1}{4}$ CMT was the prevailing tuning system, which, as discussed in the introduction chapter, indeed created tonal discrepancies between different TCs, rendering some of them sounding out of tune, resulting in the alienation from certain TCs and the characterisation of them (Sethares, 2005; True, 2018). This problem has been recognised a few centuries prior to finding a solution that equalises the tonal discrepancies across all TCs. Johann Fux, Jean-Philippe Rameau, and J.S. Bach are a few who expressed a need for a tonal system change. Indeed, Bach's Well-Tempered Clavier¹ is seen as one of the prime attempts to break from the $\frac{1}{4}$ CMT into something that utilises all TCs (Daum, 2011). However, it wasn't until the early 19th century that 12-TET became the main tuning system and equalised the tonal differences between all TCs, which led to assuming that transposition across them is perceptually invariant (Quinn & White, 2017).
- **Institutional influences:** educational and pedagogical traditions in music instruction have played a role in perpetuating certain notions in music theory. Traditional approaches to music education have focused on the teaching of functional harmony, chord progressions, and voice leading, often implicitly emphasising the notion of transpositional invariance of TCs. Furthermore, the dissemination of music literature, textbooks, and scholarly articles plays a role in shaping this discourse (Skelton, 2004). Publishing practices and the peer review process within academic journals may favour studies that align with existing theoretical frameworks and assumptions (Snyder, 1990). This institutional influence can contribute to a limited representation of alternative perspectives.
- **Technical desires and limitations:** as mentioned earlier, 12-TET was the outcome of the desire for a system that does not render some TCs practically redundant while

¹ Bach's Well-Tempered Clavier is a collection of keyboard music consisting of two volumes. Each volume contains a set of preludes and fugues in all 24 major and minor keys. The collection was composed in the early 18th century and is considered a landmark in Western classical music. It is renowned for its technical complexity, musical depth, and its significance in exploring the possibilities of a tuning system that allows for the performance of music in all TCs. Music theorists argue whether or not Bach intended for 12-TET or some other tuning system (Williams, 1983).

utilising only some of them. However, equalising all TCs from a physical perspective resulted in the assumption that all TCs are also equal from a cognitive perspective (Quinn & White, 2017; Lattner, Grachten, & Widmer, 2018), which may not be the case, especially given the fact that some TCs are still favoured for technical and habitual reasons. Furthermore, there could also be acoustical and psychoacoustical factors that perpetuate the assumption. For example, the physical properties of sound such as pitch, harmony, and timbre¹, interact with the human auditory system to shape our perception of music. However, the technical limitations of sound recording, reproduction, and analysis may not fully capture the intricacies and nuances of tonality (True, 2018). These technical limitations can hinder a comprehensive understanding of how different TCs may influence listeners' cognitive responses, thus maintaining the assumption that music perception is invariant under transposition until these technical limitations can be overcome.

2.3.1.4. Reconceptualising tonality for this research:

This research does not propose a radical paradigm shift in music theory as it's known today. In fact, Foucault (1984) rejects the sudden substitution of contemporary tradition by novel radicalised new ideas. He argues that:

... the historical ontology of ourselves must turn away from all projects that claim to be global or radical. In fact we know from experience that the claim to escape from the system of contemporary reality so as to produce the overall programs of another society, of another way of thinking, another culture, another vision of the world, has led only to the return of the most dangerous traditions.

— (p. 43)

This research aligns with Foucault's cautionary stance, as it does not propose a outright transformation of tonality or music theory. Instead, it suggests a more nuanced approach by directing attention to the examination of tonal centres individually, rather than attempting to comprehend them in an all-encompassing dichotomous manner as either major or minor. The goal is not to dismantle the existing framework of music theory but rather to expand its boundaries by questioning assumptions that may have inadvertently stifled exploration and obscured the multifaceted nature of musical experience. This can be done by challenging the Transpositional Invariance Assumption. Problematisation offers an alternative theoretical framework that considers a potential influence of the different TCs on the perception of music itself and on the perception of other variables where music plays a mediating role, such as in this research.

¹ Timbre is often defined by what it's not rather than what it is. It's not the pitch, duration, or loudness of a note. For example, if a piano and a violin both played the note A (resonating at 440 Hz) for one second and at the same loudness, then timbre would be everything else that sets the two notes apart (Wu, Horner, & Lee, 2014).

2.3.2. Classical conditioning:

Music in advertising is used to achieve certain goals, such as improving brand recall or inducing certain emotions. However, its use is seldom based on empirical knowledge, and accordingly, little is known about the actual mechanisms of action of the use of music in advertising. If one looks at the empirical attempts to explain the effect of music in advertising, it can be observed that three concepts in particular are repeatedly used to explain it: Classical Conditioning and the Elaboration Likelihood Model theory (ELM), which will be discussed here consecutively.

Classical conditioning refers to the idea that the coupling of a conditioned stimulus (such as a product) with an unconditioned stimulus (positively rated advertising music) should create an association between the two, where the repeated exposure to the conditioned stimulus can trigger a positive emotional and cognitive response independent from the unconditioned stimulus. The figure below illustrates the dynamics of classical conditioning:

Figure 2.9: Classical conditioning model

Best known in this regard is the study by Gorn (1982), who combined images of light blue and beige pens with music that the participants liked (from the movie Grease) and with music that they did not like (classic Indian music). When faced with the decision of choosing to take a pen, almost 80% of the test participants selected the pen that had been connected to the music they liked. In the context of advertising, classical conditioning refers to a psychological process through which a neutral stimulus (later becomes conditioned stimulus) becomes associated with a positive or negative emotional response (unconditioned stimulus) to evoke a desired reaction from consumers (Allen & Madden, 1985). The goal of classical conditioning in advertising is to create an association between the advertised product or brand and a specific emotional or cognitive response, ultimately influencing consumer behaviour and decision-making (Stuart, Shimp, & Engle, 1987; Pitt & Abratt, 1988).

Classical conditioning relies on the principles of stimulus generalisation and the formation of associative links between stimuli. It assumes that consumers can develop automatic, subconscious associations between the conditioned stimulus (e.g. brand logo, jingle, slogan, advertising music) and the unconditioned stimulus (e.g. positive emotions, attractive imagery, celebrity endorsement, attention, information retention, purchase intention) (Petty, Cacioppo & Schumann, 1983). Over time, through repeated exposure and reinforcement, the conditioned stimulus alone can elicit a similar emotional or cognitive response, even without the presence of the unconditioned stimulus (Bitterman, 2006).

For example, in an advertisement for a luxury fragrance, the advertisement may pair the fragrance brand with beautiful imagery, elegant settings, and glamorous celebrities (unconditioned stimulus), while simultaneously presenting the brand logo and distinctive scent cues (conditioned stimulus). Through repeated exposure, consumers may begin to associate the brand logo and scent cues with the positive emotions evoked by the imagery and overall aesthetic. As a result, the conditioned stimulus (brand logo and scent cues) alone may trigger a positive emotional response and influence consumers' perceptions, preferences, and purchasing decisions when encountering the brand in the future.

It's important to note that classical conditioning in advertising is not limited to positive associations. Negative associations can also be created or altered through conditioning, depending on the intended advertising message and strategy. While positive associations are commonly sought after, negative associations can also be intentionally created (Bierley, McSweeney, & Vannieuwkerk, 1985).

Advertisers may strategically aim to create negative associations to influence consumer behaviour. For example, in anti-smoking campaigns, advertisements often associate smoking with negative health consequences, unpleasant images, or social disapproval. By pairing the act of smoking (conditioned stimulus) with aversive stimuli or messages (unconditioned stimulus), advertisers may be able to create a negative emotional and cognitive response to smoking, thereby influencing behaviour by discouraging individuals from it (Hashimoto & Higashiyama, 2022).

In addition to intentional negative associations, classical conditioning in advertising can also lead to unintended associations. This is because conditioning operates on a subconscious level and individuals may form associations without consciously realising it (Allen & Madden, 1985). Advertisers may inadvertently create associations that they were not aware of or did not intend to create, and these unintended associations may be either positive or negative (Pitt & Abratt, 1988; Grossman, 1997).

For instance, an advertisement for a fast-food restaurant may feature popular music, vibrant colours, and joyful characters. While the intention may be to associate the brand with positive emotions and enjoyment, some viewers may also form unintended associations with either unhealthy eating habits or childhood nostalgia. These unintended associations can have both positive and negative effects on consumers' behaviour towards the brand.

It is crucial for advertisers to be mindful of the potential unintended associations that may arise through classical conditioning. They should carefully consider the context, imagery, and messaging used in their advertisements to minimise the risk of unintended negative associations (Grossman, 1997). Conducting thorough research, pre-testing, and audience analysis usually help advertisers identify and mitigate these potential unintended associations (Stuart, Shimp, & Engle, 1987). Moreover, advertisers should continually monitor and evaluate consumer responses to their advertisements to assess the effectiveness and impact of classical conditioning. By gathering feedback and data from consumers, advertisers can gain insights into the associations that are being formed and make informed decisions regarding their advertising strategies (Pornpitakpan, 2012).

However, several studies refuted Gorn's (1982) results and to this day there is a debate as to whether classical conditioning should or can be taken into account as a process for advertising (Allen & Madden, 1985; Bierley, McSweeney & Vannieuwkerk, 1985; Pitt & Abratt, 1988; Bitterman, 2006; Ballouli & Heere, 2015). This is mainly because of two issues. The first issue is that classical conditioning assumes that the unconditioned stimulus operates peripherally, thus is processed subconsciously (Stuart, Shimp, & Engle, 1987). This should be a concern depending on the nature of the unconditioned stimulus used. Within the case of advertising music, there's ample evidence indicating that it does indeed operate peripherally (Suomala *et al.*, 2012; Herget, Schramm, & Breves, 2018; Breves, Herget, & Schramm, 2020; Herget, Breves, & Schramm, 2022; Uhm *et al.*, 2022). Therefore, this fact excuses the assumption made by classical conditioning for this research.

The second issue is that classical conditioning relies on ultimately establishing the conditioned response (elevated attention) independent from the unconditioned stimulus (advertising music) by repeated exposure. Meaning that the objective of classical conditioning is typically to eliminate the unconditioned stimulus after conditioning is established (this elimination can be seen in the previous figure). This is certainly not one of the goals of this research since the advertising music is not removed from the advertisement if a positive response becomes established with the product. This is why the elaboration likelihood model (ELM) may apply more coherently to the dynamics proposed in this research.

2.3.3. Elaboration Likelihood Model (ELM):

An alternative concept to classical conditioning is perhaps the Elaboration Likelihood Model (ELM), which states that there are two means of persuasion: central and peripheral. On the central route, judgments are formed based on the diligent processing of the relevant information available about an object and its properties, and when the individual is highly and directly involved in taking a specific attitudinal position towards the object. However, on the peripheral route, judgments are formed without elaborate processing of information about the object and its properties, which is usually associated with low involvement (Petty, Cacioppo & Schumann, 1983; Shahab, Ghazali, & Mohtar, 2021). Researchers have generally shown that it is less the central message of the advertising and more the peripheral stimuli that drive the attention of the recipient, and ultimately, the judgments, attitudes, and behaviours towards a product or brand (Morris, Woo, & Singh, 2005; Kitchen *et al.*, 2014; Shahab, Ghazali, & Mohtar, 2021).

It has been mentioned in classical conditioning that advertising music does operate peripherally (Suomala *et al.*, 2012; Herget, Schramm, & Breves, 2018; Breves, Herget, & Schramm, 2020; Herget, Breves, & Schramm, 2022; Uhm *et al.*, 2022). Indeed, positive effects of advertising music are more likely to be achieved when the recipient is in a state of low involvement with the stimulus, because in this case the music acts as a peripheral stimulus and can achieve positive effects without the recipient necessarily having to be interested or highly involved in the product itself. Conversely, highly involved recipients are difficult to influence by advertising music because they are actively trying to receive and process information and advertising music can operate centrally for them, which could distract them from the advertising message (Morris, Woo, & Singh, 2005; Zander, 2006).

In the context of this research, the ELM posits that consumers process the tonal centre of advertising music through the peripheral route. Consumers may subconsciously rely on these tonal cues to make quick evaluations about the advertisement and form associations between the cognitive response elicited by the music and the advertised product. This association can then shape their attitudes and behaviours without engaging in extensive cognitive processing. For instance, if an advertisement for a luxury fragrance brand features music in a certain TC, it may evoke elevated attentional response, resulting in more brand information retention and purchase intention. By considering TCs as peripheral cues within the ELM framework, this research can explore how different tonal qualities impact consumers' cognitive and behavioural responses. It allows for an examination of how these cues serve as shortcuts in the persuasion process, shaping consumers' perceptions and judgments without requiring deep cognitive engagement, and more importantly, without the elimination of the stimulus itself as with classical conditioning.

2.3.4. Music congruence:

Musical congruence posits that the music used in advertising fits the advertisements (MacInnis & Park, 1991). According to Oakes (2007, p.39), the term “musical congruity” has replaced the term “musical fit”. The musical congruence concept has been criticised for often being unclear on what the intuitively perceived fit of music and advertisement depends (Allan, 2007; Ausín *et al.*, 2021), and that complex possible interactions between music and advertisements should not be reduced to a binary of fit or no-fit (Bode 2006).

Musical congruence can be created on different levels, so the genre of the music can fit the product or the product class more or less well. For example, it is assumed that jeans and rock music go better together than jeans and classical music. The example shows that, as a rule, clichés and stereotypical associations with music genres and product classes are the actual reason for the congruence (Planer, 1990). Additionally, the music can fit more or less depending on the target group of the brand. For instance, Ballouli & Heere, (2015) found that if the product is intended to appeal to young consumers, electronic dance music is more suitable than classical music. Moreover, the music may or may not match the information conveyed via the imagery of the advertisement or with the textual and verbal statements of the advertising message (Wallace, 1994). However, overall, there has been constant contradictions across the literature regarding the influence of music congruence on advertising (Kellaris & Mantel, 1996; Shen & Chen, 2006; Allan, 2007; Yeoh & North, 2012).

The concept of musical congruence suggests further questions about the properties and specific design of advertising music: When does a piece of music ‘fit’ an advertising message and a specific target group that is to be addressed? Which style or genre of music can convey or underscore certain information? Do various parameters of music, such as tempo or harmony, affect how the music fits the advertisement? These questions, amongst many others regarding music congruence, necessitate conducting rigorous investigations with multivariant considerations.

To ensure the control of music congruence in this research, pre-testing of the materials used in the experiments will be conducted. This pre-testing phase allows for an initial evaluation of how well the selected music aligns with the intended advertising message. By controlling the congruence between the music and the advertisements used, manipulations of other musical variables, such as tonal centres, can be made as needed without worrying about the influence of the degree to which music is congruent with the advertisement.

2.3.5. Attention economy:

The concept of attention economy has gained prominence in the last two decades due to the rapid advancements in technology, especially in social media and the proliferation of digital media (Ciampaglia, Flammini, & Menczer, 2015). In today's data-rich environment, consumers are constantly bombarded with a vast array of stimuli competing for their attention, including advertisements, social media notifications, news headlines, and entertainment content (Crogan & Kinsley, 2012). As a result, attention has become a scarce and valuable resource.

In the attention economy, consumers must allocate their limited attention to the seemingly unlimited competing demands. This creates a marketplace where consumers, advertisers, and media platforms fight for attention and engagement (Terranova, 2012). Just like in a traditional economy, attention is seen as a valuable commodity that can be bought, sold, and traded (Bhargava & Velasquez, 2021). The goal for advertisers, marketers, and content creators is to capture and hold consumer's attention in order to convey their messages, promote their products or services, and ultimately influence their behaviour (Hinz, van der Aalst, & Weinhardt, 2020; Smith & Fischer, 2021).

Digital technologies and online platforms have further intensified the competition for attention. With the rise of social media, streaming platforms, and mobile devices, consumers have access to an unprecedented amount of content and information (Cloarec, 2020). This abundance of choices has led to shorter attention spans, increased multitasking behaviour, and a higher demand for engaging in attention-grabbing content (Zimmerman, Janhonen, & Saadeh, 2023).

Since attention economy views attention not only as a finite resource, but also as a valuable currency, attention then becomes closely tied to revenue generation as businesses and media platforms rely on consumers' attention to generate advertising revenue or drive conversions (Terranova, 2012; Ciampaglia, Flammini, & Menczer, 2015). The competition for capturing and maintaining individuals' attention has intensified in the digital age. Advertisers now strive to cut through the noise and grab the limited attention span of consumers, which has led to the development of various strategies to capture and maintain attention, such as personalised advertising, clickbait headlines, and social media algorithms that prioritise content based on user engagement or expectance to engage (Zhang, Jiang, & Peng, 2019).

Attention economy can relate to this research as a theoretical framework in several ways. As this research investigates the influence of different tonal centres in advertising music on consumers' brain activity, attention becomes highly relevant in the following different ways:

- **Allocation of attention:** attention economy focuses on the limited capacity of individuals to allocate their attention between various stimuli. In the context of advertising, different tonal centres in music may act as attention-grabbing components that can influence consumers' allocation of attention (Tassi, 2018). This attention allocation may influence their cognitive responses and subsequent behaviour. The allocation of attention is a dynamic process that can be influenced by both bottom-up (stimulus-driven) and top-down (goal-directed) factors. Bottom-up factors involve the inherent properties of the stimuli themselves, such as their physical features and perceptual salience. Top-down factors, on the other hand, are influenced by the individual's goals, interests, and cognitive biases (Campos, Pinto, & Scott, 2019). These factors can shape attention allocation by directing individuals' focus toward stimuli that are personally relevant or aligned with their existing preferences. The physical factors (bottom-up) of the music used in this research differ in nothing other than the tonal centre, with all other factors controlled. Therefore, any difference in participants' attention can be attributed to their personal factors (top-down) as well as the tonal centre. Top-down factors cannot be eliminated or controlled accurately, which will be a limitation of this research. However, the size of the sample used in this research, while it has its limitations too, as well as the randomisation tonal centres for different participants, may indicate that the bottom-up factor (tonal centres) does indeed attribute to the allocation of attention.
- **Attentional bias:** attention economy recognises that consumers have cognitive biases and preferences that influence their attentional focus. In this research, it's possible to explore how different tonal centres in advertising music may elicit attentional biases or preferences among consumers. For example, certain tonal centres may be more appealing or attention-grabbing to specific target audiences, affecting their perception of the advertising message and their subsequent cognitive and behavioural responses.
- **Competition for attention:** attention economy emphasises the competitive nature of capturing and maintaining individuals' attention in an information-saturated environment (Ciampaglia, Flammini, & Menczer 2015). In the context of advertising music, different tonal centres may aim to stand out and grab consumers' attention amidst a myriad of other stimuli. If different tonal centres influence attention differently, then this research could offer advertisers a competitive edge in the market in which they operate.

2.3.6. Theory of planned behaviour:

The theory of planned behaviour is a psychological framework that seeks to explain and predict human behaviour, particularly in the context of decision-making and goal-directed actions (Ajzen, 1985). It was developed by Icek Ajzen in the 1980s. It posits that human behaviour is determined by three key factors: attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioural control. According to the theory of planned behaviour, these three factors interact with one another to influence an individual's behavioural intentions and, subsequently, their actual behaviour (Bosnjak, Ajzen, & Schmidt, 2020). Behavioural intentions serve as a proximal predictor of behaviour and are influenced by the strength and valence of attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioural control (Godin, Valois, & Lepage, 1993). The following figure illustrates this dynamic between the three factors and individuals' intentions and actual behaviour.

Figure 2.10: Theory of planned behaviour (Ajzen, 1985)

2.3.6.1. Attitudes:

Attitudes refer to an individual's overall evaluation, positive or negative, of a specific behaviour or action. According to the Ajzen (2020), attitudes are formed through a cognitive process of evaluating the potential outcomes and consequences associated with a particular behaviour. These evaluations are influenced by an individual's beliefs, values, knowledge, and past experiences. They can be seen as a reflection of an individual's subjective evaluation of the likely outcomes or benefits of engaging in a behaviour.

Attitudes consist of two components: the cognitive component and the affective component. The cognitive component of attitudes represents an individual's beliefs about the expected outcomes and consequences of a behaviour. It involves thoughts, judgments, and evaluations based on knowledge and information. For example, if someone believes that regular exercise leads to improved health and well-being, they may have a positive attitude towards exercising (Godin, Valois, & Lepage, 1993). Whereas the affective component of

attitudes relates to the emotional or affective response associated with a behaviour. It involves feelings, emotions, and personal preferences. For instance, if someone enjoys the experience of listening to music, they may have a positive attitude towards playing a musical instrument (Yoo, 2020).

Attitudes can range along a spectrum from positive to negative, with varying degrees of strength or importance. Stronger attitudes are more likely to influence behavioural intentions and subsequent behaviour (Ajzen, 2020). Attitudes that are personally relevant, salient, and have a significant impact on an individual's goals and values tend to be stronger and have a greater influence on behaviour (Ajzen, 1985).

Attitudes also interact with other factors such as subjective norms and perceived behavioural control to shape an individual's behavioural intentions. If an individual holds positive attitudes towards a behaviour, it increases the likelihood that they will develop a stronger intention to engage in that behaviour. Conversely, negative attitudes can decrease the likelihood of forming intentions and engaging in the behaviour (Cheng, Lam, & Hsu, 2006; Bosnjak, Ajzen, & Schmidt, 2020).

Understanding attitudes through the theory of planned behaviour allows researchers to identify the underlying beliefs and evaluations that influence behaviour. By targeting and modifying attitudes through interventions and persuasive messaging, it is possible to shape and influence individuals' intentions and behaviours in desired ways (Kim & Karpova, 2009).

In the context of this research, the attitudes factor may help in understanding how individuals' attitudes towards the music used in advertising can shape their behavioural intentions and subsequent actions. When individuals are exposed to advertising music, their attitudes towards the music can significantly impact their cognitive and emotional responses. Positive attitudes towards the music used in advertisements can then lead to favourable evaluations and enhanced emotional engagement (Ajzen, 2015; Cheung & To, 2017), which is similar in theory to classical conditioning.

2.3.6.2. Subjective norms:

Subjective norms refer to an individual's perception of social pressures and norms surrounding a specific behaviour (Ajzen, 1985). It is a key factor in understanding how social influence can shape an individual's intentions and actions. Subjective norms are based on the belief that people's behaviours are influenced by their perceptions of what others think they should do. It considers the social context and the importance individuals place on the opinions, expectations, and approval of significant others, like family, friends, colleagues, or society as a whole (Bosnjak, Ajzen, & Schmidt, 2020). These subjective norms can be explicit or implicit and may be influenced by cultural, social, and environmental factors.

The theory of planned behaviour suggests that subjective norms influence behaviour indirectly through their impact on an individual's attitude and perceived behavioural control. Attitudes represent the individual's positive or negative evaluations of engaging in a specific behaviour, while perceived behavioural control reflects the individual's belief in their ability to perform the behaviour itself (Al-Swidi *et al.*, 2014). Subjective norms contribute to the formation of behavioural intentions, which are a key determinant of actual behaviour. When individuals perceive that important others expect them to engage in a certain behaviour and they value the opinions and approval of those others, their behavioural intentions are likely to align with these subjective norms (La Barbera & Ajzen, 2020).

However, it's important to note that subjective norms do not operate uniformly for everyone. They can vary depending on the individual's personal characteristics, such as their personality traits, values, and past experiences, as well as the specific social context in which the behaviour occurs (Rhodes, Jones, & Courneya, 2002). The theory recognises the importance of subjective norms in understanding and predicting various behaviours, especially consumer behaviours such as purchasing decisions and product choices (Al-Swidi *et al.*, 2014; Ajzen, 2015).

2.3.6.3. Perceived behavioural control:

Perceived behavioural control refers to an individual's subjective assessment of their ability to perform a specific behaviour and the perceived ease or difficulty of doing so. The concept of perceived behavioural control complements the other two factors of the theory of planned behaviour, attitudes and subjective norms, by addressing the influence of personal control and self-efficacy on behaviour (Ajzen, 2002).

Perceived behavioural control reflects an individual's beliefs about the presence or absence of factors that may facilitate or hinder their ability to engage in a particular behaviour. These factors can include both internal and external elements (Al-Swidi *et al.*, 2014). Internally, it involves an individual's perceived skills, knowledge, resources, self-confidence, and autonomy over the behaviour. Externally, it includes the availability of necessary resources, the presence of barriers or constraints, and the perceived opportunities or environmental facilitators (Ajzen, 2002; 2015; 2020).

Individuals are more likely to engage in a behaviour if they perceive a higher level of control over it. If they believe that they have the necessary skills, resources, and opportunities to perform the behaviour, they are more likely to have a positive intention and follow through with the behaviour (Bosnjak, Ajzen, & Schmidt, 2020). On the other hand, if individuals perceive significant barriers, lack of resources, or low self-efficacy, their behavioural intentions and actual behaviour may be weakened (Ajzen, 2002; Cheng, Lam, & Hsu, 2006).

Perceived behavioural control is influenced by various factors, including personal experiences, knowledge, past performance, social support, and external circumstances. For example, individuals who have successfully performed a behaviour in the past or who possess relevant skills and knowledge are more likely to perceive higher control over that behaviour. Similarly, social support from others and favourable external circumstances can enhance an individual's perceived control and increase the likelihood of behavioural engagement.

Perceived behavioural control has practical implications in various domains, including health behaviour, organisational behaviour, and consumer behaviour. It provides insights into the factors that can influence an individual's engagement in specific behaviours and can guide the development of interventions and strategies to promote behaviour change or adoption.

By addressing individuals' perceived control over a behaviour, interventions can aim to enhance self-efficacy, provide necessary resources and support, remove barriers, and create an enabling environment that supports the desired behaviour (Ajzen, 2002).

Understanding perceived behavioural control allows researchers and practitioners to identify and address factors that may hinder or facilitate behaviour change, leading to more effective interventions and increased behaviour adoption.

In the context of consumer behaviour and advertising, perceived behavioural control can influence consumers' decision-making processes, their responses to advertising messages, and their likelihood to engage in specific consumer behaviours such as purchasing.

Consumers' perceived control over their purchasing behaviour can influence their purchase intentions. If consumers perceive that they have control over the decision-making process and believe they can easily execute the purchase, their purchase intentions are likely to be higher. On the other hand, if they perceive barriers, constraints, or a lack of control, their purchase intentions may be weakened.

In the digital age, perceived behavioural control becomes particularly relevant in online shopping. Consumers' confidence in navigating e-commerce platforms, their perceived ease of using online payment systems, and their perceived control over the security and privacy of their personal information can all impact their likelihood of engaging in online shopping. Furthermore, consumers who perceive higher control over the information search process, evaluation of alternatives, and final purchase decision are more likely to engage in active decision-making and exhibit higher levels of involvement in the consumer choice process.

Advertisers and marketers can leverage perceived behavioural control to enhance consumers' engagement and response to the advertising messages. By addressing and

alleviating perceived barriers, providing clear information and instructions, and instilling confidence in consumers' ability to choose, advertisers can increase consumers' perceived control and positively influence their attitudes, intentions, and actual behaviours (Ajzen, 2015). Furthermore, perceived behavioural control can be influenced by various advertising strategies, such as providing testimonials and success stories from other consumers who have successfully engaged in the desired behaviour, offering step-by-step guidance on how to perform the behaviour, highlighting the ease and convenience of the desired behaviour, and emphasising consumers' autonomy and control in making their own decisions.

2.3.7. Framework synthesis:

The previous theoretical frameworks proposed provide a comprehensive framework to address the various aspects and variables of this research. Each framework brings a unique perspective and contributes to understanding the complex dynamics of the research topic. The figure below provides an illustrated synthesis of the different frameworks used in this research to explain the relationships of its variables.

Figure 2.11: Research framework synthesis revisited

Firstly, problematisation serves as the initial theoretical framework, challenging the Transpositional Invariance Assumption (TIA) in music theory. By problematising this assumption, the research questions the notion that music perception remains invariant under transposition. This framework encourages a critical examination of the role of tonal centres (TCs) and their potential impact on consumers' cognitive responses. Problematisation draws inspiration from the work of Foucault, shedding light on the broader dynamics of knowledge production, power, and social practices. Problematisation is what opens up the possibility to

establish the research question and hypothesis (as generated in the introduction chapter), from which the research can branch out to discussions about the emotional, cognitive, and behavioural responses of advertising music specifically from the perspective of TCs.

Secondly, classical conditioning explores how associations between conditioned stimuli and unconditioned stimuli can shape attitudes and responses. By examining the influence of classical conditioning on initial attitudes towards advertising music, this framework helps in understanding how certain TCs can evoke positive or negative responses and influence consumer perceptions, however, the framework suggests the elimination of the unconditioned stimulus (advertising music) after the conditioning is established, which is an undesired form of action in advertising. The Elaboration Likelihood Model (ELM), however, supplements the classical conditioning notions without proposing an elimination of the unconditioned stimulus. Indeed, the ELM examines the routes through which attitude and cognition are formed and changed. It distinguishes between the central route, where individuals engage in deep cognitive processing and critically evaluate persuasive messages, and the peripheral route, where individuals rely on cues and heuristics to form attitudes. In the context of this research, the TC of advertising music operates peripherally, which may then influence attitudes and cognitive processing. Music congruence is then controlled to eliminate its potential influence on the emotional and cognitive processing of the music.

Thirdly, the attention economy framework addresses attention and brand information retention, as it views the information-rich and attention-scarce environment a landscape where advertisers face the challenge of capturing and maintaining consumers' attention. This framework assists in understanding the dynamics of attention and its relation to brand information retention, highlighting a potential practical implication for advertisers to utilise different TCs in advertising music to direct attentional allocation and subsequent memory encoding and retrieval.

And finally, the theory of planned behaviour provides a theoretical lens to investigate changes in purchase intention. It posits that individuals' behavioural intentions are influenced by their attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioural control, which can interact and shape consumers' ultimate behaviour, characterised in this research as purchase intention. This framework offers insights into the decision-making process and the potential impact of different TCs on consumers' likelihood to take action by purchasing a product.

2.4. Ethical Considerations:

The previous theoretical frameworks raise several ethical questions and considerations pertaining to the use of tonal centres in influencing consumers' attention, retention, and purchase intentions. These ethical considerations require a thoughtful approach to help navigate the complex landscape associated with what is being proposed in this research.

The following is an account of the ethical arguments capitalism, technocapitalism, AI & accelerationism, the changeability of capitalism, technological rationality, the harms and benefits of altering attention, and finally, ethical considerations from a marketing perspective.

2.4.1. Capitalism:

Capitalism is characterised by the private ownership of resources and the means of production, driven by profit-oriented production and exchange (Sennett, 2007). In capitalism, goods and services are produced and distributed through market mechanisms, where individuals and businesses engage in voluntary transactions to buy and sell goods, labour, and capital (Dobb, 1963). Capitalism has been influential in driving economic growth, technological advancement, and innovation (Levine & van Parijs, 1996; Sirico, 2012). It has also been criticised for generating social inequalities, promoting collective profit over individual well-being and environmental welfare, and leading to the concentration of wealth and power in the hands of a minority (Marcuse, 1964; Debord, 1967; Miyazaki, 2006).

2.4.1.1. Debordian critique:

Guy Debord had a critical perspective on capitalism. Debord viewed capitalism as a pervasive social and economic system that alienates individuals and individualism, and further perpetuates the commodification of daily life (Debord, 1988). Debord's critique of capitalism detailed in his book "Society of the Spectacle" argues that social relationships and human experiences become mediated by images and representations, stating that "The spectacle is capital accumulated to the point that it becomes images" (Debord, 1967, p. 34). He argued that capitalism creates a spectacle-dominated society where individuals are passive consumers of images and commodities, disconnected from genuine social interactions and authentic experiences. He viewed capitalism as a system that thrives on the production and consumption of illusions, where the accumulation of wealth and the pursuit of profit take precedence over human needs and desires (Eagles, 2012). He criticised the commodification of culture, politics, and personal relationships, asserting that capitalism reduces all aspects of life to objects of consumption. Herbert Marcuse supports these views and further adds that workers are conditioned so deeply into the system of capitalism that they view themselves as extensions of the products they produce, stating that "the people recognize themselves in their commodities" (Marcuse, 1964, p. 11).

Moreover, Debord (1967) believed that capitalism perpetuates the alienation of individuals from their own labour and creativity. He argued that the capitalist mode of production alienates workers from the products they create, turning their labour into a mere means of generating profit for the wealthy (Igoe, 2010). Debord (1988) also highlighted how capitalism fosters a society of passive spectators, where individuals are conditioned to accept their roles as passive consumers and workers. His critique of capitalism extended beyond its economic dimensions. He saw capitalism as a social order that engenders social inequality, exploitation, and the erosion of individual freedom (Igoe, 2010). He further called for the creation of alternative modes of living and genuine social relationships that would challenge the dominant capitalist framework (Debord, 1967).

2.4.1.2. Beyond imagery:

As mentioned earlier, the Debordian views on capitalism stress that social relations are built by the imagery of class powers (Debord, 1967). The present research puts an argument that goes even deeper than imagery. Indeed, the investigation made in this research suggests that music, as a form of sonic imagery, holds similar potential in mediating and constructing social connections.

Ethically, this notion raises questions about the power dynamics inherent in the production and dissemination of sound, particularly within the context of capitalism. Capitalism, as discussed earlier, with its emphasis on profit-seeking, wealth-generation, and commodification of daily life, often instrumentalises various cultural forms, including music, as tools for generating consumer demands and shaping societal perceptions and behaviours (Miyazaki, 2006). In considering Debord's critique of capitalism, he may argue that this research tries to weaponise the TCs of music to further the objectives of capitalism. While this research does indeed imply the commodification of sound in the hands of advertisers, an alternative utilitarian view could be brought into discussion here. Indeed, many practices of capitalism are often justified by utilitarianism as economies are advanced by notions of creating the greatest material value and wealth, which aligns with the utilitarianism view of creating the greatest good (Baker, 2005; Freiman, 2021). Furthermore, the perceived selfishness of capitalism is often divorced from it when utilitarianism evolves into altruism, which does not include the agent of action when maximising the good (Synowiec, 2016).

2.4.1.3. Utilitarianism, altruism, and maximin egalitarianism:

Utilitarianism promotes the notion of maximising overall happiness and well-being (Freiman, 2021). Capitalism, with its emphasis on individual freedom, market competition, and market dynamics, can be seen as a system that encourages entrepreneurial pursuits and innovation, leading to economic growth and increased prosperity (Sirico, 2012). The wealth

generated by capitalism can be redistributed and used to improve social welfare, ultimately contributing to greater overall well-being (Sennett, 2007). This is of course possible in theory, however, the application of these notions is much more complex and multifaceted (Singer, 1977; Jamieson, 2007).

While utilitarianism proposes maximising the good to all those involved, it doesn't offer the clear means of doing so fairly (Synowiec, 2016). This becomes even more difficult when decisions of wealth-distribution are often in the hands of individuals whose best interests are to centre wealth where more of it can be generated, which is often in their hands. Utilitarianism's inability to challenge capitalism's urge to prioritise the wealth generated to the entities that own the means of production rather than labourers renders it more theoretical than practical.

Altruism may offer alternative views on this issue, as it suggests distributing wealth solely to those who create it independent from those who action it (Simon, 1993). This means that capitalism can be justified from an altruistic perspective by highlighting the opportunities it provides for individuals to accumulate wealth and engage in philanthropic activities that do not benefit the agent of action (advertisers in this case). The accumulation of wealth through capitalist endeavours and altruistic distribution allows individuals to support charitable causes, fund social programs, and address pressing societal issues such as inequalities (Synowiec, 2016).

The altruistic view excuses the expansion of capitalist practices, which justifies operationalising the tonal centres of advertising music to assist in generating wealth. However, as with utilitarianism, the issue with altruism is that it's more theoretical than practical; individuals with capital would be alienated by markets in which they cannot generate profit and only engage in philanthropic practices (Simon, 1993).

Egalitarianism, on the other hand, promotes equality and equal treatment among all individuals (advertisers and consumers), grounded in the belief that all people should have equal rights, opportunities, and access to resources, regardless of their background, social status, or other distinguishing characteristics (Scheffler, 2003). Egalitarianism differs in many ways from utilitarianism and altruism. Principally, utilitarianism and altruism prioritise the overall well-being of society over strict equality. Indeed, they can even create inequalities (Myerson, 1981; Barrett, 2020). Whereas the egalitarian argument here at least aligns with Rawls' maximin principle, which always maximises the minimum outcome for all, ensuring that even the most vulnerable members of society are protected and provided with adequate resources and opportunities (Rawls, 1971; 1974).

By incorporating egalitarianism lead by maximin principles, this research can be seen as one that advocates for a more just and equitable advertising environment where there's at least a net-benefit for everyone at all times. This means that if the use of certain tonal centres in advertising music can be guaranteed to create a net-benefit to everyone without creating inequalities, then their use is justified. Furthermore, for this principle to apply, advertisers must ensure that the application of TCs in advertising music is not biased towards certain groups of consumers while marginalising other groups of consumers from the opportunity of being influenced by advertisements that are equipped with the 'right' TC that optimises their attention. This suggests that a company must apply the outcomes of this research only when it can guarantee two conditions: the first is creating a net-benefit to all parties involved, and the second is that all its advertising campaigns that target all its customers should apply the recommendations presented in this research or not at all. The following algorithm may assist in making executive marketing decisions regarding this issue.

Figure 2.12: Decision-making algorithm for the use of TCs in advertising music

Despite the clarity of this decision and the two conditions that constitute it, it remains ethically concerning as advertisers may be tempted and biased to decide 'YES' regardless of condition-breaking. Jacobsen (2015) argues that technological advancements are often confronted with ethical questions that cannot be answered using ethical theories as these decisions are made by individuals with predispositioned intentions, good or bad, and ethical theories do not predict individual behaviour. They only explain group behaviour. She further alludes that this ambiguity of intention should not alienate from technological progress.

2.4.2. Technocapitalism:

The technological progress mentioned previously leads to discussions on technocapitalism. Technocapitalism is a socio-economic system that emphasises the integration of technology and capitalism together, viewing technological advancements as a means to drive economic growth and societal progress (Suarez-Villa, 2003). It expands on traditional capitalism by not only utilising materialism and technology to grow wealth, but also creativity and new means of obtaining knowledge (Suarez-Villa, 2016). Within its context, the following points can be made about the current research:

- **Innovation and economic growth:** technocapitalism values innovation and the development of new technologies as key drivers of economic growth (Suarez-Villa, 2003; Stubbs, 2020). Research on the influence of TCs in advertising music aligns with this ethos as it explores novel approaches to target consumers who could enhance economical welfare when they engage with these advertisements. By uncovering the impact of TCs, this research contributes to the evolution of advertising innovation and the generation of new knowledge, which can stimulate economic growth and market competitiveness.
- **Consumer empowerment:** technocapitalism often emphasises the empowerment of consumers through enhanced experiences, personalised content, and targeted marketing (Suarez-Villa, 2003). The use of TCs in advertising music can be seen as a mechanism to better connect with consumers in order to deliver on their expectations and preferences and create meaningful value.
- **Enhanced advertising efficiency:** technocapitalism values efficiency and optimisation in various aspects of business operations, including advertising (Stubbs, 2020). This research may show that the influence of TCs contribute to the quest for more effective advertising strategies, and understanding how different TCs impact consumers' cognitive and behavioural responses can help advertisers allocate resources more efficiently, ensuring their messages reach the right audience. This efficiency benefits both advertisers and consumers by reducing wasteful advertising practices and delivering more relevant content (Suarez-Villa, 2016).
- **Competitive advantage and market dynamics:** technocapitalism promotes market competition and the pursuit of competitive advantage (Bauriedl & Strüver, 2020). Using different TCs in advertising music may provide valuable insights into consumer behaviours and decision-making processes, offering advertisers an opportunity to gain a competitive edge in the marketplace by optimising their advertising strategies and differentiating themselves from competitors, leading to increased market share and profitability, which will feed back into the economic growth.

2.4.3. The changeability of capitalism:

The changeability of capitalism to new forms is not a novel concept. Once capitalism confronts its limits, it changes the means through which wealth is generated, often using the most recent technological advancements. Indeed, Deleuze & Guattari (2005) state that “capitalism confronts its own limits and simultaneously displaces them, setting them down again farther along”, implying that capitalism doesn’t truly have a saturation point as “the saturation is itself relative” (p. 463).

One of their key concepts in relation to capitalism and its acceleration is the notions of “deterritorialization and reterritorialization” (Deleuze & Guattari, 1972, p. 258). They refer to how capitalism constantly seeks to deterritorialise social and cultural norms, breaking down traditional boundaries, and then reterritorialise them according to capitalist interests (generating wealth). This process involves the extraction of value and the constant creation of new desires and markets (Haynes, 2021). It allows capitalism to access new territories, resources, and markets that were previously inaccessible or underutilised.

Technological advancements play a crucial role in both the deterritorialisation and reterritorialisation processes. New technologies enable capitalism to penetrate and reshape some aspects of society such as production, distribution, communication, and consumption.

Understanding the interplay between capitalism, technological advancements, and the processes of deterritorialisation and reterritorialisation provides valuable insights into the dynamics of contemporary society. It highlights the ways in which capitalism adapts and transforms itself, constantly seeking new avenues for accumulation and exploiting emerging possibilities. This understanding could assist in predicting the next shape of capitalism, which is likely to be – and in many ways, already is – AI-driven accelerated capitalism.

2.4.3.1. AI-driven accelerated capitalism (accelerationism):

Artificial intelligence is able not only to automate tasks, but to also create and algorithmise them within a fraction of the time it typically takes by a human agent. It can further make autonomous decisions based on the algorithms it creates (Busuioc, 2020). This has the potential to significantly impact various aspects of technocapitalism, and drastically accelerate to become accelerated capitalism (accelerationism), or even to the point of technological singularity, which is a when technological advancements becomes uncontrollable and irreversible.

Accelerationism proposes using advanced technologies to accelerate the processes of capitalism with the aim of creating a more equitable and emancipatory society that reduced the need for human labour (Haynes, 2021). It further suggests that AI could not only reduce this labour, but also completely eliminate it by migrating all task creation, execution, and

supervision to AI. It argues that by pushing the boundaries of technological progress and embracing the transformative potential of AI, capitalism can be reinvented to bring about radical social change, where AI can be seen as a catalyst for driving economic growth and efficiency (Sellar & Cole, 2017).

With regards to this research, AI can help optimise advertising music by transposing it to the TC that results in the highest attention, retention, and purchase intention. Furthermore, machine learning algorithms can identify patterns or correlations between different variables, helping advertisers understand the impact of TCs in advertising music on consumers' responses even beyond the limitations of this research. Moreover, AI can generate music compositions tailored to specific target audiences, incorporating elements that are more likely to resonate with consumers. This can lead to more effective advertising campaigns and potentially increase the influence of tonal centres on consumers' response to advertising.

When discussing the ethical considerations of AI-driven accelerationism in relation to the research on tonal centres in advertising music, several important ethical questions arise: How does the use of AI in advertising impact consumer privacy? To what extent does the use of AI in advertising infringe upon individual autonomy? How can the potential algorithmic biases in advertising strategies created by AI be addressed? How can transparency and trust in AI-driven advertising be ensured? Technological rationality, as conceptualised by Herbert Marcuse, may assist in answering these questions.

2.4.3.2. Technological rationality:

Technological rationality refers to the domination of instrumental reason and the subordination of human creativity and freedom to the efficiency and productivity of technology (Marcuse, 1964). According to Marcuse (1964), technological rationality promotes a one-dimensional perspective that reduces human existence to mere functionality and the pursuit of material wealth and comfort. It emphasises the instrumental value of technology and its ability to solve problems and increase efficiency, often at the expense of human critical reflection. This mode of rationality tends to prioritise technical solutions and quantitative measures, disregarding broader social and ethical dimensions.

Marcuse is critical of technological rationality as he believes it tends to reinforce the existing social order and perpetuates systems of social control and domination (Marcuse, 1964, p. 161). He argues that, in a technologically driven society, individuals become alienated from their own desires and needs, as their desires are increasingly moulded and dictated by the dominant technological apparatus. Moreover, Technological Rationality often serves the

interests of the ruling elites, enabling the consolidation of power and maintaining the status quo (Marcuse, 1941; Leiss, 1972).

However, Marcuse (1964) also believed that technological advancements offer the promise of liberating humanity from the necessity and imposition of labour for survival, and that this liberation from labour can be viewed as true freedom, which can be achieved through adhering to technological rationality.

The incorporation of technological rationality into advertising can be seen as problematic from an ethical standpoint, especially when augmented with artificial intelligence that could optimise advertising strategies based on data analysis and consumer behaviour patterns, which may prioritise efficiency and effectiveness of advertisement over consumer values, such as autonomy and privacy. However, one could argue that technological rationality, when applied ethically, even with the involvement of AI, could provide a justifications for its practices. The following are some potential arguments:

- **Enhancing consumer experience:** AI technology has the potential to enhance the consumer experience by delivering more personalised and relevant advertisements of products and services consumers truly desire. AI's ability to analyse large amounts of data and creating algorithms based on them can tailor advertisements to individual preferences, increasing the likelihood of providing consumers with products or services that genuinely meet their needs. From a technological rationality perspective, this can be seen as a way of optimising the efficiency of advertising, making it more effective and beneficial for consumers (Bilić, 2018).
- **Efficiency and resource allocation:** AI is able to optimise advertising campaigns by efficiently allocating resources, targeting detailed audiences, and measuring campaign effectiveness in real-time, and even manipulate them as they are running (Rodgers & Nguyen, 2022). This can result in cost savings, reduced waste, and improved return on investment for advertisers. Technological rationality views these outcomes as efficient ones as the use of resources aligns with the goal of maximising productivity and minimising labour (Shah *et al.*, 2020).
- **Innovation and creativity:** AI advertising have the potential to enhance creativity and innovation as machine learning algorithms can identify patterns and generate new content based on insights that may not be apparent to human advertisers (Campbell *et al.*, 2022). By augmenting human creativity with AI capabilities, advertising campaigns can be more imaginative and compelling. This aligns with the technological rationality notion of harnessing technology to expand human creative capacities, the same could be said for the use of specific TCs in advertising music.

- **Economic growth and market competitiveness:** AI-generated and driven advertising can contribute to economic growth by supporting businesses and stimulating market activity (Han *et al.*, 2021; Yang *et al.*, 2021). Since it has the potential to optimise strategies and reaching the right target audiences, then AI can help businesses increase sales and expand their market share. If the proper wealth distribution policies are put in place, then this could bring about economic prosperity and overall societal advancement to everyone involved (both consumers and advertisers) (Dignum, 2017).

As per the final point mentioned, Dignum (2017) believes that issues of wealth inequality could be attributed to policies of wealth distribution rather than market practices. She further put forward a techno-utopists scenario where wealth inequalities could be irradiated, and that “AI will be one of the enabling technologies for this scenario. As humans will spend less time on their jobs... new forms of wealth distribution, such as a universal basic income will be needed to maintain the future economy” (p. 3).

2.4.3.3. Policies of inequality:

It is crucial to differentiate between the impact of technology-driven knowledge (such as AI-driven advertising or the influence of tonal centres in advertising music on consumer response), and the role of wealth distribution policies in addressing issues of wealth inequality. While technological advancements can have an influence on the market and marketing practices that ultimately drives economic value, they are not the primary cause of inequality. Instead, the main culprit lies in policies related to wealth distribution (Causa, Woloszko, & Leite, 2019).

The unequal distribution of wealth is predominantly a consequence of systemic economic policies and structures rather than technologies and their influence on market practices. Indeed, wealth inequality is predominantly influenced by factors such as tax policies, financial regulations, and the concentration of power in the hands of a few political decision-makers (Piketty, 2014; Stiglitz, 2012). Piketty’s (2014) work extensively analyses the historical patterns of wealth distribution and demonstrates that inequality is caused by dynamics of capital accumulation at the disposal of a few. These dynamics are shaped by policy choices rather than technological progress alone. Similarly, Stiglitz (2012) argues that inequality stems from a combination of political and economical factors, including unjust tax policies, lack of investment in the public good, and the slow erosion of workers’ rights.

While technological advancements, including AI-driven advertising, can contribute to changes in economic landscapes, they do not inherently create or exacerbate inequality by default. The impact of these technologies depends on how they are employed and the

broader socio-economic context in which they operate (Youssef *et al.*, 2020). Policies that address wealth distribution, such as progressive taxation, social welfare programs, and measures to ensure fair labour practices play a vital role in mitigating and rectifying inequality (Atkinson, Piketty, & Saez, 2011).

While it is important to recognise that political policies play a significant role in shaping wealth inequality on both a national and international scales, it is equally important for this research to address immediate ethical concerns that can arise at the individual level. While market practices may not be the root cause of widespread wealth inequality, advertising can still have some negative implications for social practices and individual experiences that should be mitigated whenever possible (Bhargava & Velasquez, 2021). Therefore, as this research is primarily concerned with altering the attentional responses of consumers, it's crucial to address both the harms and the benefits of doing so, while proposing the means of minimising the harms.

2.4.4. Harms of altering attention:

Attention alteration may have significant implications for various aspects in the digital world. It affects the way information is disseminated, how products are advertised, and how consumers navigate the digital landscape (Crogan & Kinsley, 2012). It has also raised concerns about information overload, privacy, productivity, and the manipulation of attention for commercial or political purposes. This raises several points for ethical consideration:

- **Manipulation and deception:** in the pursuit of capturing attention, there is a risk of employing manipulative or deceptive tactics. As mentioned earlier, these manipulation techniques could be in the form of clickbait headlines, misleading advertisements, or the use of psychological triggers to exploit vulnerabilities and elicit certain behaviours (Bhargava & Velasquez, 2021). Ethical concerns arise when attention-grabbing strategies cross the line into deceptive practices that undermine informed decision-making and autonomy. Advertisers should provide accurate and truthful information and avoid misleading tactics. Adhering to ethical guidelines and industry standards that promote authenticity and responsible communication helps ensure that attention-grabbing strategies do not compromise the integrity of the advertising process (Davis, 1994; Schauster & Neill, 2017).
- **Privacy and data exploitation:** attention economy relies heavily on personal data collection to tailor content and advertisements to individual preferences. This raises concerns about privacy and the potential misuse or exploitation of personal information (Crogan & Kinsley, 2012). Data tracking, profiling, and targeted advertising can intrude upon consumers' privacy, create filter bubbles, and

perpetuate echo chambers that limit exposure to diverse perspectives (Cloarec, 2020). Mitigating this issue requires a commitment to responsible data practices and privacy protection. Advertisers should be transparent in their advertising practices and communicate honestly with consumers about the type of data they collect via clear and easily accessible privacy policy statements that detail how they may use their data and the type of advertisements and strategies they use to curate content. Furthermore, advertisers should always analyse consumer data holistically rather than individually as to not infringe on consumers' privacy. This type of transparent disclosure about data collection and sharing practices is crucial to building trust with consumers (Kim, Barasz, & John, 2018). By prioritising privacy and responsible data practices, advertisers can navigate the ethical challenges of altering consumers' attention and create a more privacy-conscious environment.

- **Addiction and mental well-being:** the constant barrage of attention-seeking content in the digital landscape can contribute to addictive behaviours and negatively impact mental well-being (Bhargava & Velasquez, 2021). Social media platforms, for example, employ design features that encourage compulsive use and foster addiction-like behaviours. To combat this issue, it's possible to implement features that promote healthy digital habits, such as providing users with tools to manage the notifications they receive from advertisers, as well as setting a maximum number of the times a consumer may be exposed to an advertisement.
- **Distraction and productivity:** advertising in the attention economy often prioritises capturing and holding attention over promoting deep focus and productivity. The constant stream of notifications, alerts, and entertainment options can contribute to information overload, cognitive fatigue, decreased attention span, and reduced productivity (Zimmerman, Janhonen, & Saadeh, 2023). All of which undermine consumers' ability to focus, concentrate, and accomplish meaningful tasks in their personal lives. As with mitigating addiction and mental-wellbeing, advertisers and platform operators alike can implement features that allow consumers and platform users to customise their notification settings, providing them with control over the frequency and type of interruptions they receive.
- **Market equity and access:** attention alteration may exacerbate existing inequalities by favouring advertisers that have more resources, larger data sets, strong detailed algorithms, and strategies to capture attention effectively (Hwang, 2020). Large corporations and well-funded advertisers have an advantage in commanding attention compared to smaller businesses or consumers with limited resources. This can perpetuate disparities in visibility, market power, and influence, potentially marginalising certain voices and perspectives (Dahlberg, 2005). In the digital age of

technological acceleration businesses have access to similar platforms to utilise as a frontier of communication. However, they differ in the capital they have, which is what gives them a competitive edge over other businesses. This is, of course, expected under both technocapitalism (Suarez-Villa, 2016) and accelerationism (Haynes, 2021), however, it's possible to leverage other disproportionately affected businesses to provide them with higher opportunities of competition in the market. For example, supporting initiatives that amplify underrepresented voices and perspectives can help counteract some of the marginalisation of certain groups (Thurik, Stam, & Audretsch, 2013; Tsuruta, 2016).

- **Content quality and public discourse:** advertising in the attention economy presents a risk of prioritising sensationalism, viral content, or provocative narratives over accuracy, reliability, and quality (Helsper & van Deursen, 2016; Cover, Haw, & Thompson, 2022). This can impact public discourse, as misinformation, clickbait, and polarising content tend to attract attention and engagement. Mitigating this issue requires a collective effort from advertisers, content creators, platforms (both digital and traditional), and policy makers that prioritise accuracy, reliability, and quality of content. Implementing measures such as fact-checking mechanisms, promoting transparent sourcing and citations, and providing clear labels for sponsored or promotional content can help establish a more responsible and informed market environment. This can empower individuals to discern reliable and accurate information from misinformation (Caled & Silva, 2021; Saling *et al.*, 2021)
- **Political campaigns:** attention-altering techniques in political campaigns raise significant ethical consequences. Such techniques could be harmful when used in campaigns that exacerbate misinformation, polarisation, and encouragement of apathy (Kim, 2016). However, this circles back to becoming an issue of intention, transparency, and the policies in place that prevent harmful political communications, because alternatively, it could be argued that attention-seeking practices in political campaigns, such as optimising music that grabs attention, are beneficial for engaging more people in politics and encouraging them to vote, which would further democratise society, and when this is coupled with the right policies that prevent political misinformation, then the use of such practices could be a net-benefit. Therefore, Policies that ensure transparency, fact-checking, and accountability should be in place regardless of attention alteration techniques, and indeed many of them are already imposed on political campaigns such as financial regulation campaigns, fact-checking organisations that hold political candidates accountable, and electoral laws and regulations that govern the conduct of campaigns (Gilens, Patterson, & Haines, 2021). As from an advertising perspective, platforms, both

digital and traditional, often require disclosure requirements that mandate political campaigns to clearly present information about their funding sources, including the identification of donors and the amounts they may have contributed to the campaign (Persily & Tucker, 2020). Some platforms, such as Meta, also have restrictions on the amount of money they can spend on political campaigns, or even times and frequency of advertising (Dommett & Power, 2019). Furthermore, some jurisdictions have regulations that prohibit false or misleading statements in political campaign advertisements (Crain & Nadler, 2019). These requirements aim to promote transparency and prevent undisclosed or illicit financial influence in political advertising (Kim, 2016).

Addressing the ethical considerations mentioned so far requires a multi-stakeholder approach involving consumers, advertisers, policymakers, and media platforms. It involves promoting transparency and informed consent regarding data practices and overall use for advertising purposes, designing user interfaces that prioritise well-being, and promoting a culture of responsible content creation and consumption. Ultimately, a more ethical attention alteration practices should constantly strive to reflect on the current landscape of the market and ways to improve it with regards to individual autonomy, well-being, and the broader societal and economical impacts of its outcomes. Despite the presence of these harms, there is, on the other hand, several benefits to engaging in practices of attention alteration that can benefit both consumers, advertisers, and the wider public.

2.4.5. Benefits of altering attention:

While the ethical considerations surrounding attention alteration in advertisements are valid and important to address, it could be argued that there may be a net-benefit to its perpetuation. Within the context of techno-capitalism and accelerationism, a few proponents, such as Suarez-Villa (2003; 2016) argue that practices, such as those in the attention economy, could drive innovation, economic growth, and societal progress, with the negative impact operating at lower levels. The following highlights some of these benefits:

- **Utilitarian and altruism perspective:** utilitarian thinkers argue that advertising in the attention economy, despite its ethical issues, can present overall positive outcomes by maximising utility and well-being for everyone involved (Synowiec, 2016). They may contend that the attention economy fosters economic development and promotes consumer satisfaction by delivering personalised content and experiences as well as bring profit to advertisers (Freiman, 2021). From a utilitarian and effective altruism standpoint, the benefits of innovation, convenience, and entertainment derived from the attention economy may outweigh the ethical concerns.

- **Free market principles for consumers:** advertising practices in the attention economy could bring about principles of free markets and individual choices. Attention as a market currency is ultimately a result of market forces and voluntary interactions, where consumers have the freedom to choose the content they engage with even if some of it was presented to them via alterations of their attention (Cloarec, 2020). From this perspective, individuals are responsible for managing their behaviours and making informed choices despite the advertising influence that cognitively proximates them to a product or service. Indeed, capitalist practices do not leverage wealth if the offering is not to the satisfaction of consumers as expectations are still in place (Oliver, 2014).
- **Elimination of advertising noise:** attention alteration could provide the means for products or services to cut through other non-relevant alternatives that consumers may not care for (Pieters, Warlop, & Wedel, 2002). This practice functions as a cognitive filter that eliminates the redundant processing of unnecessary information and directly leveraging the desires and needs of consumers to them.
- **Enhanced relevance:** altering attention may help deliver content that is highly relevant and further “personalize consumers’ online navigation and improve their online experience”, assisting them in making more informed decisions about their lifestyle (Cloarec, 2020, p. 1). This relevance can enhance the overall consumer experience and potentially lead to greater satisfaction.
- **Social impact and cultural promotion:** attention alteration in advertising can be utilised to promote pressing social causes, cultural events, and positive change, such as issues on climate change or social inequalities. Consumers’ attention could, therefore, be directed to raise awareness about these issues. This allows advertising to serve as a means to counter some of the harms presented earlier in order to drive positive societal impact (Tufekci, 2013).

These may be some of the potential benefits of utilising the TCs of advertising music to leverage attention which could positively affect consumers, advertisers, and their extensions. However, some other benefits could arise within other disciplines, such as benefits in music therapy where certain TCs could be used to increase or decrease the attentional responses to achieve certain goals. Furthermore, certain TCs could perhaps be used in education where classrooms may play background music to influence attention in order to increase information retention and the overall learning experience. Indeed, some research does suggest that there’s a benefit to students’ productivity when background music is played in the classroom (Hallam, Price, & Katsarou, 2002; Hallam & Price, 2003), hence it would be interesting to examine if the TCs of music could further contribute to the learning process.

2.4.6. Considering ethics from a marketing perspective:

A thorough analysis of how to strike a balance between achieving corporate goals and upholding the rights and welfare of customers is necessary when examining ethical issues via a marketing lens (Ziv, 2016; Zimmerman, Janhonen, & Saadeh, 2023). The practices described in this research regarding the optimisation of the TCs of advertising music become a pressing issue since these practices are meant to shift attention in favour of business objectives, and since advertising plays a crucial role in shaping consumers' emotional and cognitive responses through their campaigns. As such, ethical considerations need to take into account consumer autonomy, transparency, balancing business objectives and consumer welfare, fair competition and free market principles, regulatory compliance, cultural sensitivities, and the creativity and artistic integrity musicians:

- **Consumer autonomy:** marketers must respect the autonomy of consumers to make informed choices about their marketing preferences. This means that data protection regulations must be followed, and that consumers' wishes to opt out of offering their data should be respected. Hence, there should be a system in place whereby ads with certain tonal centres that induce attention, enhance retention, and encourage purchase intention can only be displayed to those who consent to such practices, ensuring that consumers have control over the types of auditory stimuli to which they are exposed (Zimmerman, Janhonen, & Saadeh, 2023). By prioritising consent, consumer autonomy, and privacy, marketers can uphold ethical standards while still effectively advertise their offerings.
- **Transparency:** marketers must be transparent about the tools they utilise to capture attention, including the use of TCs in music. Consumers have the right to be aware of how they are being influenced. An ethical approach of this would be to provide clear information about the intentions behind the choice of TCs and their potential impact on consumer behaviour (Ziv, 2016; Kim, Barasz, & John, 2018). For example, if a company uses music in C_{maj} to create a sense of alertness, it should communicate this openly through their website, publicly accessible reports, terms and conditions, and other means of communication.
- **Balancing business objectives and consumer welfare:** marketers must balance business objectives, such as increasing sales or brand awareness, and safeguarding consumer welfare. Ethical marketing practices recognise that long-term success depends on maintaining trust with consumers (Sirico, 2012; Bhargava & Velasquez, 2021). Using certain TCs in advertising music should enhance the effectiveness of advertising without compromising consumer trust or well-being. This can only be achieved by strictly adhering to the ethical considerations discussed here.

- **Fair competition and free market:** ethical marketers should always uphold principles of fair competition and support a free market ecosystem. Within the context of this research, fair competition and free market can be achieved by refraining from gatekeeping the outcomes of this research and its proposed managerial applications (Bhargava & Velasquez, 2021). In addition, ethical marketing researchers should practice transparency and accessibility in the dissemination of their research findings, ensuring that all stakeholders, including competitors regardless of the scope of their business, have equal access to research outcomes (Sirico, 2012; Cloarec, 2020). By facilitating a landscape of fair competition and free exchange of ideas and opportunities, marketers together can contribute to advancing knowledge and innovation in their fields while remaining ethical to economical influence.
- **Regulatory compliance:** marketers must ensure compliance with the relevant policies, regulations, and standards that govern advertising practices. This includes adhering to current guidelines related to credibility and transparency, as well as being vigilant and resilient to any future regulations that might specify rules of using music in advertisements, including TCs. Ethical marketers must stay informed about any legal requirements and aim to exceed the minimum standards of regulatory compliance when utilising music as a tool for optimising their campaigns (Ziv, 2016).
- **Cultural sensitivities:** the choice to use certain TCs in advertising music can have cultural consequences of which marketers need to be mindful (Skelton, 2004; Arora & Tyagi, 2022). Ethical marketers should consider how different tonal centres may be perceived within different cultural contexts and avoid using music that could be offensive or insensitive to certain groups. For instance, while the 12-TET tuning system is generally adopted globally, some regions still practice their own tuning systems that may vary slightly or drastically from 12-TET and using them for advertising purposes might not only be perceived as incoherent within the scope of their homogeneous culture, but also insensitive to it. Therefore, intensive and rigorous marketing research must be conducted prior to adopting the practices proposed in this research whenever applied beyond the limits of its cultural considerations (Nunan & Di Domenico, 2013).
- **Creativity and artistry:** marketers must consider the impact of their advertising practices on the creative and artistic integrity of music. While what constitutes music is far more than just TCs, the practice of using specific TCs that elevate consumers' attentional responses, brand information retention rate, and purchase intention may result in a lack of tonal diversity (He, Wong, & Hui, 2017). This is why it would be advisable to diversify the TCs of advertising music if the campaign objectives are not to increase attention, retention, and purchase intention.

2.5. Methodology of the Literature Review:

Following the necessary overview of variables as well as the theoretical framework and ethical considerations of this research, it's possible now to present the literature of the research topic. This section will outline the methodology employed in conducting a systematic literature review, which is the rigorous and structured approach to reviewing the existing body of scholarly literature on a topic of concern (Linnenluecke, Marrone, & Singh, 2019). It involves a comprehensive search and analysis of relevant literature to provide a holistic overview of the existing knowledge and identify key themes and trends that help shape this research.

Moreover, a systematic approach enhances the reproducibility of the research, as all steps and decisions are clearly documented and can be replicated by other researchers in the future. Furthermore, a systematic literature review reduces the risk of cherry-picking studies that support a particular viewpoint and aims to minimise bias and subjectivity by following a transparent and replicable methodology, which has "improved significantly over the years, from traditional narrative review to systematic reviews" (Thomé, Scavarda, & Scavarda, 2016, p. 408).

This section will detail the approach for conducting the systematic literature review which will be through detailing the inclusion and exclusion criteria for selecting the literature and detailing of the search strategy and databases used, and finally procedures for screening, evaluating, and synthesising the literature.

2.5.1. Inclusion and exclusion criteria:

This refers to the specific criteria or conditions used to determine which studies will be included or excluded from the review. These criteria help ensure that the selected studies are relevant to the research questions and are able to assist in answering them. They play an important role in ensuring the quality and reliability of the selected studies and ensure that the review includes studies that are most pertinent to the research topic as to not digress to redundant areas (Ioannidis, 2016).

The following table presents the inclusion and exclusion criteria for this research with justifications of their selection. Each criterion will be carefully considered during the selection process to ensure that the chosen studies align with the research objectives and provide relevant and reliable insights.

Criteria	Inclusion and exclusion factors
Date	Due to the complexity and interdisciplinarity of the research, the date range of the literature is wide as it depends on relevant studies across various disciplines and the historical context of the research topic. The inclusion and exclusion criteria of the literature will take into consideration both older and more recent studies to ensure a comprehensive and thorough analysis of the research area and its development over time. For example, the literature regarding the development of music theory dates back as far as the 17 th century. Whereas research in neuroscience regarding techniques of neuroimaging date back as far as early 20 th century. However, the more immediate research relating to the main topic of the research, which is the use of music in advertisements, dates back to the early 1980s, allowing almost half a century of development and investigation of several research variables.
Variables	<p><u>Included:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Tonal centres: to the knowledge of the researcher, there are no studies that investigate their use in advertising music. Only a few studies have examined tonality as characterised by two categories: major and minor, due to the assumption that all TCs are perceptually equal within their category. - Tonality: advertising research examining the influence of tonality as major or minor on marketing variables. - Advertising music: advertising studies that examine music variables, specifically, tonality, and generally, music variables such as tempo, harmony, volume, popular songs, lyrics... etc. - Attention: from the perspective of marketing research (especially relating to advertising music), as well as neuroimaging and neuromarketing research (especially using EEG). - Retention: from the perspective of marketing research (especially relating to advertising music) as well as neuromarketing research (the neural processes of information retention). - Purchase intention: especially its influence by advertising music. <p><u>Excluded:</u> studies in advertising that do not examine advertising music, attention, retention, or purchase intention in any capacity whether as primary variables of interest or secondary concepts of concern.</p>
Design	<p><u>Primary:</u> neuromarketing, neuroimaging (EEG), quantitative, positivist, pragmatist.</p> <p><u>Secondary:</u> qualitative, descriptive, meta-analyses, interpretivist.</p> <p><u>Excluded:</u> case studies.</p>
Type	<p><u>Included:</u> peer-reviewed papers from well-established academic journals (the overwhelming majority of the literature), a few conference papers, a few books (by well-established authors).</p> <p><u>Excluded:</u> non-peer reviewed papers, academic theses at any level, newspapers, magazines, and websites (except from NASA and Emotiv).</p>
Language	Most of the literature examined in this research is in English, however, a few books, originally in German but translated to English, relating the historical development of music will be used. As well as a few translations of books from French to English pertaining to socioeconomical philosophical writings.

Table 2.1: Inclusion and exclusion criteria of selecting the literature

2.5.2. Detailing of the search strategy and databases used:

The search process involved a comprehensive and systematic search across multiple databases to ensure a thorough coverage of the literature and minimising the risk of missing relevant studies. The following steps outline the search strategy used:

- **Identification of keywords and search terms:** a preliminary exploration of the research topic was conducted to identify the main key terms and concepts related to the topic. These terms were selected based on their relevance to the research objectives and alignment with the research questions. The most important keywords and terms were: *tonal centres, music keys, tonality, attention, retention, memory, purchase intention, consumer behaviour, neuromarketing, electroencephalography (EEG), music theory, advertising, problematisation*. It's important to note that search through databases often incorporated more than one of these words together to narrow down results.
- **Selection of databases:** several databases were selected to retrieve relevant literature across different disciplines. These databases included: *Google Scholar, the UWS online database, which is run by One Search, the UWS physical library, Scopus, PubMed, Public Library of Science, (PLoS), JSTOR, ScienceDirect, and others*. The chosen databases were known for their extensive coverage of scholarly literature in various disciplines (it's important to note that some research will overlap across these databases).
- **Development of search queries:** search queries were constructed using a combination of the identified keywords and Boolean expressions such as: *“AND”, “OR”, “NOT”, “intitle:”, and quotation marks* to search for exact phrases... etc. This helped refine the search results, and minimised the time spent during the search process.
- **Execution of the search:** the search queries were executed in the selected databases mentioned previously, ensuring that the search terms were appropriately entered, and relevant filters, such Boolean expressions, were applied as per the research requirements.
- **Screening of search results:** the search results were subjected to a four-step screening process including:
 - Title filtering to review if the title is relevant to the research, then,
 - Abstract filtering to review the details of the article including the variables, methods, and results, then,
 - Scanning of introduction and conclusion/discussion, and finally,
 - Full-text review.

- **Exporting of relevant results:** the relevant search results were exported, saved (as PDF), and named as *Author(s), Year - Title*. Some duplicate articles were removed.
- **Hand-searching and reference mining:** in addition to the database search, a manual search was conducted by reviewing the reference lists of the relevant sources to identify additional relevant studies that might have been missed in the initial search.
- **Documentation of the search process:** detailed records were kept at each stage of the search process, including the search terms, databases searched, number of articles retrieved, and the inclusion or exclusion reasons for each source. This documentation ensures transparency, reproducibility, and adherence to the systematic literature review methodology.

2.5.3. Results of search strategy:

Using these strategies and techniques resulted in over 474 relevant results that were used in the research. 409 (86%) were research papers from peer-reviewed academic journals, 34 (7%) were books from well-established authors (mostly in music theory), 18 (4%) were proceeding from conferences relevant to the research area, and finally, 13 (3%) were other resources, such as annual industry reports, website resources (only from NASA and Emotiv), and a few dictionary entries for some music-related terminology.

Figure 2.8: Results of literature review search strategy

2.6. Themes of the Literature:

This section will provide a detailed examination of the main themes that emerge from the literature found using the techniques mentioned earlier. The presentation of themes will aim to provide a structured analysis of the literature, highlighting the main results, trends, and patterns detected across the current body of literature regarding the use of music in advertising, with specific focus to the main variables of the research, tonality, attention, retention, and purchase intention. By stating the findings thematically, it becomes possible to gain a clearer understanding of the research topic. Furthermore, it will assist in comparing the findings of this research with the literature, which would help in forming the practical implications and recommendations, as well as the future research suggestions.

2.6.1. Further expansion on tonality:

In most tonal chord progressions, the music drifts away from the tonic and sets up a resolution to come back to the tonic. Most musicians familiar with the Western music theory definition of tonality intuitively know what this progression does and to which destination it leads (Dowling & Harwood, 1986; Handel, 1989). According to Krumhansl (2000), a tonal centre (TC), or key, is a hierarchy of notes; a system for assigning an anticipated behaviour to each note and categorising those behaviours from most to least important to the music. For instance, in the key of C_{maj} , the G note is of crucial importance, second only to the tonic or root itself, C. Music can linger comfortably on G for a long time and still feels second to home, which is C. On the other hand, $C\#$ is a very uncomfortable note that holds great tension within the context of C_{maj} . As a tonal hierarchy, a tonal centre can be divided into five categories of notes. It's helpful to think of this hierarchy as a funnel; the tonic note at the very bottom is the primary consonance. It's the TC's single most important note, the one against which all other notes are measured and compared (Parncutt & Hair, 2011). The behaviour and relevance of each note will be determined by its relationship to the tonic.

The second layer consists of the chord tones, the 3rd and 5th (E and G in the case of C_{maj}) which complete the I chord. These secondary consonances sit in harmony with the tonic.

Figure 2.9: The I chord in C_{maj} (tonic in red, and chord tones in orange)

The third layer has all the other notes of the TC as the primary dissonances, which have the urge to collapse back to either the tonic, or a chord tone. These are the 2nd, 4th, 6th, and 7th degrees of the scale (D, F, A, and B, respectively, in the case of C_{maj})

The fourth layer includes the notes outside the scale as the secondary dissonances, which have the urge to collapse back to either the tonic, or a chord tone, or a primary dissonance note. These would be all the flat and sharp notes in the case of C_{maj}.

Finally, the fifth layer consists of the notes that are out of the 12-Tone Equal Temperament tuning system (12-TET). These are known as microtonalities which are tuned to pitches that fall between the typical tunings of the 12-TET notes (Wood, 1986). Microtonality is rarely used in Western music, and some musicologists argue that spending much time on this layer in music writing urges the consideration of another hierarchy that would better suit the genre of music (Duffin, 2007). Nonetheless, microtonality is included here for completeness.

Figure 2.10: Tonal hierarchy

This hierarchy can be considered to have a force of gravity; notes in the higher layers feel a pull down to the lower layers to ultimately reach the single tonic, the primary consonance.

Tonality has been found to have a range of cognitive effects in extensive experimental studies. Tonal tones (notes in the first 3 layers) are better recalled, preferred in final musical temporal positions, and more predictable than and less commonly mistaken with non-scale tones (notes in the 4th and 5th layers) (Dowling & Harwood, 1986; Handel, 1989; Krumhansl, 1990; 2000; Anta, 2015). Krumhansl (2000) argues that tonality, from a psychological point of view, seems to rely on two main principles: cognitive reference points, and frequency sensitivity.

2.6.2.1. Cognitive reference points:

The first principle, cognitive reference points, refers to items within a category that are used to encode, label, and recall other items within the same category. The task of a cognitive reference point – as a salient item – is to establish cognitive contact with the lesser salient items (Rosch, 1975; Krumhansl, 1990; 2020; Toiviainen & Krumhansl, 2003). In the category of fruit, for instance, the word ‘apple’ functions as a cognitive reference point, because other items within the category of fruit can be described in reference to ‘apple’ such as the naming of pineapple, and *Apfelsine* (which is German for ‘orange’, but literally translates to ‘apple from China’). Similarly, tonality establishes cognitive reference points as a means to define, describe, label, and remember all other tones in relation to the tonic (Krumhansl, 2000; Jackendoff & Lerdahl, 2006). This has been thoroughly examined in experimental studies using probe-tone techniques where a musical phrase is presented to participants followed by a single tone (probe-tone), which is one of the 12 tones of a chromatic scales. Participants are then prompted to rate how well the tone completes the phrase within its context (Krumhansl & Shepard, 1979; Krumhansl & Kessler, 1982; Vos, 2000; Anta, 2015). This led to the tonal hierarchy mentioned earlier.

2.6.2.2. Frequency sensitivity:

The other principle is sensitivity to the frequency with which items occur. Psychology research shows that items which occur more frequently can be easily encoded (Hintzman, 2004; Buchsbaum *et al.*, 2015), labelled (Alexomanolaki, Loveday, & Kennett, 2006; Jin, Suh, & Donovan, 2008), and recalled (Schmidt & Eisend, 2015; Shakil & Siddiqui, 2019) with more efficiency both quantitatively (more information is recalled with recurrence) and qualitatively (important information is remembered with recurrence) (Bromage & Mayer, 1986; Schmidt & Eisend, 2015). Neuroscience research further supports these findings (Buchsbaum *et al.*, 2015).

Moreover, frequent items can become important category items. Rosch (1973) found in a corpus of written English that the word ‘apple’ exemplifies this importance as it appeared far more frequently than the word ‘pineapple’, which proposes a connection between frequency sensitivity and cognitive reference points; the frequency of occurrence of cognitive reference points might be the very reason for their establishment in the first place (Krumhansl, 2000; Hintzman, 2004). What further cements this claim in a music context is that during tone-probing experiments, tones which appear more frequently are rated higher than those which appear less frequently (Krumhansl, 1990; Vos, 2000; Anta, 2015).

Furthermore, this phenomenon does not differ cross-culturally. For example, Western music listeners who are unfamiliar with North Indian classical music (Hindustani), which has

distinctly different characteristics from Western music, particularly in its tuning system which relies on 12-TET, gave similar ratings to Indian listeners during tone-probing experiments (Castellano, Bharucha, & Krumhansl, 1984).

Additionally, Oram & Cuddy (1995) found during tone-probing experiments that Western listeners, both musically literate and musically illiterate, are resilient and adaptable to novel tuning systems, and can further infer the tonal hierarchy of these tuning systems as they rate tones that are closer to the tonic higher than those further from it, and they also rate tones that occur more frequently higher than those that occur less frequently.

Since most listeners don't have absolute pitch, frequency sensitivity can be crucial in helping them strengthen their relative pitch, which provides a navigation system that assists in encoding, recalling, and classifying tones (Krumhansl, 2000).

2.6.2. The importance of advertising music:

Music is one of the main contents of advertising and is used in advertising in a variety of ways and for different purposes (Kellaris, Cox, & Cox, 1993). Its basic function has changed over the years: in the 1970s, music was primarily used as a recognition signal or "sound signet" (Riethmüller, 1973). Today, on the other hand, companies rely on holistic audio branding, a comprehensive brand sound, in order to achieve an optimal communication of the advertising message (Kellaris & Rice, 1993; Allan, 2007; Lantos & Craton, 2012; Zoghaib, 2019).

Audio branding is not to be seen as a form of advertising music, but rather as the result of the combination of different possible manifestations of advertising music: When using advertising music, a fundamental distinction can be made as to whether it is used as a recognition signal (such as sound logo or jingles), a full soundtrack accompanying the advertisement, or a combination of both (Scott, 1990; Shakil & Siddiqui, 2019). The term audio logo or sound logo is an analogy to the term visual logo: the audio logo becomes the unmistakable acoustic identifier of a brand. It is used because it has a simple learning effect in terms of brand recognition; it should serve as a memory anchor for the information and characteristics of a brand (Yalch, 1991; Taher & El Badawy, 2022).

However, this research is not concerned with sound logos or jingles. Rather, its main subject of interest lies within music as an accompanying component to an advertisement where it spans its entire length. In this way, not only is the advertising message to be conveyed, but also an emphatic conveyance of emotions, experiences, and associations (Morris & Boone, 1998; Craton & Lantos, 2011; Craton, Lantos, & Leventhal, 2017).

Within advertising music, one can further distinguish between music composed especially for advertising purposes and already written music (Stout, Leckenby, & Hecker, 1990). An example of already written music used in advertisements without changes is Coca Cola using Oasis' *'Whatever'* in 2011 and 2012 (Freund & Jacobi, 2016). Music that plays throughout the entirety of an advertisement is the most used. Background music is mostly instrumental, and often represents a soundscape complementing the product with the purpose to evoke emotions or behaviours such as purchasing (Alpert & Alpert, 1990; Morris & Boone, 1998; Wilson, 2003; Allan, 2007). Today, it is common in brand communication to combine the functions of music as a soundscape and music as a recognition signal or sound logo, which makes it possible to intensively anchor the brand acoustically (Alexomanolaki, Loveday, & Kennett, 2006; Abolhasani, Oakes, & Oakes, 2017).

As already mentioned, the forms of music that have been described so far are used in advertising in order to achieve certain effects, such as improving brand recall or inducing certain emotions. However, their use is rarely based on empirical findings, and correspondingly, little is known about the exact results of its influence on the variables that govern advertising as the limited literature that already exists is riddled with contradictions and limitations that hinder its generalisability (Dunbar, 1990; Allan, 2006; Eckhardt & Bradshaw, 2014; Shakil & Siddiqui, 2019). Nonetheless, several attempts have been made to understand the influence of different musical factors in advertising. The following sections will detail those factors and their use in advertising music.

2.6.3. The influence of music factors on advertising variables:

The dependent variables in previous research have been numerous in the study of music in advertising. Moreover, they have constantly changed in terms of priority, interest, importance, or methods of investigation and analysis. The following is an overview of the important studies from the last five decades, arranged thematically.

It's important to note that there aren't, to the knowledge of the researcher, any studies examining each tonal centre of the two tonal categories (major and minor), however, various researchers have used tonality (as major, minor, or atonal) as an independent variable to measure its influence on dependant variables such attention, retention, purchase intention, attitudes, and how consumers overall process and assess an advertisement.

2.6.3.1. Attention (A):

Attention has been an interest to researchers since the beginning of the research on advertising music. However, it has many inconsistencies and contradictions. Furthermore, there aren't any reliable tools for measuring attention other than directly via neuroimaging techniques, which is near absent in the research on advertising music.

The following will detail the relevant studies that have examined the influence of several dependant and moderating variables on attention:

- **Tonality:** Kellaris & Kent (1993) found that tonality (major, minor, and atonal) increases attention such that less consonant tonality grabs attention more (i.e. atonal relative to minor, minor relative to major). They also suggested that when music is used to influence mood via tonality, researchers should manipulate tonality but control tempo to avoid confounding pleasant feelings with arousal and its unplanned outcome.
- **Congruent vs. incongruent:** Kellaris, Cox, & Cox (1993) revealed the consumers' level of attention is increased when the advertising music is congruent with the advertising message, and that this increase in attention results in better message reception.
- **Tempo:** Kellaris & Kent (1991) found that tempo positively improves attention (named arousal in their study). In another study, they found that the tempo of the music positively influenced the perception of joy and attention in test participants (Kellaris & Kent, 1993).
- **Presence vs. absence:** Fundamentally, as one of the most common techniques of scientific analysis, is to have an experimental group (group with manipulated variables), and a control group (group with no manipulated variables). This would be, in this case, examining how placing music in advertisements works in contrast to music-free advertisements. Olsen (1995) examined the extent to which selectively silencing music can be used in advertising and concluded that silence can be used prior to any important information in the ad to increase attention. This effect only occurs, however, if the advertisement is otherwise underlaid with music, so that an accentuating effect occurs. Allan (2006) found that well-known popular music (with their original lyrics and vocals) had a more positive influence on attention to advertisements than pure instrumental music or even complete absence of music.
- **Volume:** Little is known about the effects of louder or quieter music in advertisements. Stout, Leckenby, & Hecker (1990), however, found that ads with overall louder volume were more difficult to follow than ads with softer volume. Kellaris & Rice (1993) found that women respond better to music at lower volume levels as they rated the advertisement more positively.
- **Valence:** Bolls, Lang, & Potter (2001) revealed via heart rate data that negative emotional messages receive more attention than positive ones.

2.6.3.2. Retention (*R*):

Retention has been examined more than attention, however, several contradictions persist. The following will detail the relevant studies that have examined the influence of several dependant and moderating variables on retention:

- **Congruent vs. incongruent:** Tom (1990) as well as MacInnis & Park (1991) showed for the first time that greater congruence between the music and the main message of the commercial could improve the memory of the information and lead to positive emotions regardless of recipient involvement. Both North et al. (2004) and Galan (2009) also showed that congruent music leads to increased recall of information, brand, and product. However, Heaton and Paris (2006) found no difference of retention between congruent and incongruent music. Shen & Chen (2006), on the other hand, found that if the music is not congruent with the advertisement, the desired advertising effects not only fail, but sometimes even has negative influences. In their study, a western-style television commercial was used for a shampoo product; white, blonde women used the product “with dynamic and vibrant expressions and movements typical of western commercials” (p. 58). The advertisement was accompanied by classical, traditional Chinese music, which the participants of the pilot study and the focus groups had found to be particularly incongruent with the visual stimulus of the ad. While this music slightly improved the memory of the advertising, it also had a negative impact on attitudes towards advertising. On the other hand, Shakil & Siddiqui (2019) showed that congruent music improves retention of jingles and their sung slogans. Abolhasani & Golrokhi (2022), however, developed music congruence as a four-degree spectrum (congruent - mildly incongruent - incongruent - severely incongruent) and found that mildly incongruent music improves brand information retention, as well as purchase intention and overall attitude towards the advertisement.
- **Tempo:** Similar to how the human body can physiologically acclimate to alterations of taste, touch, smell, and sight, variations of sound can trigger analogous responses. For example, when exposed to music with fast tempo, blood pressure, pulse rate, breathing rate, amplitude, and several other physiological manifestations involuntarily increase (Lundin, 1985). From an advertisement information retention viewpoint, higher rates of information and levels of informational density are recalled through faster tempi (Crozier, 1981), which improves the interest towards the advertising music, and thus contribute to the recipient’s pleasure (Berlyne, 1974). However, Brooker & Wheatley’s (1994) findings contradicted them as they found that brand recall is not influenced by fast or slow tempi. However, Hahn & Hwang (1999)

found that only particularly high and particularly low tempi have a negative effect on brand recall. Contrastingly, brand recall is improved at medium tempi (between 80 and 115 bpm). Galan (2009) was hardly able to find any impact of tempo on retention of information.

- **Vocal vs. instrumental:** In a broader sense, the factors of advertising music also include whether it is performed vocally or instrumentally or as a combination of both. Roehm (2001) found that an instrumental version of a pop song produced stronger memories of the advertising message than a vocal version of the same song if participants knew the piece in advance, because they would be more likely to sing along (i.e. fill in the gaps). However, advertising music with vocals produced stronger memories of the advertising message when the test participants did not know the song in advance. Allan (2006) found that well-known popular music (with their original lyrics and vocals) had a more positive effect on brand recall. However, Heaton and Paris (2006) found no difference of retention between vocal and instrumental music. Furthermore, there was some focus on the combination of music and spoken words. Yalch (1991), for example, found that brand recall could be improved through the use of music, concluding that if slogans were included as sung jingles in advertising, the recipient will later recall them better than if they were conveyed exclusively through speech. Wallace, (1994) also came to the same conclusion that sung words are recalled better than spoken text. Shakil & Siddiqui (2019), found that jingles with lyrics are recalled more than jingles without lyrics.
- **Present vs. absent:** Sewall & Sarel (1986) found that the presence of background music does not necessarily have an impact on brand recall, whereas Hunt (1988; cited in Bruner, 1990), stated that presence on music had positive influence on recall, which is confusing given both Sewall & Sarel and Hunt have used similar methods to examine radio advertisements. Park & Young (1986) found that a further differentiation has to be made with regards to the involvement of the recipients: for recipients with low levels of involvement, music facilitated the formation of a positive brand attitude and recall, but for highly involved recipients, the presence of music caused distractions compared to its absent. The results of Brooker & Wheatley (1994) go in a similar direction, stating that the presence of music hinders the message recall and cannot improve awareness of the advertising message. And interestingly, Olsen (1995) showed that silencing music prior to the presenting of important information can increase information retention.
- **Repetition:** Bhattacharya, Zioga, & Lewis (2017) found in an EEG study that repeated advertisements with the same advertising music showed larger frontal asymmetry in brain activity, which suggests elevated attention.

2.6.3.3. Purchase intention (*PI*):

Advertising music's influence on purchase intention has garnered some focus in the literature, with numerous studies exploring the factors that influence consumers' likelihood to make a purchase, and sometimes acting on this intention. However, there remain certain contradictions and gaps.

The following will detail the relevant studies that have examined the influence of several dependant and moderating variables on purchase intention:

- **Tonality:** Liu, Abolhasani, & Hang (2022) found that music in major tonality strengthens the effect of positive brand attitudes on purchase intention, and that that fast tempo music in major tonality can further strengthen the effect of positive brand attitudes on purchase intention. Thus, they concluded that the indirect effect of positively-rated music on purchase intention via positive brand attitudes will be jointly moderated by tonality and tempo.
- **Congruent vs. incongruent:** North *et al.* (2004) found that a more positive attitude is noticed towards the brand and a more pronounced purchase intention is shown by the recipient when advertising music is congruent. To ensure that the music used in the study fit the advertising in terms of musical congruence, North *et al.* (2004) had experts select the pieces to match the respective brands and then asked the test participants in the study to assess the extent to which they found the music to be suitable for the advertising. Galan (2009) underpinned the hypothesis that liking and congruence (i.e. positively rating congruent advertising music) is of great importance. He found that music likeability and congruence have significantly more influence purchase intention, than the structural components of the music such as tempo or genre. However, Abolhasani & Golrokhi (2022) found that mildly incongruent music improves purchase intention.
- **Attitude:** Raja, Anand, & Allan (2023) found that the attitude towards the advertising music positively correlated with consumers likelihood to purchase.
- **Tempo:** Brooker & Wheatley (1994) reached the conclusion that purchase intention is not influenced by faster or slower tempi.
- **Volume:** Sullivan (2002) concluded that within a restaurant setting, lower music volumes encouraged more spending on foods and drinks.

2.6.3.4. Attitude:

Positively rated advertising music should, as per classical conditioning and the Elaboration Likelihood Model (ELM), promote positive attitudes, which should lead to positive assessment of the brand (Gardner, 1985; Kellaris & Kent, 1993; Alpert, Alpert, & Maltz, 2005). However, there are several contradictions throughout these investigations.

The following will detail the relevant studies that have examined the influence of several dependant and moderating variables on attitude:

- **Tonality:** Scott (1990) argued that due to Western music cultural conditioning, the familiar, consonant major and minor tonalities may sound more pleasant than the unfamiliar, dissonant atonality, thus overall resulting in better ad performance. She further stated that due to this cultural bias, tonal music is generally more researched than atonal music. Alpert & Alpert (1990), for example, recognised a significant effect of the musical mood on purchase intention: sad music (minor tonality) is more likely to trigger an intention to buy than happy music (major tonality). Alpert, Alpert & Maltz (2005) again demonstrated an influence of the musical mood on purchase intention. According to them, minor (sad) music had a positive influence on the participants' purchase intention if they were in a sad mood while shopping. Furthermore, Stout, Leckenby & Hecker (1990) stated that ads with music in major tonalities can significantly evoke less irritation than music in minor tonalities. Furthermore, they concluded that ads with music in major tonalities are perceived as warmer than ads with music in minor tonalities and can even reinforce brand image. And Kellaris and Kent (1991) stated that ads with music in major tonality are perceived as more pleasant than ads with music toned to minor tonality, followed by atonality (neither major nor minor tonality) which resulted the least positive results.
- **Congruent vs. incongruent:** Shen & Chen (2006) found that incongruent music results in negative attitudes towards the advertisement. Lavack, Thakor & Bottausci (2008) found that congruent music improves attitudes towards advertising and the brand, especially when the advertisement demands high cognitive processing from the recipient. In the case of unsophisticated advertisements, on the other hand, neither the fit of the music played a role, nor whether music was played at all. Furthermore, After Yeoh & North (2010a; 2010b) concluded in their two consecutive 2010 studies that music congruence has a direct influence on product choice over alternative competitors, they later in 2012 examined the influence of congruent music on the brand preference of recipients. The result was that musical congruence could influence brand preference among consumers who did not have a clear preference before receiving the advertisement. Contrastingly, there was no influence on those

with an already existing brand preference (Yeoh & North, 2012). Yet, Ausín *et al.* (2021) found, in their EEG study, that there is no significant difference of advertising music likability between congruent and incongruent music.

- **Present vs. absent:** Bierley, McSweeney, & Vannieuwkerk (1985) showed that positively-rated advertising music will result in a more positively-rated advertisement than if the advertisement had no music.
- **Liking vs. disliking:** Gorn (1982) reported that liked advertising music during and advertisements can positively influence product preferences. Bierley, McSweeney & Vannieuwkerk (1985) replicated and expanded Gorn's study and reached similar conclusions. Contrastingly, Allen & Madden (1985), Pitt & Abratt (1988), and Kellaris & Cox (1989) could not support the assumption that product preferences could be conditioned by music that is liked or disliked. And Galan (2009) found that positively-rated advertising music positively correlates with attitudes. Indeed, Bozman, Mueling, & Pettit-O'Malley (2011) also found that positively rated background music in low-involvement situations leads to more positive branding. In high-involvement situations, music with a neutral rating is most likely to lead to favourable attitudes towards the brand.
- **Tempo:** Brooker & Wheatley (1994) found in a study of the music used in radio advertisements that there is no influence of tempo on brand attitude.
- **Genre:** Different genres of music can very well lead to different perceptions of brands. Zander (2006, p. 468) emphasised that different styles of music lead to significantly different impressions of brand and "endorser" (i.e. the person appearing in the advertisement), but without changing the general evaluation of the product. For example, depending on the music style (mainstream vs. neo-classical pop music), the "endorser" was assigned very different attributes depending on the music style, where subjects listening to the ad with the latter music style rated the endorser as tidier, more eager, and more serious in comparison to the former music style, or the condition of no music. Zander, Apaolaza-Ibanez, & Hartmann (2010) came to similar conclusions. As for old popular songs, Chou and Lien (2014) revealed that they can evoke positive emotions with the advertisements as long as participants are familiar with the song.

2.6.3.5. Other variables and themes:

The following will detail the relevant studies that have examined the influence of several dependant and moderating variables on other independent variables:

- **Perceived time:** Kellaris and Kent (1992) found, albeit not in a direct advertising context, that, from the perspective of participants, time is perceived to pass faster when they listen to music in major tonality than when they listen to music in minor or atonal tonality. Kellaris & Mantel (1996) showed an influence of music congruence on the perceived duration of ads when the background music played was soothing, as the ads were perceived to be significantly longer. Conversely, no effect could be determined with more arousing music. Caldwell and Hibbert (1999), on the other hand, showed that slow music will result in more time spent in a restaurant. And Galan (2009) found that positively-rated advertising music positively correlates with perceived ad duration.

2.6.3.6. Summary of literature findings:

The following table presents a summary of the relevant findings of the literature, detailing their authors, dates (chronologically), dependant & independent variables, and results:

Author (Date)	Independent Variables	Dependent Variables	Results
Berlyne (1974)	Tempo	Attitude	Improved interest and pleasure
Crozier (1981)	Tempo	Retention	Improved when fast
Gorn (1982)	Liked vs. disliked	Attitude	Improved when liked
Allen & Madden (1985)	Liked vs. disliked	Attitude	No association
Bierley, McSweeney, & Vannieuwkerk (1985)	Liked vs. disliked	Attitude	Improved when liked
	Presence vs. absence		Improved when present
Park & Young (1986)	Presence vs. absence	Attitude	Positive when low involvement, and negative when high involvement
Sewall & Sarel (1986)	Presence vs. absence	Retention	No difference

Hunt (1988)	Presence vs. absence	Retention	Improved when present
Pitt & Abratt (1988)	Liked vs. disliked	Attitude	No association
Kellaris & Cox (1989)	Liked vs. disliked	Attitude	No association
Alpert & Alpert (1990)	Tonality (major, minor) (described as mood and categorised as happy or sad)	Purchase intention	Higher with minor than with major
Stout, Leckenby, & Hecker (1990)	Volume (loud, soft)	Ability to follow	Difficult when loud
	Tonality (called mode: major, minor, mixed)	Attitude	Perceived warmer with major than minor or mixed, major evokes less irritation
	Tempo (slow, moderate, fast)	Attitude	Hard to follow when slow
Tom (1990)	Congruent vs incongruent	Retention	Improved when congruent regardless of involvement
Kellaris & Kent (1991)	Tempo (fast, moderate, slow)	Attention (named arousal)	Positively improved attention
	Tonality (named modality: major, minor, atonal)	Purchase intention	Improved purchase intention on a major-minor-atonal spectrum
		Attitude	Improved more with major than minor or atonal
MacInnis & Park (1991)	Congruent vs. incongruent	Retention	Improved when congruent regardless of involvement

Yalch (1991)	Presence vs. absence	Retention	Improved when present and slogans are sung
Kellaris & Kent (1992)	Tonality (named modality: major, minor, atonal)	Perception of time passing	Perceived faster with major than minor or atonal
Kellaris, Cox, & Cox (1993)	Congruent vs. incongruent	Attention	Improved when congruent, which improved message reception
Kellaris & Kent (1993)	Tempo (fast, moderate, slow)	Attention (named arousal), and attitude	Positively improved attention and attitude
	Tonality (major, minor, atonal)	Attention (named arousal)	Improved with more dissonant (i.e. more with atonal relative to minor, and more with minor relative to major)
Kellaris & Rice (1993)	Volume	Attitude	Improved for women when low
Brooker & Wheatley (1994)	Presence vs. absence	Retention and awareness	Negative when present
	Tempo (fast, slow)	Purchase intention, retention, attitude	No influence
Wallace (1994)	Presence vs. absence	Retention	Improved when present and slogans are sung
Olsen (1995)	Silencing music before important information	Attention, retention	Improved with silence
Kellaris & Mantel (1996)	Congruent vs. incongruent	Perceived duration of the ad	Longer when music is soothing, and no effect when music is arousing

Caldwell and Hibbert (1999)	Tempo	Time spent in restaurant	Improved when slow
Hahn & Hwang (1999)	Tempo	Retention	Negative only when tempo is very fast or very slow, but improved when BPM is between 80-115
Roehm (2001)	Vocal vs. instrumental	Retention	Improved with instrumental of familiar music, and improved with vocal of unfamiliar music
Bolls, Lang, & Potter (2001)	Valence of ad music and advertising message	Attention	Improved when low
Sullivan (2002)	Volume	Purchase intention and behaviour	Spending increased with lower volume
Wilson (2003)	Presence vs. absence	Purchase intention	Lower when absent
North <i>et al.</i> (2004)	Congruent vs. incongruent	Retention, attitude, purchase intention	All improved when congruent
Alpert, Alpert & Maltz (2005)	Tonality (major, minor: described as mood and categorised as happy or sad, respectively)	Purchase intention	Improved with minor music when participants were already in a sad mood
Allan (2006)	Vocal vs. instrumental vs. absence	Attention, retention	Improved more with popular and familiar music than with instrumental or no music
Heaton and Paris (2006)	Congruent vs. incongruent	Retention	No difference
	Vocal vs. instrumental		No difference

Shen & Chen (2006)	Congruent vs. incongruent	Retention	Improved retention when incongruent
		Attitude	Reduced attitude when incongruent
Zander (2006)	Different genre vs. no music	Attitude	Different associations attributed to the endorser (i.e. the person appearing in the ad), no associations with no music
Lavack, Thakor & Bottausci (2008)	Congruent vs. incongruent	Attitude	Improved when congruent, especially with ads that require high cognitive involvement
Galan (2009)	Liked vs. disliked, congruent vs. incongruent, tempo, genre	Attitude, purchase intention, perceived length of the ad, retention	All improved more with liked and congruent than with tempo (fast, medium, or so) and across different genres
Yeoh & North (2010a; 2010b)	Congruent vs. incongruent	Choice over alternative products	Improves competitive edge
Zander, Apaolaza-Ibanez & Hartmann (2010)	Different genres vs. no music	Attitude	Different associations attributed to the endorser (i.e. the person appearing in the ad), no associations with no music

Bozman, Mueling, & Pettit-O'Malley (2011)	Liked vs. disliked	Attitude	Improved when liked (in low-involvement), and no effect when liked (in high-involvement)
Yeoh & North (2012)	Congruent vs. incongruent	Choice over alternative products	Improves competitive edge only with consumers who don't already have a preference
Chou and Lien (2014)	Genre	Attitude	Positive with old popular songs if consumers are familiar with the music
Bhattacharya, Zioga, & Lewis (2017)	Repetition of the same ad music in the same campaign	Attention	Repeated ads with the same music showed larger frontal asymmetry in brain activity, which suggests elevated attention.
Shakil & Siddiqui (2019)	Congruent vs. incongruent	Retention	Improved when congruent
	Jingle with lyrics vs. jingle without lyrical		Improved with lyrics
Ausín et al. (2021)	Congruent vs. incongruent	Attitude	No difference
Abolhasani & Golrokhi (2022)	Congruence (deployed as congruent, mildly incongruent, incongruent, or severely incongruent)	Retention	Improved when mildly incongruent
		Purchase intention	
		Attitude	

Liu, Abolhasani, & Hang (2022)	Tonality, tempo	Purchase intention	Major tonality increases the effect of positive brand attitude on purchase intention, and fast major music strengthens this influence even more
Raja, Anand, & Allan (2023)	Attitude towards ad music	Purchase intention	Improved when positive

Table 2.2: Summary of literature findings from the past 50 years

2.7. Analysis of the Literature:

An evaluation of the selected literature will be presented here. This analysis aims to highlight 3 main points: the lack of research and control, the need for interdisciplinary approaches, and identifying the main gap in the research.

2.7.1. Lack of research and control:

As discussed in detail in the introduction chapter, the lack of research on advertising music is one of the main problems of this research area. Based on the importance music is given in advertising and the frequency with which advertising recipients consume music through advertising, this area should be researched far more than it currently is (North *et al.*, 2004; Graakjær, 2015). Due to the interdisciplinary nature of the topic, there is also little general research discourse, which predestines research on the effects of advertising music to a "field of perceptual new beginnings" (Graakjær & Jantzen, 2009, p. 13).

Furthermore, Bruner (1990, p. 94) views music as a "complex chemistry of controllable elements", however, the influence of intervening variables other than the dependant variable manipulated such as the case with tempo, harmony, complexity, genre, or degree of familiarity are rarely controlled. For instance, Roehm's (2001) or Allan's (2006) investigation of vocal vs instrumental music do not account for the variance in tempo, genre, chord progression and harmony, melody... etc. This could be a primary reason to the constant contradictions in the literature. Although generalised statements about the effect of music in advertising are hardly permissible given the current state of research, Allan (2007) sums up that carefully selected music is more likely to yield consistent results for the literature.

The limited amount of research conducted on the topic of advertising music has been a source of confusion and challenge for researchers, primarily due to the presence of contradictions in the findings. The multifaceted nature of the topic contributes to the inconsistencies observed in prior studies (Kellaris & Kent, 1993). For example, correlational studies have yielded varying results regarding the impact of music on ad performance. Some studies have shown that music can enhance advertising effectiveness (Hoyer, Srivastava, & Jacoby, 1984; Lantos & Craton, 2012; Liu, Abolhasani, & Hang, 2022), while others have suggested that it can hinder performance (Haley, Richardson, & Baldwin, 1984; Sewall & Sarel, 1986; Craton, Lantos, & Leventhal, 2017). Interestingly, there are also studies that have found no significant effect of music on ad performance (Stewart & Furse, 1986). These contradictory findings highlight the complexity of the relationship between music and advertising, necessitating further exploration. There is an abundance of possible effective parameters in advertising music, and researchers have only just started to understand the interactions between those different parameters.

2.7.2. A need for interdisciplinarity:

Although various studies on the effect of advertising music are already available, there is no comprehensive narrative and, above all, conclusive state of research on many of the dependent variables examined, with contradictions across the literature for several decades (Oakes 2007). This is because the primary academic disciplines involved within this topic (i.e. marketing, musicology, psychology, and in this research, neuroscience) do not conjoin with each other enough to identify and investigate a more specific phenomenon, and in the cases where they do conjoin, not enough variables are controlled to form any rigorous research results, which renders these studies riddled with limitations that drastically hinder the generalisability of their outcome, and more disadvantageously, create confounding conclusions that raise more questions than answers (Herget, Schramm, & Breves, 2018).

Musicologists too often fail to address the complexity of music design and theory, whereas advertisers and marketing scholars, on the other hand, tend to undermine the intricacy of music theory, composition, and performance (Negus & Street 2002). Furthermore, research in this area is still comparatively young and is only pursued by a few researchers. Therefore, researchers, sooner or later, will be required to adequately deal with the fundamentals of advertising music research and how it integrates with consumer psychology and neurology (Suomala *et al.*, 2012; Cambra, Martínez-Martínez, & Niño, 2018; Alsharif *et al.*, 2021). The interdisciplinary view of the topic is inevitable, which became particularly clear in the last few years (Ariely & Berns, 2010; Ford, 2019).

2.7.3. Gap identification:

Tonality, specifically the distinction between major and minor music, appears to be a music component that exhibits relatively consistent findings in the literature. For example, the studies highlighted above show that music in major tonality is generally perceived and utilised as conveying a sense of happiness, whereas music in minor tonality is associated with conveying a sense of sadness, and these two tonal categories have had a significant role in shaping attitudes and emotional responses in relation to the music used in advertisements. However, given this significance regarding the influence of the tonal categories as major and minor, it's unwise to disregard the influence of each tonal centre within these categories, especially that some researchers have highlighted that the driving reason for this dismissal is the Transpositional Invariance Assumption (Quinn & White, 2017; Lattner, Grachten, & Widmer, 2018). By acknowledging the potential significance of not only both major and minor tonal categories, but also each individual tonal centre (TC) within them, this research can provide the pioneering nuanced understanding of how tonality impacts consumer processing, perception, and behaviour towards the advertisements.

2.8. Chapter Conclusion:

This chapter needed to begin by providing necessary overview of several variables and concepts to facilitate the comprehension of following sections. Therefore, the overview elaborated on advertising, music, tonality & tonal centres (TCs), attention from a neurological perspective, retention from a psychological, neurological, & advertising perspectives, and finally, purchase intention.

Next, the theoretical framework of the research was expounded by providing a Foucauldian approach to problematising the Transpositional Invariance Assumption in order to allow for the reconceptualisation of tonality as a spectrum of TCs rather than a binary or dichotomous construct of major and minor. Following problematisation is an elaboration on classical conditioning, elaboration likelihood model (ELM), and music congruence to cement how music is going to be used in this research and to further explain tonality as a spectrum. Then, the attention economy was used as framework to justify investigating attention and retention, followed by the theory of planned behaviour to explain the attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioural control of purchase intention.

The theoretical framework was then followed by a systematic review of the literature, starting with the methodology used for the review, which detailed the inclusion and exclusion criteria, the databases and strategy used, and the results of this methodology. The themes of the literature were then presented by highlighting the findings of the most common themes in the existing body of literature (attention, retention, purchase intention, attitudes, and others). These findings were summarised in a table that showcased the main findings of the literature on advertising music from the last 5 decades.

An analysis of the literature showed that a lack of overall research is certainly one of the main driving factors for the inconsistencies, and that many researchers have urged for the adoption of interdisciplinary approach to the topic. Most importantly, tonal centres have never been examined in the literature, and if the Transpositional Invariance Assumption is suspended, then a research gap is created with regards to the influence of TCs on advertising music. This argument became central to establish the research hypotheses which were finally discussed against the literature review.

3. CHAPTER THREE - RESEARCH DESIGN

3.1. Chapter Introduction

3.2. Philosophy & Approach

3.3. Methodology, Methods, & Tools of Measurement

3.4. Sampling & Participants Selection

3.5. Data Analysis Tools & Techniques

3.6. Ethical Considerations

3.7. Research Timeline

3.8. Chapter Conclusion

3.1. Chapter Introduction:

This chapter will detail the design and methodology of this research, which is the main framework used for collecting, analysing, and interpreting the data. A well-designed research is one that ensures the validity, reliability, and rigour of the research (Tobi & Kampen, 2018). Thus, the design and methodology of this research will be carefully constructed to align with its objectives and interdisciplinary nature.

Within this chapter, the research philosophy and approach will be outlined first, highlighting the advantages and disadvantages of the adopted worldview, which would substantially influence the approach to methodology and methods used for data collection and analysis. Indeed, an insight into the ontological, epistemological, and axiological views will be the source for justifying the means with which the topic of this research is investigated.

Furthermore, this chapter will detail the exact tools of measurement that will be used to collect the necessary data to answer the research questions. Initially, it will conduct a few pre-tests to ensure the quality of the data collected is of high standards and does indeed represent what is being measured. Upon the completion of the pre-testing stage, the main experiments can commence. A convenience sampling technique will be detailed in the data collection strategy, weighing its advantages and disadvantages, and providing countering techniques such as analysis at intervals to achieve data saturation and alleviate some of the disadvantages of convenience sampling.

An account of how each piece of data will be processed and analysed is then provided, specifically highlighting the clean-up process of the EEG data, which will remove signals from eye blinks, heart rate, baseline activity, and other noises. This is a necessary step that allows the collected data to be analysed more confidently ensuring the high quality of the final results.

Undoubtedly, this methodology requires careful ethical considerations. The researcher plays a crucial role in protecting the safety and privacy of the participants, therefore, safeguarding their confidentiality and anonymity throughout the entire research has the highest priority. Participants will be reassured through several forms throughout the research, as well as verbally, that their data will be highly protected and will only be used for research purposes. Furthermore, the researcher will ensure that participants are satisfied with the experiments at all times and any of their questions are answered.

Overall, several steps will be made to guarantee a strong research design that delivers on its aim and achieve all its objectives.

3.2. Philosophy & Approach:

In the context of research design, philosophy refers to the underlying beliefs, principles, and assumptions that a researcher has about the reality surrounding the phenomenon being examined. The philosophy will guide the research’s worldview on the nature of knowledge, what constitutes truth, and the process of inquiry (Holden & Lynch, 2004).

Whereas the research approach is the means by which a theory is developed based on the philosophy and worldview adopted. It’s the route taken by the researcher to construct the main ideas, hypotheses, and questions of the research, which will largely inform the means by which data is collected, analysed, and interpreted.

The research onion figure below by Saunders, Lewis, & Thornhill (2023) offers a framework for understanding the different layers and components of research design. It’s often utilised in business research to assist in selecting the appropriate tools for the research design.

This research will take a positivist hypothetico-deductive philosophy and approach, which will be defined, justified, and criticised in the following sections.

Figure 3.1: Research design onion (Saunders, Lewis, & Thornhill, 2023, p. 128)

3.2.1. Positivism:

Positivism is a philosophical perspective that emphasises the importance of empirical evidence and scientific methods in acquiring knowledge and truth about reality. Positivism makes the postulation that reality is ultimately observable, measurable, and quantifiable. It is based on the belief that social sciences can be examined in a similar manner to the natural sciences (Irshaidat, 2022). Furthermore, the positivist view advocates for the use of deductive reasoning to uncover absolute truths about phenomena. Axiologically, positivism “relies heavily on objectivity and so dismisses the importance of individuals’ subjective experiences and values—be they the experiences and values of research participants or of researchers.” (Park, 2020, p. 692).

The separation of personal biases and subjective interpretations from the scientific means of analysis is a crucial aspect of positivism as the aim of positivism is to establish causal relationships between variables, which explain how world events interact with each other. This notion helps to uncover patterns that assist in predicting further future events (Alharahsheh & Pius, 2020).

Moreover, positivism prioritises the use of controlled experiments that employ statistical tools to gather data about the phenomenon examined. Positivism also places a strong emphasis on generalisability of the results based on empirical evidence “to identify similarities concerning the phenomenon under study within varied conditions, in order to apply the findings to another set of conditions” (Irshaidat, 2022, p. 129).

However, positivism has also faced criticisms for oversimplifying complex social issues, disregarding subjective experiences and qualitative aspects of human behaviour and interaction, and neglecting the influences of social and cultural contexts on individuals and societies. As a result, positivism tends to reduce the concept of agency to a minimal; individuals, collectively, can be measured and their behaviours can be shaped regardless of their standalone subjective experiences of reality (Park, 2020). This decontextualisation can often be an issue for research in the social sciences as, under positivism, it will view the topic of concern independent from the subjective individual context, which could hold different forms of truths that could be applicable in different contexts. However, the researcher will argue for a net-benefit to this philosophical stance.

This research indeed holds a positivist view on the topic as it looks to measure, label, and quantify the influences of the tonal centres of advertising music on consumers’ brain activity and their subsequent behaviours. This choice of philosophical stance can be justified as such:

- **Interdisciplinarity:** since this research relates to neuroscience, the research issue is no longer a purely social science issue as it has direct relevance to issues within the natural sciences, which typically align with positivism. This relevance to neurosciences further justifies the use of positivism as there are no reliable means to measure brain activity, especially attention, using other means of neuroimaging, which provides quantitative data about the human brain.
- **Subjective experiences are traceable to objective values:** this research recognises that individual experiences of consumers may be subjective. However, the researcher adopts the view that while the individual experiences of consumers are subjective, they stem from predetermined objective values that exist independent from individualism. This view allows for the identification of commonalities and predictable patterns, which can contribute to a more systematic understanding of consumer decision-making and behaviour, which can then create opportunities for other researchers to adopt other philosophical views such as interpretivism.
- **Subjectivity can be misleading in this research, as well as redundant:** the proposed methods for this research advocate that the brain can reveal what the consumer experience actually is even if it contradicted with how they subjectively perceive it. This highlights a redundancy in taking a different philosophical stance when dealing with neural data, since non-positivist worldviews, such as interpretivism, could not measure the natural and physical world.

With that said, the researcher does not dismiss the assumptions made when taking the positivist stance throughout this research. According to Kincheloe and Tobin (2009, pp. 518-519), by adopting positivism, this research would be making several assumptions about reality and the nature of this topic:

- **Formal process of inquiry:** positivism adheres to pre-decided and specific rules, methods, and lines of inquiry. It consists of identifying knowledge gaps, developing research questions, constructing hypotheses, critically addressing the literature, utilising the available methods to collect data, processing the data via pre-established analyses, and finally reflecting on results, implications, and future research. Positivist research hardly ever deviates from this process.
- **Reality is intractable:** this assumption establishes that the rules of the world in which human beings operate are fixed. This unchangeability feature ensures that the researcher can examine and understand the underlying mechanisms that govern phenomena without expectations of changes during or after the research. This assumption seems to only break at the quantum level as per the Heisenberg uncertainty principle (Hossieni *et al.*, 2016).

- **Reality is decontextualised:** the research will assume that the individuality contexts are irrelevant when they can't be measured. For example, the research will account for some, but not all, cross-cultural contexts (e.g. it will consider participants' gender, sex, educational status, music preference... etc), but it will not consider these aspects, or other personal aspects, within a wider framework that details how they change and interact across space and time for each individual participant.
- **Universalistic assumptions:** the truth discovered through positivist means are assumed to be universal and can be applied to all domains of the world. Pre-Einsteinian physics for example, sustained the universal notion that gravity is constant across the cosmos. This was only refuted in the early 20th century when Einstein published his General Theory of Relativity. An example more relevant to this research is the assumption that the auditory system is similar across all healthy humans, and functions via already established neural mechanisms and processes. Of course, as per the gravity example, such assumptions could be challenged in the future. However, in order for this to happen, the assumption has to undergo several research processes and discoveries that are replicated, verified, and empirically scrutinised for several decades, and much of this research would also be positivistic in nature.
- **Reductionistic view:** for each variable controlled or manipulated throughout this research, there are several variables unaccounted for. Positivism tends to reduce the complexity of the research context by focusing on specific variables and their relationships. This reductionistic approach is deliberate as it allows for the isolation and analysis of individual variables, assisting the research in establishing causal links and drawing practical conclusions.
- **One-dimensional reality:** positivist research believes in and seeks for a single objective truth, which can be discovered, described, and deconstructed to elements that can later be manipulated or controlled. Reality, according to other philosophical views, may be multidimensional where more than one type of truth exists.

Despite these assumptions, Kincheloe & Tobin (2009) argue that the movement in the past 4 decades to declare the “death” of positivism was much exaggerated (p. 513), as it's still the primary view driving discovery and accumulation of knowledge across all disciplines of research, and that “we have not reached the end of epistemology, for there is much analysis, conversation, and debate that must take place” (p. 526).

Accordingly with the adoption of positivism in this research, the following epistemological, ontological, axiological, and hypothetico-deduction views are held:

3.2.1.1. Ontology:

The researcher's fundamental view on the nature of reality within this research is that there exists an objective¹ truth to how the human brain perceives the different tonal centres of advertising music when incorporated into advertisements; there are inherent and consistent responses that individuals exhibit when exposed to specific tonal qualities in advertising music. The positivist stance on this issue posits that this truth can be uncovered by means of deduction, which empirically observes, measures, and analyses the phenomenon. This ontological view will assist in identifying universal patterns that are generalisable within the conditions and limitations of this investigation.

3.2.1.2. Epistemology:

The reality, as described above, can be quantified through several quantitative methods. Indeed, this research will employ rigorous quantitative techniques, such as electroencephalography (EEG) and questionnaires to collect the empirical data needed to uncover patterns, relationships, and practical conclusions. It is the researcher's view that by adhering to the quantitative principles, replicability, and systematic inquiry, this research can contribute to the existing body of literature some reliable, robust, and relevant knowledge, upon which several other research can take place.

3.2.1.3. Axiology:

The axiological perspective of this research emphasises the importance of deriving meaning from logical reasoning and objective analysis. This axiological stance posits that it's possible for the researcher and the reality to remain separate throughout the research without bias. Nonetheless, the researcher acknowledges that personal values and beliefs have already influenced the research in the initial process of topic selection due to personal interests in music theory and neuroscience. It is, therefore, important to uphold rigorous and systematic scrutiny over the succeeding processes of the research as to not extend any further personal biases. This axiological view helps to enhance the credibility and reliability of the research results and contributes directly to the overall scientific rigor of the study.

3.2.1.4. Hypothetico- deductive model:

The hypothetico-deductive model is an approach to scientific inquiry and research design. It follows a deductive reasoning process where the researcher develops hypotheses then tests these hypotheses via a research design which is structured around a cycle of design strategies, population and sampling reasoning, data collection methods, and data analysis tools in order to conduct a proper empirical testing of the phenomenon, and data analysis (Tariq, 2015). The hypotheses detailed in the first chapter of this research were the initial step of adopting the hypothetico-deductive model. The next sections in this chapter will detail the remaining steps.

¹ The word 'objective' is used here to imply that something is true within the confines of current human knowledge, and that this 'objective' truth is true for all intents and purposes within a practical sense until otherwise is revealed through other means of deduction (please consider to the gravity example earlier under the universalistic assumptions). The researcher does not believe in absolute truths that transcend space and time. The researcher also believes that this definition of objectivity is not radical enough to justify a paradigm shift that adopts a different philosophical stance.

3.3. Methodology, Methods, & Tools of Measurement:

The mono-quantitative methodology of this research will serve as a roadmap that guides the practical research process, ensuring that the study is conducted in a systematic and organised manner. This section will detail the research methodology and the methods used to conduct the research, as well as the rationale behind these choices, detailing the strengths and limitations. Furthermore, it will elaborate on the specific tools and experiments with which data is collected.

3.3.1. Overview:

This overview will provide a short process description of the research design. The design consists of electroencephalogram (EEG) experiments that measure the brain activity of participants as they view a 15-minute documentary with 2 ad breaks (juice brand, and smartphone brand. 20 seconds each). The visual elements of the ads are controlled for all participants. However, the music for the ads is manipulated only through the tonal centre (TC) (i.e. harmony, chord progression, volume, tempo... etc, are all controlled). The juice ad will feature music chosen randomly from one of the 12 major TCs, and the smartphone ad will feature music in the relative minor TC of that major TC (e.g. C_{maj} and its relative minor A_{min} for one participant, but F_{maj} and its relative minor D_{min} for another participant).

After the viewing of the documentary and two ads (i.e. after the EEG reading is recorded), the participant answers a questionnaire that includes several sections to collect data on demographics, brand information retention, and purchase intention.

Pre-testing with 6 different participants took place prior to the main experiments. The following figure illustrates the main experiment journey of the participant, which took between 25 and 35 minutes.

Figure 3.2: Main experiments participant journey

Furthermore, a pre-test was initially conducted to ensure the congruence of the music used with the ads, as well as the internal consistency of the purchase intention questionnaire items via a Chronbach's Alpha test.

As per everything mentioned so far, the research can be seen as made up of 3 phases:

- **Pre-tests:** 2 types of pre-tests:
 - Congruence & validity: to ensure the music used in the two ads is congruent with the ads, and to ensure the validity of the purchase intention questionnaire items.
 - Main experiments pre-test: before conducting the main experiments, a few EEG pre-test sessions need to be conducted to provide insight on setup process, estimated time, signal accuracy, and other potential issues.
- **Main experiments:** a 5-step process
 - Research briefing and pre-disclosed consent (as the main purpose of the research will be hidden from participants)
 - EEG prepping.
 - EEG reading.
 - Questionnaire.
 - Full disclosure and post-disclosure consent.
- **Manipulation check:** a few experiments similar to the main experiments except they include 1 major TC and 1 minor TC (transposed up one register ottava), and the same major TC and minor TC (transposed down one register ottava), to check if octaval transposition plays a role in influencing responses.

The following figure will illustrate the overall research design from start to finish.

Figure 3.3: Research design

3.3.2. Testing materials (stimuli):

As mentioned earlier, the research will be using two 20-second advertisements¹ to use in the experiments (one for each tonal category: major and minor). A juice brand named Neet has been created to be associated with the major music, while a smartphone brand named Zeel has been created to be associated with the minor music. The two brands were created specifically for this research as opposed to using already existing brands in order to eliminate a potential influence of familiarity.

The details of the two brands are as follows:

Juice ad (major condition)	Smartphone ad (major condition)
Name: NEET	Name: ZEEL
Flavours: orange, kiwi, grape	Colours: crimson red, night blue, raven black
Slogan: all you neet	Slogan: the real zeel
Logo: 	
Other details shown: 120 calories, 0 added sugar, 100% organic, 100% fruit juice, no added sugars, no preservatives	Other details shown: the all new Zeel phones, 3 unique colours, 5.8" display, 8 GB RAM

Table 3.1: Research materials (ads details)

For the purposes of this research, two original compositions² were used in the two ads (one in major and one in minor). Both pieces followed a simple 4 chord sequence of:

Tonic – Dominant – Submediant – Subdominant

Which is the 1st, 5th, 6th, and 4th degree chords, respectively. This chord progression was chosen as it is one of the most popular 4-chord progressions (Manzo, 2014; Recek *et al.*, 2021), and it would result in the following chord progression in the two tonalities, where an upper-case chord is major, and a lower-case chord is minor:

¹ Links to the two ads can be found in appendix G.

² Links to the music can be found in appendix G, and sheet music can be found in appendix N.

Major: I – V – vi - IV

Minor: i – v – VI - iv

For example, this chord progression will generate the following chords in the cases of C_{maj} and A_{min} :

- **C_{maj} TC:** $C_{maj} - G_{maj} - A_{min} - F_{maj}$ (75% major harmony, 25% minor harmony).
- **A_{min} TC:** $A_{min} - E_{min} - F_{maj} - D_{min}$ (75% minor harmony, 25% major harmony).

The music also achieves pure harmony by not playing any notes outside of the native notes of the chord. For example, when a C_{maj} chord is playing, only its native notes C, E, and G are played. This is done to eliminate any pockets of dissonance between the base chords and the leading melody, which is, for example, similar to Dmitri Shostakovich's fugue No. 7 in A_{maj} , opus 87 (Shostakovich, 1950).

The major music was written in all the 12 major TCs, and the minor music was written in all the 12 minor TCs. Indeed, research investigating the effect of individual musical properties should use the same music across different scenarios, where manipulation only occurs to those musical properties of interest, because when different musical pieces are used to manipulate a musical variable, musical properties will be confounded, which makes it difficult to extract specific causal elements (Kellaris & Kent, 1993; Craton & Lantos, 2011; Craton, Lantos, & Leventhal, 2017; Liu, Abolhasani, & Hang, 2022).

The music was produced using FL Studio v.12 and GarageBand, two digital workstation softwares that allow for the creation of realistic-sounding instrumental music aided by synthesisers that can facilitate controlling or manipulating different sound properties. It's crucial to have manipulation over the orthogonality of the main independent variable (tonality in this case) while holding all other sound properties constant (Kellaris & Kent, 1993). Therefore, tempo, texture, melodic contour, chord progression, timbre, mode, volume, and any other sound properties were invariant across different TCs.

3.3.3. Pre-test 1 (music congruence & purchase intention):

Musical congruence is the measurement that shows whether the advertising music fits the advertisements and its main message and overall feel (MacInnis & Park, 1991; Oakes, 2007; Ausín *et al.*, 2021). This initial pre-test measured the music congruence of the two music conditions (major and minor) with the two advertisements (juice and smartphone, respectively), which is done with the purpose of controlling congruence (i.e. the major music is perceived to fit the juice ad, and the minor music is perceived to fit the smartphone ad).

This was done via an online questionnaire¹ that asked participants to view the two ads and rate them on a scale from 1 to 10 (10 being the most congruent).

The music for both conditions was indeed perceived as congruent with the advertisements: One-Sample T Tests (major: sig. = 0.00, minor: sig. = 0.00), with the means (major: 8.17, minor: 8.12).

Furthermore, the questionnaire measured participants' purchase intention (*PI*) of these two brands via the following three 5-point Likert scale statements from Grewal, Monroe, & Krishnan's (1998) measurement, which is widely adopted and standardised to measure *PI* throughout the literature (Raja, Anand, & Allan, 2023):

	Very unlikely	Unlikely	Neutral	Likely	Very Likely
1. If I were going to buy such product, the probability of buying this brand is	<input type="radio"/>				
2. The probability that I would consider buying this brand is	<input type="radio"/>				
3. The likelihood that I would purchase this brand is	<input type="radio"/>				

Table 3.2: Purchase Intention (*PI*) measurement tool

It's important to note that the purchase intention for a juice brand will be much different from the purchase intention of a smartphone brand due to different levels of participant involvement as well as the unfamiliarity aspect of the brand; juice, as a fast-moving consumer good, requires less involvement overall, whereas a smartphone requires much more involvement and a longer decision-making process. Moreover, the unfamiliarity with the brands is very likely to influence *PI*. However, the research does not propose comparing the major condition (juice) with the minor condition (smartphone), and since familiarity is controlled, then testing for the *PI* of these two brands is overall valid.

Indeed, this measurement was validated by the supervisory team as well as the ethics committee, which was the external reliability of its items. As for the internal consistency between the 3 items measuring a Chronbach's Alpha test was conducted and showed a very strong internal consistency (juice *PI*: $\alpha = 0.979$, smartphone *PI*: $\alpha = 0.978$).

The online questionnaire took an estimated 2 minutes on average to complete and was distributed via social media and some personal connections.

¹ A copy of this pre-test can be found in appendix E.

3.3.4. Pre-test 2 (EEG setup and time estimation):

Following the assurance of music congruence and internal validity of the purchase intention measurement, a few EEG experiments were conducted to ensure no issues arise during setup and to estimate the time needed per session.

The following will highlight the main details and findings of this pre-test:

- The pre-test involved a small sample of 6 participants.
- During the EEG setup, no significant issues were encountered with the placement of electrodes or the recording of brain signals. This suggests that the equipment and procedure are suitable for capturing the desired brain activity.
- Participant feedback showed no reports of discomfort with the EEG headset, or any other aspect of the experiment were noted. This ensured that the participants' well-being and comfort were adequately considered throughout the experiment.
- Time estimated was between 25 – 35 minutes per session as per the figure in the overview earlier. This information was valuable for scheduling the main experiments and ensuring that the researcher's and participants' time is reasonable and manageable.

Overall, the pre-test experiments confirmed their validity for the next phase of the main data collection experiments. These 6 sessions will not be included in the final analysis of the main experiments.

3.3.5. Main experiments:

Following the pre-testing of the main experiments without encountering issues, the research progressed to the main experiments of the research through the following steps:

3.3.5.1. Participant information sheet¹:

Participants were initially provided with a participant information sheet in person or via email (more on participant selection in the next section). The participant information sheet highlighted the following important information:

- **Research purpose:** participants were not informed of the research purpose, as to not expose them to any pre-measurement biases such as consciously or subconsciously shifting their attention to the audio of the advertisements while disregarding the visuals. This is done to simulate a viewing of the ads under the most realistic conditions possible where the ad music operate as a background element rather than a foreground element. Participants were informed of this omission, and were told that the full purpose of the research would be disclosed to them after the

¹ A copy of the participant information sheet can be found in appendix B.

experiment is over, upon which they could either extend their initial consent or request for their data to be removed.

- **Participation requirements:** 18 or older individuals who are free of any current or past neurological disorders and are able to watch and listen to the documentary and ads.
- **Voluntary participation:** participation is voluntary, and participants were informed that they can withdraw from the experiment without providing any reason, upon which their data would be removed.
- **Walkthrough of the experiment:** this section detailed the steps of the experiment and the estimated time for each step. Most importantly, information on the EEG headset setup is included alongside a link for them to view the headset used in the experiment. Moreover, they were also informed that when their EEG data is being collected, they must keep their eyes on the screen, and not make many movements that would disrupt the data such as turning their heads or speaking to the researcher, but that other natural movement is allowed.
- **More information on EEG:** highlighting what EEG is and how it works, and reassuring participants that EEG is not associated with any safety concerns.
- **What participants should do prior to the experiment:** participants were asked to have their hair washed the night before or the morning of the experiment, and to have their scalp free of any products such as gels, sprays, oils, or any other additives as they would interfere with the data quality.
- **Possible benefits:** participants were informed that there aren't any direct benefits to taking part of the research, but there are indirect benefits of advancing the literature on the topic of the research.
- **Data confidentiality:** participants were reassured that their data will be kept confidential, and that their identifying data, such as name, will be stored separately from the main data in order to ensure they cannot be recognised or linked to it. Furthermore, participants were informed that all data will be handled only by the researcher and the supervisory team, and analysed only holistically, not from an individual perspective.
- **Research results:** participants were informed that the results would be published in the final thesis and may be presented in conferences of academic journals.
- **Funding:** self-funded research.
- **Ethical review:** participants were informed that the research has received ethical approval from the ethics committee at UWS, and that they can request to see a copy.
- **Contact information:** emails of both researcher and director of studies.

3.3.5.2. Pre-disclosure consent¹:

Participants were asked to provide their consent via a form that asks if they have read and understood the participant information sheet, had the opportunity to ask questions and have them answered to their satisfaction, understood that their data will be confidential and stored safely, understood that their participation is voluntary and that they could withdraw from the research at any time without providing a reason, and finally, confirmed that they are at least 18 years old and agree to take part in this research. The form was then named, signed, and dated. Participants were then requested to answer only the first section of the online questionnaire, which is designed to ensure they are a good match for the experiment (above 18, no neurological disorders, and no hearing or vision disabilities).

3.3.5.3. EEG recording:

An EEG will measure the electrical activities within a human brain. When brain cells communicate, they produce waves of electricity, then the electrodes which are placed on the cranium² pick up those electrical waves, and the variations in the signals detected by electrodes should reveal what type and intensity of brain activity is taking place. EEG is non-invasive, relatively inexpensive, and quick to collect data, as it can detect changes that happen within milliseconds (Gkaintatzis *et al.*, 2019; Sawangjai *et al.*, 2020).

This research will be using Emotiv's EPOC+, which is a portable EEG designed specifically for non-medical research such as in the social sciences, and its quality has been validated by many studies (Badcock *et al.*, 2013; Sawangjai *et al.*, 2020; Williams *et al.*, 2020; Williams, McArthur, & Badcock, 2020). The EPOC+ EEG has 14 electrodes that highlight the main points of activity across the 4 lobes of the brain as can be seen in the figure below.

Figure 3.4: EPOC+ electrodes placement (Blanco & Ramirez, 2019, p. 5)

¹ A copy of the consent form can be found in appendix C.

² The cranium is the part of the skull consisting of the bones enclosing the brain (Frackowiak, 2004).

As can be seen in the previous figure, the 7 electrodes that cover the left hemisphere are AF3, F7, F3, FC5, T7, P7, and O1, while the 7 electrodes that cover the right hemisphere are AF4, F8, F4, FC6, T8, P8, O2. The machine also has 2 reference points, CMS/DRL, at P3/P4 (left/right mastoid placement). The activity of these 14 channels can be viewed in real time on the EmotivPRO software, along with the connectivity quality of each electrode.

Once a participant confirms their initial consent, the EEG recording can begin.

The 14 felt pads of the electrodes are first hydrated with a saline solution to improve their connectivity. The headset is then placed on the participant's head and adjusted until all 14 electrodes are properly connected. EmotivPRO will show the contact quality for each electrode on a spectrum of black, red, orange, and green, where black refers to no contact detected, and green refers to good contact quality (Emotiv, 2023) as can be seen below.

Figure 3.5: Example of good EEG contact quality

Once good contact is established, the EEG headset is then placed on the participant's scalp. 30 seconds of baseline data are first recorded (15 seconds with eyes open, and 15 seconds with eyes closed).

After the baseline recording, the documentary¹ with the ads is played², which is a NASA video called "*Parker Solar Probe Countdown to T-Zero for a Journey to "Touch" the Sun*" (NASA, 2018). The entire length of the documentary with the two ads is 15:30. The two ads are placed at 04:24 and at 10:40 (roughly at the thirds intervals). The order of the ads is randomised for different participants (juice ad then smartphone ad, or smartphone ad then juice ad). Furthermore, the juice ad will feature music chosen randomly from one of the 12 major TCs, and the smartphone ad will feature music in the relative minor TC of that major TC (e.g. C_{maj} and its relative minor A_{min} for one participant, but F_{maj} and its relative minor D_{min} for another participant).

¹ A link to the documentary with the two ads placed in it can be found in appendix G.

² The researcher ensured the setting of the session is always in a quiet room with no external sound or stimuli or any forms of interruption.

3.3.5.4. Questionnaire¹:

After the EEG signals have been recorded, the participant is requested to continue to the second section of the online questionnaire (the first section was answered after signing the pre-disclosure consent form).

The second section of the online questionnaire contains some demographical questions (age, sex, education status, ethnicity, marital status, music genre preference, musical training on a 7-point Likert scale, employment status, employment field, and annual income).

Section 3 of the questionnaire contains questions about the two ads. The online form displays the juice ad questions first by default followed by the smartphone ad questions. However, if the participant was randomly served the smartphone ad first, then they're told to scroll down to the smartphone ad questions and answer them first before scrolling back up to the juice ad questions. This is necessary as to control the time spent between viewing the ad and answering its questions.

The questions in section 3 measure the participant's retention by asking if they recall the following:

- Brand name (unaided).
- The three flavours/colours (unaided).
- Slogan (unaided).
- Logo (aided with one 1 correct option and 3 wrong options).
- Open-ended section for any other information they retained and can recall.

It further measures their purchase intention (*P*) via the three 5-point Likert scale statements from Grewal, Monroe, & Krishnan's (1998) detailed earlier.

And finally, section 4 of the questionnaire is a post-experiment data validity assurance, where the participant is asked if they possess absolute pitch² (AP). This question couldn't have been asked prior to the EEG recording as it would have hinted at the research purpose. The participant is also asked if they had seen either of the two ads before (in case they had answered the online congruence and purchase intention pre-test in the past). An affirmative answer to either of these two questions results in an elimination of the participant's data entry.

¹ A copy of the questionnaire can be found in appendix J.

² Absolute Pitch (AP), or commonly known as perfect pitch, is an atypical neural phenomenon which is characterised by the ability to accurately identify and recreate the pitch of a sound without previous reference points and without necessarily being musically trained (Takeuchi & Hulse, 1991; 1993; Zatorre, 2003). AP is rare as it can only be observed in 0.01% of human population (1 in every 10,000 people) (McKetton *et al.*, 2018).

3.3.5.5. Full-disclosure information sheet¹:

Once the questionnaire is answered and submitted, the participant is provided with the full-disclosure information sheet, which includes a proposed research title, a detailed disclosure of the research purpose, why the research purpose was hidden from them prior to the experiment, why they were asked if they have absolute pitch, how the results could be applied to real-life scenarios, and finally, contact details.

The participant is then given the opportunity to ask any questions about the research and have them answer to their satisfaction.

3.3.5.6. Post-disclosure consent²:

Once participants have read the full-disclosure information sheet, they can provide their post-disclosure consent by signing the second half of the consent form, which ensures that they have read and understood the full-disclosure information sheet, have had the opportunity to ask questions and had them answered to their satisfaction, and that they agree to extending their initial consent. The participant then signs their name again.

If the participant chooses to not extend their initial consent, their data would be eliminated.

3.3.6. Manipulation check:

Due to the results of this research, which will be detailed later in chapter 4 and discussed in chapter 5, manipulation checks were necessary to ensure that the results of the experiments can indeed be attributed to the TCs regardless of octaval transposition, as the initial octaves for the 24 TCs were chosen arbitrarily. Thus, two scenarios will be retested with C_{maj} and A_{min} (transposed up one register ottava), and then again C_{maj} and A_{min} (transposed down one register ottava).

The following figure illustrates a typical piano keyboard with 88 keys showing the first notes of the 24 original TCs in red (from $F\sharp/G\flat$ on the 3rd octave to F on the 4th octave), the first notes C_{maj} and A_{min} transposed ottava in blue (C on the 5th octave. And A on the 4th octave), and C_{maj} and A_{min} transposed ottava in green (C on the 3rd octave and A on the 2nd octave).

Figure 3.6: Initial notes of the main experiments vs. manipulation check

¹ A copy of the full-disclosure information sheet can be found in appendix D.

² A copy of the consent form can be found in appendix C.

3.4. Sampling & Participant Selection:

The research utilises different sampling methods and participant selection techniques throughout the experiments. The table below clarifies the sampling structure and sizes of all the different research stages, which will then be detailed in the next sections.

Research stage	Sample size	Technique, approach, and purpose.
Pre-test 1: music congruence and purchase intention.	362 participants.	Non-probability convenience sampling. Online questionnaire via social media. Validating music congruence with the ads shown to participants and ensuring internal consistency of the purchase intention Likert scale items.
Pre-test 2: EEG setup and time estimation.	6 participants/EEG sessions (their data was not used within the final analysis).	Non-probability convenience sampling. Personally known by researcher. Estimating EEG sessions time and scanning for potential issues.
Main EEG experiments.	195 participants/EEG sessions (3 incremental quotas of 65 participants).	Convenience quota sampling / snowballing sampling. Mostly festival goers and volunteers at Doune The Rabbit Hole music festival. Collected for main research data on attention, retention (post EEG questionnaire, and purchase intention (post EEG questionnaire).
Manipulation check	30 participants/EEG sessions (15 for major TCs and 15 for minor TCs).	Convenience sampling / snowballing sampling. Mostly festival goers and volunteers at Doune The Rabbit Hole music festival. Ensuring that the results of the main experiments can indeed be attributed to the TCs regardless of octaval transposition.

Table 3.3: Sampling structure

3.4.1. Pre-test 1 (music congruence & purchase intention):

The pre-test online questionnaire was distributed via social media and some personal connections. This makes this sampling technique a non-probability convenience sampling, which involves prioritising selecting participants based on convenient accessibility rather than their representation of the population. Convenience sampling has its advantages and disadvantages within this research (Leedy & Ormrod, 2015; Creswell, 2015).

Convenient sampling is efficient as it allows researchers to gather data from readily available participants from the researcher's immediate network. It's also time and cost effective. However, it could result in some sampling bias, which would render the sample unrepresentative, limiting the generalisability of the results. Furthermore, since participants would be self-selecting for participating in this pre-test, their personal unique characteristics or motivations that differ from the broader population may also limit the generalisability of the results. Nonetheless, it was deemed that the advantages of convenience sampling outweigh its disadvantages. 362 participants ended up answering the online questionnaire.

3.4.2. Pre-test 2 (EEG setup and time estimation):

The pre-test for the EEG experiments also followed convenience sampling as 6 participants who were personally known by the researcher were asked to partake in these experiments. Generally, this technique has the same advantages and disadvantages mentioned earlier. However, it's important to mention that even though those 6 participants were known personally, they were not aware of the purpose of the research until the experiments were conducted. It's also important to mention that the data of those 6 participants will not be included in the final analysis of the research.

3.4.3. Main experiments:

A data collection permit¹ has been granted from the management of Doune The Rabbit Hole music festival. This permit grants access to the festival site in Stirlingshire, and the festival offices in Glasgow. This permit was used to collect data from crew, volunteers, and colleagues who are not known personally by the researcher (around 450 individuals).

Festival individuals were provided with physical copies of the participant information sheet and were told to contact the researcher if they wish to partake in the research.

Furthermore, the researcher recruited some students from the UWS Paisley campus, who were either given the participation information sheet physically or via email.

Due to the length of the sessions (an average of 30 minutes), as well as the number of scenarios that will be tested (13 scenarios: 12 TCs, minor and major, and one control

¹ A copy of the data collection permit can be found in appendix H.

scenario with no music), it's difficult to obtain a large sample size, which hinders the generalisability of the results. Due to this issue, data saturation needed to be reached to affirm the results more firmly, hence, the researcher collected data in quotas of 5 participants per scenario (65 participants in total), and analysed the entire data after each quota until 3 consecutive rounds showed roughly the same outcome, which resulted in the following system:

- **Quota 1:** 65 participants (5 participants per scenario), upon which, data was analysed, and collection of the second quota began.
- **Quota 2:** Another added 65 participants (5 participants per scenario) bringing the total of participants to 130, upon which, data was analysed, reaching the same conclusions as the first quota alone. Collection of the third quota then began.
- **Quota 3:** Another added 65 participants (5 participants per scenario) bringing the total of participants to 195, upon which, data was analysed, reaching the same conclusions as the first and second quotas together. Data collection is then stopped.

It's important to note that a total of 198 data sets had to be collected, because 3 of which had to be removed: one participant did not provide post-disclosure consent, one participant reported experiencing seizures in the past and was thus disqualified before the EEG experiment took place, and one participant requested to withdraw prior to the EEG experiment without providing a reason.

The sampling technique here is potentially a combination of techniques; while the recruitment of participants as detailed above is technically convenience quota sampling, it is expected that some snowballing sampling had occurred as the researcher requested existing participants to recruit other individuals from their personal acquaintances to participate in the research (they were told not to reveal the purpose of the research other than it's a neuromarketing research). This convenience quota snowball sampling technique has the same advantages and disadvantages as detailed earlier, including the possibility of some participants being informed about the research purpose by other participant.

3.4.4. Manipulation check:

The manipulation check included 15 participants to test C_{maj} and A_{min} transposed up one octave, and 15 participants to test C_{maj} and A_{min} transposed down one octave (a total of 30 participants). They had similar treatment to the participants of the main experiments.

3.5. Data Analysis Tools & Techniques:

This section will detail the means with which the research data was dealt with in terms of storage, entry, tools, and analyses used.

3.5.1. Pre-test 1 (music congruence & purchase intention):

The online pre-test questionnaire was created as a Microsoft 365 Form. Its data was exported as an Excel worksheet with 362 entries. It was then imported into SPSS for analysis.

The first question of the questionnaire (10-point music congruence scale) was analysed via a One-Sample T Test, which examines whether the mean of a population is statistically significantly different from a known value. In this case, the following two One-Sample T Tests were conducted:

- **One-Sample T Test** to examine whether the mean of the perceived congruence of the music in the juice ad is statistically significantly different from 5.5 (the mean of population, calculated as the mean of 1 to 10).
- **One-Sample T Test** to examine whether the mean of the perceived congruence of the music in the smartphone ad is statistically significantly different from 5.5 (the mean of population, calculated as the mean of 1 to 10).

The second question of purchase intention (*PI*) was only required in the pretest to ensure its internal consistency through a Cronbach's Alpha test, which showed a very strong internal consistency (juice *PI*: $\alpha = 0.979$, smartphone *PI*: $\alpha = 0.978$), indicating that the 3 items proposed to measure *PI* do indeed measure it.

3.5.2. Main experiments & manipulation check:

The main experiments and manipulation check experiments require a different approach than the pretest as they include EEG data, which will be exported from EmotivLAB, then imported into MATLAB by MathWorks for analysis, which is a software for reading and analysing raw EEG data.

The online questionnaire that participants had to answer after the EEG recording was created as a Microsoft 365 Form. Its data will be exported as an Excel worksheet with 195 entries (15 participants X 13 scenarios), and it will be imported into SPSS for analysis.

3.5.2.1. EEG data:

The raw EEG data is initially imported into MATLAB for each participant individually (only the 20 seconds of the ad viewing). The two points, CMS/DRL (at P3/P4, left/right mastoid placement) are added as references so that MATLAB can autodetect the placement of the 14 electrodes used. This step is then verified manually to ensure all 14 electrodes are accounted for and labelled correctly.

After the raw data is imported properly, a series of filtering is required to ensure the data is as clean as possible so it can be ready for analysis. The clean-up process includes several stages:

- **ICA filtering:** Independent Component Analysis or ICA is a signal preprocessing algorithm. Its purpose is to filter out artifacts from the EEG signal such as electrode noises, eyes movement, eye blinks, muscular action, and heart and blood movement. These aberrations cover a broad area of the scalp and can sometimes be “greater than the signals of concern”, which is why their removal is recommended (Motdhare & Mathur, 2022, p. 86). A default RUNICA is well-suited for low electrodes machines.
- **Baseline filtering:** the 15-seconds no-stimuli closed-eyes baseline, and the 15-second no-stimuli open-eyes baseline are then removed via a linear phase finite impulse response filter as recommended by (Bartolomé-Tomás *et al.*, 2019). This will ensure that any variability in activity can be attributed to the stimuli presented.
- **High-pass filter & low-pass filter:** a high-pass filter of 3 Hz is applied, which means that only activity above 3 Hz can pass through, and anything under 3 Hz is cleared. Furthermore, a low-pass filter of 45 Hz is applied, which means that only activity under 45 Hz can pass through, and anything above 45 Hz is cleared. This is done to create a bandwidth of activity between 3 Hz and 45 Hz, which is recommended when dealing with a small number of electrodes. Indeed, it's recommended specifically for Emotiv Epoch+ (Bartolomé-Tomás *et al.*, 2019).

Once data clean-up is done to each participant's ad viewing (2 per participant: one for the 20-second juice ad, and another one for the 20-second smartphone ad). The data is combined for each TC. For example, all 15 20-second raw data of participants viewing the juice ad in C_{maj} are added together, resulting in a 300-second EEG data stream. This stream is then averaged out. This process is repeated for all 26 scenarios (12 major TCs, 12 minor TCs, and 2 no-music conditions). An ANOVA analysis is then conducted to determine if there is a statistical significance between the means of all TCs. The same is then applied to the manipulation check 4 scenarios (C_{maj} transposed one octave up, C_{maj} transposed one octave down, A_{min} transposed one octave up, and A_{min} transposed one octave down).

3.5.2.2. Questionnaire data:

The following table will account for the processing and analysis of the different types of questionnaire data:

ITEM	PROCESSING	ANALYSIS
Are you at least 18 years old?	No processing. All participants must be 18 or above to partake in the research	—
Do you have any current or past neurological disorders?	No processing. All participants must not have any neurological disorders to partake	—
Do you currently have any hearing or vision disabilities that could impact the way you experience the documentary?	No processing. All participants must not have any hearing or vision disabilities to partake	—
How old are you?	Processes into SPSS (age groups are assigned values from 1 to 7)	Descriptive statistics analysis
What is your biological sex?	Processes into SPSS (sex is assigned values from 1 to 5)	Descriptive statistics analysis
What is your gender?	Processes into SPSS (gender is assigned values from 1 to 6)	Descriptive statistics analysis
What is the highest degree or level of school you have completed?	Processes into SPSS (degrees are assigned values from 1 to 8)	Descriptive statistics analysis
What is your ethnic origin?	Processes into SPSS (ethnic groups are assigned values from 1 to 9)	Descriptive statistics analysis
What is your marital status?	Processes into SPSS (statuses are assigned values from 1 to 7)	Descriptive statistics analysis
Which of these musical genres do you enjoy listening to you?	Processes into SPSS (each choice is processed as its own variable with the values 1 ticked, and 0 unticked)	Multiple response analysis
On a scale from 1 to 7, how well are you trained in music?	Processes into SPSS as a scale variable	Descriptive statistics analysis, and One-Sample Wilcoxon test
What is your professional employment status?	Processes into SPSS (each choice is processed as its own variable with the values 1 ticked, and 0 unticked)	Multiple response analysis

In which sector(s) do you work?	Processes into SPSS (each choice is processed as its own variable with the values 1 ticked, and 0 unticked)	Multiple response analysis
What is your annual income?	Processes into SPSS (income groups are assigned values from 1 to 8)	Descriptive statistics analysis
An ad of a juice brand was shown. What was the name of the brand?	Processes into SPSS (Verified manually where correct ¹ answers are given the value 1, and incorrect answers are given the value 0)	These 5 variables are combined into 1 scale variable called Retention (<i>R</i>) – Major, where each correct answer is awarded 1 point. An ANOVA analysis is then conducted to determine if there is a statistical significance between the retention means of all the major TCs.
The juice brand was available in 3 flavours. What were those three flavours?	Processes into SPSS (Verified manually where each correct answer is awarded 1 point)	
What was the juice brand's slogan?	Processes into SPSS (Verified manually where the correct answer is awarded 1 point)	
Which one of these is the juice brand's logo?	Processes into SPSS (Verified manually where the correct answer is awarded 1 point)	
Do you recall anything else about the juice brand?	Processes into SPSS (Verified manually where the correct details are awarded 1 point)	
If I were going to buy such product, the probability of buying this brand is...	Processes into SPSS as a scale variable with the values: very unlikely (1), unlikely (2), neutral (3), likely (4), and very likely (5)	Combined into 1 variable called Purchase Intention (<i>PI</i>) – Major. An ANOVA analysis is then conducted to determine if there is a statistical significance between the retention means of all the major TCs.
The probability that I would consider buying this brand is...		
The likelihood that I would purchase this brand is...		
An ad of a smartphone brand was shown. What was the name of the brand?	Processes into SPSS (Verified manually where correct answers are given the value 1, and incorrect	These 5 variables are combined into 1 scale variable called Retention (<i>R</i>) – Minor, where each correct

¹ Details on what is processed as correct or incorrect can be found in appendix M.

	answers are given the value 0)	answer is awarded 1 point. An ANOVA analysis is then conducted to determine if there is a statistical significance between the retention means of all the major TCs.
The smartphone brand was available in 3 colours. What were those three colours?	Processes into SPSS (Verified manually where each correct answer is awarded 1 point)	
What was the smartphone brand's slogan?	Processes into SPSS (Verified manually where the correct answer is awarded 1 point)	
Which one of these is the smartphone brand's logo?	Processes into SPSS (Verified manually where the correct answer is awarded 1 point)	
Do you recall anything else about the smartphone brand?	Processes into SPSS (Verified manually where the correct details are awarded 1 point)	
If I were going to buy such product, the probability of buying this brand is...	Processes into SPSS as a scale variable with the values: very unlikely (1), unlikely (2), neutral (3), likely (4), and very likely (5)	Combined into 1 variable called Purchase Intention (<i>PI</i>) – Minor. An ANOVA analysis is then conducted to determine if there is a statistical significance between the retention means of all the minor TCs.
The probability that I would consider buying this brand is...		
The likelihood that I would purchase this brand is...		
Do you have perfect pitch?	No processing. Participant's data set is eliminated	—
Have you seen either of the juice or smartphone ads before?	No processing. Participant's data set is eliminated	—

Table 3.4: Questionnaire data processing and analysis

3.6. Ethical Considerations:

This research has received ethical approval from the postgraduate research ethics committee in the School of Business & Creative Industries at the University of the West of Scotland (UWS). A copy of this approval can be found in appendix I.

As this research requires personal interaction with participants, it's important to elaborate on some ethical concerns.

3.6.1. Physical harm:

There is no physical harm associated with the research. However, since the research requires an EEG recording, there is a level of physical interaction with the participant. Participants were made aware of this before the experiment via the participant information sheet, and before the beginning of the experiment once they agreed to partake in the research. Participants were reassured that EEG is a widely used, well-developed, and non-invasive imaging technique that measures the electrical activity which occurs along the scalp's surface, and that it has been used safely on hundreds of millions of people all over the world for nearly a century now. No Ionising radiation, X-Rays, electric currents, magnetic stimulation, intravenous injections, or any other invasive procedures are used.

3.6.2. Invasion of privacy:

Participants were made aware that the EEG data will reveal their brain activity, however, they were informed that this data will be processed and analysed only for their attentional response, and that no other types of data or information can be inferred from the raw EEG data. Furthermore, participants were aware that they could withdraw at any stage without providing a reason. Moreover, many questions such as sex, gender, income... etc, were not required as participants were allowed to not answer if they preferred.

3.6.3. Confidentiality & anonymity:

Participants were made aware that all their data will always be treated anonymously, and that any identifying data, such as consent form which have their names and signatures, will be stored in a physical form away from the digital data, where it's not possible to link it or associate it with the raw quantitative data. Participants were also informed that only the researcher, and possibly the researcher's supervisory team, would look into the data.

3.6.4. Other ethical concerns:

The researcher ensured to check in on participants constantly (except during the EEG reading as to not distort the data) to ensure they are aware of the type of information that's revealed to them at every stage of the experiment. The researcher also ensured that the all participants are comfortable in a quiet, temperate-regulated, and evenly lit room.

3.7. Research Timeline:

The following Gantt chart illustrates the timeline and scheduling of the research:

Figure 3.7: Gantt chart of the research timeline

3.8. Chapter Conclusion:

In conclusion, this chapter has outlined the framework with which the research becomes a practical tool to investigate the topic, ensuring a systematic and rigorous approach to data collection and analysis.

This chapter initially highlighted the positivist nature of the research, detailing its ontology, epistemology, axiology, and hypothetico-deductive approach. Expounding on the advantages and disadvantages of this philosophical stance.

Furthermore, the methodology, methods, and tools of analysis were detailed, highlighting the testing materials (juice ad for music in major TCs, and smartphone ad for music in minor TCs). These two ads were used in a pre-test to ensure their validity, upon which, a few EEG experiments were also pre-tested to ensure no issues arise. Then the approach for the main experiments was defined with details on the participant information sheet, pre-disclosure consent, EEG recording process, full-disclosure information sheet post-EEG reading, and finally, post-disclosure consent. After the main experiments, a few manipulation checks will be conducted in order to measure the same data when octaval transposition occurs.

The sampling and participant selection techniques were then detailed, highlighting the advantages and disadvantages of convenience sampling, and the data saturation strategy used to overcome those disadvantages. This was followed by detailing exactly how each data collection item will be processed and analysed, where EEG data will be analysed via MATLAB and questionnaire data will be analysed using SPSS.

Moreover, ethical considerations surrounding the research process have been put forward to ensure that no participant is in any way at harm, and that their privacy, identity, and personal data are protected. Furthermore, the limitations and delimitations of this research design were listed. And finally, a timeline of the research detailed when each stage of the research took place.

The following chapter, chapter 4, will be an analysis of all the data collected, which is to be later discussed in the chapter 5.

4. CHAPTER FOUR - DATA ANALYSIS & RESULTS

4.1. Chapter Introduction

4.2. Pre-Test Analysis (Congruence & Purchase Intention)

4.3. Main Experiments Demographical Analysis

4.4. Main Experiments EEG Data Analysis (Attention)

4.5. Main Experiments Questionnaire Analysis (Retention)

4.6. Main Experiments Questionnaire Analysis (Purchase Intention)

4.7. Manipulation Check Data Analysis

4.8. Chapter Conclusion

4.1. Chapter Introduction:

The Data Analysis and Results chapter will present a comprehensive analysis of the collected data. This will facilitate a more cohesive discussion about the research aim, objectives, questions, and hypotheses in the chapter that follows it.

This chapter will first present the results of the pre-test that was conducted to ensure the music congruence of the stimuli (via a One-Sample T Test), as well as the internal consistency of the Purchase Intention (*PI*) tool measurement (via a Chronbach's Alpha test).

As for the main experiments, firstly, participants demographical data will be analysed and illustrated. This is followed by analysis of the EEG data to measure attentional responses, which once the clean-up process detailed in the previous chapter is completed, the brain activity for each individual participant will be mapped and measured, then the brain activity for all participants under the same scenario will be combined into one EEG data stream represented by the average Hz activity (e.g. all 15 participants who were subject to C_{maj} will become one EEG variable). This will be considered as the main measurement for Attention (*A*). The means for all these scenario combinations will then be subject to an ANOVA test to determine if there is a statistical significance between them.

Following the EEG data analysis will be an analysis of participants' Retention of brand information (*R*), where participants will be awarded 1 point for each brand item they recall correctly. The means of items recalled for each scenario will then be subject to an ANOVA test to determine if there is a statistical significance between them.

The Purchase Intention (*PI*) 3-item Likert statements will be combined into one variable, which will be cross-compared per each scenario via an ANOVA test to determine if there is a statistical significance between the different means of *PI* per scenario.

Finally, the manipulation check data will be analysed via an ANOVA analysis in order to check if octaval transposition (or register) of the same TC would yield different results.

4.2. Pre-Test Analysis (Congruence & Purchase Intention)¹:

This step has been analysed earlier to ensure that the stimuli is a suitable fit for the main experiments. Firstly, the following is a summary of the One-Sample T-Test results of the music congruence:

	n	\bar{x}	Mean difference from $\mu = 5.5$	σ	df	Sig.
Congruence (Major)	362	8.17	2.67	1.50	361	.00
Congruence (Minor)	362	8.12	2.62	1.49	361	.00

Table 4.1: One-Sample T-Test (music congruence)

These results show that the sig. value of both major and minor conditions is $< .05$ with means $\bar{x} = 8.17$ and 8.12 , respectively. This means that the pre-test sample of 362 participants does indeed perceive the music of both the juice ad and the smartphone ad to be highly congruent with the ads themselves, which reassures the use of the stimuli in the main experiments.

Furthermore, the 3 items of Purchase Intention (*PI*) were treated to an internal consistency test, which showed the following results:

	n	Number of items	α
Juice ad <i>PI</i>	362	3	.979
Smartphone ad <i>PI</i>	362	3	.978

Table 4.2: Internal consistency test for Purchase Intention (*PI*)

The above table shows very strong internal consistency of the 3 items used to measure *PI* with values $\alpha = .979$ and $.978$ for the juice ad (major TCs condition) and smartphone ad (minor TCs condition), respectively. These very strong values may imply the redundancy of some of the items that measure *PI*. Nonetheless, it's important to retain all three items to ensure comprehensive coverage of *PI*. This approach allows for a more nuanced understanding of participants' attitudes and intentions, contributing to the overall validity of the findings.

¹ Raw SPSS output of the pre-test can be found in appendix F.

4.3. Main Experiments Demographical Analysis¹:

This section will present the demographical data of the sample, including age, sex, gender, education level, ethnicity, marital status, genre preference, musical training, employment status, employment field, and income, commenting on any notable data.

4.3.1. Age:

Table 4.3: Demographics (age)

4.3.2. Sex:

Table 4.4: Demographics (sex)

4.3.3. Gender:

Table 4.5: Demographics (gender)

¹ Raw SPSS output can be found in appendix K.

4.3.4. Education:

Education	Frequency	Percentage	Pie Chart
No schooling completed	7	3.6	
High school (no diploma)	32	16.4	
Diploma or the equivalent	24	12.3	
Some college or university credit (no degree)	47	24.1	
Bachelor's degree	69	35.4	
Master's degree	15	7.7	
Doctorate (PhD or above)	1	.5	
Other	0	0	
Total	195	100	

Table 4.6: Demographics (education)

4.3.5. Ethnicity:

Ethnicity	Frequency	Percentage	Pie Chart
Asian/Pacific Islander (doesn't include Indian)	15	7.7	
African	22	11.3	
Indian	9	4.6	
Hispanic or Latino	4	2.1	
White/Caucasian	128	65.6	
Middle Eastern or Arab	10	5.1	
Mixed ethnicity	3	1.5	
Prefer not to say	4	2.1	
Other	0	0	
Total	195	100	

Table 4.7: Demographics (ethnicity)

4.3.6. Marital Status:

Marital Status	Frequency	Percentage	Pie Chart
Single (never married)	113	57.9	
Married (or in domestic partnership)	54	27.7	
Divorced	9	4.6	
Widowed	5	2.6	
Separated	9	4.6	
Prefer not to say	5	2.6	
Other	0	0	
Total	195	100	

Table 4.8: Demographics (marital status)

4.3.7. Genre preference:

Table 4.9: Demographics (genre preference)

4.3.8. Musical training:

Table 4.10: Demographics (musical training)

A One-Sample T Test would normally be conducted here to measure if there is a significant difference between the musical training mean of the sample (\bar{x}) and the musical training mean of the population. However, musical training is not normally distributed (ABRSM, 2014; Criscuolo *et al.*, 2019), therefore, it would be incorrect to assume that the population mean is ($\mu = 3.5$). Alternatively, a nonparametric test such as the One-Sample Wilcoxon test can be performed when the population does not follow normal distribution. It compares the mean of the sample ($\bar{x} = 2.88$) with its median ($\tilde{x} = 3$) rather than the mean of the population ($\mu = 3.5$):

Musical Training	n	\bar{x}	\tilde{x}	σ	Sig.
One-Sample Wilcoxon test	195	2.88	3	1.68	1.99

Table 4.11: Musical training One-Sample Wilcoxon test

The sig. > .05 value reveals that there is no significant difference between the musical training mean of the sample ($\bar{x} = 2.88$) and their median ($\tilde{x} = 3$).

4.3.9. Employment status:

Table 4.12: Demographics (employment status)

4.3.10. Employment field:

Table 4.13: Demographics (employment field)

4.3.11. Income:

Table 4.14: Demographics (income)

4.4. Main Experiments EEG Data Analysis (Attention):

After the clean-up process detailed in the previous chapter, the raw data from the EEG recordings of each scenario are combined into one EEG data stream represented by overall average activity in Hz.

4.4.1. Major TCs (juice ad):

All 15 participants for each of the 13 scenarios (12 major TCs and M_0) of the juice ad have been combined into one brain map showing their average brain activity in Hz throughout the viewing of the ad.

Figure 4.1: Brain mapping for participants subject to the juice ad (major TCs and M_0)

The Hz values were processed into SPSS for an ANOVA test, repeated accumulatively at every 5-participant interval. The results were as follows:

	F	df1	df2	Sig.
ANOVA values at the 5-participant interval	39.99	12	52	.00
ANOVA values at the 10-participant interval	85.76	12	117	.00
ANOVA values at the 15-participant interval	123.74	12	182	.00

Table 4.15: ANOVA test between the different major TCs at 5-participant intervals

Which can be summed up for the analysis at the 15-participant interval as follows:

$$F(12,182) = 123.74, \text{ sig.} < .05$$

The ANOVA test shows that at every 5-participant interval the sig. value was < 0.05 , which can be an argument for reaching data saturation as per the strategy proposed in the research design. The final sig. value shows that there is a statistical significance between the means of at least two of the 13 scenarios. This alone is enough to result in the rejection of the null hypothesis H_{a1} , which stated that **the attention (A) to an advertisement is invariant when the advertising music (M) is transposed across the 12 major tonal centres (TCs) of the major tonal category**, which means that major TCs of advertising music do indeed influence consumer attention differently.

As can be seen in the descriptive statistics table below, it's possible to conclude by observation alone that this difference could at least be between the mean of brain activity of the participants that were subject to C_{maj} ($\bar{x} = 25.57$ Hz) and the mean of brain activity of the participants that were subject to $F\#_{maj}/G\flat_{maj}$ ($\bar{x} = 14.48$ Hz) or the no-music (M_0) condition ($\bar{x} = 14.92$ Hz) for example.

Major TC (juice ad)	n	\bar{x}	σ
C	15	25.57	2.10
C#/D \flat	15	15.77	1.52
D	15	21.15	.80
D#/E \flat	15	19.47	.49
E	15	18.15	.55
F	15	23.38	.50
F#/G \flat	15	14.48	1.28
G	15	24.08	1.29
G#/A \flat	15	17.97	1.08
A	15	19.97	1.00
A#/B \flat	15	20.81	1.35
B	15	14.99	1.70
M_0	15	14.77	1.71
Total	195	19.27	3.76

Table 4.16: Descriptive statistics of attention in Hz (major TCs)

However, since ANOVA is an omnibus test, it can only test for an overall difference between any two groups rather than pairwise-comparing three or more groups against each other. Therefore, a Post Hoc analysis is needed for this type of pairwise comparison in order to locate exactly which scenarios differ from each other. There are several types of Post Hoc analyses Tukey's HSD (Honestly Significant Difference) is well suited for pairwise comparison between more than 3 groups, and when sample size (n) is equal across all groups (Nanda *et al.*, 2021). The following table shows the sig. values from the Post Hoc analysis as a pairwise comparison between all major TCs (including M_0):

TC	C	C# D _b	D	D# E _b	E	F	F# G _b	G	G# A _b	A	A# B _b	B	M ₀
C	1	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.08	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
C#/D _b	.00	1	.00	.00	.00	.00	.24	.00	.00	.00	.00	.90	.64
D	.00	.00	1	.02	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.36	1	.00	.00
D#/E _b	.00	.00	.02	1	.19	.00	.00	.00	.07	.99	.18	.00	.00
E	.00	.00	.00	.19	1	.00	.00	.00	1	.00	.00	.00	.00
F	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	1	.00	.95	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
F#/G _b	.00	.24	.00	.00	.00	.00	1	.00	.00	.00	.00	.99	1
G	.08	.00	.00	.00	.00	.95	.00	1	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
G#/A _b	.00	.00	.00	.07	1	.00	.00	.00	1	.00	.00	.00	.00
A	.00	.00	.36	.99	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	1	.84	.00	.00
A#/B _b	.00	.00	1	.18	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.84	1	.00	.00
B	.00	.90	.00	.00	.00	.00	.99	.00	.00	.00	.00	1	1
M ₀	.00	.64	.00	.00	.00	.00	1	.00	.00	.00	.00	1	1

Table 4.17: Tukey's HSD pairwise comparison of attention (major TCs)

As there are many sig. values < .05, it's clear that most scenarios differ from each other (statistically insignificant values are highlighted). Notably, however, is that TCs with the least number of accidentals (sharps # and flats b) have resulted in the most attentional response. For example, the brain activity as a result of C_{maj}, which has no sharps or flats, is significantly different from all other scenarios except G_{maj} which has only one accidental (F#). G_{maj} is also known as C_{maj}'s dominant TC for their close relatedness. And G_{maj} is significantly different from all other TCs except C_{maj} and F_{maj} (also has one accidental, B_b, and is C_{maj}'s subdominant TC). Furthermore, it's notable that the more complex major TC's with the most accidentals such as C_{#maj}/D_{bmaj} (7#/5b), F_{#maj}/G_{bmaj} (6#/6b), and B_{maj} (5#) differ significantly from all other TCs, but not from each other (or from the no-music control condition M₀), and they all resulted in the least levels of attention.

These relationships become clearer when the levels of attention (by Hz) are represented in the following chart (ranked from highest to lowest):

Figure 4.2: Average Hz per major TC

4.4.2. Minor TCs (smartphone ad):

All 15 participants for each of the 13 scenarios (12 minor TCs and 1 no-music) of the smartphone ad have been combined into one brain map showing their average brain activity in Hz throughout the viewing of the ad.

Figure 4.3: Brain mapping for participants subject to the smartphone ad (minor TCs and M₀)

The Hz values were processed into SPSS for an ANOVA test, repeated accumulatively at every 5-participant interval. The results were as follows:

	F	df1	df2	Sig.
ANOVA values at the 5-participant interval	45.92	12	52	.00
ANOVA values at the 10-participant interval	90.40	12	117	.00
ANOVA values at the 15-participant interval	122.90	12	182	.00

Table 4.18: ANOVA test between the different minor TCs at 5-participant intervals

Which can be summed up for the analysis at the 15-participant interval as follows:

$$F(12,182) = 122.90, \text{ sig.} < .05$$

The ANOVA test shows that at every 5-participant interval the sig. value was < 0.05 , which can be an argument for reaching data saturation as per the strategy proposed in the research design. The final sig. value shows that there is a statistical significance between the means of at least two of the 13 scenarios. This alone is enough to result in the rejection of the null hypothesis H_{a2} , which stated that **the attention (A) to an advertisement is invariant when the advertising music (M) is transposed across the 12 minor tonal centres (TCs) of the minor tonal category**, which means that minor TCs of advertising music do indeed influence consumer attention differently.

As can be seen in the descriptive statistics table below, it's possible to conclude by observation alone that this difference could at least be between the mean of brain activity of the participants that were subject to A_{\min} ($\bar{x} = 25.57$ Hz) and the mean of brain activity of the participants that were subject to $D\#_{\min}/E_{b_{\min}}$ ($\bar{x} = 14.48$ Hz) or the no-music (M_0) condition ($\bar{x} = 14.92$ Hz) for example.

Minor TC (smartphone ad)	n	\bar{x}	σ
C	15	19.44	.52
C#/D \flat	15	18.12	.49
D	15	23.33	.48
D#/E \flat	15	14.49	1.28
E	15	24.04	1.30
F	15	17.92	1.11
F#/G \flat	15	19.80	.95
G	15	20.76	1.45
G#/A \flat	15	15.25	1.94
A	15	25.49	1.60
A#/B \flat	15	15.81	1.57
B	15	21.19	.76
M_0	15	14.76	1.75
Total	195	19.26	3.71

Table 4.19: Descriptive statistics of attention in Hz (minor TCs)

However, since ANOVA is an omnibus test, it can only test for an overall difference between any two groups rather than pairwise-comparing three or more groups against each other. Therefore, a Post Hoc analysis is needed for this type of pairwise comparison in order to locate exactly which scenarios differ from each other. There are several types of Post Hoc analyses Tukey's HSD (Honestly Significant Difference) is well suited for pairwise comparison between more than 3 groups, and when sample size (n) is equal across all groups (Nanda *et al.*, 2021).

The following table shows the sig. values from the Post Hoc analysis as a pairwise comparison between all minor TCs (including M_0):

TC	C	C# D _b	D	D# E _b	E	F	F# G _b	G	G# A _b	A	A# B _b	B	M ₀
C	1	.19	.00	.00	.00	.00	1	.19	.00	.00	.00	.01	.00
C#/D _b	.19	1	.00	.00	.00	1	.02	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
D	.00	.00	1	.00	.94	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
D#/E _b	.00	.00	.00	1	.00	.00	.00	.00	.91	.00	.19	.00	1
E	.00	.00	.94	.00	1	.00	.00	.00	.00	.09	.00	.00	.00
F	.00	1	.00	.00	.00	1	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
F#/G _b	1	.02	.00	.00	.00	.00	1	.68	.00	.00	.00	.13	.00
G	.19	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.68	1	.00	.00	.00	.99	.00
G#/A _b	.00	.00	.00	.91	.00	.00	.00	.00	1	.00	.99	.00	.99
A	.00	.00	.00	.00	.09	.00	.00	.00	.00	1	.00	.00	.00
A#/B _b	.00	.00	.00	.19	.00	.00	.00	.00	.99	.00	1	.00	.54
B	.01	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.13	.99	.00	.00	.00	1	.00
M ₀	.00	.00	.00	1	.00	.00	1	.00	.99	.00	.54	.00	1

Table 4.20: Tukey's HSD pairwise comparison of attention (minor TCs)

As there are many sig. values < .05, it's clear that most scenarios differ from each other (statistically insignificant values are highlighted). Notably, however, is that, similar to the major TCs, minor TCs with the least number of accidentals (sharps # and flats b) have resulted in the most attentional response. For example, the brain activity as a result of A_{min}, which has no sharps or flats (and is C_{maj} relative minor), is significantly different from all other scenarios except E_{min} which has only one accidental (F#). E_{min} is also known as A_{min}'s dominant TC for their close relatedness. And E_{min} is significantly different from all other TCs except A_{min} and D_{min} (also has one accidental, B_b, and is A_{min}'s subdominant TC).

Furthermore, it's notable that the more complex major TC's with the most accidentals such as A_{#min}/B_{bmin} (7#/5b), D_{#min}/E_{bmin} (6#/6b), and G_{#min}/A_{bmin} (5#/7b) differ significantly from all other TCs, but not from each other (or from the no-music control condition M₀), and they all resulted in the least levels of attention.

These relationships become clearer when the levels of attention (by Hz) are represented in the following chart (ranked from highest to lowest):

Figure 4.4: Average Hz per minor TC

4.4.3. Major and minor comparison:

When comparing all major and minor TCs against their parallels (e.g. C_{maj} with C_{min}), not much is revealed as parallel TCs have different numbers of accidentals.

Figure 4.5: Major & minor TCs comparison (parallel)

However, when the same values are compared by relative TCs (e.g. C_{maj} and A_{min}), which have the exact same notes and number of accidentals, it becomes clear that the influence of relative TCs on brain activity is almost identical, where TCs, regardless of their tonal group (major or minor), have a higher influence on brain activity if they have less accidentals.

Figure 4.6: Major & minor TCs comparison (relative), where top line is major TCs and bottom line is minor TCs

4.5. Main Experiments Questionnaire Analysis (Retention):

As explained in the research design chapter, retention questions will be combined into one scale variable by awarding every correct¹ answer by participants 1 point. This variable called Retention (*R*) will be subject to an ANOVA analysis to test the difference of brand information retention of the research participants under the different TCs in both major (juice ad) and minor (smartphone) conditions.

4.5.1. Major TCs (juice ad):

An ANOVA analysis with *R* as the dependent variable and the different major TCs (and *M*₀) as the independent variables showed the following results:

	F	df1	df2	Sig.
ANOVA of Retention (<i>R</i>) between major TCs	8.82	12	182	.00

Table 4.21: ANOVA test of retention (*R*) between major TCs

Which can be summed up as per the following equation:

$$F(12,182) = 8.82, \text{ sig.} < .05$$

The ANOVA test shows that the sig. value was < 0.05, which shows that there is a statistical significance between the means of at least two of the 13 scenarios. This alone is enough to result in the rejection of the null hypothesis *H*₁₁, which stated that **the information retention (*R*) of an advertisement is invariant when the advertising music (*M*) is transposed across the 12 major tonal centres (TCs) of the major tonal category**, which means that major TCs of advertising music do indeed influence brand information retention differently.

Major TC (juice ad)	n	\bar{x}	σ
C	15	3.93	1.79
C#/D_b	15	1.00	1.46
D	15	2.26	1.79
D#/E_b	15	1.46	1.12
E	15	1.13	1.24
F	15	3.00	1.13
F#/G_b	15	.80	1.14
G	15	3.20	1.61
G#/A_b	15	1.40	1.24
A	15	1.86	1.30
A#/B_b	15	3.06	1.43
B	15	.93	1.03
M₀	15	1.26	.88
Total	195	1.94	1.64

Table 4.22: Descriptive statistics of retention under major TCs

¹ Details on what is processed as correct or incorrect can be found in appendix M.

In order to locate the TCs with the statistical significance, a Tukey's HSD (Honestly Significant Difference) Post Hoc analysis was conducted. The following table shows the sig. values from the analysis as a pairwise comparison between all major TCs (including M₀) (statistically significant values are highlighted):

TC	C	C# D _b	D	D# E _b	E	F	F# G _b	G	G# A _b	A	A# B _b	B	M ₀
C	1	.00	.06	.00	.00	.78	.00	.95	.00	.00	.86	.00	.00
C#/D _b	.00	1	.33	.99	1	.00	1	.00	1	.86	.00	1	1
D	.06	.33	1	.92	.52	.95	.14	.79	.86	1	.92	.26	.71
D#/E _b	.00	.99	.92	1	1	.10	.98	.03	1	1	.07	.99	1
E	.00	1	.52	1	1	.01	1	.00	1	.95	.00	1	1
F	.79	.00	.95	.10	.01	1	.00	1	.07	.52	1	.00	.03
F#/G _b	.00	1	.14	.98	1	.00	1	.00	.99	.62	.00	1	.99
G	.95	.00	.79	.03	.00	1	.00	1	.02	.26	1	.00	.00
G#/A _b	.00	1	.86	1	1	.07	.99	.02	1	.99	.04	.99	1
A	.00	.86	1	1	.95	.52	.62	.26	.99	1	.42	.79	.99
A#/B _b	.86	.00	.92	.07	.00	1	.00	1	.04	.42	1	.00	.02
B	.00	1	.26	.99	1	.00	1	.00	.99	.79	.00	1	1
M ₀	.00	1	.71	1	1	.03	.99	.00	1	.99	.02	1	1

Table 4.23: Tukey's HSD pairwise comparison of retention (major TCs)

As there are many sig. values < .05, it's clear that many scenarios differ from each other (statistically significant values are highlighted). Notably, major TCs with the least number of accidentals (sharps # and flats b) have resulted in the most brand information retention. For example, C_{maj}, with no accidentals, is significantly different from most TCs other than those with a small number of accidentals such as G_{maj} (with one accidental, F#, and is C_{maj}'s dominant TC), F_{maj} (with one accidental, B#, and is C_{maj}'s subdominant TC), and B_{bmaj} and D_{maj} (with 2 accidentals each). M₀ is also significantly different from the TCs with a small number of accidentals. These relationships become clearer when the average items recalled per major TC is represented in the following chart (ranked from highest to lowest):

Figure 4.7: Average items retained per major TC

4.5.2. Minor TCs (smartphone ad):

An ANOVA analysis with R as the dependent variable and the different minor TCs (and M_0) as the independent variables showed the following results:

	F	df1	df2	Sig.
ANOVA of Retention (R) between minor TCs	11.17	12	182	.00

Table 4.24: ANOVA test of retention (R) between minor TCs

Which can be summed up as per the following equation:

$$F(12,182) = 11.17, \text{ sig.} < .05$$

The ANOVA test shows that the sig. value was < 0.05 , which shows that there is a statistical significance between the means of at least two of the 13 scenarios. This alone is enough to result in the rejection of the null hypothesis H_{r2} , which stated that **the information retention (R) of an advertisement is invariant when the advertising music (M) is transposed across the 12 minor tonal centres (TCs) of the minor tonal category**, which means that minor TCs of advertising music do indeed influence brand information retention differently.

Minor TC (smartphone ad)	n	\bar{x}	σ
C	15	1.80	1.74
C#/D\flat	15	1.13	1.30
D	15	3.20	1.82
D#/E\flat	15	1.06	1.03
E	15	4.00	1.13
F	15	1.46	1.12
F#/G\flat	15	1.80	1.08
G	15	2.66	1.71
G#/A\flat	15	1.00	1.06
A	15	4.26	1.22
A#/B\flat	15	1.06	.88
B	15	3.26	1.57
M$_0$	15	1.80	1.74
Total	195	2.20	1.70

Table 4.25: Descriptive statistics of retention under minor TCs

In order to locate the TCs with the statistical significance, a Tukey's HSD (Honestly Significant Difference) Post Hoc analysis was conducted. The following table shows the sig. values from the analysis as a pairwise comparison between all minor TCs (including M_0) (statistically significant values are highlighted):

TC	C	C# D _b	D	D# E _b	E	F	F# G _b	G	G# A _b	A	A# B _b	B	M ₀
C	1	.97	.18	.95	.00	1	1	.85	.91	.00	.95	.13	1
C#/D _b	.97	1	.00	1	.00	1	.97	.09	1	.00	1	.00	.95
D	.18	.00	1	.00	.91	.02	.18	.99	.00	.60	.00	1	.24
D#/E _b	.95	1	.00	1	.00	1	.95	.06	1	.00	1	.00	.91
E	.00	.00	.91	.00	1	.00	.00	.24	.00	1	.00	.95	.00
F	1	1	.02	1	.00	1	1	.40	.99	.00	1	.01	1
F#/G _b	1	.97	.18	.95	.00	1	1	.85	.91	.00	.95	.13	1
G	.85	.09	.99	.06	.24	.40	.85	1	.04	.06	.06	.99	.91
G#/A _b	.91	1	.00	1	.00	.99	.91	.04	1	.00	1	.00	.85
A	.00	.00	.60	.00	1	.00	.00	.06	.00	1	.00	.70	.00
A#/B _b	.95	1	.00	1	.00	1	.95	.06	1	.00	1	.00	.91
B	.13	.00	1	.00	.95	.01	.13	.99	.00	.70	.00	1	.18
M ₀	1	.95	.4	.91	.00	1	1	.91	.85	.00	.91	.18	1

Table 4.26: Tukey's HSD pairwise comparison of retention (minor TCs)

As there are many sig. values < .05, it's clear that many scenarios differ from each other (statistically significant values are highlighted). Notably, however, is that, similar to the major TCs, minor TCs with the least number of accidentals (sharps # and flats b) have resulted in the most brand information retention. For example, A_{min}, with no accidentals, is significantly different from most TCs other than those with a small number of accidentals such as E_{min} (with one accidental, F#, and is A_{min}'s dominant TC), D_{min} (with one accidental, B#, and is A_{min}'s subdominant TC), B_{min} and G_{min} (with 2 accidentals each). Interestingly, M₀ is also significantly different from the TCs with a small number of accidentals (A_{min} with 0 accidentals and E_{min} with 1 accidental). These relationships become clearer when the average items recalled per minor TC is represented in the following chart (ranked from highest to lowest):

Figure 4.8: Average items retained per minor TC

4.6. Main Experiments Questionnaire Analysis (Purchase Intention):

For purchase intention (*PI*), the three Likert scale items will be combined into one variable, which will be subject to an ANOVA analysis to test the difference of purchase intention of the research participants under the different TCs in both major (juice ad) and minor (smartphone) conditions.

4.6.1. Major TCs (juice ad):

An ANOVA analysis of with *PI* as the dependent variable and the different major TCs (and M_0) as the independent variables showed the following results:

	F	df1	df2	Sig.
ANOVA of Purchase Intention (<i>PI</i>) between major TCs	9.37	12	182	.00

Table 4.27: ANOVA test of purchase intention (*PI*) between major TCs

Which can be summed up as per the following equation:

$$F(12,182) = 9.37, \text{ sig.} < .05$$

The ANOVA test shows that the sig. value was < 0.05 , which shows that there is a statistical significance between the means of at least two of the 13 scenarios. This alone is enough to result in the rejection of the null hypothesis H_{pi1} , which stated that **the purchase intention (PI) of an advertisement is invariant when the advertising music (M) is transposed across the 12 major tonal centres (TCs) of the major tonal category**, which means that major TCs of advertising music do indeed influence purchase intention differently.

Major TC (juice ad)	n	\bar{x}	σ
C	15	3.60	.74
C#/D \flat	15	1.91	.73
D	15	3.11	1.15
D#/E \flat	15	2.44	.78
E	15	2.11	.72
F	15	3.24	.80
F#/G \flat	15	1.84	.75
G	15	3.44	.72
G#/A \flat	15	2.04	.69
A	15	2.35	.73
A#/B \flat	15	3.17	1.14
B	15	1.82	.79
M_0	15	2.28	.73
Total	195	2.20	1.70

Table 4.28: Descriptive statistics of purchase intention under major TCs

In order to locate the TCs with the statistical significance, a Tukey's HSD (Honestly Significant Difference) Post Hoc analysis was conducted. The following table shows the sig. values from the analysis as a pairwise comparison between all major TCs (including M₀) (statistically significant values are highlighted):

TC	C	C# D _b	D	D# E _b	E	F	F# G _b	G	G# A _b	A	A# B _b	B	M ₀
C	1	.00	.92	.01	.00	.99	.00	1	.00	.00	.97	.00	.00
C#/D _b	.00	1	.00	.86	1	.00	1	.00	1	.95	.00	1	.98
D	.92	.00	1	.58	.055	1	.00	.99	.02	.37	1	.00	.24
D#/E _b	.01	.86	.58	1	.99	.28	.73	.055	.98	1	.42	.68	1
E	.00	1	.055	.99	1	.01	1	.00	1	1	.02	.99	1
F	.99	.00	1	.28	.01	1	.00	1	.00	.14	1	.00	.08
F#/G _b	.00	1	.00	.73	1	.00	1	.00	1	.89	.00	1	.95
G	1	.00	.99	.055	.00	1	.00	1	.00	.02	1	.00	.01
G#/A _b	.00	1	.02	.98	1	.00	1	.00	1	.99	.01	1	1
A	.00	.95	.37	1	1	.14	.89	.02	.99	1	.24	.86	1
A#/B _b	.97	.00	1	.42	.02	1	.00	1	.01	.24	1	.00	.14
B	.00	1	.00	.68	.99	.00	1	.00	1	.86	.00	1	.94
M ₀	.00	.98	.24	1	1	.08	.95	.01	1	1	.14	.94	1

Table 4.29: Tukey's HSD pairwise comparison of purchase intention (major TCs)

As there are many sig. values < .05, it's clear that many scenarios differ from each other (statistically significant values are highlighted). Notably, major TCs with the least number of accidentals (sharps # and flats b) have resulted in the most purchase intention. For example, C_{maj}, with no accidentals, is significantly different from most TCs other than those with a small number of accidentals such as G_{maj} (with one accidental, F#, and is C_{maj}'s dominant TC), F_{maj} (with one accidental, B#, and is C_{maj}'s subdominant TC), B_{bmaj} and D_{maj} (with 2 accidentals each). Interestingly, M₀ is only significantly different from C_{maj} and G_{maj}, which have 0 and 1 accidentals, respectively. These relationships become clearer when the average items recalled per minor TC is represented in the following chart (ranked from highest to lowest):

Figure 4.9: Average purchase intention per major TC

4.6.2. Minor TCs (smartphone ad):

An ANOVA analysis of with *PI* as the dependent variable and the different minor TCs (and M_0) as the independent variables showed the following results:

	F	df1	df2	Sig.
ANOVA of Purchase Intention (PI) between minor TCs	7.21	12	182	.00

Table 4.30: ANOVA test of purchase intention (PI) between minor TCs

Which can be summed up as per the following equation:

$$F(12,182) = 7.21, \text{ sig.} < .05$$

The ANOVA test shows that the sig. value was < 0.05 , which shows that there is a statistical significance between the means of at least two of the 13 scenarios. This alone is enough to result in the rejection of the null hypothesis H_{pi2} , which stated that **The purchase intention (PI) of an advertisement is invariant when the advertising music (M) is transposed across the 12 minor tonal centres (TCs) of the minor tonal category**, which means that minor TCs of advertising music do indeed influence purchase intention differently.

Minor TC (smartphone ad)	n	\bar{x}	σ
C	15	2.22	.84
C#/D\flat	15	2.00	.79
D	15	3.13	.78
D#/E\flat	15	1.68	.66
E	15	3.20	.71
F	15	1.82	.66
F#/G\flat	15	2.20	.74
G	15	3.06	1.04
G#/A\flat	15	1.68	.71
A	15	3.26	1.24
A#/B\flat	15	2.02	.84
B	15	.88	1.21
M$_0$	15	2.22	.78
Total	195	2.41	1.02

Table 4.31: Descriptive statistics of purchase intention under minor TCs

In order to locate the TCs with the statistical significance, a Tukey's HSD (Honestly Significant Difference) Post Hoc analysis was conducted. The following table shows the sig. values from the analysis as a pairwise comparison between all minor TCs (including M_0) (statistically significant values are highlighted):

TC	C	C# D _b	D	D# E _b	E	F	F# G _b	G	G# A _b	A	A# B _b	B	M ₀
C	1	1	.18	.90	.10	.98	1	.28	.90	.04	1	.66	1
C#/D _b	1	1	.02	.99	.01	1	1	.05	.99	.00	1	.21	1
D	.18	.02	1	.00	1	.00	.15	1	.00	1	.03	1	.18
D#/E _b	.90	.99	.00	1	.00	1	.92	.00	1	.00	.99	.01	.90
E	.10	.01	1	.00	1	.00	.09	1	.00	1	.01	.99	.10
F	.98	1	.00	1	.00	1	.99	.00	1	.00	1	.05	.98
F#/G _b	1	1	.15	.92	.09	.99	1	.24	.92	.05	1	.61	1
G	.28	.05	1	.00	1	.00	.24	1	.00	1	.06	1	.28
G#/A _b	.90	.99	.00	1	.00	1	.92	.00	1	.00	.99	.01	.90
A	.04	.00	1	.00	1	.00	.05	1	.00	1	.00	.99	.04
A#/B _b	1	1	.03	.99	.01	1	1	.06	.99	.00	1	.24	1
B	.66	.21	1	.01	.99	.05	.61	1	.01	.99	.24	1	.66
M ₀	1	1	.18	.90	.10	.98	1	.28	.90	.04	1	.66	1

Table 4.32: Tukey's HSD pairwise comparison of purchase intention (minor TCs)

As there are many sig. values < .05, it's clear that many scenarios differ from each other (statistically significant values are highlighted). Notably, however, is that, similar to major TCs, minor TCs with the least number of accidentals (sharps # and flats b) have resulted in the most purchase intention. For example, A_{min}, with no accidentals, is significantly different from most TCs other than those with a small number of accidentals such as E_{min} (with one accidental, F#, and is A_{min}'s dominant TC), D_{min} (with one accidental, B#, and is A_{min}'s subdominant TC), G_{min} and B_{min} (with 2 accidentals each). Interestingly, M₀ is only significantly different from A_{min}. These relationships become clearer when the average items recalled per minor TC is represented in the following chart (ranked from highest to lowest):

Figure 4.10: Average purchase intention per minor TC

4.7. Manipulation Check Data Analysis¹:

While the results earlier showed that different TCs influence attention, brand information retention, and purchase intention differently, it's important to check if octaval transposition (or register) plays a role in these findings. Therefore, a manipulation check was conducted where the original C_{maj} is compared with 2 scenarios of octaval transposition, one octave up, and one octave down (C_{maj+8} , and C_{maj-8}). Similarly, the original A_{min} is compared with 2 scenarios of octaval transposition, one octave up, and one octave down (A_{min+8} , and A_{min-8}).

30 more participants partook in the manipulation check (15 for the higher transposition scenarios, and 15 for the lower transposition scenarios), and the results were as follows:

4.7.1. Major TCs (juice ad):

All 15 participants for each of the 2 scenarios (C_{maj+8} , and C_{maj-8}) of the juice ad have been combined into one brain map showing their average brain activity in Hz throughout the viewing of the juice ad. This is then compared with the original C_{maj} .

Figure 4.11: Brain mapping for participants subject to the juice ad (C_{maj-8} , C_{maj} , C_{maj+8})

An ANOVA analysis of with brain activity in Hz (Attention) as the dependent variable and the 3 C_{maj} scenarios (C_{maj-8} , C_{maj} , C_{maj+8}) as the independent variables showed the following results:

	F	df1	df2	Sig.
ANOVA of Attention (A) between C_{maj-8}, C_{maj}, and C_{maj+8}	.006	2	42	.99

Table 4.33: ANOVA test of attention (A) between C_{maj-8} , C_{maj} , and C_{maj+8}

Which can be summed up as per the following equation:

$$F(2,42) = .006, \text{ sig.} > .05$$

¹ Raw SPSS output of the manipulation check can be found in appendix L.

The ANOVA test shows that the sig. value was > 0.05, which means that there is no statistical significance between the means of any of the 3 scenarios (C_{maj-8} , C_{maj} , C_{maj+8}). Therefore, it's possible to conclude that octaval transposition does not play a role in the influence of different major TCs in advertising music on the levels of attention. The following table shows the descriptive statistics of the 3 scenarios.

Major TC (Juice ad)	n	\bar{x}	σ
C_{maj-8}	15	25.59	1.93
C_{maj}	15	25.57	2.10
C_{maj+8}	15	25.65	2.07
Total	195	25.60	1.99

Table 4.34: Descriptive statistics of attention in Hz (C_{maj-8} , C_{maj} , C_{maj+8})

While there's no need to conduct a Tukey's HSD (Honestly Significant Difference) Post Hoc analysis since all sig values are > .05, its results are shared in the following table for completeness.

TC	C_{maj-8}	C_{maj}	C_{maj+8}
C_{maj-8}	1	1	.99
C_{maj}	1	1	.99
C_{maj+8}	.99	.99	1

Table 4.35: Tukey's HSD pairwise comparison of attention (C_{maj-8} , C_{maj} , C_{maj+8})

The levels of attention as a result of the 3 scenarios are also illustrated in the following chart alongside all other major TCs and M_0 (ranked from highest to lowest)

Figure 4.12: Average Hz per C_{maj-8} , C_{maj} , and C_{maj+8} vs. major TCs and M_0

4.7.2. Minor TCs (smartphone ad):

All 15 participants for each of the 2 scenarios ($A_{\min+8}$, and $A_{\min-8}$) of the smartphone ad have been combined into one brain map showing their average brain activity in Hz throughout the viewing of the smartphone ad. This is then compared with the original A_{\min} .

Figure 4.13: Brain mapping for participants subject to the smartphone ad ($A_{\text{maj-8}}$, A_{maj} , $A_{\text{maj+8}}$)

An ANOVA analysis of with brain activity in Hz (Attention) as the dependent variable and the 3 A_{\min} scenarios ($A_{\min-8}$, A_{\min} , $A_{\min+8}$) as the independent variables showed the following results:

	F	df1	df2	Sig.
ANOVA of Attention (A) between $A_{\min-8}$, A_{\min}, and $A_{\min+8}$.015	2	42	.98

Table 4.36: ANOVA test of attention (A) between $A_{\min-8}$, A_{\min} , and $A_{\min+8}$

Which can be summed up as per the following equation:

$$F(2,42) = .015, \text{ sig.} > .05$$

The ANOVA test shows that the sig. value was > 0.05 , which means that there is no statistical significance between the means of any of the 3 scenarios ($A_{\min-8}$, A_{\min} , $A_{\min+8}$). Therefore, it's possible to conclude that octaval transposition does not play a role in the influence of different minor TCs in advertising music on the levels of attention. The following table shows the descriptive statistics of the 3 scenarios.

Major TC (Juice ad)	n	\bar{x}	σ
$C_{\text{maj-8}}$	15	25.42	1.68
C_{maj}	15	25.49	1.60
$C_{\text{maj+8}}$	15	25.39	1.51
Total	195	25.43	1.56

Table 4.37: Descriptive statistics of attention in Hz ($A_{\min-8}$, A_{\min} , $A_{\min+8}$)

While there's no need to conduct a Tukey's HSD (Honestly Significant Difference) Post Hoc analysis since all sig values are $> .05$, its results are shared in the following table for completeness.

TC	A _{min-8}	A _{min}	A _{min+8}
A _{min-8}	1	.99	.99
A _{min}	.99	1	.98
A _{min+8}	.99	.98	1

Table 4.38: Tukey's HSD pairwise comparison of attention (A_{min-8}, A_{min}, A_{min+8})

The levels of attention as a result of the 3 scenarios are also illustrated in the following chart alongside all other minor TCs and M₀ (ranked from highest to lowest)

Figure 4.14: Average Hz per A_{min-8}, A_{min}, and A_{min+8} vs. minor TCs and M₀

4.8. Chapter Conclusion:

This chapter managed to analyse the relevant data collected from 225 participants (195 for the main experiments and a further 30 for the manipulation check). The main findings can be summarised as follows:

- Different major TCs in advertising music do indeed influence consumer attention (A), as represented by overall brain activity in Hz, differently, where TCs with a small number of accidentals evoked more (A) than TCs with a high number of accidentals or with the no-music scenario, M_0 . Similar results were found for the minor TCs.
- Different major TCs in advertising music do indeed influence consumer brand information retention (R), as represented by number of items recalled, differently, where TCs with a small number of accidentals assisted in retaining more brand-related items than TCs with a high number of accidentals or with the no-music scenario, M_0 . Similar results were found for the minor TCs. Similar results were found for the minor TCs.
- Different major TCs in advertising music do indeed influence consumer Purchase Intention (PI) differently, where TCs with a small number of accidentals resulted in higher PI than TCs with a high number of accidentals or with the no-music scenario, M_0 . Similar results were found for the minor TCs. Similar results were found for the minor TCs.
- These findings remain statistically significant even under the octaval transposition of TCs (i.e. C_{maj} evokes similar attentional response to C_{maj} on any other octave/register).

5. CHAPTER FIVE - DISCUSSION

5.1. Chapter Introduction

5.2. Interpretation of Results

5.3. Integration of Results with the Literature

5.4. Debating the Results against the Theoretical Framework

5.5. Reflections on Research Questions & Hypotheses

5.6. Reflection on Research Aim & Objectives

5.7. Chapter Conclusion

5.1. Chapter Introduction:

The purpose of this chapter is to critically interpret the findings presented in the previous chapter, and to discuss their implications within the broader context of the research questions, hypotheses, objectives, and main aim, as well as the necessary integration with the existing body of literature.

The data from the previous chapter showed that the use of different TCs in advertising music does indeed influence attention, retention, and purchase intention differently. Such results, have not, to the knowledge of the researcher, been reached before within the research literature on advertising music since TCs have not been investigated individually. However, several music researchers have alerted of a potential inequivalence between different TCs and encouraged future research to challenge the Transpositional Invariance Assumption.

Furthermore, a thorough interpretation and discussion of the results is necessary to establish a cohesive understanding of the nuances of the data. This is especially important given the limitations of this research, which will be highlighted during this discussion, but detailed further in the conclusion chapter.

This chapter will also recall upon the research questions, hypotheses, aim, and objectives. By revisiting the initial research questions asked and hypotheses tested, it's possible to assess the extent to which the research findings have addressed these inquiries and fulfilled the overarching aim and objectives of the study.

5.2. Interpretation of Results:

In this section, the interpretation of the results obtained from the data analysis in chapter 4 will be detailed. The patterns, trends, and relationships within the data are interpreted to gain a deeper understanding of the role of TCs in advertising music. These interpretations will highlight issues regarding the main variables of the research, attention, retention, and purchase intention.

There were several ways the research could have analysed the data collected, such as leaning more toward cross-analyses of the demographical variables, however, this would have distracted from the main focus of the research questions and hypotheses, which is to test if different TCs are transpositionally equivalent. With this main focus as the frontier of this research, the research can then build an argument to challenge the Transpositional Invariance Assumption (TIA), thus problematising the notion that all TCs within their category (major and minor) are perceptually equal under transposition, which, as per the results, was untrue. The following will elaborate on what this finding means for the main dependent variables of the research, attention (*A*), retention (*R*), and purchase intention (*PI*) and the role of TC accidentals in shaping the findings of this research.

5.2.1. The role of accidentals (sharps \sharp & flats \flat):

Accidentals, such as sharps \sharp and flats \flat have long influenced the means by which music is composed, notated, and played. Furthermore, accidentals have even shaped the display of keys on instruments such as the piano, where less accidentals are generally more convenient for the writer and performer as accidentals can influence the chosen chord progressions, chord shapes and inversions, scales, arpeggios, glissandos, and other writing and performing techniques that are preferred or unpreferred for different TCs that have a different number of accidentals (White, 2014). Historically, this has created a skewness in which TCs are used for writing music, such that more music is written in TCs with less accidentals like C_{maj} , G_{maj} , or F_{maj} (Prince & Schmuckler, 2014; Quinn and White, 2017). Figures 2.4 and 2.5 in the literature review show this skewness, which interestingly is similar to the degrees to which different TCs have elevated attention in this research, where C_{maj} ranked first followed by other TCs that have a small number of accidentals and an overall simpler writing, notating, and performing techniques. It's possible that consumers are subconsciously aware of this bias and exhibit a preference for TCs that align with their familiarity as well as the simplicity of musical structures associated with those TCs, resulting in an elevated attentional response, a better retention of brand information, and subsequently, a more pronounced intent to purchase.

5.2.2. Brain lateralisation:

Regarding the influence of TCs on the attentional responses of participants, the data analysis clearly revealed consistent and statistically significant results where the TCs with the least number of accidentals have resulted in the highest levels of attention. This result is true for both the major TCs and the minor TCs regardless of octaval positioning. For example, participants exhibited an increased overall neural activity (in Hertz) when exposed to advertising music in C_{maj} or A_{min} , (similar at different octaves), which have no accidentals.

Furthermore, as per figures 4.11, it's clear that C_{maj} , regardless of octaval transposition, resulted in an overall heightened activation in the left hemisphere of the brain more than other major TCs, which have resulted in an activation in other regions, however since only C_{maj} , of all the major TCs, was tested at two other octaves in the manipulation check, it has a larger sample size (45 participants vs. 15 participants for other major TCs). This reinforces which regional activation occurs when it's used.

Due to the brain lateralisation, the left hemisphere is generally responsible for functions related to speech, language, problem solving, analytical reasoning and memory retention, making it the dominant hemisphere when processing stimuli (Draganski *et al.*, 2006; Güntürkün, Ströckens, & Ocklenburg, 2020). It's important to note that this is contralaterally true, which means that right-handed people have a left hemisphere domination and vice versa. One of the research limitations is that it did not measure participants' handedness to account for this lateralisation. However, it's safe to assume that the majority of participants are right-handed (85-90%), thus have a dominant left hemisphere (Masud & Ajmal, 2012).

Nonetheless, as per Hebb's rule, regional activation triggers other regions (Hebb, 1949; Frackowiak, 2004; Guzman-Karlsson *et al.*, 2014; Keyzers & Gazzola, 2014). This function, coupled with the low number of electrodes of the EEG machine used in this research, makes it difficult to locate a specific region of brain activation. However, since the left hemisphere of the brain showed more activation under the major TC with the least number of accidentals, it's possible to argue that, paradoxically, less accidentals, trigger more attention, thus more overall left hemisphere activation, which is a reason for the heightened attention, through which memory retention increases. Even the intent to purchase, while a behavioural function rather than a neural one, will be influenced by this activation as consumers would be more alerted and sensitive to stimuli. This proposes that consumers' purchase intention may not be lower by default when using major TCs with more accidentals, but that the use of music with less accidentals alerts consumers to observe more details and retain more information, thus developing a more decisive intent to purchase. For better regional activation accuracy, further research is required using EEGs with more electrodes (128 or more) or fMRIs.

5.2.3. Occipital and parietal lobes:

As for the minor TC that resulted in the highest attentional response (A_{min}), it showed occipital and parietal activation rather than showing a hemispherical activation as can be seen in figure 4.13. This activation seems to be slightly left lateralised, which can be justified by the same arguments as the major condition (C_{maj}) where the lateralisation is more pronounced. However, in this case, the increased activation of the occipital region, which is generally responsible for visual processing (Makeig *et al.*, 2004), might be due to the significantly different visuals between the minor TC ad (smartphone) and the major TC ad (juice), where the visuals in the smartphone ad may have contained more visually stimulating elements or that captured participants' attention that elicited an increased neural activity in the occipital region, or perhaps due to a more inherent visual interest in smartphones than juice bottles. Future research could delve deeper into the specific visual characteristics and ad design that contribute to the observed occipital activation in response to minor TCs, this could be done via eye tracking alongside brain imaging techniques.

This condition also seems to be associated with more activation in the parietal lobe, which generally initiates and processes much of the functions related to the senses as well as the voluntary motor control (Fogassi & Luppino, 2005). This may be explained as participants being more engaged in processing the sensory information and integrating it with their motor responses, where the specific content presented in the smartphone ad triggered a heightened sensory-motor integration. Thus, it's possible that the familiarity and daily usage of smartphones in participants' lives may have triggered a motor response as an anticipation of the tactile sensations associated with holding and interacting with the smartphone, leading to the observed parietal activation.

However, as mentioned earlier, and due to Hebb's rule, no one cognitive function is exclusive to one region (Guzman-Karlsson *et al.*, 2014), therefore, this increased attention in both the occipital and parietal lobes is likely synergetic with many other regions of the brain, rendering the regional data difficult to read when using a 14-electrode EEG equipment. This complexity of brain functioning highlights the need for more advanced measurement tools, such as high-density EEG or functional Magnetic Resonance Imaging (fMRI), to capture the regional activation patterns with greater precision and provide a more detailed understanding of the neural mechanisms underlying the observed effects. Future research with higher quality tools of measurement is required for detecting regional activation.

5.2.4. High beta and low beta oscillations:

The EEG results showed distinctly different degrees of brain activity when using different TCs in advertising music. These brain activity frequencies are grouped into different levels, which can be seen in the figure below.

Frequency name	Frequency range in Hertz
gamma γ	>30 Hz
beta β	13-30 Hz
Alpha α	8-13 Hz
theta θ	4-8 Hz
delta δ	0.5-4 Hz

Table 5.1: Brain waves and their frequency ranges (Koudelková & Strmiska, 2018, p. 2)

As can be seen in figures 4:1 and 4:3, participants' brain activity ranged from as low as 13Hz to as high as 25Hz throughout the different scenarios of the research. This brain activity range falls within the beta β wave frequency. These frequencies represent a "waking state", "logical-analytical reasoning", and "problem solving" (Koudelková & Strmiska, 2018, p. 2). Researchers further distinguish between low-beta and high-beta brain waves for different levels of attentional response at 13-21 Hz and 22-30 Hz, respectively (Díaz *et al.*, 2022, p. 1416).

These sub-band oscillations are responsible for different levels of attention allocation, cognitive control, and information processing. For example, the lower end of the beta frequency range (13-21 Hz) is associated with a state of focused attention, cognitive engagement, and active problem-solving. On the other hand, the higher end of the beta range (22-30 Hz) reflects a state of heightened alertness and focus, cognitive processing, and analytical problem-solving (Herrmann *et al.*, 2016). The first 4 TCs of both the major and minor tonal categories, which have either no accidentals or 1 accidental, resulted in an average brain activity that falls in the high beta range (22-30 Hz). This could explain why they have led to a higher attentional response, retention rate, and purchase intention than TCs that have a bigger number of accidentals, which have resulted in the lowest responses.

However, it is important to note that brain activity and its relationship to cognitive processes are highly complex. The observed frequency ranges provide a general understanding of the brain states during the research scenarios, but there may be individual variations and other factors influencing the neural responses. Further research with more advanced neuroimaging techniques, such as state-of-the-art EEGs or fMRI, could provide deeper insights into the specific neural networks and mechanisms involved in the processing of different TCs and their impact on consumer responses.

5.3. Integration of Results with the Literature:

As mentioned earlier, the current body of literature has not considered the investigation of individual TCs. Therefore, there are no direct means of integrating the literature with regards to the influence of TCs in advertising music on many of the variables that govern advertising and its practices. Nonetheless, there are several ways through which the literature can be viewed in relation to the findings of this research.

This research builds on the suggestions of previous studies that highlight the importance of considering the role of TCs in different contexts by challenging the Transpositional Invariance Assumption (Quinn & White, 2017). By examining the influence of individual TCs on attentional and behavioural responses, this research adds novel insight to the literature and expands the understanding of how advertising music can influence consumer perceptions and reactions to advertisements. This integration of findings bridges a significant gap in the literature and contributes to a more comprehensive understanding of the role of TCs on advertising. Furthermore, this research aligns with previous studies that emphasise the role of music in advertising and its ability to shape consumer behaviour (Caldwell & Hibbert, 1999; Park, Park & Jeon, 2014; Zoghaib, 2019; Herget, Breves, & Schramm, 2022). The following will integrate the relevant literature with the findings of this research:

5.3.1. Integrating attention:

Several Kellaris studies in the 1990s have considered attention as a dependant variable to advertising music. Furthermore, they have all considered different aspects of advertising music. For example, Kellaris & Kent (1991), found that the tempo of advertising music and consumers' level of attention positively correlate. The current research controlled tempo at 120 BPM across all scenarios. However, future research could examine the influence of different TCs at different tempi on attention. Kellaris, Cox, & Cox (1993) have also examined how congruent vs. incongruent advertising music influences attention and found that attention is improved when the music is congruent with the ad, which improves the overall reception of the advertising message. The current research controlled congruence, but it's possible for future research to examine the influence of different levels of congruence across different TCs on consumers' attention, especially that some research suggests that incongruent music may lead to a sense of surprise, thus increasing attention (Boltz, Schulkind, & Kantra, 1991; Shen & Chen, 2006; Abolhasani & Golrokhi, 2022).

A slightly more relevant study is Kellaris & Kent's (1993), which examined tonality as major, minor, and atonal (but not as individual TCs) and found that attention improved when music was dissonant (atonal). This research did not examine atonality, but similar to incongruence, it's possible that atonal music elicits surprise, thus higher attentional response.

Allan (2006), on the other hand, examined vocal, instrumental, or absent music and found that attention is improved more with popular and familiar music than with instrumental or no music. This aligns with the findings of this research with regards to the no-music condition, as this research too has found that attention is increased more with the presence of music rather than its absence. Indeed, the absence of music only resulted in similar attentional response when the TC of advertising music had the most accidentals such as (F \sharp _{maj} or D \sharp _{min}).

It's important to note that while the TCs of advertising music have not been subject to individual examination in the existing body of literature, and that there's a considerable lack of neuromarketing research on the topic of advertising music in general, there is one study by Bhattacharya, Zioga, & Lewis (2017) to which the findings of this research could somewhat relate, as they found that repetition of the same advertising music in the same campaign showed larger frontal asymmetry in brain activity, which suggests elevated attention. This research found similar frontal asymmetry in the C_{maj} music condition, which is what resulted in the highest attention.

5.3.2. Integrating retention:

The current research found that most TCs elicit more brand information retention than the absence of music. This contradicts Sewall & Sarel's (1986) study that found no difference in retention between the presence and absence of advertising music, and Brooker & Wheatley (1994) who found that both brand information retention and brand awareness are decreased when advertising music is present. However, these findings do not align with Hunt (1988), Yalch (1991), Wallace (1994), Allan (2006) who found that the presence of advertising music is associated with higher brand information retention and recall. The findings of this research also supported this influence where most scenarios of TCs resulted in more brand information items recalled than the no-music scenario (M₀), or the TCs with the highest number of accidentals.

As for music congruence, Shen & Chen (2006) found that incongruent advertising music improved retention. This could be a result of incongruent music potentially increasing alertness and overall attention, which would assist in retaining more brand-related information to be recalled when needed or requested. Indeed, Abolhasani & Golrokhi (2022) have found that mildly incongruent advertising music brings about heightened retention of brand-related information, and that this is likely due to the higher alertness and sense of surprise associated with incongruent music, however, negative attitudes may be associated with the brand at the cost of this heightened retention. The current research controlled music congruence as to not confound the results. Future research could look into the influence of congruent and incongruent advertising music in different TCs on brand information retention.

5.3.3. Integrating purchase intention:

Bierley, McSweeney, & Vannieuwkerk (1985) found that the presence of music improves overall attitude toward the brand, which may improve the intent to purchase. This aligns with the findings of this research where the presence of music has overall resulted in better purchase intention across all TCs other than the ones with the most accidentals. Wilson (2003) also found that the absence of advertising music lowers consumers' purchase intention, which aligns with the present research as one of the scenarios tested that resulted in the least purchase intention is the no-music scenario (M_0).

As for tonality's influence on purchase intention, several studies have been conducted, but only examining tonal categories rather than individual TCs. For example, Alpert & Alpert (1990) found that the tonal categories, major and minor, influence purchase intention differently, where advertising music in a minor tonality increased consumers' purchase intention more than major tonality or no music. The current research does not make a direct comparison between major and minor TCs with regards to their influence on purchase intention. However, from the EEG data, it seems there's no difference between the major and minor tonal categories. Future research could perhaps initiate a comparative study between major TCs and minor TCs. Alpert, Alpert & Maltz (2005) also found similar results to their study from 15 years earlier, where tonality (major and minor, described as mood and categorised as happy and sad, respectively) improved purchase intention with minor advertising music, but only when participants were already in a sad mood. Current mood of participants was not examined in this research, but it could be a subject of interest for future research endeavours. Liu, Abolhasani, & Hang (2022) found the opposite results, where major tonality increased positive brand attitudes and purchase intention, and that fast major advertising music strengthens this influence even more. The issue with these three studies is the lack of structural control over the different elements of music. This research has controlled all aspects of music except for the tonal centres, which may constrict the generalisability of the results, however, it grounds the results more firmly into the literature, and offers the suggestion that future research should manipulate only a few variables over the ones manipulated here in an accumulative fashion rather than drastically and arbitrarily examine the influence of musical variables on marketing-related variables.

As for the congruence vs incongruence of the advertising music used, Abolhasani & Golrokhi (2022) found that congruence may be more effective on a spectrum where mildly incongruent music improved purchase intention more than congruent, incongruent, or severely incongruent advertising music. A direct comparison cannot be made here as this research controlled the level of congruence in its stimuli. However, future research could consider examining congruence on a spectrum and across different TCs.

5.4. Debating the Results against the Theoretical Framework:

It's important to revisit the theoretical framework developed for this research in light of its findings in order to fully conceptualise the results and pave a path for their applicability within real settings (Ellis & Levy, 2008). As the theoretical framework that was synthesised for this research detailed various theoretical disciplines, then it's necessary to integrate the research results into each of these aspects individually and then collectively.

5.4.1. Reviewing the results through problematisation:

Since the findings showcased that challenging the Transpositional Invariance Assumption (TIA) via problematisation indeed yielded results different from the reality under which the assumption is accepted, then this research, consequently, validates problematisation as a framework with which the status quo could be challenged. As certain TCs have been revealed to influence attention, retention, and purchase intention differently, then Foucauldian problematisation served a central purpose in this research for disclosing the intricacies of the effects of TCs in advertising music. This validation of problematisation as a framework not only challenges the TIA within marketing research but can further facilitate challenging it in other disciplines as well such as music theory, music therapy, music technology, psychoacoustics, audio engineering, music education, sound design, and more. Finally, since problematisation begins by challenging the current assumptions and status quo of phenomena, then it's important for future research to challenge the very assumptions of this research, such as the reliance on 12-TET as a main tuning system under which the experiments are conducted, the positivist worldview that reality is ultimately measurable and quantifiable, the notion that advertisers always wish to optimise their marketing efforts, and other notions that might be either explicitly or implicitly accepted within this research.

5.4.2. Reviewing the results through classical conditioning:

Since classical conditioning ultimately depends on establishing a conditioned response (higher levels of attention in the context of this research) independent from the unconditional stimulus that initially created the association (advertising music in the context of this research), and since the results not only showed a stronger case for certain TCs over others, but also showed that using music is more favourable than not using music in advertisements with the objective to increase attention, then removing the unconditional stimulus of the classical conditioning model defeats the purpose of the research.

It's important to reiterate that including classical conditioning in the theoretical framework was only intended to establish a stepping stone towards the other theoretical models such as the Elaboration Likelihood Model (ELM), music congruence, attention economy, and the theory of planned behaviour, which all helped synthesise the final theoretical framework.

5.4.3. Reviewing the results through the Elaboration Likelihood Model (ELM):

The research results showed that consumers subconsciously evaluate different TCs differently, which asserts the use of the Elaboration Likelihood Model (ELM) as part of the theoretical framework of this research, as the ELM posits that consumers do indeed process the presented stimuli peripherally and passively. Furthermore, unlike classical conditioning, the ELM does not require the elimination of the stimulus itself once the association is established.

This underscores the importance of considering the cognitive processing of TCs within the theoretical framework, as it may influence consumer responses beyond mere stimulus-response associations. Furthermore, the results suggest that TCs in advertising music may serve as peripheral cues that influence consumer attitudes and behaviours indirectly, supporting the tenets of the ELM regarding the dual-process nature of persuasion. By integrating insights from the ELM with the empirical findings, this research contributes to a deeper understanding of how tonal centres in advertising music operate within the broader theoretical framework of consumer persuasion and decision-making processes.

5.4.4. Reviewing the results through music congruence:

The pre-test results revealed that consumers do indeed perceive the advertising music used in the experiments to be congruent with the advertisement itself. This was a crucial factor to verify in order to manipulate other variables, such as the TCs of advertising music, freely without the possible interference of the influence of the degree to which music fits the advertisement. The confirmation of consumers' perception of music congruence provided a grounding point for all subsequent analyses aimed at investigating the specific effects of TCs in advertising music on consumer cognitive and behavioural responses.

Within the theoretical framework on music congruence, several questions were raised about the properties and specific design of advertising music: when does a piece of music 'fit' an advertising message and a specific target group that is to be addressed? Which style or genre of music can convey or underscore certain information? Do various parameters of music, such as tempo or harmony, affect how the music fits the advertisement? Is music congruence perceived differently cross-culturally? And is there a universal standard for music congruence? However, since this research controlled music congruence, then answering these questions would necessitate conducting a series of standalone multivariant researches with music congruence at the centre of them as a dependant variable.

5.4.5. Reviewing the results through attention economy:

With attention at the centre of this research, the attention economy theory provides a theoretical lens through which results can be interpreted. The differential effects of TCs on attention underscore the scarcity of consumer attention as a valuable resource in the digital age. Moreover, the findings suggest that TCs may function as attention-grabbing stimuli that influence consumers' allocation of attention and cognitive processing of advertising messages. Furthermore, incorporating the neural measuring of attention via EEG asserts the theory of attention economy in a novel approach that bypasses the biases of self-reporting.

Further exploration within the attention economy framework could delve into how TCs interact with other attentional stimuli and environmental factors to shape consumer attention dynamics and decision-making processes. Moreover, future research in music theory should explore how certain TCs have developed over time to bring about higher levels of attention (some were proposed earlier in the overview of the literature review chapter). Additionally, future neuroscience and psychoacoustics research should also utilise their tools to investigate the divergence in attention allocation for different TCs. And lastly, research in psychology should similarly attempt to answer this question by exploring consumers' cognitive biases and preferences that influence their attentional responses for different TCs.

5.4.6. Reviewing the results through the theory of planned behaviour:

The theory of planned behaviour allowed for a comprehensive understanding of how TCs in advertising music influence consumer behaviour. The theory also posits that behavioural intentions serve as a proximal predictor of behaviour, and the results of this research indeed clearly showcased a favourable behaviour characterised by increased intent to purchase when utilising TCs with less accidentals for the advertising music. Since most marketing efforts focus on specific calls to action (usually purchasing), then aligning TCs in advertising music with consumers' behavioural intentions becomes crucial for achieving desired outcomes. By leveraging insights from the theory of planned behaviour, advertisers can strategically design advertising campaigns that not only shape favourable attitudes towards the brand, but also enhance consumers' perceived behavioural control over their purchase decisions due to their heightened level of attention given to the advertisement.

Overall, the research findings justify the use of the theory of planned behaviour to predict consumers' subsequent actions, and similarly, the theory of planned behaviour explains the research findings that purchase intention is increased when advertising music uses TCs with less accidentals, which is a behaviour brought by consumer' attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioural control.

5.5. Reflections on Research Questions & Hypotheses:

This section provides a critical reflection on the 6 research questions and their corresponding hypotheses, evaluating the extent to which they were addressed and supported by the findings of the research.

5.5.1. Attention-related questions and hypotheses:

The research proposed two questions and hypotheses relating to attention, one regarding the major TCs and another regarding the minor TCs:

Q_{a1}: Does the Transpositional Invariance Assumption hold true for the perception of an advertisement as characterised by attention towards it when the music is transposed across all 12 major tonal centres (TCs) of the major tonal category.

H_{a1} (null): The attention (A) to an advertisement is invariant when the advertising music (M) is transposed across the 12 major tonal centres (TCs) of the major tonal category.

Q_{a2}: Does the Transpositional Invariance Assumption hold true for the perception of an advertisement as characterised by attention towards it when the music is transposed across all 12 minor tonal centres (TCs) of the minor tonal category.

H_{a2} (null): The attention (A) to an advertisement is invariant when the advertising music (M) is transposed across the 12 minor tonal centres (TCs) of the minor tonal category.

The answer to both question Q_{a1} and Q_{a2} is negative as the Transpositional Invariance Assumption has been refuted when the results of the analysis showed a transpositional variance in the attentional response to the advertising music under different TCs.

The transpositional variance observed suggests that the TCs of advertising music play a significant role in influencing attentional responses. Participants' attentional engagement differed depending on the specific TC used in the advertisements, indicating that the tonal characteristics of the music interacted with participants' cognitive and perceptual processes, where the simpler and more commonly used TCs with less accidentals resulted in higher attentional responses. As a result of this variance in attention, both H_{a1} and H_{a2} are rejected.

These results have important implications for the understanding of how TCs shape consumers' attentional responses in the context of advertising. They highlight the need to consider the TC as a fundamental element of the music chosen or written for the advertisement, rather than neglecting it or only considering it as an afterthought. By recognising the impact of TCs on attentional responses, advertisers can strategically leverage music that aligns with their intended campaign objectives and target audience. Considering TCs during the creative process can enhance the overall effectiveness of advertising campaigns, as it allows for a more intentional and cohesive integration of music and brand messaging.

5.5.2. Retention-related questions and hypotheses:

The research proposed two questions and hypotheses relating to brand information retention, one regarding the major TCs and another regarding the minor TCs:

Q_{r1}: Does the Transpositional Invariance Assumption hold true for the perception of an advertisement as characterised by information retention when the music is transposed across all 12 major tonal centres (TCs) of the major tonal category.

H_{r1} (null): The information retention (R) of an advertisement is invariant when the advertising music (M) is transposed across the 12 major tonal centres (TCs) of the major tonal category.

Q_{r2}: Does the Transpositional Invariance Assumption hold true for the perception of an advertisement as characterised by information retention when the music is transposed across all 12 minor tonal centres (TCs) of the minor tonal category.

H_{r2} (null): The information retention (R) of an advertisement is invariant when the advertising music (M) is transposed across the 12 minor tonal centres (TCs) of the minor tonal category.

The answer to both questions is negative as the Transpositional Invariance Assumption has been refuted when the results of the analysis showed that a transpositional variance in the retention of brand information occurs when the advertising music is set to different TCs.

The transpositional variance observed suggests that the TCs of advertising music play a significant role in influencing the degree to which consumers retain brand information and recall them when requested. Participants' retention differed depending on the specific TC used in the advertisements, indicating that the tonal characteristics of the music interacted with participants' cognitive load of long-term unaided memory recall, where the simpler and more commonly used TCs with less accidentals resulted in a higher rate of brand information retention. As a result of this variance in retention, both H_{r1} and H_{r2} are rejected.

These results have important implications for the understanding of how TCs shape consumers' retention of brand information in the context of advertising. They further underscore the need for advertisers to carefully consider the TCs employed in their advertising music. By selecting TCs that optimise the levels of information retained, better recall can occur, and positive subsequent actions can be made in favour of the brand. Furthermore, there's a potential snowballing effect in retention where the ability to recall certain items will result in the recall of other items. For example, most of the participants who were able to recall the slogans of the brands were the participants who were able to recall the name of the brand first, which were also the participants who were subject to the TCs with the least accidentals.

5.5.3. Purchase intention-related questions and hypotheses:

The research proposed two questions and hypotheses relating to purchase intention, one regarding the major TCs and another regarding the minor TCs:

Q_{pi1}: Does the Transpositional Invariance Assumption hold true for the perception of an advertisement as characterised by purchase intention when the music is transposed across all 12 major tonal centres (TCs) of the major tonal category.

H_{pi1} (null): The purchase intention (PI) of an advertisement is invariant when the advertising music (M) is transposed across the 12 major tonal centres (TCs) of the major tonal category.

Q_{pi2}: Does the Transpositional Invariance Assumption hold true for the perception of an advertisement as characterised by purchase intention when the music is transposed across all 12 minor tonal centres (TCs) of the minor tonal category.

H_{pi2} (null): The purchase intention (PI) of an advertisement is invariant when the advertising music (M) is transposed across the 12 minor tonal centres (TCs) of the minor tonal category.

The answer to both questions is negative as the Transpositional Invariance Assumption has been refuted when the results of the analysis showed that a transpositional variance in the purchase intention occurs when the advertising music is set to different TCs.

The transpositional variance observed suggests that the TCs of advertising music play a significant role in influencing consumers' purchase intention, as this intent differed depending on the specific TC used in the advertisements, indicating that the tonal characteristics of the music interacted with participants' behavioural responses, where the simpler and more commonly used TCs with less accidentals resulted in a higher intent to purchase than the opposite TCs. As a result of this variance in purchase intention, both H_{pi1} and H_{pi2} are rejected.

These results have important implications for the understanding of how TCs shape consumers' intent to purchase a brand when applied to advertising music. They also highlight the need for advertisers to carefully choose the TCs in their advertising music throughout the ad creation process, rather than randomly select it or completely neglect it. Selecting TCs that optimise consumer purchase intention can translate into better brand awareness, alertness to advertising efforts, positive attitude, and ultimately, action-taking behaviours such as purchasing the brand.

5.6. Reflections on Research Aim & Objectives:

The main research aim was to provide pioneering insight into the influence of the different tonal centres of advertising music, as characterised by the 12 major TCs and the 12 minor TCs by problematising the Transpositional Invariance Assumption, through an interdisciplinary approach utilising neuroimaging techniques to measure and analyse consumers' attention, retention, and purchase intention.

This research has achieved its aim by successfully investigating the influence of different TCs of advertising music. By challenging the Transpositional Invariance Assumption and employing neuroimaging techniques, this research has introduced a novel insight into the complex relationship between the TCs of advertising music and consumer responses.

The specific objectives of the research were also met through a rigorous methodology that reviewed the existing literature, developing a suitable framework, encompassed EEG experiments, questionnaire analysis, and manipulation checks. The following is an account of the original research objectives and the extent to which they were met:

5.6.1. Reviewing the existing literature:

The research managed to develop a systematic review of the literature where the relevant themes from the past 50 years of the research on advertising music were detailed, categorised, and related to the variables of interest within this research. Indeed, table 2.2 shows all the relevant research with all their dependant and independent variables, as well as the main findings reached organised chronologically. This assisted in understanding three core issues relevant to this research: understanding the reasons for the lack of research as well as the lack of control over the different variables that constitute both music and advertising, expressing the need for interdisciplinary research, and finally, confirming the gap of knowledge and further focus its identification.

Furthermore, the research offered an extensive ethical consideration of the phenomenon of attention manipulation, ensuring the best practices are followed to protect participants and maintain the integrity of the research. By addressing the ethical implications of manipulating attention in the context of advertising, this research contributed to the responsible conduct of research and underscored the importance of maintaining participants' rights and well-being while leveraging the business models of advertisers.

5.6.2. Developing an interdisciplinary theoretical framework:

Due to the interdisciplinary nature of this research, borrowing from the neurosciences and music theory, a monodisciplinary framework alone could not have sufficed as capturing the complexity of the research questions and objectives required an interdisciplinary framework.

Indeed, the research incorporated several theories and principles to develop the framework in figure 2.10, which provided an understanding of how problematisation can challenge the Transpositional Invariance Assumption, which, when challenged, can justify the attempt to examine TCs individually. Furthermore, this examination of the influence of individual TCs on consumers' attention, retention, and purchase intention via the neuroimaging techniques proposed required a framework integrating classical conditioning, elaboration likelihood model, music congruence, attention economy theory, and the theory of planned behaviour.

5.6.3. Collecting relevant data:

The research design proposed here employed a comprehensive approach to collecting relevant data, aiming to capture and analyse various aspects of participants' responses to advertising music under different TCs. The data collection process involved a combination of demographical data, neuroimaging data using EEG, and self-reported assessments regarding brand information retention and purchase intention.

Most notably, and most importantly, is the EEG data of 225 participants under different TCs. This data provided valuable insight into the neural underpinnings of participants' attentional responses to advertising music, and further allowed for the examination of brain activity associated with different TCs, offering a novel understanding of their role in advertising music.

5.6.4. Quantifying how TCs influence attentional and behavioural responses:

The objective of quantifying the influence of TCs on the overall brain activity and the behavioural responses of participants was successfully achieved through the implementation of various quantitative measures and analysis techniques. By measuring EEG data, self-reported assessments, and behavioural measures, this research has provided valuable evidence regarding the specific influences of TCs on attentional engagement, brand information retention, and purchase intention. The analysis of this data and the cross-comparison between all TCs via several ANOVA tests have helped in achieving this objective.

5.6.5. Providing practical recommendations for advertisers:

Based on the results of this research, several recommendations directed to advertisers were made (found in the next chapter). These recommendations will help advertisers become more discriminative with the ad-creation stage when purchasing the rights to use already written music or commissioning the composition of original music for the ad. These recommendations should be highly practical in all advertisements that include any musical stimuli enabling advertisers to strategically select TCs that align with their intended objectives, target audience, and desired cognitive and behavioural responses.

5.6.6. Providing valuable future research suggestions:

The objective of providing valuable future research suggestions has been successfully met as several future research suggestions have emerged from this study (found in the next chapter). These future research suggestions offer directions for further investigations of advertising music, utilising this newfound influence of TCs. The future research suggestions extend beyond marketing research. Indeed, several research relating to psychology, music therapy, and human behaviour is proposed where the impact of TCs on cognitive processes, emotional well-being, and therapeutic interventions can be explored.

5.7. Chapter Conclusion:

In this chapter, a comprehensive analysis and interpretation of the research findings were presented, pointing out the role of accidentals and historic use of TCs in shaping the results of this research, as well as highlighting observations in the EEG data such as brain lateralisation and asymmetry, occipital and parietal lobes activation, and the role of high and low beta brain waves in interpreting the heightened attentional response.

Furthermore, despite the lack of similar studies with which this research could be compared, an integration of the results with the current body of literature was provided to pinpoint issues of similarity, contradiction, or alternative views.

This chapter also reflected on the research questions and hypotheses, underscoring that all null hypotheses are rejected, which means that different TCs in advertising music influence consumers' attentional response, brand information retention, and purchase intention differently, where the TCs that are most commonly used and have the least number of accidentals result in higher values for all these variables.

This chapter also highlighted how the main aim and objectives of this research were met by systematically reviewing the existing body literature, developing an interdisciplinary theoretical framework to understand the phenomenon, collecting the relevant data necessary for testing the hypotheses, quantifying and analysing the influence of TCs on the variables of interest in this research, and finally providing recommendations and implications for both advertisers and future researchers.

6. CHAPTER SIX - RESEARCH CONCLUSION

6.1. Chapter Introduction

6.2. Practical Implications

6.3. Reflections on Research Originality & Contributions

6.4. Research Limitations

6.5. Directions for Future Research

6.6. Chapter Conclusion & Closing Remarks

6.1. Chapter Introduction:

The conclusion chapter serves as the final culmination of this research journey. It aims to provide a comprehensive overview of the research. This chapter will offer a summary of the research, highlighting the managerial and theoretical implications for both advertisers and researchers, a reflection on the research originality and contribution, the research limitations, the directions for future research, and finally, some closing remarks.

6.2. Practical Implications:

The findings of this research have important practical implications for advertisers seeking to optimise the influence of their advertising music. This research offers several implications which can be applied at different degrees across advertisers' campaigns that may benefit their effectiveness if the objective is to elevate consumers' attentional response to the ad, the number of brand-related information retained and recalled, and their intent to purchase the brand. The following implications are thus drawn from the results of this research:

6.2.1. Managerial implications:

Based on everything discussed so far, several managerial implications can be offered to facilitate an optimised utilisation of advertising music through their TCs. These applicable managerial implications are as follows:

6.2.1.1. Using TCs with less accidentals:

Since the research findings showed that TCs with less accidentals, which are the most overall used in music, result in heightened levels of attentional response, brand information retention, and purchase intention, then it's advised that advertisers incorporate those TCs into their advertising music by transposing the music they plan to use to these TCs. For example, if the music selected or composed for the advertisement is in E_{maj} , which has 4 accidentals and is overall less commonly used than TCs with no accidentals, then it's advised to transpose the same music to C_{maj} which has no accidentals and is more commonly used than E_{maj} . This of course may not always be easy for several reason such as copyright guidelines that may prevent the manipulation of already written music, in which case, negotiations may have to take place to allow for a transposition. Furthermore, transposition depends on the musical literacy of advertisers as some may not be able to accomplish it digitally without compromising the quality of music, in which case, it might be required to hire professionals to accomplish the music transposition either digitally or by recreating the music, which would be costly. Although, with the fast-moving emergence of AI that can accomplish complex musical tasks, it could be possible that future AI generations facilitate the transposition process more efficiently and cost-effectively.

6.2.1.2. Considering the TC in the early stages of ad creation:

One of the main recommendations of this research is for advertisers to prioritise the consideration of TCs in the initial stages of ad creation rather than choose them by whatever is default or convenient. Rather than treating the music selection or composition as a separate entity, TCs should be integrated into the overall creative strategy from the start. This involves working closely with composers, music supervisors, advertising creatives, or copyright owners to align the chosen TCs with the intended message, target audience, and cognitive objectives desired. By giving careful thought to the TCs of advertising music during the creative process, advertisers may have better outcomes of their advertising campaigns.

6.2.1.3. Facilitating emotional associations:

Marketers can use the emotional associations to boost brand messaging and consumer engagement. For instance, TCs associated with positive emotions (major TCs) could be used to convey feelings of happiness or joy in advertisements for aimed at leveraging consumers' well-being, with C_{maj} for optimised attention, retention, and purchase intention. Contrastly, TCs associated with negative emotions (minor TCs) may be suitable for advertisements that aim to create a sense of sympathy for specific causes, with A_{min} for optimised attention, retention, and purchase intention.

6.2.1.4. Customising TCs to target specific audience:

It may be desirable sometime to lower the attentional response to an advertisement rather than elevate it. Perhaps as to not induce consumers' brand exposure fatigue, or to keep a low profile. In which case, using TCs with the most accidentals such as $F\sharp_{maj}$, B_{maj} , or $D\sharp_{min}$ would be more favourable over using TCs with less accidentals such as C_{maj} , G_{maj} , or A_{min} . It's important to stress that such practice must comply to any current or future regulations that may detail the use of music in advertising such as publicly disclosing these advertising techniques, adhering to data protection policies, and respecting consumers autonomy and consent when opting in or out of certain marketing preferences.

6.2.1.5. Conducting pre-testing and pilot studies:

It is important that advertisers conduct pre-testing and pilot studies to evaluate the effectiveness of different TCs in achieving the desired outcomes. This is generally easier in the age of social media where platforms allow for convenient and accurate testing tools. By gathering consumer feedback and measuring their responses to various TCs, advertisers can gain insights into which TCs are most effective in capturing attention, improving brand information retention, and increasing purchase behaviour. This approach allows for data-driven decision-making and helps refine the selection of TCs for future campaigns as well as confirm the results of this research through practical real-world campaigns.

6.2.1.6. Conducting split testing:

As a result of the nuanced effects of TCs on consumers attentional and behavioural responses, it's advisable that advertisers experiment with split testing to identify areas of improvement and optimisation. A/B testing by changing only one variable to which the difference in results can be attributed would benefit this objective.

6.2.1.7. Using music instead of no music:

The results showed that eliminating music in both the juice and smartphone ads resulted in the least levels of attention, retention, and purchase intention. Which was similar to the TCs with the most accidentals such as F \sharp _{maj} or D \sharp _{min}. Therefore, it's advised to keep music present in audio-visual ads.

6.2.2. Theoretical implications:

Alongside the managerial implications of this research, several theoretical implications could also be extracted as well. These implications relate directly to the theoretical framework used within this research, but also extent beyond it. The following implications are proposed:

6.2.2.1. Further testing Foucauldian problematisation:

The present research highlighted that Foucauldian problematisation was successful at challenging a deeply-rooted assumption within the literature, the Transpositional Invariance Assumption (TIA). This validates problematisation as a theoretical framework with which accepted notions could be challenged. This implies that researchers, in all fields, may find it helpful to adopt Foucauldian problematisation to defy the status quo that governs the foundations and assumptions within those disciplines. Therefore, it is recommended that researchers in music theory, music therapy, music technology, psychoacoustics, audio engineering, music education, sound design, and many other fields identify the assumptions within their disciplines in order to potentially challenge them via Foucauldian problematisation.

It's also important to stress that since problematisation leads with challenging assumptions, it's important to challenge one's own assumptions as well. Hence why Foucauldian problematisation is a continuous process that keeps furthering knowledge and innovativeness. As a result of this perpetual scepticism, future research should challenge the very assumptions of this research: relying on the 12-Tone Equal Temperament (12-TET) tuning system, the positivist worldview that reality is measurable and quantifiable, that cognitive processing of TCs primarily occurs at the neural level, and even the assumption that marketers desire to seek optimisation. While some of these assumptions may seem safe to adopt, challenging them might yield results that are not only interesting to their respective field, but even beyond.

6.2.2.2. Implication for the theory of attention economy:

As the theory of attention economy posits that attention is a scarce resource in an information-rich and message-cluttered landscape, and that businesses compete for consumers' limited attention (Ciampaglia, Flammini, & Menczer, 2015), then the results brought by this research directly foster this theory. Particularly, revealing that certain TCs with less accidentals elicit heightened levels of attentional response suggests that advertisers can strategically leverage music composition or selection to optimise attention allocation and consumer engagement. This not only aligns with the principles of attention economics, but further asserts them.

Above all, from a theoretical standpoint, the many ways in which TCs in advertising music affect consumers' attention imply that attention is not a fixed resource but rather a complex and diverse phenomenon shaped by a range of sensory inputs. This contradicts the conventional view that attention economy adopts, which focuses on visual stimuli and information overload, both of which have been the subject of much research in the past (Miller, 1956; Herget, Schramm, & Breves, 2018; Herget, Breves, & Schramm, 2022). Whereas, the results of this research highlight the significance of subtle auditory changes, such as the TCs of advertising music, in modulating the neural and cognitive attentional process. This suggests that the theory of attention economy should expand or elaborate on its definition to include the role of auditory stimuli in capturing consumer attention. Future theoretical developments within this theory may explore how auditory stimuli interact with visual stimuli (or compares against them) in influencing consumer attention allocation.

6.2.2.3. Further define music congruence:

The music congruence (or fit) within this research was examined by a self-reported pre-test. This practice may not accurately reflect what constitutes congruent music. Therefore, expanding on the theoretical implications, it is crucial to consider alternative methods for assessing music congruence within the context of advertising music. Future research could explore objective measures, such as physiological responses or neuroimaging techniques, to provide a more nuanced understanding of how consumers rate congruent music against non-congruent music.

Furthermore, considering the dynamic nature of consumer perceptions and preferences, longitudinal studies could be conducted to examine if perceived musical congruence would increase or diminish after repeated exposure to the same advertisement with the same advertising music. By tracking any gradual changes in consumer responses, researchers can identify trends and patterns that may inform more effective advertising strategies.

6.2.2.4. Further challenging the TIA:

By challenging the Transpositional Invariance Assumption (TIA), this research was able to view tonality differently, mainly pertaining to viewing it as a spectrum of TCs rather than a dichotomous binary of either major or minor tonality. Several other research disciplines also adopt the TIA as a core assumption within the scope of their worldview. These disciplines consist of music theory, music therapy, music technology, psychoacoustics, audio engineering, music education, sound design, and much more. Reimagining music tonality within these areas by rejecting the TIA could lead to a better understanding of the role of tonality and pitch designation in them.

6.2.2.5. Further interdisciplinary research:

The findings of this research highlight the need for interdisciplinary collaboration between marketing and several other disciplines such as neuroscience, music theory, psychology, economy, and many more. Such collaboration holds great potential for advancing the theoretical understanding of the relationship between TCs in advertising music and consumer behaviour.

6.2.2.6. The future of advertising music and AI:

Additionally, given the increasing use of AI and machine learning in advertising, future research could explore how these technologies can be leveraged to optimise music selection and customisation. AI-powered predictive modelling techniques, such as machine learning algorithms, can offer insights into the underlying mechanisms driving consumer responses to advertising music by identifying non-linear relationships and interactions among variables that traditional research may not allow.

6.2.2.7. Exploring further themes and theories at the neural level:

Themes and theories at the neural level may present an interesting field for theoretical exploration in understanding the effects of TCs in advertising music. By mapping the neural correlates of consumer responses to advertising music, researchers can uncover insights into the neural pathways through which TCs influence brain activity. Furthermore, exploring neural theories such as predictive coding, attentional gating, or brain lateralisation (which was detected in this research) can provide theoretical frameworks for understanding how the brain filters and prioritises auditory information, including TCs, to guide behaviour and decision-making.

6.3. Reflections on Research Originality & Contributions:

The research has proposed in the introduction chapter several contributions to be made from having TCs as the focal centre of investigation. Through its interdisciplinary approach and utilisation of neuroimaging techniques, this research offered novel insight into an overlooked area of research, a deeper exploration of the neurocognitive processes underlying the influence of TCs in advertising. The following is a reflection on the main points of originality and contributions made by this research:

6.3.1. Challenging of prevailing assumptions:

The present research's main originality and contribution has been challenging the Transpositional Invariance Assumption in the context of advertising music by problematising it, where the current body of literature uncritically accepts it or does not address it at all. Indeed, problematisation served as the central theoretical framework through which the TIA assumption was critically scrutinised. By interrogating the implicit acceptance of transpositional invariance in advertising music, this research opened up new lines of inquiry surrounding advertising music and its potential, and even within disciplines beyond marketing research.

6.3.2. Originality of methods:

This research also managed to challenge the traditional approach of researching advertising music by viewing the phenomenon through an interdisciplinary lens that examines it from several angles: marketing, music theory, and neuroscience. Indeed, the research utilised brain imagining techniques, specifically EEG, to reveal results that traditional marketing techniques, which mostly rely on participants' self-report, would not be able to reveal. And indeed, this offered new data insight that disclosed how different TCs influence attentional responses differently.

6.3.3. Practical implications within advertising:

Advertisers constantly aspire to optimise the performance of their advertising efforts. Consumer attention, specifically, is one variable that advertisers strive to capture. Based on the findings of this research, several practical implications were suggested through which advertisers can gain more consumer attention such as transposing the selected or composed music to TCs that are more commonly used and have fewer accidentals. The offering of these suggestions raises the level of scientific sophistication of advertisers and businesses as these practical implications provide actionable insights that optimise advertising strategies and improve consumer engagement and response.

6.3.4. Future research implications:

The research offered many suggestions to future research endeavours (these are detailed in section 6.5). As the area of investigating the individual TCs of advertising music is a novel one, so are most of the future research implications that stem from the findings reached here. Indeed, many of the research suggestions deal with inserting TCs in different contexts that may lead to new perspectives of the application of advertising music. These suggestions extend even beyond advertising research as they can be applied into other disciplines such as psychology, human behaviour control, and music therapy. Overall, this research offers several avenues of future research, all of which may contribute to expanding the knowledge of music's influence on day-to-day life.

6.3.5. Providing an understanding of the underlying psychological mechanisms:

While this research doesn't directly examine the psychological responses of consumers, it managed to shed a light onto many of the mechanisms underlying their psychological traits attentional allocation and information processing, memory formation and unaided recall of processed information, and decision-making. These are fundamentals in the psychology of human behaviour. The findings of this research may be of interest to the field of human behaviour, informing psychologists about the role of music in shaping much of human thought and action.

6.3.6. Validation of non-medical EEGs as a tool for marketing research:

The use of non-medical EEGs in the social sciences research is relatively new. By using Emotiv's EPOC+ this research contributes to the validation of EEG as a reliable way to measure attention within the context of advertising, and overall social sciences. Furthermore, future research that replicates this research and confirms its findings can validate the use of EEGs even further. EEG technology will also become of better quality and less costly over time, making it more accessible for researchers in various disciplines. As technology continues to advance, future studies can build upon the findings of this research, using more advanced EEG devices and exploring additional variables to gain a deeper understanding of consumer responses to advertising and other related stimuli. Ultimately, the validation of EEG in marketing research contributes to the broader field of social sciences by providing researchers with a reliable and more objective tool to investigate neural processes underlying human behaviour and decision-making rather than relying on self-report and other indirect techniques.

6.4. Research Limitations:

No research is without limitations that hinder its generalisability. The limitations of this research address the boundaries and potential constraints of the way with which it was designed. It's acknowledged here that these limitations create some issues that may weaken the research findings or restrict the conditions in which they operate. It's important to maintain this transparent outlook as the limitations will inform the directions for future research. The following is an account of the limitations relating to the research design adopted, the stimuli used in the experiments, and limitations of application.

6.4.1. Research design limitations:

The following limitations relate directly to the research design where the chosen methodology and methods constricted some of the ways with which data is collected, analysed, and interpreted:

- **Sampling and sample size issues:** the research deals with three distinct sampling issues: the sampling method used, the sample size per scenario of the experiments, and the sample of ads used. Firstly, the research used convenience sampling as the method by which data is collected. While convenience sampling is a non-probabilistic and non-random method, it allowed for the gathering of data from readily available participants. However, it comes with the disadvantage of potential unrepresentativeness or skewness, limiting the generalisability of the results. Secondly, the sample size per each scenario of TC was only 15 participants. While this issue was somewhat mitigated by the data saturation strategy of analysing the data accumulatively at every 5-participant interval and conclude that data saturation is reached once 3 consecutive rounds showed roughly the same outcome, this still results in an overall small n for each scenario experimented. And finally, the research used only two ads, one per each tonal category (juice/smartphone for major/minor). This may not capture the full range of possible influences and nuances associated with the TCs. Further research needs to be carried out with a larger overall sample size of participants and ads using a randomised probabilistic sampling methods to solidify the findings.
- **EEG data quality:** the EEG machine used in this research (Emotiv EPOC+) has only 14 electrodes. While this number of electrodes is good to measure the overall brain activity, it's not efficient or accurate when it comes to specifying regional brain activity. Indeed, even machines with 64 electrodes can't always provide accurate regional data. For this reason, interpreting the location of brain activity within this research was confounded.

- **Self-reporting on retention and purchase intention:** while the research contribute greatly by directly measuring attention via neuroimaging rather than relying of self-report, it still measures two main variables in such manner, which is flawed due to personal biases and inaccuracies in reporting (Bell *et al.*, 2018; Bergkvist & Langner, 2019). Future research should measure retention and purchase behaviour by conducting online ad campaigns using different TCs and measuring the analytics of these campaigns to gauge a more accurate understanding of these two variables.
- **Cross-cultural negligence:** the present research did not fully account for cultural differences of its participants. It relied on two assumptions: the assumption that listeners across the globe are familiar with the 12-TET tuning system, and the assumption that an auditory stimulus is processed similarly across different human listeners due to a unified physiological auditory system. While this is a biological fact that's understood and mapped extensively throughout the neurosciences and biology research, it doesn't mean that the subjective perception and interpretation of auditory stimuli cannot be influenced by cultural biases, values, preferences, and other culture-related elements. Future research should not neglect these constructs and rather involve them in their analyses more directly.
- **Anticipatory biases:** while many pre-measurement biases have been eliminated by not revealing to participants the purpose of the research prior to data collection, research participants were still aware that they are in an artificial environment designed to collect their data for marketing research purposes. This could have resulted in participants anticipating some memory tests, thus paying closer attention to details, and skewing the data from the normal population.
- **Pre-test errors:** a possible limitation to note is that there was no guarantee that the online pre-test participants watched the two full ads or with the audio turned on even though the pre-test takes around two minutes to answer. This could have resulted in inaccurate data on music congruence and purchase intention.
- **Over-control of stimuli variables:** the stimuli used in this research was controlled in every possible aspect except for the TC used. While this creates a focus on the TCs as the main variable to which different results can be attributed, it creates very strict limitations and conditions under which the results are valid. These limitations will be detailed in the following point.

6.4.2. Technical stimuli limitations:

The stimuli used in the experiments of this research have many limitations, which occurred as a result of over-controlling the musical variables of the experiments:

- **Chord progression:** the music written for this research used one chord progression for all conditions, a 4-chord sequence of the 1st, 5th, 6th, then 4th degree of the diatonic scale. While this is one of the most commonly used chord progressions, several other formats are used and may yield different outcomes. Diversifying the musical structure of the advertising music may be an interest for future research.
- **Pure harmony:** in an attempt to eliminate dissonance within each chord (or musical bar), only notes native to the chord were played over it. This resulted in a pure harmony, which means that the results do not account for the small pockets of dissonance that may occur if the advertising music included other types of music that do not have this type of pure harmony.
- **No vocals, spoken words, or sound effects:** the stimuli of this research did not include any sung vocals, spoken words, or sound effects, which limits the generalisability of the results, as many advertisements' auditory stimuli use these elements to communicate more important brand-related information and enhance their overall advertising messages (Craton, Lantos, & Leventhal, 2017).
- **Fixed tempo:** the tempo used for the music is 120 BPM throughout all scenarios across both the major and minor experiments. The tempo of advertising music has played a significant role in shaping consumers' attentional response (Kellaris & Kent, 1991; 1993; Caldwell & Hibbert, 1999; Knoferle *et al.*, 2011). Future research can examine different tempi to elicit different attentional responses.
- **Strict to 12-TET:** the music used in the experiments is tuned to the Twelve-Tone Equal Temperament tuning system (12-TET), which is the predominant tuning system used in the West as well as most regions in the world. However, future research should look into other tuning systems, especially for cultural considerations.
- **Synthetic viewing environment:** viewing conditions were over-controlled and may have appeared too clinical for participants, as real viewing conditions include background noises, ability to move freely, ability to look away, and not having to wear an EEG headset. The technology of EEGs is the best currently available that minimises the interference with participants. However, future technological advancements may bring about better features that eliminate this interference entirely, thus simulating the experiments such that they mimic real-life conditions.
- **No atonality or polytonality:** the music in this research only considers tonal stimuli. While tonal music is much more commonly used than atonal or polytonal music, future research could compare the influence of tonal music with its TCs against non-tonal music systems. Investigating the effects of atonality or polytonality in advertising music may provide insights into the impact of dissonance, complexity, and unconventional harmonic structures.

6.4.3. Application limitations:

Some limitations may occur when trying to implement the recommendations of this research into real-world scenario, such as the difficulty of transposing already written music to other TCs. Existing musical compositions that advertisers wish to use in their campaigns may be subject to copyright guideline that disallow the manipulation of musical elements including transposition to other TCs, and advertisers may have to negotiate these guidelines to be able to use the desired music transposed to the desired TC, which may be costly both in time and resources.

Furthermore, while many music transposition tools are readily available, the transposition of existing music to other TCs is musically challenging, especially when the music is complex and includes sung lyrics, which may require professional musicians to achieve. This can be particularly challenging for complex musical arrangements that heavily rely on specific tonal and harmonic relationships. Future research could explore strategies and techniques to overcome these implementation challenges, such as developing better software plug-ins, algorithms, or AI tools that deal better with the transposition of complex music and can further automate the process of transposing music to different TCs.

6.4.4. Other research limitations:

Some other limitations have occurred while researching the topic. For example, due to the COVID-19 pandemic, the researcher was not able to collect data for nearly two years during 2020 and 2021, which caused some delays throughout the research design, data collection, data analysis, and other chapters of this research, especially that the researcher was reliant on most of the research participants to be from the music festival scene, which was suspended for two years.

6.5. Directions for Future Research:

Ariely & Berns (2010, p. 284) argued that, for marketing applications, it is more important to “predict future behaviour than to understand the ‘why’ of behaviour”. While this pragmatic view often helps advertisers achieve short-term successes, sustaining it indefinitely does not advance their knowledge beyond what they already know. Therefore, it’s important to know ‘why’ things happen, so that transition to change is easier in the future.

One of the main contributions of this research is the offering of a variety of desirable research in the future in many disciplines, and with regards to many variables. By offering some of future research directions, researchers can build upon the findings of this study and further advance the understanding music TCs in daily life. The following suggestions are made to guide some of the future research endeavours:

6.5.1. Research design recommendations:

Some future research can access different areas of interest by changing some elements in the research design with regards to the topic of TCs in advertising music:

- **Research replication:** perhaps most importantly is that future research should aim to replicate the findings of this research. Replication assists in establishing the robustness and generalisability of the results and have the chance to overcome some of the limitations faced in this research. For example, it would be recommended to increase the number of ads used as the stimuli, rely on random sampling techniques, aim for a larger and more representative sample size, and utilising EEG equipment with a higher number of electrodes to provide a more detailed analysis of regional brain activity.
- **Confirming the findings:** while this research relied on self-reported measures of retention and purchase intention, future studies could benefit from conducting online ad campaigns that track and measure these variables directly rather than requesting participants to self-report on them. By employing real-time data collection methods, such as website visits from ads, click-through rates, and actual purchase behaviour, researchers can obtain firsthand and accurate measures of consumer responses to the different TCs incorporated into the advertising music. This approach would not only validate the findings of this study but also provide a deeper understanding of the impact of TCs on actual consumer behaviour in real-world advertising contexts. Additionally, incorporating advanced data analytics techniques, such as machine learning algorithms, can further enhance the analysis and interpretation of the collected data, allowing for more robust and comprehensive insights into the relationship between advertising music TCs and consumer responses.

- **Further examination of other variables:** future research can explore the influence of additional variables that may interact with TCs in advertising. For example, investigating the role of individual differences such as personality traits, cultural backgrounds, or musical preferences may provide valuable insights into how these factors shape individuals' responses to different TCs in advertising music. Moreover, exploring the impact of contextual factors such as the type of product or the target audience characteristics can help uncover the nuances of the relationship between TCs and consumer behaviour in specific contexts. This is especially important given that this research only explored one product per tonal category. Furthermore, many of the over-controlled variables of the stimuli could be examined alongside the different TCs such as tempo, chord progression, harmonies, spoken words, sung lyrics... etc.
- **Integration of advanced research methods:** technological advancements in research methods offer exciting opportunities for future investigations, especially that when cost of production of these technologies goes down, so does their price, which avails more equipment that are typically exclusive for the natural sciences to the social sciences. For example, integrating eye-tracking technology alongside EEG or fMRI techniques may offer a more comprehensive understanding of the cognitive and neural processes involved in perceiving and responding to TCs in a commercial context.
- **Examining the role of emotional arousal:** this research focused on the cognitive and subsequent behavioural aspects of consumer response to TCs in advertising music. Future research could explore the influence of emotional arousal induced by different TCs. Examining consumers' emotional variety as a reactionary response to music may offer a more comprehensive understanding of the role of TCs in advertising music.
- **Integrating interpretivist and qualitative research:** the current research focused on a positivist quantitative approach that adopted the world-view that all phenomena are ultimately measurable and quantifiable. Music perception, under most contexts, is complex and multidimensional, involving subjective experiences, meanings, and interpretations that may not be fully captured by quantitative measures alone. Therefore, future research could benefit from integrating interpretivist and qualitative research methods to gain a deeper understanding of the nuanced aspects of music in advertising and how TCs play a role in shaping subjective experiences. Therefore, qualitative research methods, such as interviews, focus groups, open-ended surveys, or ethnographical research may provide novel insights into individual experiences that may highlight overlooked areas of research.

- **Examine other tuning systems:** other tuning systems, equal or unequal temperaments, could be a subject of interest in future research. Exploring how TCs in these alternative tuning systems affect consumer responses to advertising can provide insights into the influence of different musical contexts and cultural preferences in shaping consumer behaviour. By expanding the scope beyond the traditional major and minor diatonic TCs under the 12-TET tuning system, researchers can uncover how other variations of designating music pitch may impact the perceived congruence of the advertising message across different cultures, which would influence the emotional engagement, attentional response, attitude towards the ad, and overall effectiveness of the advertising campaigns. This exploration will contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of the intricate relationship between music theory, cultural contexts, and consumer responses, allowing advertisers to tailor their strategies to diverse audiences from different cultural backgrounds and musical preferences.
- **Comparative analysis between major and minor TCs:** the current research did not focus on this direct comparison because advertisers are rarely faced with the choice of selecting one tonal category over the other due to the very distinct sound qualities and characteristics associated with each tonal category. A comparative analysis may, however, offer new insight that favours certain major TCs over minor TCs depending on the advertising message and the objectives of the advertising campaign. This comparative analysis can explore how major and minor TCs elicit different emotional and cognitive responses in consumers. It can investigate whether major TCs, typically associated with positive and uplifting emotions, have a greater persuasive effect compared to minor TCs, which are often linked to more negative or melancholic emotions. By examining the effects of major and minor TCs on various outcome variables such as attention, emotional engagement, memory, and purchase intention and behaviour, future researchers can gain a deeper understanding of how these TCs within the different tonal categories influence consumer perceptions and their decision-making processes.
- **Investigating the impact of temporal factors:** this present research primarily examined the immediate influences of the different TCs of advertising music. Future research could explore the long-term effects and durability of these influences over time, especially regarding brand information retention which might differ significantly on a spectrum of short-term to long-term retention. Understanding how the influence of TCs evolves and sustains over extended periods of time may offer novel insights that lead to further understanding of the role of tonal music in advertising.

- **Multi-sensory neuromarketing research:** music is a multisensory stimulus that can interact with other sensory modalities, such as visual and even olfactory cues and perceptions in advertising. Future research could investigate the cross-modal effects of TCs by examining how the combination of music and other sensory stimuli influences consumer perceptions and behaviours. Understanding the interplay between music and the sensory inputs may offer valuable insights into the design of holistic and impactful advertising campaigns.
- **Considering the role of cultural factors:** this study focused on a mono-dimensional cultural context, which was somewhat excused due to the fact that 12-TET has been globally accepted despite originating from Western music theory, and most importantly, due to the direct measuring of auditory perception of sound, which relies on a fixed physiological auditory system that does not differ culturally. However, this does not mean that cultural elements do not mediate the relationship between this auditory system and the perception of the stimuli. Therefore, future research could explore the influence of cultural factors on the influence of TCs in advertising music. Investigating how cultural dimensions, cultural values, and cultural preferences shape individuals' responses can provide valuable insights for global advertising campaigns and cross-cultural advertising strategies.
- **Congruence vs. incongruence:** this research controlled the congruence of the music used in the stimuli with the advertising message, however, there is some evidence showing that incongruent music may elicit a sense of surprise (Boltz, Schulkind, & Kantra, 1991; Shen & Chen, 2006), which may be associated with a heightened level of attention. Future research should consider examining the role of TCs in advertising music via a cross-comparison between congruent and incongruent music.

6.5.2. Other areas of research:

Since music is a universal phenomenon used across many disciplines, the future research recommendations are not exclusive to marketing research only. The following are a few areas of research that may draw some inspiration from the findings of this research:

- **Music therapy:** given the potential influence of different TCs on individuals' cognitive and emotional responses, future research could explore the application of tonal centres in music therapy. Investigating how different TCs may impact emotional regulation, stress reduction, and overall mental well-being can contribute to the development of more effective therapeutic interventions. Additionally, examining the role of TCs in specific clinical settings, such as individuals with mood disorders or

neurodevelopmental disorders, may provide valuable insights into personalised music-based interventions.

- **Psychology research:** building on the understanding of how different TCs influence emotional and cognitive responses, future research in psychology could explore the psychological mechanisms underlying these influences. This could include investigating the role of TCs in cognitive processes such as attention and memory, and subjective experiences such as aesthetic preferences and emotional contagion. Moreover, examining individual differences in the perception and interpretation of TCs, such as personality traits, musical background, and cultural influences, can shed light on the psychological factors that mediate the relationship between TCs and psychological outcomes. Such research can deepen the understanding of the psychological dimensions of music perception and its implications for human behaviour and well-being.
- **Human behaviour control:** further expanding on the findings of this research, future investigations can explore the application of TCs in controlling some human behaviour in various contexts. For example, examining the impact of the different TCs on attentional responses, behaviour, and performance in the workplace, waiting rooms, classrooms, and other environments may offer insights into how music can be strategically used to influence mood, attention, and productivity.

6.6. Chapter Conclusion & Closing Remarks:

Since its inception, music has been widely accepted as a powerful tool for altering moods and communicating nonverbal information. As a result, it has always had the potential to produce a wide range of complex cognitive, emotional, and behavioural responses within listeners when used in a commercial setting.

Music's influence on consumer behaviour has been studied moderately as can be seen in this research. However, the findings have been inconsistent, which made it difficult for researchers and businesses to draw any firm conclusions. The overwhelming majority of the literature on the use of music in advertising employs traditional research methods. Hence, in an attempt to combat the findings inconsistency issue, researchers have been urging future studies to invest in non-traditional research methods, and even stating neuromarketing as a highly desired one, as it has the potential to produce more precise results (Ariely & Berns, 2010; Cambra, Martínez-Martínez, & Niño, 2018; Alsharif *et al.*, 2021).

This research followed on these recommendations and offered a novel and nuanced insight into one overlooked variable, namely tonal centres (TCs). The reason for this negligence is deeply rooted in the historical development of tuning systems. The adoption of the 12-TET, which is the dominant tuning system in Western music, resulted in an elimination of the tuning differences between TCs as they all became theoretically equal. However, the influence of historical practices and instrument design configurations persisted. Instrument families such as keyboard instruments, string instruments, and brass instruments were designed based on the principles of the earlier tuning systems and retained specific characteristics associated with certain TCs. This bias was reflected in the way with which composers write music, which favoured certain TCs over others for different musical functions. Over time, it's possible that music listeners have subliminally adopted this bias into their cognitive processing, making them more sensitive or alert toward some TCs than others.

Advertising campaigns are often multimodal, which means that they do not encode their core message using a single system, but rather by using spoken language, text, typography, images, and, most importantly for this research, music (Zoghaib, 2019), and given the daily media contact with consumers, consumer attention becomes a valuable asset to advertisers. This research realised that this attention is not optimised via the advertising music, specifically not through the TCs used. From this knowledge gap and problem emerged several research questions and hypotheses aimed at examining the influence of these different TCs. The research design proposed to inquire about this phenomenon employed tools from the neuroscience to directly measure the main variable of interest, attention.

Indeed, the results showed that individuals' responses to advertisements differ depending on the TC used for the advertising music, where the less complex TCs with less accidentals, which are the most commonly used in music writing and performing, elevate attentional responses more than their opposites.

This finding proposes several practical implications where both advertising researchers and advertisers can look into the future of advertising music with a new lens through which they can better understand the role of music in advertising campaigns, and how they may influence consumers' cognitive and behavioural responses.

Despite the ever-changing landscape of society and technology, the role of music in human lives remains strong, weaved into all experiences and advancing knowledge. It is only under the collaboration between art and science that new frontiers of understanding are unlocked.

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APPENDICES

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Appendix A: Music Theory

1. Tuning systems and how they resulted in the characteristics of TCs:

These different characteristics of different TCs are a result of tuning systems (i.e. the way pitch ratios of different intervals are designated). For example, 12-TET dictates that pitch ratios of the same interval in different TCs are similar; a perfect fifth¹ in C_{maj} has the same pitch ratio as a perfect fifth in F[♯]_{maj}, which is $(^{12}\sqrt{2})^7:1$ (approximately 3:2), or specifically, a distance of 700 cents (ϕ) between the two notes when the octave is logarithmically divided into 12 equally distanced frequencies, 100 ϕ apart each (Apel, 1944; Sethares, 2005).

This ratio uniformity that is a result of 12-TET guarantees an elimination of any tuning discrepancies between different TCs, unlike $\frac{1}{4}$ CMT, which favoured major third² intervals to be tuned to the ratio of 5:4 by slightly flattening perfect fifth intervals. However, the problem that arose was that this flattening increased as the TC moved clockwise around the circle of fifths³, which resulted in purer major thirds, but other intervals, such as fourths⁴ and sixths⁵, became progressively out of tune the more accidentals (i.e. sharps and flats) were added to a TC (Laitz, 2012). This made certain TCs sound more dissonant than others because of irregular interval ratios, rendering some TCs impractical, such as F[♯]_{maj} which was deemed as "one of the most problematic keys" with its 6 sharps (Isacoff, 2003, p. 108), and was used only sparingly in specific contexts as a "remote key" (Spitzer & Zaslav, 2004, p. 202).

¹ An interval of two pitches consisting of the first note and the fifth note of a diatonic scale.

² An interval of two pitches consisting of the first note and the third note of a diatonic major scale.

³ A clock-like diagram which illustrates the relation between different TCs and provides a means to memorise their signatures. Moving clockwise around the circle leads to the fifth scale degree of the previous TC. Whereas, moving anticlockwise around the circle leads to the fourth scale degree of the previous TC (Kostka, Payne, & Almén, 2017).

⁴ An interval of two pitches consisting of the first note and the fourth note of a diatonic scale.

⁵ An interval of two pitches consisting of the first note and the sixth note of a diatonic scale.

This means that different TCs in $\frac{1}{4}$ CMT indeed sounded different from one another, even to the untrained ear or to those who did not possess absolute pitch¹. This has led to the characterisation of the different TCs by many musicologists, philosophers, and historians, perhaps most prominently by Schubart² (1806) in his posthumously-published book “Ideen zu einer Aesthetik der Tonkunst”, translated from German to “Ideas Towards an Aesthetic of Music”, where he laid out descriptions to each of the 12 major TCs and 12 minor TCs³.

These differences led composers to favour certain TCs over others. Hence, more music was written in the TCs that are more consonant, whereas dissonant TCs were generally avoided. Indeed, after Serra-Peralta, Serrà, & Corral (2021) analysed a corpus of 9,489 pieces of music from 76 different composers ranging from the 14th century to the 20th century, they concluded that G_{maj}, C_{maj}, D_{maj}, and F_{maj} respectively were the most frequently used major TCs. Conversely, F_{#maj}, C_{#maj}, B_{maj}, and G_{#maj} respectively were the least frequently used major TCs. On the other hand, D_{min}, A_{min}, G_{min}, and E_{min} respectively were the most frequently used minor TCs. Conversely, E_{bmin}, B_{bmin}, A_{bmin}, and F_{#min} respectively were the least frequently used minor TCs.

The limitations presented by $\frac{1}{4}$ CMT accelerated the adoption of 12-TET, which equalises the distances between intervals, thereby, dissonances are equally distributed among all TCs making an interval in a certain TC never more dissonant or consonant than the same interval in any other TC, and no intervals are so impure that some TCs become unusable. This elimination of tonal discrepancies between different TCs enabled musicians to use all 12 notes of the chromatic scale as TCs in either major or minor tonalities and opened up opportunities for more complex modulations⁴ (Daum, 2011; True, 2018).

However, despite the 12-TET tuning system’s attempt to unify the intervals’ frequency ratios across different TCs, many of their characteristics that are a result of unequal temperaments such as the $\frac{1}{4}$ CMT have remained associated with them in 12-TET (e.g. C_{maj} in 12-TET is still associated with purity, simplicity, child-likeness, and free-spiritedness despite its intervals’ ratios being the same as any of the other 11 major TCs) (Arnn, 1983; Steblin, 1983; 2002; Young, 1991; Ellison, 2014).

¹ Absolute Pitch (AP), or commonly known as perfect pitch, is an atypical neural phenomenon which is characterised by the ability to accurately identify and recreate the pitch of a sound without previous reference points and without necessarily being musically trained (Takeuchi & Hulse, 1991; 1993; Zatorre, 2003). AP is rare as it can only be observed in 0.01% of human population (1 in every 10,000 people) (McKetton *et al.*, 2018).

² Christian Friedrich Daniel Schubart (1739 – 1791), a German poet, organist, composer, and journalist. Not to be confused with Franz Schubert (1797 – 1828), an Austrian composer of the late classical and early romantic eras.

³ A translation from German by Steblin (2002) of the 24 TCs descriptions can be found in Appendix A, alongside more descriptions from other people.

⁴ Modulation is the change of the TC of a piece of music from one to another (True, 2018).

There are several proposed reasons why the characteristics of TCs have lingered even after adopting 12-TET as the main tuning system. These reasons include instrument design (especially the layout of keyboard instruments, and the open strings of string instruments), historical and cultural associations, habitual reasons, and psychological and psychoacoustical explanations (Arnn, 1983; Young, 1991). These will be discussed further in the literature review. But since TCs are still being perceived differently from one another in 12-TET (i.e. C_{maj} is perceived differently from G_{maj} despite its physical characteristics being similar to any other major TC), it can then be postulated that this difference in perception is also associated with changes in overall brain activity, therefore, brain response to different TCs may be different.

2. All tonal categories and all tonal centres:

The two tables below show the proposed distinction between the tonal categories and the tonal centres in this research in order to standardise nomenclature. The tonal categories that will be subject to experimentation in this research are only the major, minor, and a control no-music scenario. The tonal centres table shows the TCs within each tonal category, where vertically aligned TCs are relative (i.e. A_{min} is C_{maj} 's relative minor).

Tonal Categories			
Major	Minor	Atonal ¹	No-music ²
12 TCs	12 TCs	No TC	N/A

Tonal Centres (TCs) ^{3 4}											
Major & Number of Accidentals											
C_{maj}	$C^{\#}_{maj}$ $D_{b_{maj}}$	D_{maj}	$D^{\#}_{maj}$ $E_{b_{maj}}$	E_{maj}	F_{maj}	$F^{\#}_{maj}$ $G_{b_{maj}}$	G_{maj}	$G^{\#}_{maj}$ $A_{b_{maj}}$	A_{maj}	$A^{\#}_{maj}$ $B_{b_{maj}}$	B_{maj}
0	7 \sharp 5 \flat	2 \sharp	5 \sharp 2* 3 \flat	4 \sharp	1 \flat	6 \sharp 6 \flat	1 \sharp	6 \sharp 1* 4 \flat	3 \sharp	4 \sharp 3* 2 \flat	5 \sharp
Minor & Number of Accidentals											
A_{min}	$A^{\#}_{min}$ $B_{b_{min}}$	B_{min}	C_{min}	$C^{\#}_{min}$ $D_{b_{min}}$	D_{min}	$D^{\#}_{min}$ $E_{b_{min}}$	E_{min}	F_{min}	$F^{\#}_{min}$ $G_{b_{min}}$	G_{min}	$G^{\#}_{min}$ $A_{b_{min}}$
0	7 \sharp 5 \flat	2 \sharp	3 \flat	4 \sharp 6 \flat 1 \flat	1 \flat	6 \sharp 6 \flat	1 \sharp	4 \flat	3 \sharp 5 \flat 2 \flat	2 \flat	5 \sharp 7 \flat

¹ Atonal music will not be considered in the experiments of this research, however, it's important to mention it as a category here as it will be discussed further in the following chapters alongside polytonality, which is employing two or more TCs simultaneously (Krumhansl & Schmuckler, 1986).

² No-music is not a tonal category per se, but it's important to mention that participants in this research will be treated to a control scenario that plays no music.

³ Some TCs can be referred to using their enharmonic equivalent (e.g. $D_{b_{maj}}$ is also $C^{\#}_{maj}$, and $G^{\#}_{min}$ is also $A_{b_{min}}$), which have the same notes and pitches in 12-TET but are "spelled" differently (Apel, 1944, p. 293). This is done to make some cases of music notation more convenient by eliminating the chance of having one note repeated twice in the scale (one in its natural form and another in an accidental form).

⁴ TCs that have Double sharps ($\sharp\sharp$) or double flats ($\flat\flat$) are hardly ever used in music notation. Their alternatives that don't have double accidentals are used instead (e.g. $E_{b_{maj}}$ is almost always used instead of $D^{\#}_{maj}$, which has 2* music in addition to its 5 \sharp). Nonetheless, TCs with double accidentals are added here for completeness.

3. Descriptions of all TCs characteristics:

Descriptions of TCs by musicians, historians, poets, psychologists, and philosophers:

TC Number:	TC Name:	Descriptions
1	C _{maj}	<p>- (Schubart, 1806) translated from German by Steblin (2002): Completely pure. Its character is: innocence, simplicity, naïvety, children's talk.</p> <p>- (Charpentier, c. 1682) translated from French by Hitchcock (1990): Gay and militant.</p> <p>- (Helmholtz, 1895): Pure, certain, decisive; expressive of innocence, powerful resolve, manly earnestness and deep religious feeling.</p> <p>- (Knecht, 1792, quoted in Steblin, 2002): Cheerful and pure.</p> <p>- (Heinse, 1795, quoted in Steblin, 2002): State of nature, virginal chastity and purity, lovely innocence of youth.</p> <p>- (Gervasoni, 1812, quoted in Steblin, 2002): Naturalness and nobility.</p> <p>- (Weikert, 1827, quoted in Steblin, 2002): Cheerful and pure; innocence and simplicity.</p> <p>- (Schumann, 1835, quoted in Steblin, 2002): Simple, unadorned.</p> <p>- (Schilling, 1835, quoted in Steblin, 2002): Concerning the physical expression of this key, it appears to be completely pure.</p>
2	C _{min}	<p>- (Schubart, 1806) translated from German by Steblin (2002): Declaration of love and at the same time the lament of unhappy love. — All languishing, longing, sighing of the lovesick soul lies in this key.</p> <p>- (Charpentier, c. 1682) translated from French by Hitchcock (1990): Gloomy and sad.</p> <p>- (Rousseau, 1765, quoted in Steblin, 2002): Tenderness.</p>
3	C _{♯maj} , D _{bmaj}	<p>- (Schubart, 1806) translated from German by Steblin (2002): A leering key, degenerating into grief and rapture. It cannot laugh, but it can smile; it cannot howl, but it can at least grimace its crying. — Consequently, only unusual characters and feelings can be brought out in this key.</p> <p>- (Helmholtz, 1895): Fullness of tone, sonority and euphony.</p>
4	C _{♯min} , D _{bmin}	<p>- (Schubart, 1806): translated from German by Steblin (2002): Penitential lamentation, intimate conversation with God, the friend and help-meet of life; sighs of disappointed friendship and love lie in its radius.</p> <p>- (Knecht, 1792; Schrader, 1827; Weikert, 1827; Ebhardt, 1830, quoted in Steblin, 2002): Despair.</p>
5	D _{maj}	<p>- (Schubart, 1806) translated from German by Steblin (2002): The key of triumph, of Hallelujahs, of war-cries, of victory-rejoicing. Thus, the inviting symphonies, the marches, holiday songs and heaven-rejoicing choruses are set in this key.</p> <p>- (Charpentier, c. 1682) translated from French by Hitchcock (1990): Joyful and very militant.</p> <p>- (Rousseau, 1765, quoted in Steblin, 2002): Gay things and grandeur.</p> <p>- (Masson, 1697, quoted in Steblin, 2002): Pleasant, joyful, bright, songs of victory.</p> <p>- (Rameau, 1722, quoted in Steblin, 2002): Songs of mirth and rejoicing; grandeur and magnificence.</p> <p>- (Hawkins, 1776, quoted in Steblin, 2002): Martial ardour.</p>

		- (Gathy, 1835, quoted in Steblin, 2002): The key of triumph, of Hallelujahs, of war-cries, of victory-rejoicing.
6	D _{min}	- (Schubart, 1806) translated from German by Steblin (2002) : Melancholy womanliness, the spleen and humours brood. - (Charpentier, c. 1682) translated from French by Hitchcock (1990) : Serious and pious.
7	D [#] _{maj} , E _b _{maj}	- (Schubart, 1806) translated from German by Steblin (2002) : The key of love, of devotion, of intimate conversation with God; through its three flats [1789; according to Euler] expressing the holy trinity. [1789: D-sharp was the favourite key of the great Jomelli; therefore, he poured out his soul so often in this key. He wrote his most beautiful arias in it.] - (Charpentier, c. 1682) translated from French by Hitchcock (1990) : Cruel and hard.
8	D [#] _{min} , E _b _{min}	- (Schubart, 1806) translated from German by Steblin (2002) : Feelings of the anxiety of the soul's deepest distress, of brooding despair, of blackest depression, of the most gloomy condition of the soul. Every fear, every hesitation of the shuddering heart, breathes out of horrible E _b _{min} . If ghosts could speak, their speech would approximate this key. - (Charpentier, c. 1682) translated from French by Hitchcock (1990) : Horrible, frightful.
9	E _{maj}	- (Schubart, 1806) translated from German by Steblin (2002) : Noisy shouts of joy, laughing pleasure and not yet complete, full delight lies in E _{maj} . - (Charpentier, c. 1682) translated from French by Hitchcock (1990) : Effeminate, amorous, and plaintive. - (Helmholtz, 1895): Joy, magnificence, splendour; brightest and most powerful key. - (Junker, 1777, quoted in Steblin, 2002): Uplifting. - (Gretry, 1797, quoted in Steblin, 2002): Bright.
10	E _{min}	- (Schubart, 1806) translated from German by Steblin (2002) : Naïve, womanly, innocent declaration of love, lament without grumbling; sighs accompanied by few tears; this key speaks of the imminent hope of resolving in the pure happiness of C _{maj} . Since by nature it has only one colour, it can be compared to a maiden, dressed in white, with a rode-red bow at her breast. From this key one steps with inexpressible charm back again to the fundamental key of C _{maj} , where heart and ear find the most complete satisfaction. - (Charpentier, c. 1682) translated from French by Hitchcock (1990) : Quarrelsome and clamorous. - (Helmholtz, 1895): Grief, mournfulness, restlessness.
11	F _{maj}	- (Schubart, 1806) translated from German by Steblin (2002) : Complaisance and calm. - (Charpentier, c. 1682) translated from French by Hitchcock (1990) : Furious and quick-tempered. - (Helmholtz, 1895): Peace, joy, light, passing regret, religious sentiment.
12	F _{min}	- (Schubart, 1806) translated from German by Steblin (2002) : Deep depression, funereal lament, groans of misery and longing for the grave. - (Charpentier, c. 1682) translated from French by Hitchcock (1990) : Gloomy and plaintive. - (Helmholtz, 1895): Harrowing, melancholy. - (Rousseau, 1765, quoted in Steblin, 2002): Lugubriousness and sadness.
13	F [#] _{maj} , G _b _{maj}	- (Schubart, 1806): translated from German by Steblin (2002) : Triumph over difficulty, free sigh of relief uttered when hurdles are surmounted; echo of a soul which has fiercely struggles and finally conquered lies in all uses of this key.

		- (Helmholtz, 1895): F ^{#maj} : Brilliant, very clear. G ^{bmaj} : Softness, richness
14	F ^{#min} , G ^{bmin}	- (Schubart, 1806) translated from German by Steblin (2002): A gloomy key: it tugs at passion as a dog biting a dress. Resentment and discontent are its language. It really does not seem to like its own position: therefore, it languishes ever for the calm of A ^{maj} or for the triumphant happiness of D ^{maj} .
15	G ^{maj}	- (Schubart, 1806) translated from German by Steblin (2002): Everything rustic, idyllic and lyrical, every calm and satisfied passion, every tender gratitude for true friendship and faithful love, --in a word, every gentle and peaceful emotion of the heart is correctly expressed by this key. What a pity that because of its seeming lightness it is so greatly neglected nowadays... - (Charpentier, c. 1682) translated from French by Hitchcock (1990): Sweetly joyful.
16	G ^{min}	- (Schubart, 1806) translated from German by Steblin (2002): Discontent, uneasiness, worry about a failed scheme; bad-tempered gnashing of teeth; in a word: resentment and dislike. - (Charpentier, c. 1682) translated from French by Hitchcock (1990): Serious and magnificent.
17	G ^{#maj} , A ^{bmaj}	- (Schubart, 1806) translated from German by Steblin (2002): They of the grave. Death, grave, putrefaction, judgment, eternity lie in its radius.
18	G ^{#min} , A ^{bmin}	- (Schubart, 1806): translated from German by Steblin (2002): Grumbler, heart squeezed until it suffocates; wailing lament which sighs in double sharps, difficult struggle; in a word, the colour of this key is everything struggling with difficulty.
19	A ^{maj}	- (Schubart, 1806) translated from German by Steblin (2002): This key includes declarations of innocent love, satisfaction with one's state of affairs; hope of seeing one's beloved again when parting; youthful cheerfulness and trust in God. - (Charpentier, c. 1682) translated from French by Hitchcock (1990): Joyful and pastoral.
20	A ^{min}	- (Schubart, 1806) translated from German by Steblin (2002): Pious womanliness and tenderness of character. - (Charpentier, c. 1682) translated from French by Hitchcock (1990): Tender and plaintive.
21	A ^{#maj} , B ^{bmaj}	- (Schubart, 1806) translated from German by Steblin (2002): Cheerful love, clear conscience, hope, aspiration for a better world. - (Charpentier, c. 1682) translated from French by Hitchcock (1990): Magnificent and joyful.
22	A ^{#min} , B ^{bmin}	- (Schubart, 1806) translated from German by Steblin (2002): A quaint creature, often dressed in the garment of night. It is somewhat surly and very seldom takes on a pleasant countenance. Mocking God and the world; discontented with itself and with everything; preparation for suicide sounds in this key. - (Charpentier, c. 1682) translated from French by Hitchcock (1990): Gloomy and terrible. - (Rameau, 1722, quoted in Steblin, 2002): Mournful songs.
23	B ^{maj}	- (Schubart, 1806): translated from German by Steblin (2002): Strongly coloured, announcing wild passions, composed from the most glaring colours. Anger, rage, jealousy, fury, despair and every emotion of the heart lies in its sphere. - (Charpentier, c. 1682) translated from French by Hitchcock (1990): Harsh and plaintive.
24	B ^{min}	- (Schubart, 1806) translated from German by Steblin (2002): This is as it were the key of patience, of calm awaiting one's fate and of submission to divine dispensation. For that reason, its lament is so mild, without ever breaking out into offensive murmuring or whimpering. The use of this key is rather difficult for all instruments; therefore, so few pieces are found which are expressly set in this key. - (Charpentier, c. 1682) translated from French by Hitchcock (1990): Lonely and melancholic.

4. Note differences between 12-TET and ¼CMT:

The table below compares the differences between 12-TET and ¼CMT in terms of cent values as well as interval ratios from the base of C.

Note	C	C#	D _b	D	D#	E _b	E
Cents in 12-TET	0	100		200	300		400
Cents in ¼CMT	0	76.05	117.11	193.16	269.21	310.26	386.31
Ratio in 12-TET	$(\sqrt[12]{2})^0:1 = 1:1$	$(\sqrt[12]{2})^1:1 \approx 16:15$		$(\sqrt[12]{2})^2:1 \approx 9:8$	$(\sqrt[12]{2})^3:1 \approx 6:5$		$(\sqrt[12]{2})^4:1 \approx 5:4$
Ratio in ¼CMT	1:1	25:24	16:15, 27:25	9:8, 10:9	144:125	6:5, 32:27	5:4
Note	E#	F	F#	G _b	G	G#	A _b
Cents in 12-TET	500		600		700	800	
Cents in ¼CMT	462.36	503.42	579.47	620.53	696.58	772.63	813.69
Ratio in 12-TET	$(\sqrt[12]{2})^5:1 \approx 4:3$		$(\sqrt[12]{2})^6:1 \approx 45:32$		$(\sqrt[12]{2})^7:1 \approx 3:2$	$(\sqrt[12]{2})^8:1 \approx 8:5$	
Ratio in ¼CMT	125:96	4:3, 27:20	25:18, 45:32	36:25, 64:45	3:2, 40:27	25:16	8:5
Note	A	A#	B _b	B	C _b	C	
Cents in 12-TET	900	1000		1100		1200	
Cents in ¼CMT	889.74	965.78	1006.84	1082.89	1123.95	1200	
Ratio in 12-TET	$(\sqrt[12]{2})^9:1 \approx 5:3$	$(\sqrt[12]{2})^{10}:1 \approx 9:5$		$(\sqrt[12]{2})^{11}:1 \approx 15:8$		$(\sqrt[12]{2})^{12}:1 = 2:1$	
Ratio in ¼CMT	5:3, 27:16	125:72	9:5, 16:9	15:8, 50:27	48:25	2:1	

Comparison of cent values and interval ratios from the note C in 12-TET and ¼CMT (rounded to 2 decimals). Developed from (Kostka, Payne, & Almén, 2017).

Appendix B: Participant Information Sheet

School of Business & Creative Industries

PARTICIPANT INFORMATION SHEET

Researcher: **Omar Hraib**

Director of Studies: **Dr. Matthew Frew**

Dear Participant,

You are being invited to participate in this research study. Before choosing whether or not to participate, it's important that you understand why and how the study is being conducted. Please read the information on this sheet carefully. Please do not hesitate to contact me if you require any further information or clarification.

What is the purpose of this research?

This research aims to understand the brain's response to certain stimuli within advertisements which will be disclosed to you at a later stage. The reason for the temporary omission of certain information from you is because the research requires an electroencephalography (EEG), which is a non-invasive tool that measures the real-time activity that occurs within the brain as it reacts to certain stimuli. Therefore, **the main aim of this research as well as further information about the variables that are being examined will only be revealed to you AFTER the electroencephalography reading has been recorded** so that you are not exposed to any pre-measurement biases that would invalidate the data. You can still opt out of the research when more information is disclosed to you after the EEG reading has been taken. In this case, all data collected from you will be deleted immediately.

Who can participate in this research?

Adults of 18 years of age or older can participate. Participants must be free of any current or past neurological disorders and are able to watch and listen to the documentary and ads presented. After the data has been collected, there will be another set of questions to ensure that your data still meets the research criteria. Revealing those questions prematurely might

hint at the research purpose, hence they are only asked after the EEG reading has been taken.

Do I have to participate in this research?

Your participation is voluntary. You are free to withdraw from the experiment at any time without providing any reason. In this case, any data collected from you will be deleted immediately.

What will happen to me if I participate in this research?

The following is a detailed structure of each step of the experiment:

- 1. Research Brief & Pre-Disclosure Consent (2-4 minutes):** You will first be briefed about the nature of the research (i.e. mainly that it's a neuromarketing research involving an EEG reading as you watch a documentary with 2 ad breaks without disclosing more details about the main variables of interest in this research). Next, you will be informed about the steps of the experiment and how long each step will take. Following this, you'll be asked to sign the first half of the consent form (Pre-Disclosure Consent), which will basically ask you to confirm that you consent for your data to be collected despite not knowing the full purpose of the research, but that you'll have another chance to extend or withdraw your consent after the purpose of the research is disclosed.
- 2. EEG Prepping (2-4 minutes):** A wireless EEG headset (Emotiv EPOC+) will be placed on your scalp at the beginning of the EEG session. The headset has 14 electrodes which sit comfortably on the scalp and are completely harmless. Regular wired EEG machines require a long setup time that includes measuring the size of the head, clearing some skin patches near the ears and eyes with alcohol swabs, wearing a cap, injecting a conductive gel into the electrode holders of the cap, placing the electrodes on the cap, and finally connecting the cable to the signal amplifier. However, Emotiv's EPOC+ has a much simpler process as it does not require any scalp measuring or cleaning, or wearing a cap and connecting electrodes to it. The 14 electrodes are simply hydrated with a few drops of saline solution (water and salt), then the headset will be placed on your head, which may take a minute or two to adjust properly. You can find videos, images, and read more about the EEG headset used in this research on Emotiv's official website here: <https://www.emotiv.com/epoc/>

3. **EEG Reading (15 minutes):** After the EEG headset has been placed correctly on your scalp, you will be asked to watch a 15-minute short documentary, which will include two 20-second ad breaks. You should keep your eyes on the screen throughout the EEG reading and try not to make many movements that would disrupt the data such as turning your head or speaking to the researcher. However, natural movement is allowed.
4. **Questionnaire (4-8 minutes):** This is where you'll be asked a few questions about the ads you've watched. Further demographical data will be collected as well (e.g. age, gender, education, employment status, marital status... etc). Also, a few neurological questions will also be asked to ensure that your data is a good fit for the research.
5. **Full Disclosure Information Sheet & Post-Disclosure Consent (2-4 minutes):** After all data has been collected from you, the full title of the research and its purpose will be disclosed. You'll be given a Full Disclosure Information Sheet which has information detailing exactly what the research is trying to investigate, what the variables of the research mean, and how the results of the research could be implemented in real-life scenarios. You'll then be asked if you wish to sign the second half of the consent form (Post-Disclosure Consent) in light of the new information disclosed. If you choose not to consent for your data to be used in the research, it will be deleted immediately.

Everything will be done to ensure that you are comfortable and relaxed during the experiment. Please don't hesitate to mention if you have any questions or are unhappy with anything about the experiment.

The timeline illustrated below summarises the experiment with estimated time for each step:

How much of my time will be needed for this research?

It has been estimated through a few mock-experiments that participants will only be needed to provide 25-35 minutes of their time for the entire experiment.

Where will these experiments take place?

A Data Collection Permit has been granted from Doune The Rabbit Hole Festival to collect data on the festival site as well as the festival offices. Many of the participants will be the festival crew, staff, and volunteers. The festival will take place on Cardross Estate, Port of Menteith, Stirlingshire. A quiet room will be provided on site for the experiments. This permit also grants access to the management offices of the festival in Glasgow. The permit is available upon request if you wish to see it.

Some experiments may also take place in an office room in the main building of the School of Business and Creative Industries on the UWS campus in Paisley, Renfrewshire. However, other arrangement can be made for your convenience upon request. The ideal environment for the experiment is a quiet room to ensure no disturbances or interruptions occur regardless of where the room is.

What is Electroencephalography (EEG)?

EEG is a widely used, well-developed, and non-invasive imaging technique that measures the electrical activity which occurs along the scalp's surface. It records the voltage changes resulting from the naturally-occurring ionic current flows within the brain's neurons. This technique is excellent at picking up the brain activity as a response to different stimuli.

What should I do to prepare for the EEG session?

You should have your hair washed the morning of the session or the night before. Your hair should also be free from any hair products like gels, sprays, oils, or any other additives as these products can interfere with minimising impedances, which would negatively impact the data quality, or even completely invalidate it.

Are there any risks associated with this research?

EEG has been used safely on hundreds of millions of people all over the world for nearly a century now. No ionising radiation, X-Rays, electric currents, magnetic stimulation, intravenous injections, or any other invasive procedures are used. An EEG machine simply picks up the brain activity that naturally occurs within the brain.

What are the possible benefits of taking part in this research study?

You will receive no direct benefit from taking part in this study. However, you could experience some indirect benefits as your participation may provide information about the neural mechanisms of the brain and their impact on some of the most paramount variables that govern marketing. In other words, your contribution to this research may advance

neuromarketing and provide relevant information to the literature surrounding it, which can offer many research opportunities for perspective students and researchers.

Will my data remain confidential throughout the research?

All data collected from you will be kept confidential, and any identifying data, such as your name, will be stored separately from any other data in order to ensure you cannot be recognised or linked to the research data. All data will be stored on a password-protected device and will only be handled by the researcher and his supervisors.

Your privacy will be respected throughout all stages of the research, and you will only be asked questions that are likely to have a bearing on how the research's findings are interpreted.

What will happen to the research results?

The findings will be published in the final thesis submitted to the University of the West of Scotland (UWS), and may also be presented at conferences and published in relevant academic journals. The data published in any form will always be presented anonymously. Please inform the researcher if you would like a copy of any papers that are published as a result of this research.

How is this research funded?

This research is entirely self-funded by the Ph.D. researcher, Omar Hraib.

Has this research been reviewed by an ethical committee?

This research has received ethical approval from the postgraduate research ethics committee in the School of Business & Creative Industries at the University of the West of Scotland (UWS). Please feel free to request to see a copy of this approval.

Further information:

If you have any questions or concerns about the research, please don't hesitate to contact the researcher or researcher's Director of Studies:

Researcher: Omar Hraib (████████████████████)

Director of Studies: Dr. Matthew Frew (████████████████████)

Appendix C: Participant Consent Form

School of Business & Creative Industries

PARTICIPANT CONSENT FORM

I. Pre-Disclosure Consent (before experiment): Please tick the boxes if you agree.

1. I confirm that I have read and understood the Participant Information Sheet
2. I have had the opportunity to ask questions and had them answered to my satisfaction
3. I understand that the research data will be stored anonymously and securely and may be used in future research
4. I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time without providing a reason
5. I am an adult (18 years old or above) and agree to take part in this research

Participant Name

Participant Signature

Date

II. Post-Disclosure Consent (after experiment): Please tick the boxes if you agree.

1. I confirm that I have been provided with the Full Disclosure Information sheet after the experiment, and that I have read and understood it
2. I have had the opportunity to ask questions after the experiment and I had them answered to my satisfaction
3. I extend my previous consent, and any data collected from me can still be used in this research

Participant Signature

Researcher Signature

Appendix D: Full Disclosure Information Sheet

School of Business & Creative Industries

FULL DISCLOSURE INFORMATION SHEET

Dear Participant,

Thank you for participating in this research and dedicating some of your time to partake in the experiment. Your contribution is highly appreciated.

As per the Participant Information Sheet that was given to you prior to the experiment, the full purpose of the research was not fully disclosed. This sheet, however, will disclose all the details about the nature of this research. Please read the following information carefully before you decide if you wish to sign the second half of the consent form.

What is the full title of the research?

The research is entitled: *Tonality in advertising music and its influence on attentiveness, recall, and purchase intention; an empirical neuromarketing approach*. Please be aware that the wording of the title in the final submitted thesis might differ from the one here.

What is the purpose of this research?

The research's main purpose is to investigate if certain tonal centres (i.e. keys) could influence attention, memory, and purchase intention more than other tonal centres when used in the background music of advertisements. There are 12 major tonal centres and 12 minor tonal centres in Western music theory. The experiments are designed to test each one of these tonal centres to measure any differences in how the brain responds to them (as well as a control no-music scenario).

The 2 ads that have been placed in the documentary included background music (unless they were the control scenario with no music). One played in a major key (juice ad), and the other played in a minor key (smartphone ad).

Other research participants will have been subjected to the same experiment. However, the order of the 2 ads was randomised (i.e. juice ad then smartphone ad, or smartphone ad then juice ad). Also, the tonal centre in which the music was played was randomised as well (e.g. C major, and A minor for one participant, but F major and D minor for another participant).

Your EEG data has been collected to measure your brain activity which would show your level of attentiveness to the ads. Moreover, your recall has been measured when you were asked about the details you remember from the ads (e.g. brand name, colour, slogan... etc). Moreover, your purchase intention (or willingness to buy) was also recorded.

Why was the purpose of the research hidden from me before the experiment?

The experiment needed to be designed in a manner that best simulates a viewing of ads under the most realistic conditions possible. Therefore, the purpose of the research was hidden from you prior to the experiment so that you are not exposed to pre-measurement biases which would have rendered the data invalid. Had you been made aware that the experiment is testing the influence of the tonal centres of advertising music on brain activity prior to the experiment, you would have either consciously or subconsciously shifted much of your attention to the music and disregarded the visual aspect of the ad, making the music operate as a foreground element, which is unlike real viewing conditions.

Why was I asked if I have perfect pitch after the experiment?

Individuals who possess perfect pitch (scientifically known as absolute pitch) have a neural genetic predisposition to recognise tonal centres regardless of their musical literacy status. Hence, it is best if their data is not included in the research as it might skew the results. If you possess absolute pitch, your data will not be considered in the final analysis.

This question could not have been asked prior to the experiment as it would have hinted at the research purpose involving something to do with the brain's perception to music, possibly exposing you to some pre-measurement biases, thus invalidating the data.

How could the results of this research be implemented in real-life scenarios?

If the research concludes that certain tonal centres (i.e. keys) can enhance consumers' attention, recall, or purchase intention, then these tonal centres can be used in the composition or selection of the background music of the ad if one of the ad goals is to prompt attention, recall, or purchase intention.

Further information:

If you have any questions or concerns about the research, please don't hesitate to contact the researcher or the researcher's Director of Studies:

Researcher: Omar Hraib ()

Director of Studies: Dr. Matthew Frew

Appendix E: Pre-Test¹

Thank you for participating in this short questionnaire as a part of a Ph.D. research in marketing. This questionnaire is aimed to examine the fit/congruence of the background music of two ads, as well as the purchase intention towards the two brands. This step of the research is necessary to ensure the utility of the ads in another part of the research.

The questionnaire is estimated to take around 2 minutes to complete as it involves watching only two short videos (20 seconds each) and answering only a few questions about them.

Please note that there are no right or wrong answers. Only your own opinion matters here.

Please watch the videos with the audio turned on.

Juice Ad:

Do you think this music fits the juice ad? *

1 being the least fitting and 10 being the most fitting.

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
<input type="radio"/>									

What is your opinion on the statements below with regards to the juice brand? *

	Very unlikely	Unlikely	Neutral	Likely	Very likely
1. If I were going to buy such product the probability of buying this brand is	<input type="radio"/>				
2. The probability that I would consider buying this brand is	<input type="radio"/>				
3. The likelihood that I would purchase this brand is	<input type="radio"/>				

¹ A link to the pre-test can be found here: <https://forms.gle/Nzr4PsoYEeRtWTVg6>
Also, within this form, any question with a red asterisk is required.

Smartphone Ad:

Do you think this music fits the smartphone ad? *

1 being the least fitting and 10 being the most fitting.

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

What is your opinion on the statements below with regards to the smartphone brand? *

	Very unlikely	Unlikely	Neutral	Likely	Very likely
1. If I were going to buy such product the probability of buying this brand is	<input type="radio"/>				
2. The probability that I would consider buying this brand is	<input type="radio"/>				
3. The likelihood that I would purchase this brand is	<input type="radio"/>				

Submit

Your response has been recorded. Thank you for participating in this short questionnaire.
Your help is greatly appreciated.

Appendix F: Pre-Test SPSS Results

Music congruence:

One-Sample Statistics

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Congruence (major)	362	8.1713	1.50104	.07889
Congruence (minor)	362	8.1215	1.49297	.07847

One-Sample Test

	Test Value = 5.5					
	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
Congruence (major)	33.859	361	.000	2.67127	2.5161	2.8264
Congruence (minor)	33.409	361	.000	2.62155	2.4672	2.7759

Internal consistency (Chronbach's Alpha test) of purchase intention items of juice ad (major condition):

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.979	.980	3

Summary Item Statistics

	Mean	Minimum	Maximum	Range	Maximum / Minimum	Variance	N of Items
Item Means	2.863	2.820	2.923	.102	1.036	.003	3

Internal consistency (Chronbach's Alpha test) of purchase intention items of smartphone ad (minor condition):

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.978	.978	3

Summary Item Statistics

	Mean	Minimum	Maximum	Range	Maximum / Minimum	Variance	N of Items
Item Means	2.858	2.818	2.914	.097	1.034	.003	3

Appendix G: Experiment Materials

All juice ads (12 major TCs and 2 for manipulation check):	https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/11d8MYqvyONlp8m6JZB4hLGR9dCx5BYq4?usp=sharing
All smartphone ads (12 minor TCs and 2 for manipulation check):	https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1CvtiBnFthpXppglfywv3h8e46ucWntA?usp=sharing
Music only of the 12 major TCs (and music for manipulation check):	https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1c6pLkPIRb5asxf6NyUtiMxKu2ha5iwqF?usp=sharing
Music only of the 12 minor TCs (and music for manipulation check):	https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1o4-_9qNAbwAExGKrPKoplyM3SYWObCwB?usp=sharing
The NASA documentary, Parker Solar Probe Countdown to T-Zero for a Journey to “Touch” the Sun, from NASA’s official YouTube channel:	https://youtu.be/tvqrXBoQY_M
The NASA documentary with the ads used during the experiments:	https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1mKe1vClv5B6heTHhqSdZ9aO7j_mZuA1y?usp=sharing
Sheet music for all music used in the experiments and manipulation check. These can also be found in appendix N:	https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1PI9Nhuw_syf0o-gO7EtH2eZNA1hYF91m?usp=share_link

Appendix H: Data Collection Permit from DTRH

22 August 2022

Festival, Beverage & Property Services Ltd.

2K, Festival Studios,

249 West George Street, Glasgow, G2 4QE

Data Collection Permit

This letter is to confirm that Omar Hraib is given access to the festival site of Doune The Rabbit Hole (Cardross Estate, Port of Menteith, Stirlingshire), as well as the festival offices (2K Festival Studios, 249 West George Street, Glasgow).

By signing this document, Mr. Hraib acknowledges the following:

- Data should never be collected from the security staff on site or from the residents around the site area.
- Data from crew, staff, and volunteers can only be collected outside of working hours.
- Data will only be collected from willing participants who are briefed on the research and who provide their written consent.

The management at Doune The Rabbit Hole acknowledges the nature of Mr. Hraib's research, and have received copies of the Participant Information Sheet, Consent Form, and Full Disclosure Information Sheet, and provides this permit accordingly. Mr. Hraib will be provided with keys to an empty room in the management campsite for research purposes.

Regards,

Doune The Rabbit Hole Management

JAMMIE MURRAY

Festival Director Name

ALAN GOVAN

Project Manager Name

OMAR HRAIB

Researcher Name

24/08/2022

Date

24/08/2022

Date

24/08/2022

Date

Appendix I: Letter of Ethical Approval

21/10/2022

Dear Omar Hraib,

Your application 19569: Tonality in advertising music and its influence on attentiveness and recall; an empirical neuromarketing approach, submission reference 15708, has been approved, with conditions, by the Business and Creative Industries SEC. **You may proceed with your study provided you meet the conditions outlined below;**

Title	Comment
Who will have access to the data collected during the study and how will you keep it confidential?	Please store participant data on your UWS One Drive account.

If you wish to make any significant changes to your study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Dr John Quinn

As per the following email exchange, an unconditional approval letter was not required as long as the research meets the condition stated above, which it did.

Omar Hraib
To: PGR

Thu 11/17/2022 5:15 PM

 Letter of Ethical Approval.pdf
98 KB

Hello,

Hope you're doing well.

I have received my ethical approval letter (attached here) with one condition, which is to store the data collected on a UWS One Drive account, which I will. However, it does not state if I need to obtain an unconditional approval letter, and the email I received this letter from is a "do not reply" email, and my ethics application form doesn't show any comments made by the reviewers. Can you please advise on this? Am I required to do anything from my end other than meeting the condition?

Many thanks,
Omar Hraib
B00317651

BCIethics

To: PGR

Cc: Omar Hraib

Tue 11/22/2022 3:47 PM

Dear Omar,

You may proceed with your study provided you meet the conditions outlined in your approval letter.

There is no need to obtain an unconditional approval.

All the best and good luck with your project.

Dr John Quinn
for and on behalf of the School Ethics Committee

Omar Hraib

To: BCIethics; PGR

Wed 11/23/2022 12:23 PM

Hello Dr. Quinn,

Thank you for the clarification. I will meet the condition by storing all data on my UWS One Drive.

Many thanks,
Omar Hraib

Appendix J: Main Data Collection Form¹

Thank you for participating in this research as a part of a Ph.D. in marketing.

This form has 4 sections:

- A pre-experiment data validity assurance, which is designed to ensure you're a good match for the research. This part will be answered before the electroencephalogram reading is recorded;
- a demographics questionnaire that involves some personal information such as age, education, professional life... etc. This part, and following parts, will be answered after the electroencephalogram reading is recorded;
- a questionnaire about the advertisements viewed during the documentary;
- and finally, a post-experiment data validity assurance, which is designed to ensure you're still a good match for the research.

Please feel free to ask the researcher any questions if you're unsure about any part of the questionnaire. However, please don't interact with the researcher while the EEG reading is being recorded.

Please be reminded that there are no right or wrong answers, and that you are free to withdraw from the research at any point without providing any reason.

¹ A link to the form can be found here: <https://forms.gle/aosqucziHqH8dUZ48>
Within the form, any question with a red asterisk * is required.

SECTION 1: Pre-experiment data validity assurance:

This section will ensure if you're a good match for the research.

If some of these conditions aren't met, you will not be able to participate in this research.

Are you at least 18 years old?¹ *

Yes No

Do you have any current or past neurological disorders?² *

This includes, but not limited to, epilepsy, seizures, brain aneurysms, Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis (ALS), Parkinson's, and others.

If you are unsure what constitutes a neurological disorder, please ask the researcher.

Yes No

Do you currently have any hearing or vision disabilities that could impact the way you experience the documentary?³ *

If you are unsure what constitutes a hearing or vision disability, please ask the researcher.

Yes No

You're a good match for the research!

Thank you for answering the first section of this questionnaire. It seems you are a good match for the research so far, which means you can proceed to watching the documentary while an electroencephalography is being conducted.

As a reminder, please don't interact with the researcher while the EEG reading is being recorded, keep your eyes on the screen, and try not to make sudden moves.

This tab will stay open, and you'll come back to it after the EEG reading has been recorded.

¹ Answering 'No' to this question submits the form and disqualifies the participant, even though they will have been expected to be 18 years old or over after having read the Information Participant Sheet.

² Answering 'Yes' to this question submits the form and disqualifies the participant.

³ Answering 'Yes' to this question submits the form and disqualifies the participant.

SECTION 2: Demographics questionnaire:

Thank you for taking part in the EEG reading. The following section is designed to collect personal data about you (e.g. age, gender, education, sector of work... etc). Please answer as accurately as possible and feel free to ask questions if you're unsure about this section.

How old are you? *

- 18 - 24 25 - 34 35 - 44 45 - 54
 55 - 64 65 - 74 75 or older

What is your biological sex? *

This refers to the sex identity assigned at birth. It does not refer to your gender identity and how you personally identify.

- Male Female Intersex Prefer not to answer Other...

What is your gender? *

This refers to how you personally identify.

- Woman Man Non-binary Gender fluid
 Prefer not to answer Other...

What is the highest degree or level of school you have completed? *

If currently enrolled, please state the highest degree received.

- No schooling completed High school (no diploma)
 Diploma or the equivalent Some college or university credit (no degree)
 Bachelor's degree Master's degree
 Doctorate (PhD or above) Other...

What is your ethnic origin? *

- Asian/Pacific Islander (doesn't include Indian) African Indian
 Hispanic or Latino White/Caucasian Middle Eastern or Arab
 Mixed ethnicity Prefer not to answer Other...

What is your marital status? *

- Single (never married) Divorced Separated
 Married (or in domestic partnership) Widowed Prefer not to answer
 Other...

Which of these musical genres do you enjoy listening to you? *

Select all that apply.

- | | | | |
|------------------------------------|--------------------------------|--|----------------------------------|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Classical | <input type="checkbox"/> Disco | <input type="checkbox"/> Pop | <input type="checkbox"/> Folk |
| <input type="checkbox"/> House | <input type="checkbox"/> Latin | <input type="checkbox"/> Jazz | <input type="checkbox"/> Hip-hop |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Dance | <input type="checkbox"/> Indy | <input type="checkbox"/> Rap | <input type="checkbox"/> Reggae |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Metal | <input type="checkbox"/> Rock | <input type="checkbox"/> Country | <input type="checkbox"/> R&B |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Punk | <input type="checkbox"/> Soul | <input type="checkbox"/> Musical theatre | <input type="checkbox"/> Blues |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Other... | | | |

On a scale from 1 to 7, how well are you trained in music? *

1 being having no musical training and 7 being having extensive musical training.

Musical training in this context includes being self-taught and/or having theoretical music knowledge.

- | | | | | | | |
|-----------------------|-----------------------|-----------------------|-----------------------|-----------------------|-----------------------|-----------------------|
| 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 | 6 | 7 |
| <input type="radio"/> |

What is your professional employment status? *

Select all that apply.

- | | | | |
|---|---|------------------------------------|---|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Employed (full-time) | <input type="checkbox"/> Employed (part-time) | <input type="checkbox"/> Student | <input type="checkbox"/> Self-employed |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Unemployed | <input type="checkbox"/> Military or armed forces | <input type="checkbox"/> Pensioner | <input type="checkbox"/> Unable to work |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Other... | | | |

In which sector(s) do you work? *

Select all that apply. If you're retired, then please choose the sector(s) from which you have retired.

- | | | |
|--|--|---|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Healthcare Services | <input type="checkbox"/> Environment or agriculture | <input type="checkbox"/> Teaching & education |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Business & administration | <input type="checkbox"/> Computing or IT | <input type="checkbox"/> Transport or logistics |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Retail & sales | <input type="checkbox"/> Law & politics | <input type="checkbox"/> Student |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Charity & voluntary work | <input type="checkbox"/> Leisure, sport, or tourism | <input type="checkbox"/> Unemployed |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Creative arts & design | <input type="checkbox"/> Marketing, advertising, or PR | |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Hospitality & events | <input type="checkbox"/> Real estate & property consultation | |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Social care | <input type="checkbox"/> Engineering or manufacturing | |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Other... | | |

What is your annual income? *

- | | | |
|--|--|--|
| <input type="radio"/> £0 | <input type="radio"/> £1 to £9,999 | <input type="radio"/> £10,000 to £24,999 |
| <input type="radio"/> £25,000 to £49,999 | <input type="radio"/> £50,000 to £74,999 | <input type="radio"/> £75,000 to £99,999 |
| <input type="radio"/> £100,000 or more | <input type="radio"/> Prefer not to answer | |

SECTION 3: Advertisements questionnaire¹:

This section includes questions about the 2 advertisements shown during the documentary:

An ad of a juice brand was shown. What was the name of the brand?

If you are unable to recall, leave this field empty.

Short answer text

The juice brand was available in 3 flavours. What were those three flavours?

If you are unable to recall all three flavours, then only type down the ones you recall.

If you are unable to recall any flavour, leave this field empty.

Short answer text

What was the juice brand's slogan?

If you are unable to recall, leave this field empty.

Short answer text

Which one of these is the juice brand's logo? *

1 2 3 4 I don't recall

Do you recall anything else about the juice brand?

Feel free to elaborate. If you are unable to recall anything else, leave this field empty.

Long answer text

What is your opinion on the statements below with regards to the juice brand? *

	Very unlikely	Unlikely	Neutral	Likely	Very likely
1. If I were going to buy such product the probability of buying this brand is	<input type="radio"/>				
2. The probability that I would consider buying this brand is	<input type="radio"/>				
3. The likelihood that I would purchase this brand is	<input type="radio"/>				

¹ In this section, participants were instructed to scroll down and answer all questions about the smartphone ad if it were the first ad shown in the documentary, and then they were told to scroll back up to the juice ad questions and answer them. If the first ad shown to the participant was the juice ad, the participant was left to navigate this section in its current form without any instructions.

An ad of a smartphone brand was shown. What was the name of the brand?

If you are unable to recall, leave this field empty.

Short answer text

The smartphone brand was available in 3 colours. What were those three colours?

*If you are unable to recall all three colours, then only type down the ones you recall.
If you are unable to recall any colour, leave this field empty.*

Short answer text

What was the smartphone brand's slogan?

If you are unable to recall, leave this field empty.

Short answer text

Which one of these is the smartphone brand's logo? *

1 2 3 4 I don't recall

Do you recall anything else about the smartphone brand?

Feel free to elaborate. If you are unable to recall anything else, leave this field empty.

Long answer text

What is your opinion on the statements below with regards to the smartphone brand? *

	Very unlikely	Unlikely	Neutral	Likely	Very likely
1. If I were going to buy such product the probability of buying this brand is	<input type="radio"/>				
2. The probability that I would consider buying this brand is	<input type="radio"/>				
3. The likelihood that I would purchase this brand is	<input type="radio"/>				

SECTION 4: Post-experiment data validity assurance:

This is the final section of the questionnaire. This section will ensure if you're still a good match for the research.

Do you have perfect pitch?¹ *

Perfect pitch, or scientifically known as absolute pitch, is an atypical neural phenomenon which is characterised by the ability to accurately identify and recreate the pitch of a sound without previous reference points and without necessarily being musically trained.

Yes No

Have you seen either of the juice or smartphone ads before?² *

Yes No

Submit

Thank you for partaking in this research. Your time and help are greatly appreciated.

¹ Answering 'Yes' to this question disqualifies the participant.

² This question is asked just in case they had previously come across the music congruence and purchase intention pre-test and seen the ads. Answering 'Yes' to this question disqualifies the participant.

Appendix K: Main Data SPSS Results

Age descriptive statistics:

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 18 - 24	41	21.0	21.0	21.0
25 - 34	87	44.6	44.6	65.6
35 - 44	48	24.6	24.6	90.3
45 - 54	10	5.1	5.1	95.4
55 - 64	6	3.1	3.1	98.5
65 - 74	2	1.0	1.0	99.5
75 or older	1	.5	.5	100.0
Total	195	100.0	100.0	

Sex descriptive statistics:

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Male	101	51.8	51.8	51.8
Female	90	46.2	46.2	97.9
Intersex	1	.5	.5	98.5
Prefer not to say	3	1.5	1.5	100.0
Total	195	100.0	100.0	

Gender descriptive statistics:

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Man	101	51.8	51.8	51.8
Woman	88	45.1	45.1	96.9
Non-binary	1	.5	.5	97.4
Gender fluid	3	1.5	1.5	99.0
Prefer not to say	2	1.0	1.0	100.0
Total	195	100.0	100.0	

Education descriptive statistics:

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid No schooling completed	7	3.6	3.6	3.6
High school (no diploma)	32	16.4	16.4	20.0
Diploma or the equivalent	24	12.3	12.3	32.3
Some college or university credit (no degree)	47	24.1	24.1	56.4
Bachelor's degree	69	35.4	35.4	91.8
Master's degree	15	7.7	7.7	99.5
Doctorate (PhD or above)	1	.5	.5	100.0
Total	195	100.0	100.0	

Ethnicity descriptive statistics:

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Asian/Pacific Islander (doesn't include Indian)	15	7.7	7.7	7.7
African	22	11.3	11.3	19.0
Indian	9	4.6	4.6	23.6
Hispanic or Latino	4	2.1	2.1	25.6
Valid White/Caucasian	128	65.6	65.6	91.3
Middle Eastern or Arab	10	5.1	5.1	96.4
Mixed ethnicity	3	1.5	1.5	97.9
Prefer not to answer	4	2.1	2.1	100.0
Total	195	100.0	100.0	

Marital status descriptive statistics:

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Single (never married)	113	57.9	57.9	57.9
Married (or in domestic partnership)	54	27.7	27.7	85.6
Valid Divorced	9	4.6	4.6	90.3
Widowed	5	2.6	2.6	92.8
Separated	9	4.6	4.6	97.4
Prefer not to answer	5	2.6	2.6	100.0
Total	195	100.0	100.0	

Genre preference multiple response analysis:

		Responses		Percent of Cases
		N	Percent	
Genre_Preference	Classical	5	2.43	2.56
	Jazz	5	2.43	2.56
	Folk	5	2.43	2.56
	Indy	4	1.94	2.05
	Rock	31	15.05	15.90
	Punk	6	2.91	3.08
	Blues	6	2.91	3.08
	Disco	6	2.91	3.08
	House	4	1.94	2.05
	Hip-hop	22	10.68	11.28
	Rap	10	4.85	5.13
	Country	11	5.34	5.64
	Soul	4	1.94	2.05
	Reggae	4	1.94	2.05
	Pop	26	12.62	13.33
	Latin	6	2.91	3.08
	Dance	4	1.94	2.05
Metal	18	8.74	9.23	
R&B	21	10.19	10.77	
Music theatre	6	2.91	3.08	
Other	2	0.97	1.03	
Total		206	100.0	105.64

a. Dichotomy group tabulated at value 2.

Musical training descriptive statistics:

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1.00	51	26.2	26.2
	2.00	45	23.1	49.2
	3.00	35	17.9	67.2
	4.00	27	13.8	81.0
	5.00	21	10.8	91.8
	6.00	9	4.6	96.4
	7.00	7	3.6	100.0
	Total	195	100.0	100.0

Musical training One-Sample Wilcoxon test:

Hypothesis Test Summary				
	Null Hypothesis	Test	Sig.	Decision
1	The median of Musical Training equals 3.000.	One-Sample Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test	.199	Retain the null hypothesis.
Asymptotic significances are displayed. The significance level is .05.				

Employment status multiple response analysis:

		Responses		Percent of Cases
		N	Percent	
Employment_Status	Employed (full-time)	103	45.18	52.82
	Employed (part-time)	50	21.93	25.64
	Student	48	21.05	24.62
	Self-employed	14	6.14	7.18
	Unemployed	5	2.19	2.56
	Military or armed forces	1	0.44	0.51
	Pensioner	4	1.75	2.05
	Unable to work	3	1.32	1.54
	Other	0	.00	.00
Total		228	100.0	116.92

a. Dichotomy group tabulated at value 2.

Employment field multiple response analysis:

		Responses		Percent of Cases
		N	Percent	
Employment Field	Healthcare services	9	4.09	4.62
	Business & administration	7	3.18	3.59
	Retail & sales	64	29.09	32.82
	Charity & voluntary work	6	2.73	3.08
	Creative arts & design	2	0.91	1.03
	Hospitality & events	8	3.64	4.10
	Engineering or manufacturing	4	1.82	2.05
	Environment or agriculture	1	0.45	0.51
	Computing or IT	10	4.55	5.13
	Law or politics	5	2.27	2.56
	Leisure, sport, or tourism	24	10.91	12.31
	Marketing, advertising, or PR	8	3.64	4.10
	Real estate & property consultation	6	2.73	3.08
	Social care	7	3.18	3.59
	Teaching & education	4	1.82	2.05
	Transport or logistics	4	1.82	2.05
	Student	39	17.73	20.00
	Unemployed	12	5.45	6.15
	Other	0	.00	.00
	Total		220	100.0

a. Dichotomy group tabulated at value 2.

Income:

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
£0	7	3.6	3.6	3.6
£1 to £9,999	46	23.6	23.6	27.2
£10,000 to £24,999	97	49.7	49.7	76.9
£25,000 to £49,999	2	1.0	1.0	77.9
Valid £50,000 to £74,999	2	1.0	1.0	79.0
£75,000 to £99,999	1	.5	.5	79.5
£100,000 or more	0	.00	.00	79.5
Prefer not to answer	40	20.5	20.5	100.0
Total	195	100.0	100.0	

Descriptive statistics for the brain activity of major TCs (in Hz for attention):

MAJOR_TC AT15

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
C	15	25.5773	2.10589	.54374	24.4111	26.7435	22.19	29.42
C#/Db	15	15.7727	1.52057	.39261	14.9306	16.6147	12.55	16.87
D	15	21.1547	.80290	.20731	20.7100	21.5993	20.15	23.04
D#/Eb	15	19.4773	.49615	.12811	19.2026	19.7521	18.50	20.41
E	15	18.1527	.55538	.14340	17.8451	18.4602	17.09	18.87
F	15	23.3860	.50810	.13119	23.1046	23.6674	22.46	24.41
F#/Gb	15	14.4887	1.28451	.33166	13.7773	15.2000	12.54	16.51
G	15	24.0860	1.29125	.33340	23.3709	24.8011	22.98	27.50
G#/Ab	15	17.9707	1.08782	.28087	17.3683	18.5731	15.74	19.41
A	15	19.9713	1.00897	.26052	19.4126	20.5301	18.50	21.64
A#/Bb	15	20.8140	1.35671	.35030	20.0627	21.5653	18.54	23.45
B	15	14.9900	1.70105	.43921	14.0480	15.9320	12.54	18.74
M ₀	15	14.7760	1.71437	.44265	13.8266	15.7254	12.54	18.40
Total	195	19.2783	3.76056	.26930	18.7471	19.8094	12.54	29.42

Major TCs ANOVA at the 5-participant interval (attention):

ANOVA

MAJOR_TC AT5

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	911.038	12	75.920	39.999	.000
Within Groups	98.698	52	1.898		
Total	1009.737	64			

Major TCs ANOVA at the 10-participant interval (attention):

ANOVA

MAJOR_TC AT10

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	1628.704	12	135.725	85.760	.000
Within Groups	185.166	117	1.583		
Total	1813.871	129			

Major TCs ANOVA at the 15-participant interval (attention):

ANOVA

MAJOR_TC AT15

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	2443.969	12	203.664	123.743	.000
Within Groups	299.548	182	1.646		
Total	2743.517	194			

Tukey's HSD Post Hoc Analysis (Major TCs) – (attention):

Multiple Comparisons

Dependent Variable: MAJOR_TC_S_AT15

Tukey HSD

(I) MAJOR_GROUPS_AT15	(J) MAJOR_GROUPS_AT15	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
C	C#/D _b	9.80467*	.46845	.000	8.2319	11.3775
	D	4.42267*	.46845	.000	2.8499	5.9955
	D#/E _b	6.10000*	.46845	.000	4.5272	7.6728
	E	7.42467*	.46845	.000	5.8519	8.9975
	F	2.19133*	.46845	.000	.6185	3.7641
	F#/G _b	11.08867*	.46845	.000	9.5159	12.6615
	G	1.49133	.46845	.082	-.0815	3.0641
	G#/A _b	7.60667*	.46845	.000	6.0339	9.1795
	A	5.60600*	.46845	.000	4.0332	7.1788
	A#/B _b	4.76333*	.46845	.000	3.1905	6.3361
	B	10.58733*	.46845	.000	9.0145	12.1601
M ₀	10.80133*	.46845	.000	9.2285	12.3741	
C#/D _b	C	-9.80467*	.46845	.000	-11.3775	-8.2319
	D	-5.38200*	.46845	.000	-6.9548	-3.8092
	D#/E _b	-3.70467*	.46845	.000	-5.2775	-2.1319
	E	-2.38000*	.46845	.000	-3.9528	-.8072
	F	-7.61333*	.46845	.000	-9.1861	-6.0405
	F#/G _b	1.28400	.46845	.240	-.2888	2.8568
	G	-8.31333*	.46845	.000	-9.8861	-6.7405
	G#/A _b	-2.19800*	.46845	.000	-3.7708	-.6252
	A	-4.19867*	.46845	.000	-5.7715	-2.6259
	A#/B _b	-5.04133*	.46845	.000	-6.6141	-3.4685
	B	.78267	.46845	.904	-.7901	2.3555
M ₀	.99667	.46845	.644	-5.761	2.5695	
D	C	-4.42267*	.46845	.000	-5.9955	-2.8499
	C#/D _b	5.38200*	.46845	.000	3.8092	6.9548
	D#/E _b	1.67733*	.46845	.025	.1045	3.2501
	E	3.00200*	.46845	.000	1.4292	4.5748
	F	-2.23133*	.46845	.000	-3.8041	-.6585
	F#/G _b	6.66600*	.46845	.000	5.0932	8.2388
	G	-2.93133*	.46845	.000	-4.5041	-1.3585
	G#/A _b	3.18400*	.46845	.000	1.6112	4.7568
	A	1.18333	.46845	.364	-.3895	2.7561
	A#/B _b	.34067	.46845	1.000	-1.2321	1.9135
	B	6.16467*	.46845	.000	4.5919	7.7375
M ₀	6.37867*	.46845	.000	4.8059	7.9515	
D#/E _b	C	-6.10000*	.46845	.000	-7.6728	-4.5272
	C#/D _b	3.70467*	.46845	.000	2.1319	5.2775
	D	-1.67733*	.46845	.025	-3.2501	-.1045
	E	1.32467	.46845	.199	-.2481	2.8975
	F	-3.90867*	.46845	.000	-5.4815	-2.3359
	F#/G _b	4.98867*	.46845	.000	3.4159	6.5615
	G	-4.60867*	.46845	.000	-6.1815	-3.0359
	G#/A _b	1.50667	.46845	.075	-.0661	3.0795
	A	-.49400	.46845	.998	-2.0668	1.0788
	A#/B _b	-1.33667	.46845	.188	-2.9095	.2361
	B	4.48733*	.46845	.000	2.9145	6.0601
M ₀	4.70133*	.46845	.000	3.1285	6.2741	
E	C	-7.42467*	.46845	.000	-8.9975	-5.8519
	C#/D _b	2.38000*	.46845	.000	.8072	3.9528
	D	-3.00200*	.46845	.000	-4.5748	-1.4292
	D#/E _b	-1.32467	.46845	.199	-2.8975	.2481
	F	-5.23333*	.46845	.000	-6.8061	-3.6605
	F#/G _b	3.66400*	.46845	.000	2.0912	5.2368

	G	-5.93333*	.46845	.000	-7.5061	-4.3605
	G#/Ab	.18200	.46845	1.000	-1.3908	1.7548
	A	-1.81867*	.46845	.009	-3.3915	-.2459
	A#/Bb	-2.66133*	.46845	.000	-4.2341	-1.0885
	B	3.16267*	.46845	.000	1.5899	4.7355
	M ₀	3.37667*	.46845	.000	1.8039	4.9495
F	C	-2.19133*	.46845	.000	-3.7641	-.6185
	C#/D _b	7.61333*	.46845	.000	6.0405	9.1861
	D	2.23133*	.46845	.000	.6585	3.8041
	D#/E _b	3.90867*	.46845	.000	2.3359	5.4815
	E	5.23333*	.46845	.000	3.6605	6.8061
	F#/G _b	8.89733*	.46845	.000	7.3245	10.4701
	G	-.70000	.46845	.956	-2.2728	.8728
	G#/Ab	5.41533*	.46845	.000	3.8425	6.9881
	A	3.41467*	.46845	.000	1.8419	4.9875
	A#/B _b	2.57200*	.46845	.000	.9992	4.1448
	B	8.39600*	.46845	.000	6.8232	9.9688
	M ₀	8.61000*	.46845	.000	7.0372	10.1828
F#/G _b	C	-11.08867*	.46845	.000	-12.6615	-9.5159
	C#/D _b	-1.28400	.46845	.240	-2.8568	.2888
	D	-6.66600*	.46845	.000	-8.2388	-5.0932
	D#/E _b	-4.98867*	.46845	.000	-6.5615	-3.4159
	E	-3.66400*	.46845	.000	-5.2368	-2.0912
	F	-8.89733*	.46845	.000	-10.4701	-7.3245
	G	-9.59733*	.46845	.000	-11.1701	-8.0245
	G#/Ab	-3.48200*	.46845	.000	-5.0548	-1.9092
	A	-5.48267*	.46845	.000	-7.0555	-3.9099
	A#/B _b	-6.32533*	.46845	.000	-7.8981	-4.7525
	B	-.50133	.46845	.997	-2.0741	1.0715
	M ₀	-.28733	.46845	1.000	-1.8601	1.2855
G	C	-1.49133	.46845	.082	-3.0641	.0815
	C#/D _b	8.31333*	.46845	.000	6.7405	9.8861
	D	2.93133*	.46845	.000	1.3585	4.5041
	D#/E _b	4.60867*	.46845	.000	3.0359	6.1815
	E	5.93333*	.46845	.000	4.3605	7.5061
	F	.70000	.46845	.956	-.8728	2.2728
	F#/G _b	9.59733*	.46845	.000	8.0245	11.1701
	G#/Ab	6.11533*	.46845	.000	4.5425	7.6881
	A	4.11467*	.46845	.000	2.5419	5.6875
	A#/B _b	3.27200*	.46845	.000	1.6992	4.8448
	B	9.09600*	.46845	.000	7.5232	10.6688
	M ₀	9.31000*	.46845	.000	7.7372	10.8828
G#/Ab	C	-7.60667*	.46845	.000	-9.1795	-6.0339
	C#/D _b	2.19800*	.46845	.000	.6252	3.7708
	D	-3.18400*	.46845	.000	-4.7568	-1.6112
	D#/E _b	-1.50667	.46845	.075	-3.0795	.0661
	E	-.18200	.46845	1.000	-1.7548	1.3908
	F	-5.41533*	.46845	.000	-6.9881	-3.8425
	F#/G _b	3.48200*	.46845	.000	1.9092	5.0548
	G	-6.11533*	.46845	.000	-7.6881	-4.5425
	A	-2.00067*	.46845	.002	-3.5735	-.4279
	A#/B _b	-2.84333*	.46845	.000	-4.4161	-1.2705
	B	2.98067*	.46845	.000	1.4079	4.5535
	M ₀	3.19467*	.46845	.000	1.6219	4.7675
A	C	-5.60600*	.46845	.000	-7.1788	-4.0332
	C#/D _b	4.19867*	.46845	.000	2.6259	5.7715
	D	-1.18333	.46845	.364	-2.7561	.3895
	D#/E _b	.49400	.46845	.998	-1.0788	2.0668
	E	1.81867*	.46845	.009	.2459	3.3915
	F	-3.41467*	.46845	.000	-4.9875	-1.8419
	F#/G _b	5.48267*	.46845	.000	3.9099	7.0555
	G	-4.11467*	.46845	.000	-5.6875	-2.5419
	G#/Ab	2.00067*	.46845	.002	.4279	3.5735

	A#/Bb	-.84267	.46845	.848	-2.4155	.7301
	B	4.98133*	.46845	.000	3.4085	6.5541
	M ₀	5.19533*	.46845	.000	3.6225	6.7681
A#/Bb	C	-4.76333*	.46845	.000	-6.3361	-3.1905
	C#/D _b	5.04133*	.46845	.000	3.4685	6.6141
	D	-.34067	.46845	1.000	-1.9135	1.2321
	D#/E _b	1.33667	.46845	.188	-.2361	2.9095
	E	2.66133*	.46845	.000	1.0885	4.2341
	F	-2.57200*	.46845	.000	-4.1448	-.9992
	F#/G _b	6.32533*	.46845	.000	4.7525	7.8981
	G	-3.27200*	.46845	.000	-4.8448	-1.6992
	G#/A _b	2.84333*	.46845	.000	1.2705	4.4161
	A	.84267	.46845	.848	-.7301	2.4155
	B	5.82400*	.46845	.000	4.2512	7.3968
	M ₀	6.03800*	.46845	.000	4.4652	7.6108
	B	C	-10.58733*	.46845	.000	-12.1601
C#/D _b		-.78267	.46845	.904	-2.3555	.7901
D		-6.16467*	.46845	.000	-7.7375	-4.5919
D#/E _b		-4.48733*	.46845	.000	-6.0601	-2.9145
E		-3.16267*	.46845	.000	-4.7355	-1.5899
F		-8.39600*	.46845	.000	-9.9688	-6.8232
F#/G _b		.50133	.46845	.997	-1.0715	2.0741
G		-9.09600*	.46845	.000	-10.6688	-7.5232
G#/A _b		-2.98067*	.46845	.000	-4.5535	-1.4079
A		-4.98133*	.46845	.000	-6.5541	-3.4085
A#/B _b		-5.82400*	.46845	.000	-7.3968	-4.2512
M ₀		.21400	.46845	1.000	-1.3588	1.7868
M ₀		C	-10.80133*	.46845	.000	-12.3741
	C#/D _b	-.99667	.46845	.644	-2.5695	.5761
	D	-6.37867*	.46845	.000	-7.9515	-4.8059
	D#/E _b	-4.70133*	.46845	.000	-6.2741	-3.1285
	E	-3.37667*	.46845	.000	-4.9495	-1.8039
	F	-8.61000*	.46845	.000	-10.1828	-7.0372
	F#/G _b	.28733	.46845	1.000	-1.2855	1.8601
	G	-9.31000*	.46845	.000	-10.8828	-7.7372
	G#/A _b	-3.19467*	.46845	.000	-4.7675	-1.6219
	A	-5.19533*	.46845	.000	-6.7681	-3.6225
	A#/B _b	-6.03800*	.46845	.000	-7.6108	-4.4652
	B	-.21400	.46845	1.000	-1.7868	1.3588

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Descriptive statistics for the brain activity of minor TCs (in Hz for attention):

MINOR TCs AT15

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
C	15	19.4493	.52902	.13659	19.1564	19.7423	18.40	20.45
C#/D _b	15	18.1287	.49723	.12839	17.8533	18.4040	17.05	18.74
D	15	23.3393	.48475	.12516	23.0709	23.6078	22.54	24.20
D#/E _b	15	14.4973	1.28887	.33278	13.7836	15.2111	12.50	16.48
E	15	24.0493	1.30116	.33596	23.3288	24.7699	22.84	27.40
F	15	17.9213	1.11869	.28884	17.3018	18.5408	15.26	19.40
F#/G _b	15	19.8033	.95916	.24765	19.2722	20.3345	18.56	21.65
G	15	20.7667	1.45344	.37528	19.9618	21.5716	18.20	23.25
G#/A _b	15	15.2593	1.97123	.50897	14.1677	16.3510	12.45	18.88
A	15	25.4953	1.60137	.41347	24.6085	26.3821	22.62	28.00
A#/B _b	15	15.8133	1.57426	.40647	14.9415	16.6851	12.54	17.00
B	15	21.1953	.76192	.19673	20.7734	21.6173	20.14	22.54
M ₀	15	14.7607	1.75289	.45259	13.7899	15.7314	12.34	18.65
Total	195	19.2676	3.71266	.26587	18.7433	19.7920	12.34	28.00

Minor TCs ANOVA at the 5-participant interval (attention):

ANOVA

MINOR_TC_s_AT5

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	831.161	12	69.263	45.927	.000
Within Groups	78.423	52	1.508		
Total	909.584	64			

Minor TCs ANOVA at the 10-participant interval (attention):

ANOVA

MINOR_TC_s_AT10

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	1560.657	12	130.055	90.405	.000
Within Groups	168.313	117	1.439		
Total	1728.970	129			

Minor TCs ANOVA at the 15-participant interval (attention):

ANOVA

MINOR_TC_s_AT15

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	2380.315	12	198.360	122.900	.000
Within Groups	293.745	182	1.614		
Total	2674.061	194			

Tukey's HSD Post Hoc Analysis (Minor TCs) – (attention):

Multiple Comparisons

Dependent Variable: MINOR_TC_s_AT15

Tukey HSD

(I) MINOR_GROUPS_AT15	(J) MINOR_GROUPS_AT15	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
C	C#/Db	1.32067	.46389	.190	-.2368	2.8781
	D	-3.89000*	.46389	.000	-5.4475	-2.3325
	D#/Eb	4.95200*	.46389	.000	3.3945	6.5095
	E	-4.60000*	.46389	.000	-6.1575	-3.0425
	F	1.52800	.46389	.060	-.0295	3.0855
	F#/Gb	-.35400	.46389	1.000	-1.9115	1.2035
	G	-1.31733	.46389	.194	-2.8748	.2401
	G#/Ab	4.19000*	.46389	.000	2.6325	5.7475
	A	-6.04600*	.46389	.000	-7.6035	-4.4885
	A#/Bb	3.63600*	.46389	.000	2.0785	5.1935
C#/Db	B	-1.74600*	.46389	.014	-3.3035	-.1885
	M0	4.68867*	.46389	.000	3.1312	6.2461
	C	-1.32067	.46389	.190	-2.8781	.2368
	D	-5.21067*	.46389	.000	-6.7681	-3.6532
	D#/Eb	3.63133*	.46389	.000	2.0739	5.1888
	E	-5.92067*	.46389	.000	-7.4781	-4.3632
	F	.20733	.46389	1.000	-1.3501	1.7648
	F#/Gb	-1.67467*	.46389	.023	-3.2321	-.1172
	G	-2.63800*	.46389	.000	-4.1955	-1.0805
G#/Ab	2.86933*	.46389	.000	1.3119	4.4268	

	A	-7.36667*	.46389	.000	-8.9241	-5.8092
	A#/Bb	2.31533*	.46389	.000	.7579	3.8728
	B	-3.06667*	.46389	.000	-4.6241	-1.5092
	M ₀	3.36800*	.46389	.000	1.8105	4.9255
D	C	3.89000*	.46389	.000	2.3325	5.4475
	C#/Db	5.21067*	.46389	.000	3.6532	6.7681
	D#/Eb	8.84200*	.46389	.000	7.2845	10.3995
	E	-.71000	.46389	.947	-2.2675	.8475
	F	5.41800*	.46389	.000	3.8605	6.9755
	F#/Gb	3.53600*	.46389	.000	1.9785	5.0935
	G	2.57267*	.46389	.000	1.0152	4.1301
	G#/Ab	8.08000*	.46389	.000	6.5225	9.6375
	A	-2.15600*	.46389	.000	-3.7135	-.5985
	A#/Bb	7.52600*	.46389	.000	5.9685	9.0835
	B	2.14400*	.46389	.001	.5865	3.7015
	M ₀	8.57867*	.46389	.000	7.0212	10.1361
D#/Eb	C	-4.95200*	.46389	.000	-6.5095	-3.3945
	C#/Db	-3.63133*	.46389	.000	-5.1888	-2.0739
	D	-8.84200*	.46389	.000	-10.3995	-7.2845
	E	-9.55200*	.46389	.000	-11.1095	-7.9945
	F	-3.42400*	.46389	.000	-4.9815	-1.8665
	F#/Gb	-5.30600*	.46389	.000	-6.8635	-3.7485
	G	-6.26933*	.46389	.000	-7.8268	-4.7119
	G#/Ab	-.76200	.46389	.914	-2.3195	.7955
	A	-10.99800*	.46389	.000	-12.5555	-9.4405
	A#/Bb	-1.31600	.46389	.195	-2.8735	.2415
	B	-6.69800*	.46389	.000	-8.2555	-5.1405
	M ₀	-.26333	.46389	1.000	-1.8208	1.2941
E	C	4.60000*	.46389	.000	3.0425	6.1575
	C#/Db	5.92067*	.46389	.000	4.3632	7.4781
	D	.71000	.46389	.947	-.8475	2.2675
	D#/Eb	9.55200*	.46389	.000	7.9945	11.1095
	F	6.12800*	.46389	.000	4.5705	7.6855
	F#/Gb	4.24600*	.46389	.000	2.6885	5.8035
	G	3.28267*	.46389	.000	1.7252	4.8401
	G#/Ab	8.79000*	.46389	.000	7.2325	10.3475
	A	-1.44600	.46389	.098	-3.0035	.1115
	A#/Bb	8.23600*	.46389	.000	6.6785	9.7935
	B	2.85400*	.46389	.000	1.2965	4.4115
	M ₀	9.28867*	.46389	.000	7.7312	10.8461
F	C	-1.52800	.46389	.060	-3.0855	.0295
	C#/Db	-.20733	.46389	1.000	-1.7648	1.3501
	D	-5.41800*	.46389	.000	-6.9755	-3.8605
	D#/Eb	3.42400*	.46389	.000	1.8665	4.9815
	E	-6.12800*	.46389	.000	-7.6855	-4.5705
	F#/Gb	-1.88200*	.46389	.005	-3.4395	-.3245
	G	-2.84533*	.46389	.000	-4.4028	-1.2879
	G#/Ab	2.66200*	.46389	.000	1.1045	4.2195
	A	-7.57400*	.46389	.000	-9.1315	-6.0165
	A#/Bb	2.10800*	.46389	.001	.5505	3.6655
	B	-3.27400*	.46389	.000	-4.8315	-1.7165
	M ₀	3.16067*	.46389	.000	1.6032	4.7181
F#/Gb	C	.35400	.46389	1.000	-1.2035	1.9115
	C#/Db	1.67467*	.46389	.023	.1172	3.2321
	D	-3.53600*	.46389	.000	-5.0935	-1.9785
	D#/Eb	5.30600*	.46389	.000	3.7485	6.8635
	E	-4.24600*	.46389	.000	-5.8035	-2.6885
	F	1.88200*	.46389	.005	.3245	3.4395
	G	-.96333	.46389	.680	-2.5208	.5941
	G#/Ab	4.54400*	.46389	.000	2.9865	6.1015
	A	-5.69200*	.46389	.000	-7.2495	-4.1345
	A#/Bb	3.99000*	.46389	.000	2.4325	5.5475

	B	-1.39200	.46389	.132	-2.9495	.1655
	M ₀	5.04267*	.46389	.000	3.4852	6.6001
G	C	1.31733	.46389	.194	-.2401	2.8748
	C#/D _b	2.63800*	.46389	.000	1.0805	4.1955
	D	-2.57267*	.46389	.000	-4.1301	-1.0152
	D#/E _b	6.26933*	.46389	.000	4.7119	7.8268
	E	-3.28267*	.46389	.000	-4.8401	-1.7252
	F	2.84533*	.46389	.000	1.2879	4.4028
	F#/G _b	.96333	.46389	.680	-.5941	2.5208
	G#/A _b	5.50733*	.46389	.000	3.9499	7.0648
	A	-4.72867*	.46389	.000	-6.2861	-3.1712
	A#/B _b	4.95333*	.46389	.000	3.3959	6.5108
	B	-.42867	.46389	.999	-1.9861	1.1288
	M ₀	6.00600*	.46389	.000	4.4485	7.5635
	G#/A _b	C	-4.19000*	.46389	.000	-5.7475
C#/D _b		-2.86933*	.46389	.000	-4.4268	-1.3119
D		-8.08000*	.46389	.000	-9.6375	-6.5225
D#/E _b		.76200	.46389	.914	-.7955	2.3195
E		-8.79000*	.46389	.000	-10.3475	-7.2325
F		-2.66200*	.46389	.000	-4.2195	-1.1045
F#/G _b		-4.54400*	.46389	.000	-6.1015	-2.9865
G		-5.50733*	.46389	.000	-7.0648	-3.9499
A		-10.23600*	.46389	.000	-11.7935	-8.6785
A#/B _b		-.55400	.46389	.993	-2.1115	1.0035
B		-5.93600*	.46389	.000	-7.4935	-4.3785
M ₀		.49867	.46389	.997	-1.0588	2.0561
A		C	6.04600*	.46389	.000	4.4885
	C#/D _b	7.36667*	.46389	.000	5.8092	8.9241
	D	2.15600*	.46389	.000	.5985	3.7135
	D#/E _b	10.99800*	.46389	.000	9.4405	12.5555
	E	1.44600	.46389	.098	-.1115	3.0035
	F	7.57400*	.46389	.000	6.0165	9.1315
	F#/G _b	5.69200*	.46389	.000	4.1345	7.2495
	G	4.72867*	.46389	.000	3.1712	6.2861
	G#/A _b	10.23600*	.46389	.000	8.6785	11.7935
	A#/B _b	9.68200*	.46389	.000	8.1245	11.2395
	B	4.30000*	.46389	.000	2.7425	5.8575
	M ₀	10.73467*	.46389	.000	9.1772	12.2921
	A#/B _b	C	-3.63600*	.46389	.000	-5.1935
C#/D _b		-2.31533*	.46389	.000	-3.8728	-.7579
D		-7.52600*	.46389	.000	-9.0835	-5.9685
D#/E _b		1.31600	.46389	.195	-.2415	2.8735
E		-8.23600*	.46389	.000	-9.7935	-6.6785
F		-2.10800*	.46389	.001	-3.6655	-.5505
F#/G _b		-3.99000*	.46389	.000	-5.5475	-2.4325
G		-4.95333*	.46389	.000	-6.5108	-3.3959
G#/A _b		.55400	.46389	.993	-1.0035	2.1115
A		-9.68200*	.46389	.000	-11.2395	-8.1245
B		-5.38200*	.46389	.000	-6.9395	-3.8245
M ₀		1.05267	.46389	.542	-.5048	2.6101
B		C	1.74600*	.46389	.014	.1885
	C#/D _b	3.06667*	.46389	.000	1.5092	4.6241
	D	-2.14400*	.46389	.001	-3.7015	-.5865
	D#/E _b	6.69800*	.46389	.000	5.1405	8.2555
	E	-2.85400*	.46389	.000	-4.4115	-1.2965
	F	3.27400*	.46389	.000	1.7165	4.8315
	F#/G _b	1.39200	.46389	.132	-.1655	2.9495
	G	.42867	.46389	.999	-1.1288	1.9861
	G#/A _b	5.93600*	.46389	.000	4.3785	7.4935
	A	-4.30000*	.46389	.000	-5.8575	-2.7425
	A#/B _b	5.38200*	.46389	.000	3.8245	6.9395
	M ₀	6.43467*	.46389	.000	4.8772	7.9921

M0	C	-4.68867*	.46389	.000	-6.2461	-3.1312
	C#/Db	-3.36800*	.46389	.000	-4.9255	-1.8105
	D	-8.57867*	.46389	.000	-10.1361	-7.0212
	D#/Eb	.26333	.46389	1.000	-1.2941	1.8208
	E	-9.28867*	.46389	.000	-10.8461	-7.7312
	F	-3.16067*	.46389	.000	-4.7181	-1.6032
	F#/Gb	-5.04267*	.46389	.000	-6.6001	-3.4852
	G	-6.00600*	.46389	.000	-7.5635	-4.4485
	G#/Ab	-.49867	.46389	.997	-2.0561	1.0588
	A	-10.73467*	.46389	.000	-12.2921	-9.1772
	A#/Bb	-1.05267	.46389	.542	-2.6101	.5048
	B	-6.43467*	.46389	.000	-7.9921	-4.8772

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Descriptive statistics for the brand information retained under major TCs (Retention):

Brand information retention of the juice ad (major condition)

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
C	15	3.9333	1.79151	.46257	2.9412	4.9254	1.00	7.00
C#/Db	15	1.0000	1.46385	.37796	.1893	1.8107	.00	5.00
D	15	2.2667	1.79151	.46257	1.2746	3.2588	.00	6.00
D#/Eb	15	1.4667	1.12546	.29059	.8434	2.0899	.00	3.00
E	15	1.1333	1.24595	.32170	.4434	1.8233	.00	4.00
F	15	3.0000	1.13389	.29277	2.3721	3.6279	1.00	5.00
F#/Gb	15	.8000	1.14642	.29601	.1651	1.4349	.00	4.00
G	15	3.2000	1.61245	.41633	2.3071	4.0929	1.00	6.00
G#/Ab	15	1.4000	1.24212	.32071	.7121	2.0879	.00	4.00
A	15	1.8667	1.30201	.33618	1.1456	2.5877	.00	4.00
A#/Bb	15	3.0667	1.43759	.37118	2.2706	3.8628	1.00	6.00
B	15	.9333	1.03280	.26667	.3614	1.5053	.00	3.00
M0	15	1.2667	.88372	.22817	.7773	1.7561	.00	3.00
Total	195	1.9487	1.64581	.11786	1.7163	2.1812	.00	7.00

Major TCs ANOVA (Retention):

ANOVA

Brand information retention of the juice ad (major condition)

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	193.221	12	16.102	8.820	.000
Within Groups	332.267	182	1.826		
Total	525.487	194			

Tukey's HSD Post Hoc Analysis (Major TCs) – (Retention):

Multiple Comparisons

Dependent Variable: Brand information retention of the juice ad (major condition)

Tukey HSD

(I) MAJOR_GROUPS_AT15	(J) MAJOR_GROUPS_AT15	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
C	C#/Db	2.93333*	.49337	.000	1.2769	4.5898
	D	1.66667*	.49337	.067	.0102	3.3231
	D#/Eb	2.46667*	.49337	.000	.8102	4.1231
	E	2.80000*	.49337	.000	1.1435	4.4565
	F	.93333	.49337	.798	-.7231	2.5898

	F#/Gb	3.13333*	.49337	.000	1.4769	4.7898
	G	.73333	.49337	.957	-.9231	2.3898
	G#/Ab	2.53333*	.49337	.000	.8769	4.1898
	A	2.06667*	.49337	.003	.4102	3.7231
	A#/Bb	.86667	.49337	.868	-.7898	2.5231
	B	3.00000*	.49337	.000	1.3435	4.6565
	M0	2.66667*	.49337	.000	1.0102	4.3231
C#/Db	C	-2.93333*	.49337	.000	-4.5898	-1.2769
	D	-1.26667	.49337	.338	-2.9231	.3898
	D#/Eb	-.46667	.49337	.999	-2.1231	1.1898
	E	-.13333	.49337	1.000	-1.7898	1.5231
	F	-2.00000*	.49337	.005	-3.6565	-.3435
	F#/Gb	.20000	.49337	1.000	-1.4565	1.8565
	G	-2.20000*	.49337	.001	-3.8565	-.5435
	G#/Ab	-.40000	.49337	1.000	-2.0565	1.2565
	A	-.86667	.49337	.868	-2.5231	.7898
	A#/Bb	-2.06667*	.49337	.003	-3.7231	-.4102
	B	.06667	.49337	1.000	-1.5898	1.7231
	M0	-.26667	.49337	1.000	-1.9231	1.3898
	D	C	-1.66667*	.49337	.067	-3.3231
C#/Db		1.26667	.49337	.338	-.3898	2.9231
D#/Eb		.80000	.49337	.921	-.8565	2.4565
E		1.13333	.49337	.522	-.5231	2.7898
F		-.73333	.49337	.957	-2.3898	.9231
F#/Gb		1.46667	.49337	.142	-.1898	3.1231
G		-.93333	.49337	.798	-2.5898	.7231
G#/Ab		.86667	.49337	.868	-.7898	2.5231
A		.40000	.49337	1.000	-1.2565	2.0565
A#/Bb		-.80000	.49337	.921	-2.4565	.8565
B		1.33333	.49337	.260	-.3231	2.9898
M0		1.00000	.49337	.714	-.6565	2.6565
D#/Eb		C	-2.46667*	.49337	.000	-4.1231
	C#/Db	.46667	.49337	.999	-1.1898	2.1231
	D	-.80000	.49337	.921	-2.4565	.8565
	E	.33333	.49337	1.000	-1.3231	1.9898
	F	-1.53333	.49337	.100	-3.1898	.1231
	F#/Gb	.66667	.49337	.980	-.9898	2.3231
	G	-1.73333*	.49337	.031	-3.3898	-.0769
	G#/Ab	.06667	.49337	1.000	-1.5898	1.7231
	A	-.40000	.49337	1.000	-2.0565	1.2565
	A#/Bb	-1.60000	.49337	.070	-3.2565	.0565
	B	.53333	.49337	.997	-1.1231	2.1898
	M0	.20000	.49337	1.000	-1.4565	1.8565
	E	C	-2.80000*	.49337	.000	-4.4565
C#/Db		.13333	.49337	1.000	-1.5231	1.7898
D		-1.13333	.49337	.522	-2.7898	.5231
D#/Eb		-.33333	.49337	1.000	-1.9898	1.3231
F		-1.86667*	.49337	.013	-3.5231	-.2102
F#/Gb		.33333	.49337	1.000	-1.3231	1.9898
G		-2.06667*	.49337	.003	-3.7231	-.4102
G#/Ab		-.26667	.49337	1.000	-1.9231	1.3898
A		-.73333	.49337	.957	-2.3898	.9231
A#/Bb		-1.93333*	.49337	.008	-3.5898	-.2769
B		.20000	.49337	1.000	-1.4565	1.8565
M0		-.13333	.49337	1.000	-1.7898	1.5231
F		C	-.93333	.49337	.798	-2.5898
	C#/Db	2.00000*	.49337	.005	.3435	3.6565
	D	.73333	.49337	.957	-.9231	2.3898
	D#/Eb	1.53333	.49337	.100	-.1231	3.1898
	E	1.86667*	.49337	.013	.2102	3.5231
	F#/Gb	2.20000*	.49337	.001	.5435	3.8565
	G	-.20000	.49337	1.000	-1.8565	1.4565

	G#/Ab	1.60000	.49337	.070	-.0565	3.2565
	A	1.13333	.49337	.522	-.5231	2.7898
	A#/Bb	-.06667	.49337	1.000	-1.7231	1.5898
	B	2.06667*	.49337	.003	.4102	3.7231
	M0	1.73333*	.49337	.031	.0769	3.3898
F#/Gb	C	-3.13333*	.49337	.000	-4.7898	-1.4769
	C#/Db	-.20000	.49337	1.000	-1.8565	1.4565
	D	-1.46667	.49337	.142	-3.1231	.1898
	D#/Eb	-.66667	.49337	.980	-2.3231	.9898
	E	-.33333	.49337	1.000	-1.9898	1.3231
	F	-2.20000*	.49337	.001	-3.8565	-.5435
	G	-2.40000*	.49337	.000	-4.0565	-.7435
	G#/Ab	-.60000	.49337	.992	-2.2565	1.0565
	A	-1.06667	.49337	.620	-2.7231	.5898
	A#/Bb	-2.26667*	.49337	.001	-3.9231	-.6102
	B	-.13333	.49337	1.000	-1.7898	1.5231
	M0	-.46667	.49337	.999	-2.1231	1.1898
G	C	-.73333	.49337	.957	-2.3898	.9231
	C#/Db	2.20000*	.49337	.001	.5435	3.8565
	D	.93333	.49337	.798	-.7231	2.5898
	D#/Eb	1.73333*	.49337	.031	.0769	3.3898
	E	2.06667*	.49337	.003	.4102	3.7231
	F	.20000	.49337	1.000	-1.4565	1.8565
	F#/Gb	2.40000*	.49337	.000	.7435	4.0565
	G#/Ab	1.80000*	.49337	.020	.1435	3.4565
	A	1.33333	.49337	.260	-.3231	2.9898
	A#/Bb	.13333	.49337	1.000	-1.5231	1.7898
	B	2.26667*	.49337	.001	.6102	3.9231
	M0	1.93333*	.49337	.008	.2769	3.5898
G#/Ab	C	-2.53333*	.49337	.000	-4.1898	-.8769
	C#/Db	.40000	.49337	1.000	-1.2565	2.0565
	D	-.86667	.49337	.868	-2.5231	.7898
	D#/Eb	-.06667	.49337	1.000	-1.7231	1.5898
	E	.26667	.49337	1.000	-1.3898	1.9231
	F	-1.60000	.49337	.070	-3.2565	.0565
	F#/Gb	.60000	.49337	.992	-1.0565	2.2565
	G	-1.80000*	.49337	.020	-3.4565	-.1435
	A	-.46667	.49337	.999	-2.1231	1.1898
	A#/Bb	-1.66667*	.49337	.047	-3.3231	-.0102
	B	.46667	.49337	.999	-1.1898	2.1231
	M0	.13333	.49337	1.000	-1.5231	1.7898
A	C	-2.06667*	.49337	.003	-3.7231	-.4102
	C#/Db	.86667	.49337	.868	-.7898	2.5231
	D	-.40000	.49337	1.000	-2.0565	1.2565
	D#/Eb	.40000	.49337	1.000	-1.2565	2.0565
	E	.73333	.49337	.957	-.9231	2.3898
	F	-1.13333	.49337	.522	-2.7898	.5231
	F#/Gb	1.06667	.49337	.620	-.5898	2.7231
	G	-1.33333	.49337	.260	-2.9898	.3231
	G#/Ab	.46667	.49337	.999	-1.1898	2.1231
	A#/Bb	-1.20000	.49337	.426	-2.8565	.4565
	B	.93333	.49337	.798	-.7231	2.5898
	M0	.60000	.49337	.992	-1.0565	2.2565
A#/Bb	C	-.86667	.49337	.868	-2.5231	.7898
	C#/Db	2.06667*	.49337	.003	.4102	3.7231
	D	.80000	.49337	.921	-.8565	2.4565
	D#/Eb	1.60000	.49337	.070	-.0565	3.2565
	E	1.93333*	.49337	.008	.2769	3.5898
	F	.06667	.49337	1.000	-1.5898	1.7231
	F#/Gb	2.26667*	.49337	.001	.6102	3.9231
	G	-.13333	.49337	1.000	-1.7898	1.5231
	G#/Ab	1.66667*	.49337	.047	.0102	3.3231
	A	1.20000	.49337	.426	-.4565	2.8565

	B	2.13333*	.49337	.002	.4769	3.7898
	MO	1.80000*	.49337	.020	.1435	3.4565
B	C	-3.00000*	.49337	.000	-4.6565	-1.3435
	C#/Db	-.06667	.49337	1.000	-1.7231	1.5898
	D	-1.33333	.49337	.260	-2.9898	.3231
	D#/Eb	-.53333	.49337	.997	-2.1898	1.1231
	E	-.20000	.49337	1.000	-1.8565	1.4565
	F	-2.06667*	.49337	.003	-3.7231	-.4102
	F#/Gb	.13333	.49337	1.000	-1.5231	1.7898
	G	-2.26667*	.49337	.001	-3.9231	-.6102
	G#/Ab	-.46667	.49337	.999	-2.1231	1.1898
	A	-.93333	.49337	.798	-2.5898	.7231
	A#/Bb	-2.13333*	.49337	.002	-3.7898	-.4769
	MO	-.33333	.49337	1.000	-1.9898	1.3231
MO	C	-2.66667*	.49337	.000	-4.3231	-1.0102
	C#/Db	.26667	.49337	1.000	-1.3898	1.9231
	D	-1.00000	.49337	.714	-2.6565	.6565
	D#/Eb	-.20000	.49337	1.000	-1.8565	1.4565
	E	.13333	.49337	1.000	-1.5231	1.7898
	F	-1.73333*	.49337	.031	-3.3898	-.0769
	F#/Gb	.46667	.49337	.999	-1.1898	2.1231
	G	-1.93333*	.49337	.008	-3.5898	-.2769
	G#/Ab	-.13333	.49337	1.000	-1.7898	1.5231
	A	-.60000	.49337	.992	-2.2565	1.0565
	A#/Bb	-1.80000*	.49337	.020	-3.4565	-.1435
	B	.33333	.49337	1.000	-1.3231	1.9898

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Descriptive statistics for the brand information retained under minor TCs (Retention):

Brand information retention of the smartphone ad (minor condition)

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
A	15	4.2667	1.22280	.31573	3.5895	4.9438	2.00	6.00
A#/Bb	15	1.0667	.88372	.22817	.5773	1.5561	.00	3.00
B	15	3.2667	1.57963	.40786	2.3919	4.1414	1.00	7.00
C	15	1.8000	1.74028	.44934	.8363	2.7637	.00	5.00
C#/Db	15	1.1333	1.30201	.33618	.4123	1.8544	.00	4.00
D	15	3.2000	1.82052	.47006	2.1918	4.2082	1.00	6.00
D#/Eb	15	1.0667	1.03280	.26667	.4947	1.6386	.00	3.00
E	15	4.0000	1.13389	.29277	3.3721	4.6279	2.00	6.00
F	15	1.4667	1.12546	.29059	.8434	2.0899	.00	3.00
F#/Gb	15	1.8000	1.08233	.27946	1.2006	2.3994	.00	4.00
G	15	2.6667	1.71825	.44365	1.7151	3.6182	.00	6.00
G#/Ab	15	1.0000	1.06904	.27603	.4080	1.5920	.00	3.00
MO	15	1.8667	1.24595	.32170	1.1767	2.5566	.00	4.00
Total	195	2.2000	1.70687	.12223	1.9589	2.4411	.00	7.00

Minor TCs ANOVA (Retention):

Brand information retention of the smartphone ad (minor condition)

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	239.733	12	19.978	11.172	.000
Within Groups	325.467	182	1.788		
Total	565.200	194			

Tukey's HSD Post Hoc Analysis (Minor TCs) – (Retention):

Multiple Comparisons

Dependent Variable: Brand information retention of the smartphone ad (minor condition)

Tukey HSD

(I) Minor TCs	(J) Minor TCs	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
A	A#/Bb	3.20000*	.48830	.000	1.5606	4.8394
	B	1.00000	.48830	.700	-.6394	2.6394
	C	2.46667*	.48830	.000	.8272	4.1061
	C#/Db	3.13333*	.48830	.000	1.4939	4.7728
	D	1.06667	.48830	.604	-.5728	2.7061
	D#/Eb	3.20000*	.48830	.000	1.5606	4.8394
	E	.26667	.48830	1.000	-1.3728	1.9061
	F	2.80000*	.48830	.000	1.1606	4.4394
	F#/Gb	2.46667*	.48830	.000	.8272	4.1061
	G	1.60000	.48830	.063	-.0394	3.2394
	G#/Ab	3.26667*	.48830	.000	1.6272	4.9061
M0	2.40000*	.48830	.000	.7606	4.0394	
A#/Bb	A	-3.20000*	.48830	.000	-4.8394	-1.5606
	B	-2.20000*	.48830	.001	-3.8394	-.5606
	C	-.73333	.48830	.954	-2.3728	.9061
	C#/Db	-.06667	.48830	1.000	-1.7061	1.5728
	D	-2.13333*	.48830	.001	-3.7728	-.4939
	D#/Eb	.00000	.48830	1.000	-1.6394	1.6394
	E	-2.93333*	.48830	.000	-4.5728	-1.2939
	F	-.40000	.48830	1.000	-2.0394	1.2394
	F#/Gb	-.73333	.48830	.954	-2.3728	.9061
	G	-1.60000	.48830	.063	-3.2394	.0394
	G#/Ab	.06667	.48830	1.000	-1.5728	1.7061
M0	-.80000	.48830	.915	-2.4394	.8394	
B	A	-1.00000	.48830	.700	-2.6394	.6394
	A#/Bb	2.20000*	.48830	.001	.5606	3.8394
	C	1.46667	.48830	.131	-.1728	3.1061
	C#/Db	2.13333*	.48830	.001	.4939	3.7728
	D	.06667	.48830	1.000	-1.5728	1.7061
	D#/Eb	2.20000*	.48830	.001	.5606	3.8394
	E	-.73333	.48830	.954	-2.3728	.9061
	F	1.80000*	.48830	.018	.1606	3.4394
	F#/Gb	1.46667	.48830	.131	-.1728	3.1061
	G	.60000	.48830	.991	-1.0394	2.2394
	G#/Ab	2.26667*	.48830	.000	.6272	3.9061
M0	1.40000	.48830	.182	-.2394	3.0394	
C	A	-2.46667*	.48830	.000	-4.1061	-.8272
	A#/Bb	.73333	.48830	.954	-.9061	2.3728
	B	-1.46667	.48830	.131	-3.1061	.1728
	C#/Db	.66667	.48830	.978	-.9728	2.3061
	D	-1.40000	.48830	.182	-3.0394	.2394
	D#/Eb	.73333	.48830	.954	-.9061	2.3728
	E	-2.20000*	.48830	.001	-3.8394	-.5606
	F	.33333	.48830	1.000	-1.3061	1.9728
	F#/Gb	.00000	.48830	1.000	-1.6394	1.6394
	G	-.86667	.48830	.859	-2.5061	.7728
	G#/Ab	.80000	.48830	.915	-.8394	2.4394
M0	-.06667	.48830	1.000	-1.7061	1.5728	
C#/Db	A	-3.13333*	.48830	.000	-4.7728	-1.4939
	A#/Bb	.06667	.48830	1.000	-1.5728	1.7061
	B	-2.13333*	.48830	.001	-3.7728	-.4939
	C	-.66667	.48830	.978	-2.3061	.9728
	D	-2.06667*	.48830	.002	-3.7061	-.4272

	D#/Eb	.06667	.48830	1.000	-1.5728	1.7061
	E	-2.86667*	.48830	.000	-4.5061	-1.2272
	F	-.33333	.48830	1.000	-1.9728	1.3061
	F#/Gb	-.66667	.48830	.978	-2.3061	.9728
	G	-1.53333	.48830	.092	-3.1728	.1061
	G#/Ab	.13333	.48830	1.000	-1.5061	1.7728
	M0	-.73333	.48830	.954	-2.3728	.9061
D	A	-1.06667	.48830	.604	-2.7061	.5728
	A#/Bb	2.13333*	.48830	.001	.4939	3.7728
	B	-.06667	.48830	1.000	-1.7061	1.5728
	C	1.40000	.48830	.182	-.2394	3.0394
	C#/Db	2.06667*	.48830	.002	.4272	3.7061
	D#/Eb	2.13333*	.48830	.001	.4939	3.7728
	E	-.80000	.48830	.915	-2.4394	.8394
	F	1.73333*	.48830	.028	.0939	3.3728
	F#/Gb	1.40000	.48830	.182	-.2394	3.0394
	G	.53333	.48830	.997	-1.1061	2.1728
	G#/Ab	2.20000*	.48830	.001	.5606	3.8394
	M0	1.33333	.48830	.245	-.3061	2.9728
D#/Eb	A	-3.20000*	.48830	.000	-4.8394	-1.5606
	A#/Bb	.00000	.48830	1.000	-1.6394	1.6394
	B	-2.20000*	.48830	.001	-3.8394	-.5606
	C	-.73333	.48830	.954	-2.3728	.9061
	C#/Db	-.06667	.48830	1.000	-1.7061	1.5728
	D	-2.13333*	.48830	.001	-3.7728	-.4939
	E	-2.93333*	.48830	.000	-4.5728	-1.2939
	F	-.40000	.48830	1.000	-2.0394	1.2394
	F#/Gb	-.73333	.48830	.954	-2.3728	.9061
	G	-1.60000	.48830	.063	-3.2394	.0394
	G#/Ab	.06667	.48830	1.000	-1.5728	1.7061
	M0	-.80000	.48830	.915	-2.4394	.8394
E	A	-.26667	.48830	1.000	-1.9061	1.3728
	A#/Bb	2.93333*	.48830	.000	1.2939	4.5728
	B	.73333	.48830	.954	-.9061	2.3728
	C	2.20000*	.48830	.001	.5606	3.8394
	C#/Db	2.86667*	.48830	.000	1.2272	4.5061
	D	.80000	.48830	.915	-.8394	2.4394
	D#/Eb	2.93333*	.48830	.000	1.2939	4.5728
	F	2.53333*	.48830	.000	.8939	4.1728
	F#/Gb	2.20000*	.48830	.001	.5606	3.8394
	G	1.33333	.48830	.245	-.3061	2.9728
	G#/Ab	3.00000*	.48830	.000	1.3606	4.6394
	M0	2.13333*	.48830	.001	.4939	3.7728
F	A	-2.80000*	.48830	.000	-4.4394	-1.1606
	A#/Bb	.40000	.48830	1.000	-1.2394	2.0394
	B	-1.80000*	.48830	.018	-3.4394	-.1606
	C	-.33333	.48830	1.000	-1.9728	1.3061
	C#/Db	.33333	.48830	1.000	-1.3061	1.9728
	D	-1.73333*	.48830	.028	-3.3728	-.0939
	D#/Eb	.40000	.48830	1.000	-1.2394	2.0394
	E	-2.53333*	.48830	.000	-4.1728	-.8939
	F#/Gb	-.33333	.48830	1.000	-1.9728	1.3061
	G	-1.20000	.48830	.409	-2.8394	.4394
	G#/Ab	.46667	.48830	.999	-1.1728	2.1061
	M0	-.40000	.48830	1.000	-2.0394	1.2394
F#/Gb	A	-2.46667*	.48830	.000	-4.1061	-.8272
	A#/Bb	.73333	.48830	.954	-.9061	2.3728
	B	-1.46667	.48830	.131	-3.1061	.1728
	C	.00000	.48830	1.000	-1.6394	1.6394
	C#/Db	.66667	.48830	.978	-.9728	2.3061
	D	-1.40000	.48830	.182	-3.0394	.2394
	D#/Eb	.73333	.48830	.954	-.9061	2.3728
	E	-2.20000*	.48830	.001	-3.8394	-.5606

	F	.33333	.48830	1.000	-1.3061	1.9728
	G	-.86667	.48830	.859	-2.5061	.7728
	G#/Ab	.80000	.48830	.915	-.8394	2.4394
	M0	-.06667	.48830	1.000	-1.7061	1.5728
G	A	-1.60000	.48830	.063	-3.2394	.0394
	A#/Bb	1.60000	.48830	.063	-.0394	3.2394
	B	-.60000	.48830	.991	-2.2394	1.0394
	C	.86667	.48830	.859	-.7728	2.5061
	C#/Db	1.53333	.48830	.092	-.1061	3.1728
	D	-.53333	.48830	.997	-2.1728	1.1061
	D#/Eb	1.60000	.48830	.063	-.0394	3.2394
	E	-1.33333	.48830	.245	-2.9728	.3061
	F	1.20000	.48830	.409	-.4394	2.8394
	F#/Gb	.86667	.48830	.859	-.7728	2.5061
	G#/Ab	1.66667*	.48830	.042	.0272	3.3061
	M0	.80000	.48830	.915	-.8394	2.4394
G#/Ab	A	-3.26667*	.48830	.000	-4.9061	-1.6272
	A#/Bb	-.06667	.48830	1.000	-1.7061	1.5728
	B	-2.26667*	.48830	.000	-3.9061	-.6272
	C	-.80000	.48830	.915	-2.4394	.8394
	C#/Db	-.13333	.48830	1.000	-1.7728	1.5061
	D	-2.20000*	.48830	.001	-3.8394	-.5606
	D#/Eb	-.06667	.48830	1.000	-1.7061	1.5728
	E	-3.00000*	.48830	.000	-4.6394	-1.3606
	F	-.46667	.48830	.999	-2.1061	1.1728
	F#/Gb	-.80000	.48830	.915	-2.4394	.8394
	G	-1.66667*	.48830	.042	-3.3061	-.0272
	M0	-.86667	.48830	.859	-2.5061	.7728
M0	A	-2.40000*	.48830	.000	-4.0394	-.7606
	A#/Bb	.80000	.48830	.915	-.8394	2.4394
	B	-1.40000	.48830	.182	-3.0394	.2394
	C	.06667	.48830	1.000	-1.5728	1.7061
	C#/Db	.73333	.48830	.954	-.9061	2.3728
	D	-1.33333	.48830	.245	-2.9728	.3061
	D#/Eb	.80000	.48830	.915	-.8394	2.4394
	E	-2.13333*	.48830	.001	-3.7728	-.4939
	F	.40000	.48830	1.000	-1.2394	2.0394
	F#/Gb	.06667	.48830	1.000	-1.5728	1.7061
	G	-.80000	.48830	.915	-2.4394	.8394
	G#/Ab	.86667	.48830	.859	-.7728	2.5061

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Descriptive statistics under major TCs (Purchase Intention):

MAJOR_PI

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
C	15	3.6000	.74748	.19300	3.1861	4.0139	2.00	4.67
C#/Db	15	1.9111	.73966	.19098	1.5015	2.3207	1.00	3.67
D	15	3.1111	1.15241	.29755	2.4729	3.7493	1.00	5.00
D#/Eb	15	2.4444	.78343	.20228	2.0106	2.8783	1.00	4.00
E	15	2.1111	.72008	.18592	1.7123	2.5099	1.00	3.33
F	15	3.2444	.80145	.20693	2.8006	3.6883	2.00	4.67
F#/Gb	15	1.8444	.75453	.19482	1.4266	2.2623	1.00	3.33
G	15	3.4444	.72008	.18592	3.0457	3.8432	2.00	4.67
G#/Ab	15	2.0444	.69996	.18073	1.6568	2.4321	1.00	3.33
A	15	2.3556	.73966	.19098	1.9459	2.7652	1.00	3.67
A#/Bb	15	3.1778	1.14688	.29612	2.5427	3.8129	1.00	5.00
B	15	1.8222	.79549	.20539	1.3817	2.2627	1.00	3.67
M0	15	2.2889	.73319	.18931	1.8829	2.6949	1.00	3.67
Total	195	2.5692	1.01488	.07268	2.4259	2.7126	1.00	5.00

Major TCs ANOVA (Purchase Intention):

MAJOR_PI

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	76.349	12	6.362	9.379	.000
Within Groups	123.467	182	.678		
Total	199.815	194			

Tukey's HSD Post Hoc Analysis (Major TCs) – (Purchase Intention):

Multiple Comparisons

Dependent Variable: MAJOR_PI
Tukey HSD

(I) MAJOR_GROUPS_AT15	(J) MAJOR_GROUPS_AT15	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
C	C#/D _b	1.68889*	.30075	.000	.6791	2.6986
	D	.48889	.30075	.920	-.5209	1.4986
	D#/E _b	1.15556*	.30075	.010	.1458	2.1653
	E	1.48889*	.30075	.000	.4791	2.4986
	F	.35556	.30075	.994	-.6542	1.3653
	F#/G _b	1.75556*	.30075	.000	.7458	2.7653
	G	.15556	.30075	1.000	-.8542	1.1653
	G#/A _b	1.55556*	.30075	.000	.5458	2.5653
	A	1.24444*	.30075	.004	.2347	2.2542
	A#/B _b	.42222	.30075	.973	-.5875	1.4320
	B	1.77778*	.30075	.000	.7680	2.7875
M0	1.31111*	.30075	.002	.3014	2.3209	
C#/D _b	C	-1.68889*	.30075	.000	-2.6986	-.6791
	D	-1.20000*	.30075	.006	-2.2097	-.1903
	D#/E _b	-.53333	.30075	.860	-1.5431	.4764
	E	-.20000	.30075	1.000	-1.2097	.8097
	F	-1.33333*	.30075	.001	-2.3431	-.3236
	F#/G _b	.06667	.30075	1.000	-.9431	1.0764
	G	-1.53333*	.30075	.000	-2.5431	-.5236
	G#/A _b	-.13333	.30075	1.000	-1.1431	.8764
	A	-.44444	.30075	.959	-1.4542	.5653
	A#/B _b	-1.26667*	.30075	.003	-2.2764	-.2569
	B	.08889	.30075	1.000	-.9209	1.0986
M0	-.37778	.30075	.989	-1.3875	.6320	
D	C	-.48889	.30075	.920	-1.4986	.5209
	C#/D _b	1.20000*	.30075	.006	.1903	2.2097
	D#/E _b	.66667	.30075	.580	-.3431	1.6764
	E	1.00000	.30075	.055	-.0097	2.0097
	F	-.13333	.30075	1.000	-1.1431	.8764
	F#/G _b	1.26667*	.30075	.003	.2569	2.2764
	G	-.33333	.30075	.996	-1.3431	.6764
	G#/A _b	1.06667*	.30075	.028	.0569	2.0764
	A	.75556	.30075	.373	-.2542	1.7653
	A#/B _b	-.06667	.30075	1.000	-1.0764	.9431
	B	1.28889*	.30075	.002	.2791	2.2986
M0	.82222	.30075	.244	-.1875	1.8320	
D#/E _b	C	-1.15556*	.30075	.010	-2.1653	-.1458
	C#/D _b	.53333	.30075	.860	-.4764	1.5431
	D	-.66667	.30075	.580	-1.6764	.3431

	E	.33333	.30075	.996	-6764	1.3431
	F	-.80000	.30075	.283	-1.8097	.2097
	F#/Gb	.60000	.30075	.735	-4097	1.6097
	G	-1.00000	.30075	.055	-2.0097	.0097
	G#/Ab	.40000	.30075	.982	-6097	1.4097
	A	.08889	.30075	1.000	-.9209	1.0986
	A#/Bb	-.73333	.30075	.422	-1.7431	.2764
	B	.62222	.30075	.685	-3875	1.6320
	M0	.15556	.30075	1.000	-.8542	1.1653
E	C	-1.48889*	.30075	.000	-2.4986	-.4791
	C#/Db	.20000	.30075	1.000	-.8097	1.2097
	D	-1.00000	.30075	.055	-2.0097	.0097
	D#/Eb	-.33333	.30075	.996	-1.3431	.6764
	F	-1.13333*	.30075	.013	-2.1431	-.1236
	F#/Gb	.26667	.30075	1.000	-.7431	1.2764
	G	-1.33333*	.30075	.001	-2.3431	-.3236
	G#/Ab	.06667	.30075	1.000	-.9431	1.0764
	A	-.24444	.30075	1.000	-1.2542	.7653
	A#/Bb	-1.06667*	.30075	.028	-2.0764	-.0569
	B	.28889	.30075	.999	-.7209	1.2986
	M0	-.17778	.30075	1.000	-1.1875	.8320
F	C	-.35556	.30075	.994	-1.3653	.6542
	C#/Db	1.33333*	.30075	.001	.3236	2.3431
	D	.13333	.30075	1.000	-.8764	1.1431
	D#/Eb	.80000	.30075	.283	-2.097	1.8097
	E	1.13333*	.30075	.013	.1236	2.1431
	F#/Gb	1.40000*	.30075	.000	.3903	2.4097
	G	-.20000	.30075	1.000	-1.2097	.8097
	G#/Ab	1.20000*	.30075	.006	.1903	2.2097
	A	.88889	.30075	.148	-1.209	1.8986
	A#/Bb	.06667	.30075	1.000	-.9431	1.0764
	B	1.42222*	.30075	.000	.4125	2.4320
	M0	.95556	.30075	.083	-.0542	1.9653
F#/Gb	C	-1.75556*	.30075	.000	-2.7653	-.7458
	C#/Db	-.06667	.30075	1.000	-1.0764	.9431
	D	-1.26667*	.30075	.003	-2.2764	-.2569
	D#/Eb	-.60000	.30075	.735	-1.6097	.4097
	E	-.26667	.30075	1.000	-1.2764	.7431
	F	-1.40000*	.30075	.000	-2.4097	-.3903
	G	-1.60000*	.30075	.000	-2.6097	-.5903
	G#/Ab	-.20000	.30075	1.000	-1.2097	.8097
	A	-.51111	.30075	.893	-1.5209	.4986
	A#/Bb	-1.33333*	.30075	.001	-2.3431	-.3236
	B	.02222	.30075	1.000	-.9875	1.0320
	M0	-.44444	.30075	.959	-1.4542	.5653
G	C	-.15556	.30075	1.000	-1.1653	.8542
	C#/Db	1.53333*	.30075	.000	.5236	2.5431
	D	.33333	.30075	.996	-.6764	1.3431
	D#/Eb	1.00000	.30075	.055	-.0097	2.0097
	E	1.33333*	.30075	.001	.3236	2.3431
	F	.20000	.30075	1.000	-.8097	1.2097
	F#/Gb	1.60000*	.30075	.000	.5903	2.6097
	G#/Ab	1.40000*	.30075	.000	.3903	2.4097
	A	1.08889*	.30075	.022	.0791	2.0986
	A#/Bb	.26667	.30075	1.000	-.7431	1.2764
	B	1.62222*	.30075	.000	.6125	2.6320
	M0	1.15556*	.30075	.010	.1458	2.1653
G#/Ab	C	-1.55556*	.30075	.000	-2.5653	-.5458
	C#/Db	.13333	.30075	1.000	-.8764	1.1431
	D	-1.06667*	.30075	.028	-2.0764	-.0569
	D#/Eb	-.40000	.30075	.982	-1.4097	.6097
	E	-.06667	.30075	1.000	-1.0764	.9431
	F	-1.20000*	.30075	.006	-2.2097	-.1903

	F#/Gb	.20000	.30075	1.000	-.8097	1.2097
	G	-1.40000*	.30075	.000	-2.4097	-.3903
	A	-.31111	.30075	.998	-1.3209	.6986
	A#/Bb	-1.13333*	.30075	.013	-2.1431	-.1236
	B	.22222	.30075	1.000	-.7875	1.2320
	MO	-.24444	.30075	1.000	-1.2542	.7653
A	C	-1.24444*	.30075	.004	-2.2542	-.2347
	C#/Db	.44444	.30075	.959	-.5653	1.4542
	D	-.75556	.30075	.373	-1.7653	.2542
	D#/Eb	-.08889	.30075	1.000	-1.0986	.9209
	E	.24444	.30075	1.000	-.7653	1.2542
	F	-.88889	.30075	.148	-1.8986	.1209
	F#/Gb	.51111	.30075	.893	-.4986	1.5209
	G	-1.08889*	.30075	.022	-2.0986	-.0791
	G#/Ab	.31111	.30075	.998	-.6986	1.3209
	A#/Bb	-.82222	.30075	.244	-1.8320	.1875
	B	.53333	.30075	.860	-.4764	1.5431
	MO	.06667	.30075	1.000	-.9431	1.0764
A#/Bb	C	-.42222	.30075	.973	-1.4320	.5875
	C#/Db	1.26667*	.30075	.003	.2569	2.2764
	D	.06667	.30075	1.000	-.9431	1.0764
	D#/Eb	.73333	.30075	.422	-.2764	1.7431
	E	1.06667*	.30075	.028	.0569	2.0764
	F	-.06667	.30075	1.000	-1.0764	.9431
	F#/Gb	1.33333*	.30075	.001	.3236	2.3431
	G	-.26667	.30075	1.000	-1.2764	.7431
	G#/Ab	1.13333*	.30075	.013	.1236	2.1431
	A	.82222	.30075	.244	-.1875	1.8320
	B	1.35556*	.30075	.001	.3458	2.3653
	MO	.88889	.30075	.148	-.1209	1.8986
B	C	-1.77778*	.30075	.000	-2.7875	-.7680
	C#/Db	-.08889	.30075	1.000	-1.0986	.9209
	D	-1.28889*	.30075	.002	-2.2986	-.2791
	D#/Eb	-.62222	.30075	.685	-1.6320	.3875
	E	-.28889	.30075	.999	-1.2986	.7209
	F	-1.42222*	.30075	.000	-2.4320	-.4125
	F#/Gb	-.02222	.30075	1.000	-1.0320	.9875
	G	-1.62222*	.30075	.000	-2.6320	-.6125
	G#/Ab	-.22222	.30075	1.000	-1.2320	.7875
	A	-.53333	.30075	.860	-1.5431	.4764
	A#/Bb	-1.35556*	.30075	.001	-2.3653	-.3458
	MO	-.46667	.30075	.942	-1.4764	.5431
MO	C	-1.31111*	.30075	.002	-2.3209	-.3014
	C#/Db	.37778	.30075	.989	-.6320	1.3875
	D	-.82222	.30075	.244	-1.8320	.1875
	D#/Eb	-.15556	.30075	1.000	-1.1653	.8542
	E	.17778	.30075	1.000	-.8320	1.1875
	F	-.95556	.30075	.083	-1.9653	.0542
	F#/Gb	.44444	.30075	.959	-.5653	1.4542
	G	-1.15556*	.30075	.010	-2.1653	-.1458
	G#/Ab	.24444	.30075	1.000	-.7653	1.2542
	A	-.06667	.30075	1.000	-1.0764	.9431
	A#/Bb	-.88889	.30075	.148	-1.8986	.1209
	B	.46667	.30075	.942	-.5431	1.4764

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Descriptive statistics under minor TCs (Purchase Intention):

MINOR_PI

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
A	15	3.2667	1.24212	.32071	2.5788	3.9545	1.33	5.00
A#/Bb	15	2.0222	.84013	.21692	1.5570	2.4875	1.00	4.00
B	15	2.8889	1.21281	.31315	2.2173	3.5605	1.00	5.00
C	15	2.2222	.84202	.21741	1.7559	2.6885	1.00	3.67
C#/Db	15	2.0000	.79682	.20574	1.5587	2.4413	1.00	3.67
D	15	3.1333	.78478	.20263	2.6987	3.5679	2.00	5.00
D#/Eb	15	1.6889	.66029	.17049	1.3232	2.0545	1.00	3.00
E	15	3.2000	.71047	.18344	2.8066	3.5934	1.67	4.33
F	15	1.8222	.66508	.17172	1.4539	2.1905	1.00	3.00
F#/Gb	15	2.2000	.74322	.19190	1.7884	2.6116	1.00	3.33
G	15	3.0667	1.04045	.26864	2.4905	3.6428	1.00	4.33
G#/Ab	15	1.6889	.71787	.18535	1.2913	2.0864	1.00	3.33
M0	15	2.2222	.78343	.20228	1.7884	2.6561	1.00	3.67
Total	195	2.4171	1.02285	.07325	2.2726	2.5616	1.00	5.00

Minor TCs ANOVA (Purchase Intention):

MINOR_PI

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	65.395	12	5.450	7.210	.000
Within Groups	137.570	182	.756		
Total	202.965	194			

Tukey's HSD Post Hoc Analysis (Minor TCs) – (Purchase Intention):

Multiple Comparisons

Dependent Variable: MINOR_PI

Tukey HSD

(I) Minor TCs	(J) Minor TCs	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
A	A#/Bb	1.24444*	.31747	.008	.1786	2.3103
	B	.37778	.31747	.993	-.6881	1.4436
	C	1.04444	.31747	.041	-.0214	2.1103
	C#/Db	1.26667*	.31747	.006	.2008	2.3325
	D	.13333	.31747	1.000	-.9325	1.1992
	D#/Eb	1.57778*	.31747	.000	.5119	2.6436
	E	.06667	.31747	1.000	-.9992	1.1325
	F	1.44444*	.31747	.001	.3786	2.5103
	F#/Gb	1.06667*	.31747	.050	.0008	2.1325
	G	.20000	.31747	1.000	-.8659	1.2659
A#/Bb	A	-1.24444*	.31747	.008	-2.3103	-.1786
	B	-.86667	.31747	.246	-1.9325	.1992
	C	-.20000	.31747	1.000	-1.2659	.8659
	C#/Db	.02222	.31747	1.000	-1.0436	1.0881
	D	-1.11111*	.31747	.032	-2.1770	-.0453
	D#/Eb	.33333	.31747	.998	-.7325	1.3992
	E	-1.17778*	.31747	.016	-2.2436	-.1119
	F	.20000	.31747	1.000	-.8659	1.2659
	F#/Gb	-.17778	.31747	1.000	-1.2436	.8881

	G	-1.04444	.31747	.061	-2.1103	.0214
	G#/Ab	.33333	.31747	.998	-.7325	1.3992
	M0	-.20000	.31747	1.000	-1.2659	.8659
B	A	-.37778	.31747	.993	-1.4436	.6881
	A#/Bb	.86667	.31747	.246	-.1992	1.9325
	C	.66667	.31747	.664	-.3992	1.7325
	C#/Db	.88889	.31747	.212	-.1770	1.9547
	D	-.24444	.31747	1.000	-1.3103	.8214
	D#/Eb	1.20000*	.31747	.013	.1341	2.2659
	E	-.31111	.31747	.999	-1.3770	.7547
	F	1.06667*	.31747	.050	.0008	2.1325
	F#/Gb	.68889	.31747	.614	-.3770	1.7547
	G	-.17778	.31747	1.000	-1.2436	.8881
	G#/Ab	1.20000*	.31747	.013	.1341	2.2659
	M0	.66667	.31747	.664	-.3992	1.7325
C	A	-1.04444	.31747	.041	-2.1103	.0214
	A#/Bb	.20000	.31747	1.000	-.8659	1.2659
	B	-.66667	.31747	.664	-1.7325	.3992
	C#/Db	.22222	.31747	1.000	-.8436	1.2881
	D	-.91111	.31747	.181	-1.9770	.1547
	D#/Eb	.53333	.31747	.900	-.5325	1.5992
	E	-.97778	.31747	.108	-2.0436	.0881
	F	.40000	.31747	.989	-.6659	1.4659
	F#/Gb	.02222	.31747	1.000	-1.0436	1.0881
	G	-.84444	.31747	.283	-1.9103	.2214
	G#/Ab	.53333	.31747	.900	-.5325	1.5992
	M0	.00000	.31747	1.000	-1.0659	1.0659
C#/Db	A	-1.26667*	.31747	.006	-2.3325	-.2008
	A#/Bb	-.02222	.31747	1.000	-1.0881	1.0436
	B	-.88889	.31747	.212	-1.9547	.1770
	C	-.22222	.31747	1.000	-1.2881	.8436
	D	-1.13333*	.31747	.026	-2.1992	-.0675
	D#/Eb	.31111	.31747	.999	-.7547	1.3770
	E	-1.20000*	.31747	.013	-2.2659	-.1341
	F	.17778	.31747	1.000	-.8881	1.2436
	F#/Gb	-.20000	.31747	1.000	-1.2659	.8659
	G	-1.06667*	.31747	.050	-2.1325	-.0008
	G#/Ab	.31111	.31747	.999	-.7547	1.3770
	M0	-.22222	.31747	1.000	-1.2881	.8436
D	A	-.13333	.31747	1.000	-1.1992	.9325
	A#/Bb	1.11111*	.31747	.032	.0453	2.1770
	B	.24444	.31747	1.000	-.8214	1.3103
	C	.91111	.31747	.181	-.1547	1.9770
	C#/Db	1.13333*	.31747	.026	.0675	2.1992
	D#/Eb	1.44444*	.31747	.001	.3786	2.5103
	E	-.06667	.31747	1.000	-1.1325	.9992
	F	1.31111*	.31747	.004	.2453	2.3770
	F#/Gb	.93333	.31747	.153	-.1325	1.9992
	G	.06667	.31747	1.000	-.9992	1.1325
	G#/Ab	1.44444*	.31747	.001	.3786	2.5103
	M0	.91111	.31747	.181	-.1547	1.9770
D#/Eb	A	-1.57778*	.31747	.000	-2.6436	-.5119
	A#/Bb	-.33333	.31747	.998	-1.3992	.7325
	B	-1.20000*	.31747	.013	-2.2659	-.1341
	C	-.53333	.31747	.900	-1.5992	.5325
	C#/Db	-.31111	.31747	.999	-1.3770	.7547
	D	-1.44444*	.31747	.001	-2.5103	-.3786
	E	-1.51111*	.31747	.000	-2.5770	-.4453
	F	-.13333	.31747	1.000	-1.1992	.9325
	F#/Gb	-.51111	.31747	.925	-1.5770	.5547
	G	-1.37778*	.31747	.002	-2.4436	-.3119
	G#/Ab	.00000	.31747	1.000	-1.0659	1.0659
	M0	-.53333	.31747	.900	-1.5992	.5325

E	A	-.06667	.31747	1.000	-1.1325	.9992
	A#/Bb	1.17778*	.31747	.016	.1119	2.2436
	B	.31111	.31747	.999	-.7547	1.3770
	C	.97778	.31747	.108	-.0881	2.0436
	C#/Db	1.20000*	.31747	.013	.1341	2.2659
	D	.06667	.31747	1.000	-.9992	1.1325
	D#/Eb	1.51111*	.31747	.000	.4453	2.5770
	F	1.37778*	.31747	.002	.3119	2.4436
	F#/Gb	1.00000	.31747	.090	-.0659	2.0659
	G	.13333	.31747	1.000	-.9325	1.1992
	G#/Ab	1.51111*	.31747	.000	.4453	2.5770
M0	.97778	.31747	.108	-.0881	2.0436	
F	A	-1.44444*	.31747	.001	-2.5103	-.3786
	A#/Bb	-.20000	.31747	1.000	-1.2659	.8659
	B	-1.06667*	.31747	.050	-2.1325	-.0008
	C	-.40000	.31747	.989	-1.4659	.6659
	C#/Db	-.17778	.31747	1.000	-1.2436	.8881
	D	-1.31111*	.31747	.004	-2.3770	-.2453
	D#/Eb	.13333	.31747	1.000	-.9325	1.1992
	E	-1.37778*	.31747	.002	-2.4436	-.3119
	F#/Gb	-.37778	.31747	.993	-1.4436	.6881
	G	-1.24444*	.31747	.008	-2.3103	-.1786
	G#/Ab	.13333	.31747	1.000	-.9325	1.1992
M0	-.40000	.31747	.989	-1.4659	.6659	
F#/Gb	A	-1.06667*	.31747	.050	-2.1325	-.0008
	A#/Bb	.17778	.31747	1.000	-.8881	1.2436
	B	-.68889	.31747	.614	-1.7547	.3770
	C	-.02222	.31747	1.000	-1.0881	1.0436
	C#/Db	.20000	.31747	1.000	-.8659	1.2659
	D	-.93333	.31747	.153	-1.9992	.1325
	D#/Eb	.51111	.31747	.925	-.5547	1.5770
	E	-1.00000	.31747	.090	-2.0659	.0659
	F	.37778	.31747	.993	-.6881	1.4436
	G	-.86667	.31747	.246	-1.9325	.1992
	G#/Ab	.51111	.31747	.925	-.5547	1.5770
M0	-.02222	.31747	1.000	-1.0881	1.0436	
G	A	-.20000	.31747	1.000	-1.2659	.8659
	A#/Bb	1.04444	.31747	.061	-.0214	2.1103
	B	.17778	.31747	1.000	-.8881	1.2436
	C	.84444	.31747	.283	-.2214	1.9103
	C#/Db	1.06667*	.31747	.050	.0008	2.1325
	D	-.06667	.31747	1.000	-1.1325	.9992
	D#/Eb	1.37778*	.31747	.002	.3119	2.4436
	E	-.13333	.31747	1.000	-1.1992	.9325
	F	1.24444*	.31747	.008	.1786	2.3103
	F#/Gb	.86667	.31747	.246	-.1992	1.9325
	G#/Ab	1.37778*	.31747	.002	.3119	2.4436
M0	.84444	.31747	.283	-.2214	1.9103	
G#/Ab	A	-1.57778*	.31747	.000	-2.6436	-.5119
	A#/Bb	-.33333	.31747	.998	-1.3992	.7325
	B	-1.20000*	.31747	.013	-2.2659	-.1341
	C	-.53333	.31747	.900	-1.5992	.5325
	C#/Db	-.31111	.31747	.999	-1.3770	.7547
	D	-1.44444*	.31747	.001	-2.5103	-.3786
	D#/Eb	.00000	.31747	1.000	-1.0659	1.0659
	E	-1.51111*	.31747	.000	-2.5770	-.4453
	F	-.13333	.31747	1.000	-1.1992	.9325
	F#/Gb	-.51111	.31747	.925	-1.5770	.5547
	G	-1.37778*	.31747	.002	-2.4436	-.3119
M0	-.53333	.31747	.900	-1.5992	.5325	
M0	A	-1.04444	.31747	.041	-2.1103	.0214
	A#/Bb	.20000	.31747	1.000	-.8659	1.2659

B	-.66667	.31747	.664	-1.7325	.3992
C	.00000	.31747	1.000	-1.0659	1.0659
C#/Db	.22222	.31747	1.000	-.8436	1.2881
D	-.91111	.31747	.181	-1.9770	.1547
D#/Eb	.53333	.31747	.900	-.5325	1.5992
E	-.97778	.31747	.108	-2.0436	.0881
F	.40000	.31747	.989	-.6659	1.4659
F#/Gb	.02222	.31747	1.000	-1.0436	1.0881
G	-.84444	.31747	.283	-1.9103	.2214
G#/Ab	.53333	.31747	.900	-.5325	1.5992

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Appendix L: Manipulation Check SPSS Results

Descriptive statistics C_{maj-8} , C_{maj} , and C_{maj+8} :

C major transposition

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
C major (-8)	15	25.5947	1.93046	.49844	24.5256	26.6637	23.10	29.20
C major	15	25.5773	2.10589	.54374	24.4111	26.7435	22.19	29.42
C major (+8)	15	25.6547	2.07263	.53515	24.5069	26.8025	22.50	29.70
Total	45	25.6089	1.99118	.29683	25.0107	26.2071	22.19	29.70

C_{maj-8} , C_{maj} , and C_{maj+8} ANOVA:

C major transposition

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	.049	2	.025	.006	.994
Within Groups	174.402	42	4.152		
Total	174.451	44			

Tukey's HSD Post Hoc Analysis (C_{maj-8} , C_{maj} , and C_{maj+8}):

Multiple Comparisons

Dependent Variable: C major transposition

Tukey HSD

(I) C major transposition group	(J) C major transposition group	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
C major (-8)	C major	.01733	.74408	1.000	-1.7904	1.8251
	C major (+8)	-.06000	.74408	.996	-1.8677	1.7477
C major	C major (-8)	-.01733	.74408	1.000	-1.8251	1.7904
	C major (+8)	-.07733	.74408	.994	-1.8851	1.7304
C major (+8)	C major (-8)	.06000	.74408	.996	-1.7477	1.8677
	C major	.07733	.74408	.994	-1.7304	1.8851

Descriptive statistics A_{min-8} , A_{min} , and A_{min+8} :

A minor transposition

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
A minor (-8)	15	25.4220	1.68041	.43388	24.4914	26.3526	22.62	28.40
A minor	15	25.4953	1.60137	.41347	24.6085	26.3821	22.62	28.00
A minor (+8)	15	25.3967	1.51936	.39230	24.5553	26.2381	22.10	28.10
Total	45	25.4380	1.56548	.23337	24.9677	25.9083	22.10	28.40

A_{min-8} , A_{min} , and A_{min+8} ANOVA:

A minor transposition

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	.079	2	.039	.015	.985
Within Groups	107.753	42	2.566		
Total	107.832	44			

Tukey's HSD Post Hoc Analysis (A_{min-8} , A_{min} , and A_{min+8}):

Multiple Comparisons

Dependent Variable: A minor transposition

Tukey HSD

(I) A minor transposition group	(J) A minor transposition group	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
A minor (-8)	A minor	-.07333	.58487	.991	-1.4943	1.3476
	A minor (+8)	.02533	.58487	.999	-1.3956	1.4463
A minor	A minor (-8)	.07333	.58487	.991	-1.3476	1.4943
	A minor (+8)	.09867	.58487	.984	-1.3223	1.5196
A minor (+8)	A minor (-8)	-.02533	.58487	.999	-1.4463	1.3956
	A minor	-.09867	.58487	.984	-1.5196	1.3223

Appendix M: Retention Data Processing

Item	Juice ad		Smartphone ad	
	Accepted	Unaccepted	Accepted	Unaccepted
Name	Typos such 'neat' instead of 'neet'	Wrong brand name (e.g. nice, beat, beet, nine, night, lean, fun, keen... etc)	Typos such 'zeal' instead of 'zeel'	Wrong brand name (e.g. zed, zane, zoom, zinc, zool, zoro... etc)
Flavour, colour	Typos such as 'orang'	Wrong flavours	Typos such as 'blak'	Wrong colours
Slogan	'what you net' instead of 'all you neet' or adding 'it's' before the slogan	Wrong slogan	Forgetting the 'the' in 'the real zeal' or adding 'it's' or 'get' before the slogan	Wrong slogan
Other info	Organic, 0 sugars, no sugars, sugar free, 100% fruit juice, all fruit juice, 330 ml, no preservatives, and any other accurate information.	Any inaccurate information	Names of colour (Raven, Crimson, and Night), 3 cameras, 5.8" display, 8 GB RAM, and any other accurate information such as "it showed an ocean on the screen"	Any inaccurate information

Appendix N: Music Scores

Juice Ad Music Score

F # MAJOR / G b MAJOR

♩ = 120

Guitar

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9

Detailed description: This musical score is for a guitar part in F# Major / Gb Major, 4/4 time, with a tempo of 120. It consists of nine measures. Measures 1-3 are marked with a '1', measures 4-5 with a '2', and measures 6-7 with a '3'. The notation features a treble clef, a key signature of two sharps (F# and C#), and a 4/4 time signature. The melody is primarily eighth-note based, with a consistent bass line of low E and A. Measure 9 ends with a double bar line and a circled 'C' with a wavy line underneath, indicating a specific guitar effect.

G MAJOR

♩ = 120

Guitar

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9

Detailed description: This musical score is for a guitar part in G Major, 4/4 time, with a tempo of 120. It consists of nine measures. Measures 1-3 are marked with a '1', measures 4-5 with a '2', and measures 6-7 with a '3'. The notation features a treble clef, a key signature of one sharp (F#), and a 4/4 time signature. The melody is primarily eighth-note based, with a consistent bass line of low E and A. Measure 9 ends with a double bar line and a circled 'C' with a wavy line underneath, indicating a specific guitar effect.

G # MAJOR / A b MAJOR

♩ = 120

Guitar

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9

Detailed description: This block contains the guitar tablature for the first section, G# Major / Ab Major. It consists of nine measures of music. The first measure is marked with a '1' above the staff. The key signature has two flats (Bb and Eb) and the time signature is 4/4. The music is written in a treble clef. The first seven measures feature a complex rhythmic pattern of eighth and sixteenth notes, with some notes beamed together. The eighth measure is a whole note chord. The ninth measure is a whole note chord with a circled 'C' above it, indicating a barre. The tablature uses numbers 1-5 to indicate fret positions and includes various symbols for bends and vibrato.

A MAJOR

♩ = 120

Guitar

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9

Detailed description: This block contains the guitar tablature for the second section, A Major. It consists of nine measures of music. The first measure is marked with a '1' above the staff. The key signature has two sharps (F# and C#) and the time signature is 4/4. The music is written in a treble clef. The first seven measures feature a complex rhythmic pattern of eighth and sixteenth notes, with some notes beamed together. The eighth measure is a whole note chord. The ninth measure is a whole note chord with a circled 'C' above it, indicating a barre. The tablature uses numbers 1-5 to indicate fret positions and includes various symbols for bends and vibrato.

A # MAJOR / B b MAJOR

♩ = 120

Guitar

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9

Detailed description: This block contains the first nine measures of a guitar piece in A# Major / Bb Major. The music is written in 4/4 time with a tempo of 120 bpm. It features a complex melodic line with many triplets and slurs. Measure 9 ends with a circled chord diagram: (x111111).

B MAJOR

♩ = 120

Guitar

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9

Detailed description: This block contains the first nine measures of a guitar piece in B Major. The music is written in 4/4 time with a tempo of 120 bpm. It features a complex melodic line with many triplets and slurs. Measure 9 ends with a circled chord diagram: (x111111).

C MAJOR

♩ = 120

Guitar

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9

Detailed description: This block contains the first nine measures of a guitar piece in C Major, 4/4 time. The tempo is marked as ♩ = 120. The music is written on a single treble clef staff. Measures 1-3 show a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes with a descending bass line. Measures 4-6 continue this pattern with some melodic variation. Measure 7 starts with a new rhythmic motif. Measure 8 continues the eighth-note pattern. Measure 9 concludes with a final chord and a fermata over a whole note chord.

C # MAJOR / D ♭ MAJOR

♩ = 120

Guitar

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9

Detailed description: This block contains the first nine measures of a guitar piece in C# Major / D♭ Major, 4/4 time. The tempo is marked as ♩ = 120. The key signature has four sharps (F#, C#, G#, D#). The music is written on a single treble clef staff. Measures 1-3 show a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes with a descending bass line. Measures 4-6 continue this pattern with some melodic variation. Measure 7 starts with a new rhythmic motif. Measure 8 continues the eighth-note pattern. Measure 9 concludes with a final chord and a fermata over a whole note chord.

D MAJOR

♩ = 120

Guitar

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9

Detailed description: This block contains the guitar score for the D Major section, spanning measures 1 to 9. The music is written in treble clef with a key signature of two sharps (F# and C#) and a 4/4 time signature. The tempo is marked as ♩ = 120. The score is divided into three systems. The first system contains measures 1, 2, and 3. The second system contains measures 4, 5, and 6. The third system contains measures 7, 8, and 9. Each measure is numbered above the staff. The notation features a consistent rhythmic pattern of eighth notes and quarter notes, with a final measure (9) ending with a double bar line and a fermata over a whole note chord.

D # MAJOR / E ♭ MAJOR

♩ = 120

Guitar

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9

Detailed description: This block contains the guitar score for the D# Major / Eb Major section, spanning measures 1 to 9. The music is written in treble clef with a key signature of three flats (Bb, Eb, and Ab) and a 4/4 time signature. The tempo is marked as ♩ = 120. The score is divided into three systems. The first system contains measures 1, 2, and 3. The second system contains measures 4, 5, and 6. The third system contains measures 7, 8, and 9. Each measure is numbered above the staff. The notation features a consistent rhythmic pattern of eighth notes and quarter notes, with a final measure (9) ending with a double bar line and a fermata over a whole note chord.

E MAJOR

♩ = 120

Guitar

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9

Detailed description: This block contains the musical notation for an E Major guitar exercise. It consists of nine measures of music in 4/4 time, with a tempo of 120 beats per minute. The key signature has three sharps (F#, C#, G#). The notation is written on a single staff in treble clef. Measures 1-3 show a sequence of eighth-note chords: E2-E4, E2-E4, and E2-E4. Measures 4-6 show a sequence of eighth-note chords: E2-E4, E2-E4, and E2-E4. Measures 7-9 show a sequence of eighth-note chords: E2-E4, E2-E4, and E2-E4. The exercise concludes with a final chord in measure 9.

F MAJOR

♩ = 120

Guitar

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9

Detailed description: This block contains the musical notation for an F Major guitar exercise. It consists of nine measures of music in 4/4 time, with a tempo of 120 beats per minute. The key signature has one flat (Bb). The notation is written on a single staff in treble clef. Measures 1-3 show a sequence of eighth-note chords: F2-F4, F2-F4, and F2-F4. Measures 4-6 show a sequence of eighth-note chords: F2-F4, F2-F4, and F2-F4. Measures 7-9 show a sequence of eighth-note chords: F2-F4, F2-F4, and F2-F4. The exercise concludes with a final chord in measure 9.

Smartphone Ad Music Score

F # MINOR / G b MINOR

1 $\text{♩} = 120$

Piano

Strings

2 3

4 5

The musical score is written for Piano and Strings in F# minor / Gb minor, 4/4 time, with a tempo of 120 beats per minute. The score is divided into five measures. Measures 2 and 3, 4 and 5, and 5 are double-measure rests. The Piano part features a melodic line with slurs and ties, while the Strings part provides a harmonic accompaniment with slurs and ties.

6 7

8 9

The image displays a musical score for piano accompaniment, organized into two systems. The first system covers measures 6 and 7, and the second system covers measures 8 and 9. Each system consists of two staves: a treble clef staff on top and a bass clef staff on the bottom. The key signature is three sharps (F#, C#, G#). The music is written in a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes, with chords indicated by vertical lines. In measure 9, the music concludes with a final chord in both systems, marked with a double bar line and a repeat sign.

G MINOR

1 $\text{♩} = 120$

Piano

Strings

2 3

4 5

6 7

This block contains the musical notation for measures 6 and 7. It consists of two systems. Each system has a treble clef staff and a bass clef staff. The key signature has two flats (B-flat and E-flat). The music is written in a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes, with some chords. Measure 6 is followed by measure 7. The notation includes various musical symbols such as stems, beams, and note heads.

8 9

This block contains the musical notation for measures 8 and 9. It consists of two systems. Each system has a treble clef staff and a bass clef staff. The key signature has two flats (B-flat and E-flat). The music is written in a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes, with some chords. Measure 8 is followed by measure 9. The notation includes various musical symbols such as stems, beams, and note heads. The piece concludes with a double bar line at the end of measure 9.

G # MINOR / A b MINOR

1 $\text{♩} = 120$

Piano

Strings

2 3

4 5

The musical score is written for Piano and Strings in G# minor / A b minor, 4/4 time, with a tempo of 120. It consists of five measures. Measure 1 shows the beginning of the piece. Measures 2 and 3 show the continuation of the piano and string parts. Measures 4 and 5 show a more complex texture with multiple voices in both instruments.

6 7

Musical score for measures 6 and 7. The score is written for two systems of piano. Each system has a grand staff with a treble clef and a bass clef. The key signature is three sharps (F#, C#, G#). The time signature is 4/4. Measures 6 and 7 show a complex rhythmic pattern with sixteenth and thirty-second notes in the right hand and chords in the left hand. The bass clef part includes a 'C' time signature and a '4' time signature.

8 9

Musical score for measures 8 and 9. The score is written for two systems of piano. Each system has a grand staff with a treble clef and a bass clef. The key signature is three sharps (F#, C#, G#). The time signature is 4/4. Measures 8 and 9 show a complex rhythmic pattern with sixteenth and thirty-second notes in the right hand and chords in the left hand. The bass clef part includes a 'C' time signature and a '4' time signature. Measure 9 ends with a double bar line and repeat signs.

A MINOR

1 $\text{♩} = 120$

Piano

2

3

4

5

6

Strings

The musical score is written for Piano and Strings in A minor, 4/4 time, with a tempo of 120. The score is divided into six measures. Measures 1-2 show the Piano and Strings playing a melodic line in the right hand and a bass line in the left hand. Measures 3-4 show the Piano and Strings playing a similar melodic line. Measures 5-6 show the Piano and Strings playing a more complex melodic line with triplets in the right hand and a bass line in the left hand.

7 8 9

The image shows two systems of musical notation for piano. Each system consists of a grand staff with a treble clef on the upper staff and a bass clef on the lower staff. The music is written in a rhythmic pattern of eighth notes, with some beamed sixteenth notes. The first system is labeled with measure numbers 7, 8, and 9. The second system continues the same musical material. The notation includes stems, beams, and note heads, with some notes beamed together. The piece concludes with a double bar line and repeat signs.

A # MINOR / B b MINOR

1 $\text{♩} = 120$

Piano

Strings

2 3

4 5

The musical score is written for Piano and Strings in A# minor / Bb minor, 4/4 time, with a tempo of 120. The score is divided into five measures. Measure 1 shows the beginning of the piece with a piano part and a string part. Measures 2 and 3 continue the piano part. Measures 4 and 5 continue the piano part and introduce a more complex string part with triplets and sixteenth notes.

6 7

Musical score for measures 6 and 7. The score is written for two systems of piano. Each system has a grand staff with a treble clef on top and a bass clef on the bottom. The key signature is three sharps (F#, C#, G#). The time signature is common time (C). Measures 6 and 7 show a consistent rhythmic pattern of eighth notes in the right hand and chords in the left hand.

8 9

Musical score for measures 8 and 9. The score is written for two systems of piano. Each system has a grand staff with a treble clef on top and a bass clef on the bottom. The key signature is three sharps (F#, C#, G#). The time signature is common time (C). Measures 8 and 9 show the continuation of the rhythmic pattern from the previous measures, ending with a double bar line and repeat signs.

B MINOR

1 $\text{♩} = 120$ 2

Piano

Strings

3 4

5 6

The image displays a musical score for Piano and Strings in B minor, spanning six measures. The score is organized into three systems, each with two staves (Piano and Strings). The key signature is B minor (two sharps: F# and C#), and the time signature is 4/4. The tempo is marked as quarter note = 120. Measures 1 and 2 show the Piano part with a melodic line of eighth notes and the Strings part with a similar eighth-note accompaniment. Measures 3 and 4 continue this pattern. Measures 5 and 6 feature a more complex texture with the Piano part playing chords and the Strings part playing a rhythmic accompaniment. The score is numbered 1 through 6 at the beginning of each measure.

7 8 9

The image shows two systems of musical notation, each consisting of a grand staff (treble and bass clefs) with a key signature of two sharps (F# and C#). The first system is labeled with measure numbers 7, 8, and 9. The second system is identical to the first. The music features a complex, rhythmic pattern in the right hand, primarily consisting of eighth and sixteenth notes, often beamed together. The left hand provides a steady accompaniment with chords and single notes. The notation includes various accidentals and dynamic markings, though they are not explicitly labeled with text. The piece concludes with a double bar line and repeat signs in both systems.

C MINOR

1 $\text{♩} = 120$ 2

Piano

Strings

3 4

5 6

The image displays two systems of musical notation for piano accompaniment, covering measures 7, 8, and 9. Each system consists of a grand staff with a treble clef and a bass clef. The key signature is two flats (B-flat and E-flat). The time signature is common time (C). The music features a consistent rhythmic pattern of eighth notes in the right hand and chords in the left hand. Measure 7 shows the beginning of the pattern. Measure 8 continues the sequence. Measure 9 concludes with a double bar line and repeat signs in both staves.

C # MINOR / D b MINOR

1 $\text{♩} = 120$ 2

Piano

Strings

3 4

5 6

The musical score is written for Piano and Strings in C# minor / Db minor, 4/4 time, with a tempo of 120. The score is divided into six measures. Measures 1-2 show the piano and strings playing a rhythmic pattern. Measures 3-4 show the piano and strings playing a similar pattern. Measures 5-6 show the piano and strings playing a more complex pattern with triplets.

7 8 9

The image shows two systems of musical notation for piano. Each system consists of a grand staff with a treble clef on the upper staff and a bass clef on the lower staff. The key signature is three sharps (F#, C#, G#). The time signature is common time (C). The first system contains measures 7, 8, and 9. The second system contains measures 10, 11, and 12. The music features a complex texture with multiple voices in both hands, including sixteenth-note runs and chords. The notation includes various note values, rests, and dynamic markings. The piece concludes with a double bar line and repeat signs at the end of each system.

D MINOR

1 $\text{♩} = 120$ 2

Piano

Strings

3 4

5 6

The musical score is for the key of D minor (two flats) in 4/4 time, with a tempo of 120. It is divided into six measures. The Piano part (top system) and Strings part (bottom system) are shown. Measures 1-2: The Piano part has a melodic line starting on D4, moving up stepwise to G4, then down to F4, E4, D4, C4, B3, A3, G3, F3, E3, D3. The Strings part has a similar melodic line. Measures 3-4: The Piano part continues the melodic line. The Strings part has a similar melodic line. Measures 5-6: The Piano part has a more complex texture with multiple voices. The Strings part has a similar texture.

The image displays a musical score for two systems, covering measures 7, 8, and 9. Each system consists of a grand staff with a treble clef and a bass clef. The key signature is one flat (B-flat). The music is written in a style that suggests a 19th-century piano piece, possibly a study or a short piece. The notation includes sixteenth-note runs in the right hand and block chords in the left hand. Measure 7 shows the beginning of a melodic phrase in the right hand, which continues through measures 8 and 9. The left hand provides harmonic support with chords. The score concludes with a double bar line and repeat signs in both staves of each system.

D # MINOR / E b MINOR

1 $\text{♩} = 120$ 2

Piano

Strings

3 4

5 6

The musical score is written for Piano and Strings in D# minor / Eb minor, 4/4 time, with a tempo of 120. It consists of six measures. Measures 1-2 show the initial piano and string entries. Measures 3-4 continue the piano and string parts. Measures 5-6 show a more complex piano texture with multiple voices in both hands, while the strings continue their pattern.

E MINOR

1 $\text{♩} = 120$ 2

Piano

Strings

3 4

5 6

The musical score is for E minor, 4/4 time, with a tempo of 120. It consists of six measures. The first two measures (1-2) show the initial melodic lines for the Piano and Strings. The Piano part starts with a treble clef and a key signature of one sharp (F#). The Strings part starts with a bass clef and a key signature of one sharp (F#). Measures 3-4 continue the melodic development. Measures 5-6 show a more complex texture with multiple voices in both parts.

F MINOR

1 $\text{♩} = 120$ 2

Piano

Strings

3 4

5 6

The musical score is for the key of F minor (three flats) in 4/4 time, with a tempo of 120. It consists of six measures. The first four measures are divided into two systems. The first system contains measures 1 and 2, and the second system contains measures 3 and 4. The last two measures, 5 and 6, form a third system. The Piano part is written in a grand staff (treble and bass clefs). In measures 1-4, the right hand plays a melodic line of eighth notes, while the left hand plays a simple bass line of quarter notes. In measures 5-6, the piano texture becomes more complex, with multiple voices in both hands. The Strings part is also written in a grand staff. In measures 1-4, the right hand plays a melodic line of eighth notes, and the left hand plays a simple bass line of quarter notes. In measures 5-6, the strings play a more complex texture, with multiple voices in both hands.

The image displays two systems of musical notation for piano accompaniment, covering measures 7, 8, and 9. Each system consists of a grand staff with a treble clef and a bass clef. The key signature is three flats (B-flat, E-flat, A-flat), and the time signature is common time (C).
- **Measure 7:** The right hand features a complex, sixteenth-note arpeggiated pattern. The left hand provides a steady accompaniment with a bass line of quarter notes and a chordal accompaniment of eighth notes.
- **Measure 8:** The right hand continues the arpeggiated pattern, while the left hand maintains the same accompaniment structure.
- **Measure 9:** Both hands conclude with a final chord, marked with a fermata. The right hand chord is a triad (F4, A4, C5) and the left hand chord is a triad (B2, D3, F3).

Manipulation Check Sheet Music

C MAJOR +8

$\text{♩} = 120$ 8

Guitar

1 2 3

4 5 6

7 8 9

C MAJOR -8

$\text{♩} = 120$

Guitar

1 2 3

4 5 6

7 8 9

A MINOR +8

♩ = 120

1 2

Piano

8

8

8

8

3 4

8

8

8

8

5 6

8

8

8

8

The image displays two systems of musical notation, each consisting of a grand staff (treble and bass clefs). The first system is labeled with measure numbers 7, 8, and 9. The second system is identical to the first. In both systems, the right hand (treble clef) plays a complex, rhythmic pattern of eighth and sixteenth notes, while the left hand (bass clef) provides a steady accompaniment of eighth notes. The notation includes various musical symbols such as stems, beams, and clefs. The page concludes with a double bar line and repeat signs.

A MINOR -8

1 $\text{♩} = 120$

Piano

8

2

8

Strings

8

8

3

4

8

8

8

8

5

6

8

8

8

8

7 8 9

The image shows two systems of musical notation for piano. Each system consists of a grand staff with a treble clef on top and a bass clef on the bottom. The music is in 3/4 time, as indicated by the 'C' time signature at the end of each system. Measure 7 shows a complex texture with sixteenth-note runs in the right hand and chords in the left hand. Measure 8 continues this texture. Measure 9 concludes the passage with a final chord in the right hand and a bass clef chord in the left hand. The dynamics are marked with '8' (likely fortissimo) and 'ppp' (pianissimo) at the end of the piece.